

Phonetic Transfer Learning from Healthy
References for the Analysis of Pathological
Speech

Phonetisches Transferlernen von gesunden
Referenzen für die Analyse pathologischer
Sprache

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Philipp Klumpp
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Bad Ems

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Gutachter: Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Elmar Nöth
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Jan Rusz
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Juan Rafael Orozco-Arroyave

Abstract

Automatic speech recognition (ASR) experienced a major leap forward through many advances in deep machine learning over the past decade. In each new iteration of neural ASR architecture, the increase in performance was accompanied by an increasing number of model parameters. Speech recognizers could be optimized with many thousands of hours of audio data to explore a vast amount of different speakers, acoustic conditions or recording setups, resulting in very robust decision boundaries. However, if the utilized training dataset was small and did not cover much variability, optimization attempts could quickly lead to an overfitted model.

Compared to large general-purpose ASR datasets, pathological speech corpora are much smaller. Additionally, they were often recorded under very controlled conditions to serve as a valid reference for scientific experiments. Nevertheless, it is common practice to optimize large neural networks with small amounts of pathological speech and report results on a held-out test set of the same corpus: A valid strategy to evaluate and support a particular methodology, but the reported results often collapse under the presence of entirely new data. This thesis proposes an opposite approach: All models presented throughout this work had been optimized only on healthy speech from standard ASR datasets, with the base task of recognizing speech sounds from the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). These highly robust recognizers could then be used to analyze speech signals from different pathologies. For Parkinson’s Disease (PD), it was possible to estimate the available phonetic inventory of speakers as the condition progressed through various stages of severity. It could also be shown that any humanly perceived decrease of intelligibility also manifested in the recognition confidences of the proposed models, indicating a clear shift away from the well-explored healthy reference. PD greatly impacts the phonation of vowels: An increasing monotonicity manifested in a clear shrinkage of the estimated vowel triangles of severely affected patients. The estimated vowel space could also be used as a surrogate to track the severity of speech symptoms over time, with correlations of up to 0.81 compared to the expert annotation.

For the analysis of Covid-19 speech, the proposed models served primarily as feature extractors. Each extracted feature vector was associated with a speech sound, thus it was possible to identify differences between speaker cohorts and directly relate them to particular structures in the vocal tract. Results showed a clear impact of the respiratory condition on the speech signal, but, unlike reported by many other studies, the differences between Covid-19 and other conditions, such as a common cold, were small in terms of effect size and almost never found to be significant.

The proposed methods were not limited to speech, but could also be used for therapy of aphasia, a language disorder. Various keyword recognition models were proposed – grounded on the existing phone recognizers – which modeled an open vocabulary of target words via plain phoneme sequences. Attention-based models achieved F-scores above 0.9. Even for those patients who suffered from concomitant speech deficits, the recognizers reliably differentiated between correct and invalid keyword productions. While overcoming the lack of available pathological speech data, this thesis also highlighted a path towards more explainable neural networks and classifiers in general. Instead of directly mapping an input signal to an output prediction, the extraction

of phonetic knowledge could help support any further decision making or evaluation, for both medical experts and algorithms.

Zusammenfassung

Die automatische Spracherkennung (ASR) hat in den letzten zehn Jahren einen großen Fortschritt durch zahlreiche Entwicklungen im Bereich des Deep Learnings erlebt. In jeder neuen Generation einer neuronalen ASR-Architektur ging die Steigerung der Leistung einher mit einer zunehmenden Anzahl von Modellparametern. Spracherkennungssysteme konnten mit Tausenden von Stunden an Audiodaten optimiert werden, um eine Vielzahl unterschiedlicher Sprecherinnen und Sprecher, akustischer Bedingungen oder Aufnahmesetups zu erkunden, was zu sehr robusten Entscheidungsgrenzen führte. Wenn jedoch der verwendete Trainings-Datensatz klein war und nicht viel Variabilität abdeckte, konnten Optimierungsversuche schnell zu einem überangepassten Modell führen.

Im Vergleich zu großen Standard-ASR-Datensätzen sind pathologische Sprachkorpora viel kleiner. Zusätzlich wurden sie oft unter sehr kontrollierten Bedingungen aufgenommen, um als gültige Referenz für wissenschaftliche Experimente zu dienen. Dennoch ist es gängige Praxis, große neuronale Netzwerke mit geringen Mengen pathologischer Sprache zu optimieren und Ergebnisse auf einem zurückgehaltenen Testset derselben Korpora zu berichten: Eine gültige Strategie zur Bewertung und Untermauerung einer bestimmten Methodik, jedoch brechen die berichteten Ergebnisse oft beim Vorhandensein völlig neuer Daten zusammen. Diese Arbeit schlägt einen entgegengesetzten Ansatz vor: Alle in dieser Arbeit vorgestellten Modelle wurden ausschließlich auf gesunde Sprache aus standardmäßigen ASR-Datensätzen optimiert, mit der Grundaufgabe, Sprachlaute des Internationalen Phonetischen Alphabets (IPA) zu erkennen. Diese äußerst robusten Erkennungssysteme könnten dann verwendet werden, um Sprachsignale von verschiedenen Pathologien zu analysieren.

Im Fall der Parkinson-Krankheit (PD) war es möglich, das verfügbare phonetische Inventar der Sprecher abzuschätzen, während sich die Krankheit im Verlauf verschiedener Schweregrade verschlimmerte. Es konnte auch gezeigt werden, dass jede menschlich wahrgenommene Abnahme der Verständlichkeit sich auch in den abgegebenen Konfidenzen der vorgeschlagenen Modelle zeigte, was auf eine klare Abkehr von der gut erforschten gesunden Referenz hinweist. PD beeinflusst stark die Phonetik von Vokalen: Eine zunehmende Monotonie manifestierte sich in einer klaren Verkleinerung der geschätzten Vokaldreiecke bei stark betroffenen Patienten. Der geschätzte Vokalraum konnte auch als Surrogat verwendet werden, um die Schwere der Sprachsymptome im Laufe der Zeit zu verfolgen, mit Korrelationen von bis zu 0.81 im Vergleich zur Expertenbewertung.

Für die Analyse von Covid-19-Sprache dienten die vorgeschlagenen Modelle hauptsächlich als Merkmalsextraktoren. Jeder extrahierte Merkmalsvektor war mit einem Sprachlaut verbunden, sodass es möglich war, Unterschiede zwischen Sprechergruppen zu identifizieren und sie direkt mit bestimmten Strukturen im Stimmtrakt in Beziehung zu setzen. Die Ergebnisse zeigten einen deutlichen Einfluss der Atemwegserkrankung auf das Sprachsignal, aber im Gegensatz zu vielen anderen Studien waren die Unterschiede zwischen Covid-19 und ähnlichen Erkrankungen wie einer gewöhnlichen Erkältung in Bezug auf die Effektgröße gering und fast nie signifikant.

Die vorgeschlagenen Methoden beschränkten sich nicht nur auf die Aussprache, sondern konnten auch für die Therapie von Aphasie, einer Sprachstörung, verwendet werden. Es wurden verschiedene Modelle zur Erkennung von Schlüsselwörtern vorgeschla-

gen – basierend auf den vorhandenen Sprachlauterkennern –, die ein offenes Vokabular von Zielwörtern durch einfache Phonemsequenzen modellierten. Attention-basierte Modelle erreichten ein F-Maß von über 0.9. Selbst für Patienten, die unter begleitenden Sprechdefiziten litten, unterschieden die Erkenner zuverlässig zwischen korrekten und ungültigen Zielwortproduktionen.

Der vorgestellte Ansatz überwindet den Mangel an verfügbaren pathologischen Sprachdaten und weist auch den Weg zu erklärbareren neuronalen Netzwerken und Klassifikatoren im Allgemeinen. Anstatt ein Eingangssignal direkt einer Zielklasse zuzuordnen, kann die Extraktion phonetischen Wissens dazu beitragen, jede weitere Entscheidungsfindung oder Bewertung sowohl für medizinische Experten als auch für Algorithmen zu unterstützen.

Acknowledgment

During a hike in the Austrian Alps, a friend and former colleague at the Pattern Recognition Lab described his thoughts about the ups and downs while pursuing a doctorate degree:

“We should always remain humble and never forget that the opportunities we have been given are an extraordinary privilege.”

Not a single word of complaint, frustration, discouragement or fatigue. In the same spirit, this preface is dedicated to the many people who, knowingly or unknowingly, have enabled me to conclude my years in academic research with this thesis.

None of the experiments described throughout this manuscript would have been possible without the donated speech samples from Parkinson’s Disease, Covid-19 or aphasia patients. Despite suffering from a severe neurological or respiratory condition, which often has a profound impact on a person’s everyday life, each data donor voluntarily participated in extensive recording protocols to help researchers better understand how different diseases affect speech and language abilities. In recognition of their donations, the first words of acknowledgement are dedicated to the patients who contributed to any of the pathological speech corpora which had been utilized throughout this work.

Over the course of several interdisciplinary research projects, I learned that looking at the same problem from a different point of view is often the key to find a good solution. Thankfully, I was very lucky to work with many skilled colleagues from various disciplines, like speech and language therapy, phonetics, healthcare, signal processing or electrical engineering, who were always supportive and incredibly motivated. No textbook could keep up with the insights and hands-on knowledge these experts had acquired over years or decades. I will always be grateful for their ability to take me on a walk through the space of knowledge, only to guide me to a new location from which a once insurmountable problem suddenly appeared solvable.

During my time at the Pattern Recognition Lab, I had the opportunity to work on several interesting problems in the domain of sequence analysis, while also focusing on my own academic progress. None of this would have been possible without the tremendous amount of support coming from the many heroes behind the scenes. Our technical staff keeps an impressive stack of hardware and software up and running, only for users like me to regularly cause them a headache because our systems are once again running out of disk space. Our secretaries miraculously bring order to chaos in the mist of a chaotic bunch of computer scientists. At the same time, they keep us sheltered from the despair of administrative work. One could say it is their job and their responsibility, but over the years at the lab, I have not only seen how much tedious work this can be, but also how the amount of work and pressure has increased more and more. I can hardly express the incredible gratitude I feel for their dedication, willingness to help and their frustration tolerance.

I joined the lab in late 2017, therefore I witnessed the effects of several Covid-19 lockdowns and the associated shutdown of social life at the lab first hand. It can be incredibly difficult to translate onsite routines into a virtual environment. Once

per semester, the lab holds a symposium (PRS) to allow its members to exchange about their respective research. But PRS is much more, it is also an important social event where you get to know your colleagues outside of a work environment and make lifelong friends. In fact, the hike in Austria mentioned in the beginning also took place at a PRS. The reason why these important traditions never ceased despite the circumstances of a pandemic is the head of the lab, Andreas Maier. In the maze of countless PhD students, conference deadlines, administrative work, research contributions and an overbooked calendar, he still managed to bind the lab together. It is all too easy to take these things for granted, as it takes true leadership to make a university lab feel like a second home to its people.

I also want to dedicate a few words to all the other PhD students and post-docs at the lab. During my six years, I met so many brilliant and motivated minds, and to me, you all have become much more my friends than just colleagues. This is especially true for the speech group (SAGI), which I was a part of. In my last years, I shared an office with my two SAGI colleagues Paula and Tomás, and I will always be grateful from the bottom of my heart that I can call you my friends. We have spent so much time together at the lab, but also beyond, and if my life would be a big picture, you two definitely contributed a couple of puzzle pieces to it to make it complete. The same holds for Christian, who always had an open door to chat about the GPU cluster, SAGI, the lab, but most importantly all the other fun stuff that was not work-related. I feel nothing but deep thankfulness for the entire speech group for the way they welcomed me, helped me to become a part of this unique team, and ultimately supported me to grow as a researcher and as a person.

My journey with SAGI began in 2013 when I started working on my Bachelor's thesis. I was closing in on my studies in medical engineering, and was looking out for a thesis topic in the image processing domain, when Elmar Nöth, the head of SAGI, convinced me to change my mind and instead work with speech signals. It turned out to be one of the best – and one of the most influential – decisions of my life. A whole new world of opportunities had opened up to me, an extraordinary privilege as my friend described it during our hike. This privilege was granted to me by Elmar. He trusted in me, saw my strengths and weaknesses, guided me in my research, and had an open ear for all the big and small things that happened in my life. How much I will miss the telephone ring on Fridays at 4 p.m. sharp for our weekly get-together in the kitchen. How much I will miss his assertion in Franconian *Des kriang ma scho!* (We will find a solution!) whenever something did not go according to plan. Elmar taught me some invaluable life lessons, but most importantly, he taught me a lot about myself. I would really like to put the degree of gratitude I feel for all of his support and his friendship into words, but neither my nor any other language model is powerful enough to convey a message of such weight.

The past six years were an incredible journey, and yet there were times when frustration or discouragement almost took the better of me. It was in these moments when I could always rely on my anchor and safe haven Marlina. Her ability to put a smile on my face, to cheer me up, to motivate me to finish what I had started, have had a tremendous influence on my life. Going through the ups and downs of a PhD was all so much easier with her unconditional support. Having a partner like her, who always has your back, who believes in you, who would do anything to help

you, and who truly loves you the way you are is one of the extraordinary privileges I mentioned in the beginning. Thank you Marlena, and thank you to your family, for all your love and kindness.

It took me quite some time in my life to come to the realization that I had pretty much everything one could ask for to be happy: The love and security of my family. I never really had to be worried about anything, simply because I knew I could always return into the arms of my mother and my two sisters. Whatever would happen, they would always stay by my side. This lifelong bond of a caring family is something you cannot replace. I am eternally grateful for having a family that I always love to return to, that believes in me at all times and that always welcomes me with their arms and hearts wide open.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Machine learning (ML) has experienced an impressive surge in attention in recent years, not only in the scientific community. *Intelligent* algorithms pilot cars [Wang 19], detect cancerous tissue in microscopic images [Sun 10], recognize speech [Zhan 16] or predict stock prices [Mogh 20]. Their presence in everyday life has quickly been adopted by many, but at the same time, concerns were raised about the danger of *computers taking over*. Fortunately (or unfortunately?), at the time of writing this thesis, we are still far away from any system of such capability.

In fact, most modern AI models, no matter how powerful they are, required tremendous amounts of baby-sitting during development and optimization. To make things worse, they often depended on ridiculous amounts of data to learn from. Lastly, even the most advanced models usually lack the ability of *abstraction*. Among the many different definitions, which also depend on the particular context, *Cambridge's Advanced Learner's Dictionary & Thesaurus* [Camb 20] describes the term abstraction as the 'situation in which a subject is very general and not based on real situations'. A simple example demonstrates how this definition translates to the scope of ML: Consider a sophisticated neural network for recognizing cars in photographic images, which had been optimized with millions of high-resolution training samples. For any input signal, the network solves the binary classification problem of whether there is a car in the image or not. If this model was shown the hand-drawing of a car from a three-year-old infant, recognition success would certainly experience a sharp drop. The reasoning behind this is straightforward: The neural network had never before seen any hand-drawn images, it simply cannot make much sense of the input signal, which only shows the characteristic contours of a car, instead of all the photographic details. This could be interpreted as missing abstraction on the signal analysis level. If this is already difficult, can we expect sufficient abstraction on the content level? Assuming the model was able to successfully recognize parts of the hand-drawn image as doors, tires and chassis, would it be able to detect the car? Or would it reject the sample, because it couldn't find any glossy car finish, no reflections on the windshield or screws on the tires? From the real examples seen during training, the model learned that these features could be found on most pictures with cars, and their absence likely means that there is no car.

The tendency of neural networks to cling to prior observations is a well-known problem. Instead of learning general concepts applicable to a vast amount of samples, modern architectures try to memorize every little aspect of a signal that was found to be helpful to solve the problem at hand. The simple answer to the question why models do not learn general rules in the first place is: They don't have to. In *Machine Learning*, the parameters of some function are optimized with respect to certain criteria using a collection of prior experiences, commonly in the form of annotated data [Alpa 19]. With an increasing amount of trainable parameters, ML techniques can learn more sophisticated decision rules that cover every slight detail which is potentially helpful. This conflicts with the inherent principle of abstraction to understand a subject independent of its realizations.

In the domain of biomedical signal analysis, physicians' abstract understanding of a pathology still renders them superior to most algorithmic solutions. However, ML models entail several advantages over the human expert. Firstly, their performance remains constant over any amount of time, whilst that of the physician would eventually decline, for example due to fatigue. Secondly, a model could be made available at almost any place and time, which makes their application a lot more flexible. Lastly, the algorithmic solution is able to process far more patients in less time, and at significantly lower cost. Hence, an ideal solution could, at best, not replace but support medical experts in their everyday routine. Computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) for example is no tool of the future, but has already made its way into the clinical workflow, predominantly in the imaging domain [Shir 11]. Algorithms are able to provide automated annotation [Yin 18], segmentation [Hesa 19], quality enhancement (e.g. denoising [Gond 16]), registration of corresponding point clouds [Hask 20] or classification [Mira 16]. Frequently, advancements in ML for medical image processing benefit from findings in other research areas such as general image classification, computer vision and representation learning.

For modern ML methods, medical imaging features several important advantages. Image acquisition is expensive, hence data is usually archived for years. This increases availability, although for most tasks, such data may still lack appropriate ground truth annotation. What is also noteworthy is the fact that imaging devices in hospitals are operated by experts, leaving smaller room for errors. Lastly, compared to the domain of speech analysis, imaging is much more established in the clinical workflow. There exist all kinds of techniques, like ultrasound, computed tomography, or magnetic resonance imaging, to mention a few notable examples. On the other side, speech signals are seldom recorded. On the first glance, this might sound surprising. Imaging devices are quite expensive and often take years to amortize. Even a high-quality recording environment with some decent hardware would be less costly. The reason why physicians still mostly rely on imaging hardware is because they used it successfully for decades, and it gives them insights into the human body without being invasive. Against this background, recording an audio signal appears redundant. The medical expert could just as well listen to the patient's speech, and derive a diagnosis from the original signal. A recording is much more likely to be taken for the purpose of documentation. In this context, the recording quality would most probably fall short of the requirements posed by today's computational efforts to analyze pathological speech.

Nevertheless, the diagnosis is only one of several important steps in clinical care. Another one is therapy. Speech is a human being's primary tool of communication, and an impaired ability to speak has a significant impact on one's everyday life. Many medical conditions could be the reason for a speech or language disorder, for example a cleft lip and palate (CLP) or a neurological problem like a stroke could render a patient unable to communicate without limitations. The typical treatment of a speech or language impairment frequently encompasses two major branches, a curative and a symptomatic therapy. The former aims to cure the root cause of the disease. This may not always be possible, for example, in the case of Parkinson's Disease, the degeneration of certain brain cells cannot be reverted, but at best be delayed to slow down the overall progression of the pathology. The goal of a symptomatic therapy, as the name already suggests, is to alleviate symptoms that are caused by an underlying medical condition. Patients receive symptomatic therapy for speech and language impairments from a speech therapist. Together with the expert, they learn relevant exercises to practice at home. A standard procedure could look like this: Every day, patients on average do 15 minutes of speech exercises. Once a week, they visit their therapist to validate therapy progress and learn new exercises. Besides the initial diagnosis and the consecutive therapy, monitoring of pathology development and therapy progress is yet another important step in medical care. A close meshed series of examinations to validate the success of therapeutic measures is key to quickly react to changes in a patient's individual needs. However, the frequency of speech therapy sessions varies quite a lot, and usually the supply falls short of a growing demand. Studies have shown that intensive speech therapy (together with a therapist on a daily basis) can significantly improve treatment results [Pulv 01, Albe 84]. Despite the existence of sufficient evidence for the superiority of highly frequent speech therapy, it is rarely implemented in regular care. Qualified speech therapists are simply outnumbered by the immense amount of patients who need treatment. Furthermore, treatment sessions are an expensive resource, whilst *training at home on your own* is for free. In this context, the economic pressure within the healthcare system takes its toll on the individual patient's well-being. The growing gap between supply and demand for speech therapy creates opportunities for automated monitoring and feedback systems. Even if patients are fully capable of doing a 15 minutes self-exercise session every day, how can they progress quickly if they do not receive any sort of feedback? How does a patient maintain a high level of motivation to do speech exercises over the course of several weeks or months? It is not only about the invaluable feedback which an artificial intelligence could provide, but also about the constant monitoring of therapy progress [McKe 20]. If the patient's speech improved measurably after two weeks of daily training, the system could let patients know about this success, and encourage them to continue the hard work. Just as important as monitoring success, it would be to identify stagnation. The reasons for reduced effectiveness of speech therapy could be diverse, but if the system informed the speech therapist about the problem, a solution could likely be implemented much quicker.

Digital solutions for speech therapy have already entered the market and provide at-home training for children as well as the elderly. Systems like *PEAKS* [Maie 09] (**P**rogram for **E**valuation and **A**nalysis of all **K**inds of **S**peech disorders), which fo-

Figure 1.1: Screenshot from the *PEAKS* therapy application for desktop computers.

cuses on multiple different pathologies, or the *neolexon* therapy application [Pfab15] for aphasia patients aim to provide long-term care and go hand in hand with real training sessions together with the responsible speech therapist. *PEAKS* and *neolexon* are good examples for successfully deployed therapy applications, although they both excel in very different ways. Written in *Java*, *PEAKS* can be used on any computer that features a corresponding run-time environment. The hardware requirements were set to be low to improve availability of the system, a regular headset or chest microphone would suffice to achieve acceptable audio quality for the subsequent signal analysis. The entire user interface (when used as a patient) is structured as simple as possible, without any distractions, such that a user could effortlessly navigate through the digital therapy session. A common exercise is to accurately pronounce different exercise words. Because *PEAKS* also offers support for children, exercise items could be presented not only in written form, but also as pictograms (Figure 1.1). Furthermore, children did not use *PEAKS* on their own, but were assisted by a speech therapist throughout their recording session.

The key strength of *PEAKS* lies in its potent signal analysis. The automatic assessments of the system showed strong correlations of 0.9 for patients after laryngectomy and 0.87 for children with CLP, when compared to the respective judgement of an expert physician [Maie09]. This was comparable to the inter-rater correlation between two clinicians.

The *neolexon* application for aphasia patients took a different approach to provide digital at-home speech therapy. Unlike *PEAKS*, it was developed for a variety of platforms, like desktop computers or tablets. It features a high-quality app design (Figure 1.2) which had been evaluated with respect to user experience and accessibility together with a cohort of patients several times.

For someone who had worked with, and tried out, many applications for speech ther-

Figure 1.2: User interface of the *neolexon* aphasia therapy application for tablet computers.

apy, probably one of the first impressions of the *neolexon* aphasia app might be: *It is a pleasure to work with it.* After a five-minutes trial use, however, one may be wondering: The app is recording my speech, but what happens with it in the background? Does the evaluation happen on the device, or is the data sent to some remote server? Is this server part of the *neolexon* ecosystem, or is my audio data sent to a third-party API (**A**pplication **P**rogramming **I**nterface) for speech recognition? And why do I not see any feedback on whether my utterances had been correct? The answer to all those potential questions is simple: Nothing happens with the recorded speech. There is no signal analysis, no ASR, no sophisticated feedback algorithms. Patients are being shown an image of the object they are required to name, and after recording their speech, they can simply play back the recorded audio (application design in 2022). In this setup, the users are their own evaluators, which is far from ideal. It could be highly frustrating and introduce a significant bias into the exercise results, but in some cases, this might even be impossible. The *neolexon* app targets patients with aphasia, a condition which is characterized by a loss of semantic connections between words and the objects they represent. This loss of understanding is bidirectional, so patients do not only struggle to find the correct word for an object they see, but they also fail to remember the particular object if they are given the word. Hence, it seems very unlikely that aphasia patients are able to provide a correct self-evaluation. As surprising the fact may be that no feedback algorithms had been implemented, as astonishing may be the success of the application. Several statutory health insurance companies fully cover the expenses for at-home therapy with *neolexon*, because studies showed that it encouraged patients to exercise frequently and it helped achieve significant language improvements over time [Jako 18, Jako 22]. This clearly shows the pressing demand for supplementary digital speech and language exercise solutions.

Both therapy applications also serve as interesting examples for two very different deployment strategies. *PEAKS* built a user interface around a sophisticated automatic speech analysis framework. Signals are captured via a close-talk microphone to reduce the amount of recorded background noise, and also to maintain a somewhat controlled acoustic environment [Maie09]. This would greatly help to improve the robustness of the underlying signal analysis. On the other hand, *neolexon* was designed to maximize the availability of the application. It is available on various platforms, most importantly on tablet computers. No additional recording hardware is required, hence the speech signal is recording directly with the built-in microphone. While this is a cheap solution with very low hardware requirements, it also opens up a tremendous amount of potential devices and recording conditions. While this may be OK for general purpose speech recognition, it could quickly become a disadvantage when it comes to processing pathological speech signals robustly. Let alone the circumstance that sensitive audio data from an at-home medical speech or language therapy session should never be transmitted to any powerful third-party speech recognition interface without the explicit consent of a patient.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has already made its way into the clinical work-flow, with valid use-cases in diagnostics, monitoring and therapy of medical conditions. For speech in particular, *PEAKS* has been used successfully for more than a decade now, and new applications like the *neolexon* aphasia app aim to provide mobile therapy solutions that only require a tablet computer. But the transition towards more diverse hardware- and software-ecosystems also introduces a significant challenge: Algorithms need to be robust against all kinds of deviations from the environment that they had been exposed to during training. In simple words, this means that even if a signal had been recorded with a new microphone, in a new acoustic environment, with a new speaker and an unseen noise pattern, the output should only show little to no deviation. With *PEAKS*, recording conditions are quite stable, with users sitting in front of their computer, doing the speech exercise with a headset and only having small amount of background noise. The *neolexon* therapy app runs on tablet computers, and it could be used anywhere and anytime. The requirements with respect to algorithm robustness are hence much larger in that context. Using a robust third-party ASR is no option for two important reasons: Firstly, *neolexon* is certified as a medical product, and data privacy regulations are very strict in this context. Sending an audio recording to some third-party is forbidden in almost every case. Secondly, even the most powerful ASR would struggle to correctly interpret the signals. The common ASR interfaces were optimized for speech-to-text applications. There is no feature extraction available, and more importantly, the systems had been trained with healthy speakers in the first place. One might argue that aphasia is not a speech, but a language disorder. Hence, patients should be as intelligible as healthy speakers. Unfortunately, the real world often does not align with the textbook. The main cause for an aphasia is brain damage, frequently resulting from a major accident or a stroke. In many cases, the aphasia is only one of several conditions, and speech production could easily be altered as well. Off-the-shelf ASR systems are still far away from being able to reliably understand pathological speech. If robust speech-to-text models trained with vast amounts of audio data from healthy speakers are unable to interpret pathological speech, and specialized solutions suffer from the

small amount of available pathological speech data, a solution for the problem could be found somewhere in between the two approaches.

Let there be an average human listener, who is *a)* a native speaker of some arbitrary language *L*, *b)* has no speech, language or hearing impairment, and *c)* is neither a medical nor a speech expert. The listener was now given recordings from different speakers, of which some suffered from a speech impairment. If the impairment would deteriorate the speech intelligibility, non-expert human listeners would likely be successful at identifying these samples as *abnormal*. Despite the lack of experience with impaired speech and no task-related background knowledge, they were most certainly able to classify pathological speech as less intelligible. During decision-making, they had to base their judgement on the only reference they knew: healthy speech. If an audio sample would strongly deviate from this known reference, it could be recognized as *odd*. *Odd* is quite a fitting term in this context, because the listeners would almost certainly be unable to precisely explain why the speech is less intelligible, as they lack the required knowledge. It is the speech expert who is capable to precisely characterize how a certain disease would impact the speech signal. The average human listener can recognize a deviation from the healthy norm, but it requires a professional to correctly interpret the cause of the impairment and its progression. The goal of this thesis is to mimic this relationship.

In general, the more parameters a ML model comprises, the more data is required during optimization to estimate a valid and robust decision function. Following the intuitions resulting from the presented non-expert vs. expert setup, all parameter-intensive models presented throughout this work should be estimated over speech samples from healthy speakers exclusively. We can then utilize them to analyze pathological speech data, find out how it deviates from known healthy patterns and retrieve as much expert knowledge as possible. With a primary focus on acoustic modelling, the presented algorithms should learn what unimpaired human speech sounds like. Afterwards, this knowledge could be used to analyze speech samples from different pathologies in various ways: How does the phonetic inventory of a patient suffering from a particular disease sound like? How does it differ from healthy speakers? How are individual sounds produced? Is it possible to observe transitions from one sound towards another due to articulatory problems? Can phonetic recognizers optimized with healthy speakers be used for segmentation, feature extraction and clustering of large amounts of pathological speech signals to better understand how known articulatory problems are perceived by state-of-the-art acoustic models? And, from the point of acoustic modelling, is it possible to assist not only patients with speech, but also those with language impairments?

Model complexities, especially with respect to the amount of trainable parameters, have increased by orders of magnitude in the last decade. Simultaneously, the architectures developed more and more towards end-to-end solutions, learning everything from the feature extraction to the final classification or regression in one large system. The drawback of such black box solutions is obvious: Feed in data, extract the result, without any clue about what happens in between. State-of-the-art ML architectures are powerful, but it is the cases that cause the algorithm to fail that are of utmost importance to understand the critical boundaries of operation. Compared to the speedy progress in the domain of deep learning, little is known about how

Dataset	PD		HC		Age (PD)		UPDRS		m-FDA	
	♀	♂	♀	♂	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
A	12	40	12	40	71.0	12.0	80.0	25.0	15.0	4.0
B	30	80	30	20	67.0	5.0	40.0	17.0	-	-
C	20	20	-	-	72.0	11.0	95.0	45.0	20.0	9.0

Table 1.1: Exemplary statistics summarized for three toy datasets. PD: Parkinson’s Disease; HC: Healthy Controls; UPDRS: Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale; m-FDA: modified Frenchay Dysarthria Assessment. μ : Mean value; σ : Standard deviation

such systems handle knowledge internally or to what extent relationships between pieces of information are preserved. Consequently, this thesis does not only describe acoustic models as closed systems which have to process pathological speech, but it should also provide insights into how these models understand the signals they are being shown and how they are transformed internally.

1.2 Problem Formulation

The shortage of pathological speech data is a well-known issue, but it is not limited to a shortage of audio data alone. Let there be three datasets A , B and C , all comprising speech recordings from Parkinson’s Disease (PD) patients. If the lack of available data was the sole problem, one could easily merge all three sets to increase the amount of resources. Combined with several ML techniques to counteract the impact of small datasets, it should be possible to train a model that would be more robust than any model estimated over only one of the three sets alone.

Let Table 1.1 provide some example properties for each of the three toy datasets. It summarizes the most important contributor statistics, such as age, gender or disease state. It also informs about the underlying annotation. In this case, two different types of labels are available for PD speakers, the Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS: best 0 – 260 worst) as well as the modified Frenchay Dysarthria Assessment (m-FDA: best 0 – 52 worst). A detailed explanation of both scores can be found in section 4.1.

In general, the UPDRS describes motor abilities of patients, but only one item considers speech production. The score resembles the general condition of a patient, with little information about the remaining articulatory abilities. The m-FDA on the other side focuses on speech respiratory, and swallowing symptoms, hence it offers a more accurate estimate of an individual’s speech quality. According to the table, dataset B comprises the most amount of speakers, both for the PD group as well as for the healthy controls (HC). Unfortunately, it is the only dataset which only features UPDRS labels, the more accurate m-FDA scores for speech analysis are missing. Set A provides both UPDRS and m-FDA labels, it could be a more reasonable choice to study speech of PD patients. Additionally, there is an equal number of female and male speakers in the PD and HC group. The importance of equal

speaker distributions can be demonstrated with dataset *B*: Among all (PD and HC combined) female subjects, the prior probability of PD is 50%. For male subjects, the prior probability is 80%. While PD is in fact more likely among men [Kali 15a], the bias introduced with dataset *B* would have a significant impact for ML applications. Instead of learning PD-related patterns from the speech signals, an algorithm could simply exploit the presented imbalance by learning to identify the gender. If a sample was recognized as a male speaker, the system could always output PD. Given the input was speech from a male speaker, this pointless strategy would be successful in 80% of all cases. Coming back to dataset *A*, the equal numbers of PD and HC contributors is desirable, but notice that overall, female speakers are clearly underrepresented. This could bias the final model once more, in a way that it would produce more accurate results for male speakers, because of their larger representation among the entire population. The only dataset that features the same number of subjects for both genders is *C*. It also provides the important m-FDA labels. However, this is the dataset with no HC reference speakers, it is hence more likely to be used for a regression task to estimate the degree of speech impairment, instead of classifying between HC and PD.

When comparing two independent datasets, the distribution of labels plays as much of an important role as does the distributions of age or gender. The average UPDRS value of patients in *A* is twice as large as the one from patients in *B*. Both UPDRS as well as m-FDA were designed in a way that inter-rater agreement would be as large as possible. Consequently, if two independent raters were to judge the speech of a cohort of patients, their respective results should be very similar. However, a strong agreement is not guaranteed, particularly in the case of less experienced annotators. Fusing datasets *A* and *B* could work well, but in the presence of a systematic bias between their labels, the joint annotation could be corrupted.

If all concerns discussed so far had been taken care of, before merging data from different sources, one had to validate that the study protocols would show sufficient overlap. After all, subjects should have executed similar tasks, for example a sustained vowel phonation and a diadochokinesis task (the fast repetition of consonant-vowel clusters), two popular exercises for PD patients. This is important, because it allows to effectively increase the amount of available data for one task of interest. If the overlap of performed exercises was small, or maybe even non-existent due to entirely different study designs, it would be difficult to merge the two datasets in a meaningful way, simply because the different tasks of each protocol require unique analysis methods anyway.

One last aspect worth mentioning is the configuration of recording hardware and acoustic environment. The chances of two datasets being recorded with comparable noise conditions and the same microphone are very small. Furthermore, the datasets should be of roughly equal size, such that the resulting model would not be biased towards one of the two configurations. As a general rule of thumb, if the goal of a study is more research-driven, the number of included ecosystems should be kept small to lower their impact on the final results. If the goal is to deploy a system on a larger scale, for example to make it available for patients at home, the number of ecosystems considered during the study should be as large as possible to cover a wide range of environments.

One important motivation of this thesis introduced in the previous section is to train models only with large amounts of healthy speech. Against the potential problems that had just been discussed, this appears strongly controversial. Why could it make sense to show a model large amounts of data, but hide exactly that portion that is of interest for the final task? Why should incorporating countless microphones and recording environments be helpful in a research scenario? And how could a model derive knowledge about properties such as articulation or phonation if it wasn't shown any ground truth about them?

Let us consider one of the most elemental equations from the domain of signal processing to explain the rationale behind the presented approach:

$$x = x_{signal} + x_{noise} \tag{1.1}$$

Any observation of a signal x can be written as the sum of the clean, undistorted information x_{signal} and some noise signal x_{noise} . The reasons for noise are diverse, a signal could be altered by environmental background noise, reverberation or quantization for example. Note that this general formulation is not restricted to additive noise types. Noise could also be multiplicative, but even then the resulting signal could be decomposed into the form of a sum. If a model was trained to interpret such data, for example a neural network, the most natural approach would be to mitigate x_{noise} , such that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) increases. In most cases, this requires some knowledge about the underlying noise pattern, because the challenging part is not the actual suppression of noise, but the conservation of the clean signal at the same time. Naturally, a signal is not corrupted by only one source of noise, but many different ones. A feasible approach for noise suppression would be to estimate a noise profile in the frequency domain, over a time interval where x_{signal} is 0. This profile could then be used to precisely attenuate individual frequency bands with low SNR. Whilst this is not an uncommon approach for noise reduction, it introduces a constraint: The noise profile can either be estimated reliably during runtime, or it is already known in advance. This constraint cannot always be met, for example in the case where noise is not stationary and changes over time.

Matters become even more delicate if we adhere to a more strict interpretation of what is defined by the 'signal'. In the case of acoustic modelling, where we want to observe a particular sequence of speech sounds, this sequence is the signal. Hence, all parts of the audio signal that relate to the speaker of said sequence, for example the fundamental frequency or other prosodic information, could be considered noise. The true sequence of speech sounds is superimposed by the signal of speaker-characteristics.

Let us now revisit a fundamental concept of ML. Whenever a model, for example a neural network, is optimized with respect to some criterion, that model is effectively trying to approximate a function, usually in the high-dimensional space. In the standard case of classification, this is called the decision function. It resembles a hyperplane separating two or more classes from each other. When a point lies exactly on the hyperplane, the probability of belonging to either of the two classes

separated by the plane is 50%. Let f be the approximated decision function for a binary classification task, then the predicted class y for input x can be written as:

$$y = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } f(x) < 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

Here, $f(x)$ maps input x to some floating point number. If the result of $f(x) < 0$, observation x is assigned the class $y = 0$. In the other case, x is assigned the opposite class $y = 1$. Classes 0 and 1 are simple placeholders in this case, and could represent arbitrary categories, such as healthy and diseased. During optimization of $f(x)$, for example by means of gradient descent, f is pushed towards the optimal decision boundary with respect to the task at hand. This happens in the form of an iterative procedure. First, a new sample is plugged into f , and the model hypothesis is then compared to the correct expectation. The difference between hypothesis and expectation is the error, and the parameters of f are then modified slightly such that the error would decrease. A more detailed explanation on optimization in ML will follow in section 2.1.3. Let us now plug equation 1.1 into f :

$$f(x) = f(x_{signal} + x_{noise}) \quad (1.3)$$

Following the strict definition about signal and noise from before, then the information about the correct expectation is found in x_{signal} , whilst all other information in x_{noise} acts as distraction. Accordingly, a well-optimized decision function $f(x)$ should be strongly influenced by x_{signal} , whilst the impact of x_{noise} ideally remains as small as possible. Coming back to acoustic modelling, if f was optimized to classify speech sounds, it was concluded that speaker-related information would not be part of the signal, but more part of noise. In this context, let us decompose the noisy part of a signal into two elements. On the one hand, there is destructive noise, which occurs randomly and could be the result of any process which is independent of the original signal. Additionally, there is distractive noise, which is a by-product of the undistorted signal. If the observed signal conveys information such as a sequence of speech sounds, then there is also distractive noise like the emotional state or loudness. x_{signal} cannot exist without distractive noise, hence $f(x)$ is always exposed to this type of distortion during optimization, and it will learn to filter the required information out of it. Let the emotional state of a speaker be *excited* for example, then this state slightly transforms his or her speech, or, in other words, it distracts the speech from an unbiased, average waveform, conveying the exact same information. On the other side, if there is loud music in the background, then this type of noise has a destructive influence on the information in the acquired signal.

These two definitions of noise are important to understand the core idea behind leaving out pathological data during model training. If a neural network is shown thousands of speakers during training, its parameters are exposed to all kinds of distractive noise during optimization. There are female and male contributors, they may be younger or older, they could speak slower or faster, and much more. With a successful approximation of $f(x)$, the model is able to constantly output the correct sequence of speech sounds, despite the variable speaker traits which also manifest in x . In ML, this ability is called robustness, and it goes hand in hand with the stationarity

assumption, which states ‘*that the future examples will be like the past*’ [Russ 21]. A model will most likely not be able to make sense out of something it had never seen before. Thus, the more exploration happens during training, the less likely are unknown observations during application. Accordingly, with increasing robustness of an acoustic model, chances are higher to successfully predict speech sounds from pathological samples. Not only is this helpful because it automatically segments the audio data into relevant chunks of information, but it also allows further evaluation about which sounds patients are able to produce. No dedicated speech exercise would be necessary, a system could just listen to the patient in an every-day situation, collect a few minutes of speech, compute the relative frequency of individual speech sounds, and compare this to a healthy reference or the subject’s own performance one week earlier. Although the underlying acoustic model had never been trained on pathological speech, it would still be able to understand the speech sounds of a patient. If the individual was not able to produce some parts of the acoustic inventory of his or her language anymore, this would quickly lead to a decrease of intelligibility. If the system was not interested in recognizing words, but only speech sounds, this would not be a problem.

Assuming that an acoustic model was still able to identify speech sounds from pathological speech, it would be possible to segment a speech signal, and to identify sounds that are difficult or impossible for an individual to produce. However, the analysis of pathological speech signals with healthy reference models holds a lot more if we come back to the concept of distractive noise. The way a disease influences an individual’s speech is yet another form of distractive noise. Let $f(x)$ now be the approximated decision function from a deep neural network (DNN). A DNN is called deep because it is composed of many layers, and a sample x passes through these stages from the input all the way to the output. It was already mentioned that one major downside of such models is the fact that they act like a black box. What exactly happens within the model, for example after a particular layer, often remains unknown. To analyze how information is processed inside of a multi-layered model, it is necessary to decompose $f(x)$ such that

$$f(x) = g(h(x)), \quad (1.4)$$

where h models the intermediate output after some layer, hence it resembles $f(x)$ until this point, and g represents the remaining layers which transform the output of the current layer h to the output of $f(x)$. By slicing the neural network between different layers, various combinations of g and h are possible. Further knowledge about deep architectures is required to identify reasonable pairs. To understand why g and h could prove helpful, let $h(x)$ be the output for the second-last layer of a classification DNN, and $g(h(x))$ resembles the last layer, which maps down the output of h to the class targets. If there were, for example, five different classes, then g would output a 5-dimensional vector, with the maximum value at the position of the predicted class. Given a robust decision function $f(x)$, $h(x)$ provides a sufficient amount of information for g to perform the final classification. Hence, the output of h could be interpreted as a feature vector (FV). The information encoded by individual components of the FV remain unknown, but under the assumption of robustness, a general formulation of h can be given as:

$$h(x) = h(x_{signal} + x_{noise}) = h(x_{signal}) + X \quad (1.5)$$

with

$$X \sim \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(\mu_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (1.6)$$

According to equation 1.5, the output $h(x)$ of the last hidden layer before the final classification layer can be written in terms of a signal and noise component. In a robust model, the classification layer is able to map expressions of constant x_{signal} and variable x_{noise} to the same target class. Hence, one can argue that the output of $h(x)$ could also be written in terms of x_{signal} plus a random vector X which follows a multi-variate Gaussian mixture distribution. The perturbation introduced by X causes the output of h to scatter in the high-dimensional space. The resulting probability density reflects the hyperspace in which various expressions of the same class, for example on speech sound produced by two different speakers, could be found. Consequently, $g(h(x))$ only projects this high-dimensional hyperspace into a (usually, but not necessarily) lower-dimensional output space. Both distractive as well as destructive noise manifest in X . Whilst the former, as it is an inherent part of the signal, could successfully be explored during training given a sufficiently diverse dataset, the latter could potentially be unknown, and therefore introduce a disruption which could lead to false classification results. Even the most robust models cannot make sense of a signal that was heavily distorted by destructive noise. In fact, the required amount of destructive noise could also be very small, as shown in some studies on adversarial attacks [Good 14, Scho 18].

For one particular target class y , the hyperspace in $h(x)$ which would be mapped to class y through g is defined during model optimization, and it contains all kinds of hidden information induced by distractive noise. A simple and straightforward approach to understand and interpret this space could be to compare how known properties of samples influence their respective realizations in $h(x)$. Such property could be for example gender, age, or some other feature like the state and progression of a disease. The exploration of that hyperspace is more efficient if all samples used for it share a common destructive noise profile. If we wanted to analyze how gender, and with it the fundamental frequency of voiced speech segments, would be reflected in $h(x)$, then it would be inadequate to compare the speech signals from female speakers recorded with one, and male speakers recorded with another microphone, as it would induce an unwanted difference in their destructive noise profiles. Putting it simple, one is looking for the difference in fundamental frequency, not for the different microphones.

As different configurations of h and g can be realized, it is possible to evaluate the internal state of a neural network after specific building blocks of the entire architecture. In end-to-end models, the hidden state could be extracted with temporal context (after a recurrent layer for example) or without (directly after the feature extraction). The general formulation 1.5 would still hold, but the way different properties affected the distribution in the hyperspace could change significantly.

Lastly, if X reflected a hyperspace which was explored during training, and the model had been optimized with healthy speech only, how would pathological speech sounds arrange in it. If they produced a noticeable deviation from the healthy reference, a neural architecture could be able to evaluate the intelligibility of human articulation on the level of individual speech sound categories.

To build such acoustic reference model for healthy speech, a large amount of speakers is required to allow the system to explore as much of the potential input space as possible. At the same time, balance between certain groups of contributors is key to produce unbiased results for pathological speech data. Such groups could reflect obvious categories like age or gender, but also different languages or dialects. After all, the architecture should be able to resemble the hearing of any non-expert listener.

1.3 Outline

The following chapter will introduce traditional and modern deep ML methods and motivate both approaches by discussing their individual strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, key concepts such as gradient descent optimization, learning strategies and pattern analysis will be explained. Acoustic modelling does not only require knowledge in ML, but also in phonetics, the science of human speech sounds. Consequently, this thesis will also cover a short recap on human speech production, introduce the concept of phones and phonemes, and explain different categories of speech sounds.

The three subsequent chapters focus on acoustic modelling and speech analysis in the domains of PD, Covid-19 and aphasia, respectively. Each section first provides an introduction into the particular medical condition and then outlines the related scientific discourse. Afterwards, the model design and experimental setup are explained, as well as the data utilized during the individual experiments. A detailed description and visualization of findings, each chapter is then rounded up with a discussion and the overall contribution to the progress of research.

The summary will contextualize the results from the previous chapters within the scope of the entire thesis and outline the major similarities and differences between the three presented domains. Lastly, the work is concluded with a brief revision of the identified problems and the proposed answers, as well as an outlook on prospective research topics which could be derived from this work.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

2.1 Traditional Machine Learning

2.1.1 Fundamentals

This chapter lays the theoretical foundation for all presented models, methods and experiments throughout this thesis. As such, it introduces the groundwork on which this thesis was built. None of the methods or theories presented in the scope of this chapter were contributed by the author of this thesis. The content of this chapter is based on relevant standard literature of the particular disciplines. The sections on traditional and deep ML were strongly influenced by the books *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning* [Bish06], *Maschinelles Lernen* [Alpa19] and *Artificial Intelligence – A Modern Approach* [Russ21]. Insights into speech and language understanding were mainly grounded on the books *Fundamentals of speech recognition* [Rabi93] and *Introduction to Natural Language Processing* [Eise19]. If no further references were provided, the presented theory was based on those textbooks.

The core principle of ML is that a machine is able to solve the problem of mapping an observation x to a prediction y , such that the deviation between y and the expected value \hat{y} is reasonably small, and that this mapping was not defined by another intelligent unit, but was estimated through exploration of prior observations. The most common technique is to expose a ML model to a collection of training samples. One sample consists of the observation itself, for example an image, audio file or any feature vector, and additionally some ground truth information. This is the expected output which the model should produce if it was successful at processing the respective observation. Consequently, the correctness of a prediction could be formulated in terms of the prediction and that reference. Through an iterative scheme, the parameters of a model are repeatedly updated to improve the correctness of predictions. An ML algorithm hence derives task-specific rules from a set of examples. The amount of available examples directly influences the resulting model performance. The more versatile data is available during optimization, the more a model is able to explore the potential input space. Consequently, it is less likely to see an unfamiliar pattern later during application.

There are three major approaches to train a classifier or regressor. The standard method is called supervised learning, during which the model is exposed to a sample

x , and the optimization is performed based on some reference \hat{y} . The term *supervised* indicates that one is guiding and monitoring the training process by using some sort of ground truth information. The second discipline encompasses unsupervised learning approaches. For this setup, it is not required to have information about y , as the algorithm will not be exposed to it. An important category of such methods are auto-encoders. An auto-encoder learns some sort of feature extraction by taking an input signal $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, mapping it down to a lower-dimensional space \mathbb{R}^d , where usually $d \ll n$, and then trying to reconstruct the original signal from this low-dimensional representation. Such architecture is composed of an encoder and a decoder, and the hidden low-dimensional representations from the former are called bottleneck features. During unsupervised training, the auto-encoder receives an input x , encodes it to the bottleneck feature space, then decodes the bottleneck features to recreate x . The loss can be described as the difference between the input and output of the model, making it unnecessary to have any further reference. Lastly, there is the method of semi-supervised learning. It refers to a combination of supervised and unsupervised techniques. Normally, some model is first trained in an unsupervised fashion, for example an auto-encoder. This auto-encoder is used afterwards to extract features which can then be used for classification. A straightforward reason for such a setup could be to use a large dataset during the stage of unsupervised learning, where no reference information for the task at hand is available, but the system could still explore the different realizations of a particular signal.

2.1.2 The Importance of Data

Most ML models build their success on the quality and quantity of available data during training. Whilst the quantity of data is self-explanatory, the quality certainly is not. The difference between a low- and high-quality dataset does not always manifest in the observed results. If one is lucky, the findings show that the quality of the dataset was not sufficient for the particular task. However, one could also be unlucky, and the findings would indicate a decently performing model, only to learn during deployment that the architecture had not learned anything. The quality of a dataset, and this is a crucial point of this thesis, does not reflect the quality of the data itself. It reflects the quality of annotation, the meaningful distribution of samples, the balance between classes and the extent to which a dataset is able to reflect the real world.

Ideally, a set of samples comes with predefined training, development (sometimes also called validation) and test splits. The training portion usually comprises the most data, and as the name already gives away, it is used during training to actively tweak the parameters of a ML model. In an iterative optimization scheme commonly applied in deep learning, it is necessary to regularly validate the training progress, such that the procedure could be terminated as soon as the model reached convergence. One full iteration of training and validation is also called an epoch. The data used during validation is that from the development split. Note that it is only used to determine if the model had improved in the last epoch, the model's parameters are not updated during validation. The motivation of this procedure is to prevent the architecture from overfitting. In ML, we want an algorithm to learn decision rules

that apply on a general basis. If the model is large enough, and training continues for too long, the model may likely learn individual properties of the training data, which are not helpful for the task. For example, a neural network trained on image classification (predict the object shown in an image) should learn how to extract features from an image and how to interpret them. If the model starts memorizing certain images from the training set, this is likely not helpful to successfully classify new, unseen images. As soon as an architecture starts memorizing training-examples instead of learning rules that apply in general, it is overfitting on the training data. This point can easily be identified during optimization by running the validation procedure after every epoch. The results on the validation data should slowly improve over a number of subsequent iterations. As soon as the results observed for the validation data start to degrade, the model began to over-fit. Lastly, after a successful training, it is important to test the goodness of the resulting model. Testing can obviously not be done with the training data, because the model had seen it already. The validation data was not seen (the parameters had not been updated on it), but the results computed with it served as the condition to stop the optimization, so it must also be ruled out for testing. Hence, a third data split is required, one that had never been touched until that very last step of testing. It gives a more reliable estimate of what a model is really able to produce and also serves as the data basis to compute important metrics for reporting and documentation.

A key requirement for the three splits is that they are as independent as possible. For a speech dataset, this implies many different conditions, some of which have to be met, others are a plus which will increase the quality of a dataset. An important example of a necessary condition is the distribution of speakers. The samples of one contributor must only be assigned to one of the three splits. If the speaker was seen during training, we do not want to include him or her for testing, because the model should be able to handle not this particular speaker, but any *other* speaker as well. For the same reason, all three splits should also contain mostly unique sequences (of phonemes, characters, or others) for example. Another important criterion is called balance, and it reflects properties of the raw data as well as the annotation. Ideally, the collected data represents the potential input space during deployment. If a speech dataset contained 80 % male speakers, it would poorly reflect the average population, and the resulting model would likely be biased towards male speakers. A similar problem could arise from imbalances in the ground truth information. If one target class (for example a speech sound) was poorly represented in the dataset, then the model could tend to ignore it completely.

If the requirement of having meaningful training, development and test splits was met, the overall diversity of the dataset greatly affects its quality. Note that this is a general rule of thumb. In some cases, for example if the model would only be used on clean, nearly noise-free data, then it could be helpful to stick to this ideal scenario during training and restrict diversity. In general, however, a diverse speech dataset is more likely to produce robust results. Diversity is characterized by a high variability of speakers (number, age, gender, dialect, and others), microphones, acoustic environments, spoken sentences and more. The more an algorithm is able to explore during training, the less likely it is to end up in a blind spot during deployment. Hence, if the diversity within a dataset plays such an important role, then having

Figure 2.1: Subsequent steps of an iterative gradient descent optimization over a quadratic error curve with respect to some parameter θ .

for example high-quality audio recordings may not necessarily mean having a high-quality dataset. Whilst the audio quality may be very good and there would only be little amounts of noise, the resulting model would require exactly these conditions during application. If it had seen many types of noise, chances are much larger that a noisy input could still be processed successfully.

2.1.3 Parameter Optimization

All ML models, traditional as well as deep, have to learn a particular task before they could be considered useful. The procedure of learning is called optimization. Upon creation of a model, its parameters are, in most cases, initialized with random values. In the iterative learning procedure, the model is then shown samples of data, and the predicted output is compared with the expected one. The difference between the two is referred to as the loss. There are numerous ways to formulate such loss, one of the most well-known variants is the mean squared error (MSE):

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2 \quad (2.1)$$

In the above equation, \hat{y} represents the expectation and y the prediction. Accordingly, the produced error is always positive, and only if $y = \hat{y}$, the error becomes 0. Although primarily used for regression tasks, MSE loss could also be applied in a classification setup. Figure 2.1 illustrates a corresponding error curve which, for the sake of simplicity, only depends on a single parameter θ . Any deviation of a prediction y from the reference \hat{y} causes the loss (or error) to increase quadratically. While Equation 2.1 describes the error in terms of the prediction y , Figure 2.1 visualizes the error in terms of some parameter θ . In fact, the relationship between y and θ lays

the foundation for all gradient-based optimization strategies. A learning algorithm could be formulated as some function $f_{\theta}(x) = y$, where θ denotes the learnable parameters of function $f(x)$. If θ changes, the output y of algorithm f changes as well. Consequently, if we want to change the prediction y to bring it closer to a reference \hat{y} , we have to adjust θ accordingly. The main goal in gradient descent optimization is to evaluate the error in terms of one particular parameter and analyze how said parameter had to be changed to lower the error. The example in Figure 2.1 simplifies the problem in a way that the error only depended on a single parameter. In practice, learning algorithms often comprise a large number of parameters, and each of them influences the final loss. Therefore, it is almost impossible to fully evaluate the resulting hyperplane which describes the error. If such a global analysis of the error is infeasible, it could instead be performed locally. In this case, one is looking for $\Delta\theta$, a small modification of θ such that the error would decrease. This approach is called gradient descent optimization and it is one of the most important techniques to optimize parameter-intensive ML architectures.

Figure 2.1 illustrates several update steps for θ , which consequently lead to a lower error. As the name of the method already implies, the local gradient on the error hyperplane is determined with respect to the parameter to be updated. Its magnitude reflects the steepness on the hyperplane, and the gradient vector points towards the direction of increase. Hence, to lower the error, the parameter is updated by some component $\Delta\theta$ that points into the opposite direction, which equals a multiplication with -1 . Additionally, the local steepness of the hyperplane plays an important role in the update step. As shown in Figure 2.1, an increasing steepness leads to a larger step size. This can be desirable because the further we approach a minimum during optimization, the smaller the step size should be to prevent overshooting. Nevertheless, if the gradient's magnitude is too large, this may already cause overshooting and the algorithm would not reach convergence. This is why it is common to take smaller steps into the right direction by multiplying the update $\Delta\theta$ with some learning rate η . The learning rate must be chosen carefully, if it is too small, the gradient descent algorithm is likely to converge in a local minimum, if it is too large, the algorithm would overshoot. In the worst case, the gradients would start diverging as they have no upper bound, this is commonly known as the exploding gradients problem.

Whilst gradient descent is certainly one of the most frequently used optimization methods today, it introduces an important requirement. Performing an update step for the parameters of a model is only possible if all sub-parts of the model are differentiable functions, and that their derivative is at least partially non-zero. An example for a non-differentiable function is the *argmax* operation, which yields the index of the largest element inside a vector. A differentiable alternative of *argmax* is introduced in the section on deep ML. The second requirement of having a non-zero derivative over a continuous interval would be violated by the step function.

Figure 2.2 shows the development of training and development loss during optimization of a neural network over 50 epochs. The plot was taken from the training of a deep acoustic model and it illustrates the different stages of an iterative optimization like a textbook example. Initially, over the course of the first ten epochs, the network improved quite quickly. Notice that the development loss was smaller than the training loss after each epoch. The reason was that the training loss of one epoch is

Figure 2.2: Loss values computed on training (blue) and development (orange) data splits during optimization. The red dashed line indicates the epoch (32) with the lowest development loss. This is a typical pattern of an overfitting model, which started to learn rules that only applied on the training data and were not helpful on a general basis.

computed as the averaged loss over all training samples of said epoch. Consequently, the model learns from the loss of each training example, and the development loss is then computed with the improved model parameters after the entire epoch is finished. After the rapid improvement over the first few epochs, the two loss values for training and development continued to decrease. However, it can be seen that in the interval from epoch 10 to 30, the difference between the two loss values was shrinking. The average training error decreased quicker than the development error. This pattern could be observed because the model did not only learn decision rules which would generalize on unseen data, but it had already started to remember particular characteristics of the training data, which held no relevant information about the problem at hand. The training loss kept decreasing until the very last epoch, hence the model was able to learn more and more decision rules that were helpful for the training data. Unfortunately, these rules turned out to be unhelpful for the unseen development data. The smallest loss value computed on this portion was observed at epoch 32 (as indicated by the red dashed line). From this point on, the model's performance on the development set deteriorated, which was a clear indicator of overfitting. The steady increase of the development loss after epoch 32 revealed that the model was forgetting valid decision rules, in favor of case-specific decision boundaries, which only applied on the particular set of training examples. With a high-quality dataset, it is usually straightforward to identify a model that learned invalid decision rules. If some of the necessary principles introduced in the subsection on the importance of data were violated, it could be impossible to find that an architecture was overfitting. One such scenario would be if the same speakers were included in both the training and development data splits. As the model would learn speaker-dependent decision rules, which would clearly not be helpful for processing new speakers, this behavior would not be detected because the rules would also be

Figure 2.3: Decision boundaries produced by an SVM classifier, the margin is shaded in yellow. a) shows the hard-margin case, where samples are distributed in a way that they are linearly separable. The dotted line indicates another decision boundary which would successfully separate the two classes, but would result in a smaller margin. b) shows the same distribution of class samples as a), with the addition of two new samples (solid colors) which violate the condition of linearly separable clusters. This problem requires a soft-margin SVM.

helpful for the speakers in the development set, simply because they overlap with those from the training split. A careful selection of data is therefore indispensable not only for a reasonable optimization, but also for the termination of it.

2.1.4 Traditional Algorithms

Throughout this thesis, ML algorithms are grouped into two major categories, ‘traditional’ and ‘deep’. The former encompasses all methods that had already been employed before the breakthrough of the latter, deep neural networks. Although there are plenty of applications where deep models outperform traditional approaches in a direct comparison, it would be a beginner’s mistake to immediately rule out the toolkit of non-deep methods. It is a matter of fact that many modern ML solutions rely on a combination of neural networks and traditional algorithms, simply because they come with some important advantages which sometimes even renders them superior to the omnipresent neural networks.

A frequent reason to select a traditional method over a neural network is the amount of parameters they employ, which is in most cases a lot smaller. Accordingly, they require less amount of training data and are less prone to overfitting. Furthermore, neural networks are commonly very demanding with respect to hardware, particularly during optimization. But also after successful training, a traditional algorithm is likely to outperform the neural network when it comes to computational costs. Whilst this may not be a primary concern in a research environment, it strongly impacts the deployment of ML solutions, and ultimately still justifies the application of various traditional algorithms and toolkits.

One of the most popular non-deep methods is the so-called support-vector machine (SVM). Given two point clouds of samples that belong to different classes, the idea

of the SVM is to find an ideal decision boundary. Figure 2.3a shows two such clusters of samples, green and orange, and it also illustrates a decision boundary colored in red. The dotted line also represents a valid decision boundary for the given data, but the idea behind SVMs is to find a boundary which maximizes the margin between it and the samples of the separated classes. This is what is called the ideal decision boundary in the SVM algorithm. The intuition is to increase the robustness of the model. If a sample close to the boundary showed some variance, it would be more likely to be classified correctly if the distance to the boundary, hence the distance to the wrong class, was sufficiently large. Let

$$\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} - b = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

describe a hyperplane, and \mathbf{x}_i and y_i are the feature vectors and class labels $y \in \{-1, 1\}$, respectively, then we want to find \mathbf{w} and b which satisfy

$$\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_i - b \leq -1 \quad \text{if } y_i = -1 \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_i - b \geq +1 \quad \text{if } y_i = +1 \quad (2.4)$$

The two conditions can be combined to

$$y_i(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_i - b) \geq +1 \quad (2.5)$$

The resulting classifier could then simply be formulated as

$$f(x) = \text{sgn}(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} - b) \quad (2.6)$$

The scalar b now reflects the offset of the plane from the coordinate system's origin, and \mathbf{w} is a normal vector on the plane. To find the decision boundary with the largest margin, the objective is to minimize $\|\mathbf{w}\|^2$. Whilst this may sound counterintuitive on the first glance, there is a straightforward geometric explanation. Equations 2.3 and 2.4 define the margin from the decision boundary such that the feature vectors which fall exactly on that margin, and hence define the hyperplane, produce an absolute output of $|1|$. If we ignore the offset b for the sake of simplicity, then it is trivial that a larger \mathbf{x} requires a smaller \mathbf{w} to yield the same scalar result of $|1|$. The method is called support vector machine because the samples which lie exactly on their respective margin are support vectors of that plane.

The hard-margin variant of the SVM is often infeasible because the underlying data is not linearly separable. In this case, the SVM should allow for some samples to be located inside of the margin, or even on the wrong side of the decision boundary. The constraint from 2.5 is then softened by adding a slack variable such that

$$y_i(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_i - b) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad (2.7)$$

If a sample \mathbf{x}_i is located exactly on the margin (a support vector), or outside of it on the correct side of the decision boundary, then ξ_i equals 0. In any other case, it is equal to the relative distance from the margin hyperplane of the correct class. This can be written in terms of a hinge loss function:

$$\xi_i = \max(0, 1 - y_i(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}_i - b)) \quad (2.8)$$

Consequently, for the soft-margin SVM, the loss which has to be minimized can be written in terms of $\|\mathbf{w}\|^2$ plus the contribution of samples which violate the margin [Alpa 19]:

$$L = \frac{1}{2}\|\mathbf{w}\|^2 + C \sum_i \xi_i \quad (2.9)$$

The hyper-parameter C allows to dynamically adjust the contribution of the hinge loss. For smaller values of C , the loss is more dependant on $\|\mathbf{w}\|^2$, which results in a larger margin. The case of a soft-margin SVM is also shown in 2.3b, which shows an almost identical distribution as in 2.3a. Two new samples (solid colors) had been introduced, one for each class. The new orange sample would still be classified correctly, however, it would lie inside of the margin. The additional green sample is located farther away of the original green cluster, and it would not be classified correctly.

The SVM can be extended with a non-linear kernel to apply the algorithm to datasets which are not linearly separable more reliably. It could also be used for regression instead of classification, where the final regression line would only be affected by samples that lie within the margin. Whilst the method is quite versatile, it comes with an important disadvantage. Particularly during classification, it is often helpful to compute the posterior $P(y_i|\mathbf{x})$ which describes the probability of a given sample \mathbf{x} to belong to class y_i . Such information cannot be directly computed from an SVM classifier and instead has to be estimated through a cross-validation performed during training.

Another classifier worth mentioning belongs to the group of ensemble learning techniques. Accordingly, it would actually be wrong to call it a single classifier, but rather an aggregation of many classifiers. The idea is that if high-dimensional data had to be analyzed, then this problem could essentially be decomposed into an independent analysis of many subsets of lower dimension. For each of these subsets, a new classifier is learned in the form of a classification tree. The tree's root receives an input, plugs it into a decision function, and then assigns the sample to the corresponding output node. As there are many decision trees acting in parallel, and the ultimate result is commonly acquired through a majority vote, the method is called Random Forest (RF) classification.

If a single tree in the RF only sees a small portion of the entire feature vector and has to make a decision based on this limited knowledge, then it can be considered a weak classifier. In this sense, *weak* does not stand for a poor performance, it rather reflects the success compared to a large classifier which would see the entire feature vector. This raises the question why it would be desirable to choose a weak classifier over a stronger one. RFs are known primarily for their ability to resist overfitting [Russ 21], even if the hyperparameters, for example the number of trees in the forest, were chosen too high. The weak classifiers which contribute to the final majority decision are, as the name already suggests, usually too weak to overfit on the problem. And at the same time, if there are a few trees which suffered from overfitting, their impact is mitigated by the other trees.

A single decision tree within a RF can have an arbitrary depth (which is commonly capped at some point). Interestingly, a RF operates similar to an artificial neural network. Figure 2.4 illustrates a feed-forward architecture which processes an in-

Figure 2.4: Similarities between Random Forests and Deep Neural Networks. The initial randomized feature selection could be represented as a sparse fully-connected layer of a neural network. The subsequent decision tree classifiers could be approximated with regular fully-connected layers. Lastly, the majority vote would yet be another fully connected layer with weights equal to 1.

coming observation step by step, from the input to the output layer, which maps the stream of information down to the number of target classes. The internal stages are highlighted above and below the sketch for the RF and the DNN, respectively. In the beginning, the RF selects a random set of features from the input feature vector as input for a particular decision tree. This is equivalent to a sparse fully-connected layer of a neural network, in which some weights are equal to 1, hence they allow information to pass through, whilst most others are 0. In the following, each decision tree performs its own classification, and outputs its own result. This is reflected in the hidden layers in the middle of the neural network. Ultimately, the decision of the random forest is aggregated by majority voting, which could be realized through another fully-connected layer with all weights set to 1, assuming that the previous layer would contain $N_{trees} \times N_{classes}$ output nodes, and for each tree, the nodes would output 1 for the predicted class and 0 for all others. Subsection 2.2 will provide a more detailed overview over DNN architectures, and introduce important properties which distinguish them from RFs, for example the combination of linear and non-linear functions. On the other hand, a decision tree applies a sequence of Boolean operations [Russ21] which makes the entire decision process easy to understand. This makes decision trees and RFs in general an excellent choice for any tasks where a high interpretability is required. The similarities shown in Figure 2.4 are illustrated mainly due to their helpful insights to understand the motivation of certain techniques introduced later in the following section on deep learning.

2.1.5 Dimensionality Reduction

A large portion of today’s ML-related research focuses on problems which enable researchers to compare their results to some sort of ground truth, and then evaluate with respect to certain metrics. This approach comes with the important advantage of being able to compare different methods and quantify how well they solve a particular task. In the domain of acoustic modelling for example, it has become extremely popular to report results for English phoneme recognition on the TIMIT corpus [Garo 93]. The state-of-the-art *wav2vec 2.0* model [Baev 20] achieved a Phoneme Error Rate (PER) of 8.3 % on the test split of TIMIT. The more it has become popular to report new benchmark-defining results on reference dataset, the more important it should also be to understand how these successful models operate and, in case they are unable to produce a correct result, what is the reason for a false prediction. ML is not limited to feeding data in and getting predictions out. The internal high-dimensional representations of a model, commonly referred to as hidden states, already encode plenty of information about the observed signal. An analysis of these intermediate feature vectors can provide helpful insights into the various properties that have a strong influence on the data distribution. This is where techniques for dimensionality reduction, density estimation, representation learning or clustering come into play, as they enable researchers to better understand high-dimensional data. They help to track down edge cases where methods may be unable to produce correct outputs or identify outliers within a dataset which are harder to interpret with general rules. Moreover, they enable researchers to visualize vast amounts of information in a concise way and find out how individual properties affect feature vectors from a larger population.

A frequently used method for dimensionality reduction is the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). It does not take information about the ground truth y into account, hence it allows to project data into a lower dimension without trying to preserve information about y . Instead, a PCA decomposition projects high-dimensional data from \mathbb{R}^n down to d components in \mathbb{R}^d . The first principal component is computed as a projection from \mathbb{R}^n to \mathbb{R}^d along the direction of maximum variance in \mathbb{R}^n . Every new principal component must be orthogonal to all previous projections, and represents the direction of the largest remaining variance. The intuition behind the approach is to preserve as much information as possible.

Consider a dataset [Xu 92] of around 1.800 samples of 8×8 bitmaps representing handwritten digits from 0 to 9. Each pixel is represented as an integer in the range from 0 to 15. Accordingly, a single sample x comprises 64 values. If we use a 2-dimensional PCA, estimated over all samples, then we only preserve the two directions with the maximum variance in \mathbb{R}^{64} which are orthogonal to each other, and project their information to \mathbb{R}^2 . Figure 2.5 shows the projection of samples belonging to class 0, 1 or 7. Although the feature space had been reduced by a factor of 32, the samples representing digit 0 clearly separate from the other two classes. Because the digits 1 and 7 look very similar, they show a noticeable overlap in the 2-dimensional space. This clearly highlights one of the key strengths of the PCA: Because it does not take into account ground truth information, it also does not yield a projection which would result in a decent separation of classes. As it primarily focuses on preserving as much variance as possible, it enabled us to identify 1 and 7 as digits which

Figure 2.5: 2-dimensional PCA decomposition estimated over 8×8 bitmaps containing handwritten digits between 0 and 9. The plot only shows the PCA for samples of digits 0, 1 and 7. The cluster of 0 samples clearly separates from the other two classes. Samples containing a 1 or 7 show a clear overlap, which is explained by the similar shape of both digits.

look similar, without looking at the bitmap examples. In this toy example, this intuition is straightforward, but it also applies on many other problems, where it may be much harder, if not impossible, to manually investigate all the different cases. An important property of a PCA is that the principal components are eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of the underlying data [Alpa 19]. Consequently, the resulting projection to the lower-dimensional space is also applicable to new observations.

This is an important difference in comparison to another method for dimensionality reduction used throughout this thesis, which is called t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) [Hint 02]. Given a set of observations in the high-dimensional space, it is also possible to preserve information in the lower-dimensional space by preserving neighborhood information. Let

$$p_{ij} = \frac{\exp(-d_{ij}^2)}{\sum_{k \neq i} \exp(-d_{ik}^2)} \quad (2.10)$$

denote the probability of a sample i to select sample j as its neighbor out of k neighboring samples, with

$$d_{ij}^2 = \frac{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \quad (2.11)$$

defining the distance between two observations. This distance is scaled by $2\sigma_i^2$ depending on the density of samples around \mathbf{x}_i . For samples \mathbf{z} from the lower-dimensional space, this neighborhood-relationship can be expressed as

$$q_{ij} = \frac{\exp(-\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j\|^2)}{\sum_{k \neq i} \exp(-\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_k\|^2)} \quad (2.12)$$

Note that the scaling factor for varying sample densities σ was removed in this expression, such that the density would remain constant. The aim of a t-SNE embedding is

Figure 2.6: 2-dimensional t-SNE embedding computed from 8×8 bitmaps containing handwritten digits between 0 and 9. For each digit, samples form one (or more) distinct clusters, with few outliers. Notice that, unlike observed through the PCA result, the similarity of digits 1 and 7 is barely reflected in the t-SNE embedding.

to find a distribution of samples Q_i in the low-dimensional space which is very similar to that of observations P_i in the original space. The Kullback-Leibler divergence can be used as a metric to describe how different the two distributions are to each other. Accordingly, to find a suitable arrangement of samples Q_i , the objective is to minimize

$$\sum_i KL(P_i || Q_i) = \sum_i \sum_j p_{ij} \log \frac{p_{ij}}{q_{ij}} \quad (2.13)$$

A t-SNE embedding for the aforementioned toy dataset of handwritten digits is shown in Figure 2.6. The illustration shows a clear separation of samples which belong to different classes. This is particularly impressive considered that t-SNE is yet another unsupervised method for dimensionality reduction. The algorithm had no ground truth information available, and only by preserving statistical relationships in the lower-dimensional space, clusters of samples clearly correspond to certain digits. It is also possible to identify outliers, which could potentially lead to false classification results. For the visualization of high-dimensional data structures, t-SNE is a very strong and popular method. However, it is important to understand its limitations in order to choose the best method for a particular task. A closer look on Figure 2.6 reveals that the similarity of digits 1 and 7, which was clearly preserved in the PCA result, is not visible anymore. The reason for the loss of this information lies in the neighborhood relationships which should be preserved by t-SNE. In equations 2.10 and 2.12, parameter k represents the number of local neighbors considered, commonly referred to as the *perplexity* of the embedding. Within a cluster of samples of the same class, all these samples will prioritize each other as potential neighbor choices. This is why the embedding space produces such distinct point clouds for particular classes. At the same time, effects of inter-class relationships seemed to contribute less to the overall result. This could be mitigated by choosing larger values for k , but this could quickly introduce too much disturbance in the lower-dimensional space.

Figure 2.7: Toy example of a Hidden Markov Model which describes a series of observable outputs (drinks) and an unobservable sequence of states. Such a model is used to estimate the most probable sequence of hidden states from another observable sequence. π_i denote entry probabilities, the arrows summarize all possible transitions \mathbf{T} between states, and the probabilities for each drink (observable output) are dependent on the weather conditions (unobservable state).

Another downside of t-SNE, potentially much more important than the first one, is that it performs an embedding, usually to a 2- or 3-dimensional space, of the data at hand, by searching for a new distribution of points Q_i such that they resemble the characteristics of the distribution in P_i . The result is a low-dimensional distribution, but t-SNE, unlike PCA, does not produce a mapping to this new space. Consequently, any new observation cannot be projected, and instead it is required to compute an entirely new embedding.

2.1.6 Traditional Sequence Understanding

As one of the core topics of this thesis is phone recognition, the section on traditional ML techniques should be completed by the Viterbi algorithm, which had been used in the domain of sequence understanding for decades, and is still among the most popular methods to interpret sequential model output. It solves the problem of decoding the most probable sequence of hidden states from an underlying sequence of observable outputs. Figure 2.7 illustrates a stochastic process which follows the Markov assumption. It states that the next state s_{t+1} only depends on the current state s_t , and is independent of the state sequence prior to s_t [Boch 13]. At $t = 0$, the initial probability of each state is denoted by π_i . The arrows between the different states indicate the probabilities to transition from one state to another, or to remain in the current state. Within every state, there are different probabilities to observe a certain output. In the presented example, the output is one of three drinks. To understand what the Viterbi algorithm does, let us consider the following problem: A professor lives in the remote countryside, and at the start of each lecture, he sits in front of his webcam with a beverage and welcomes the audience. Only with the information about which drinks the professor had for the past four lectures, we want to estimate the *hidden* underlying sequence of weather conditions at his location. For

a given sequence of drinks, there are different possible sequences of underlying weather conditions. Each of those sequences has a different probability. Viterbi’s algorithm takes the different entry, transition and emission probabilities into account, and allows to determine the most probable sequence of states which led to the observations. It belongs to the group of dynamic programming algorithms, and instead of keeping track of all possible state sequences, which is computationally inefficient, it only considers the most probable path which leads to a particular state. For the first output, this can be simply given as

$$\mathbf{D}_{1,i} = \pi_i \cdot \mathbf{E}_{i,o_1} \quad (2.14)$$

\mathbf{D} is a $T \times S$ matrix, where T denotes the number of time steps, and S the number of states. π_i is the probability to start in state i , and matrix \mathbf{E} contains emission probabilities for each state and each symbol. Consequently, equation 2.14 denotes the joint probabilities of starting in state i and observing the first output symbol o_1 . For all following time steps, \mathbf{D} is updated as

$$\mathbf{D}_{t,i} = \max_k (\mathbf{D}_{t-1,k} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{k,i} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{i,o_t}) \quad (2.15)$$

At time step t , Viterbi considers every of the k possible states from the previous time step $\mathbf{D}_{t-1,k}$, multiplies it with the transition probability $\mathbf{T}_{k,i}$ to traverse from k to current state i and the respective emission probability for the current observation in that state. As described before, Viterbi only keeps track of the most probable path which leads to current state i , hence only the maximum value is preserved. Viterbi’s algorithm is computationally efficient, and it is guaranteed to find an optimal solution, either by storing the state sequence during path search, or by simple backtracking afterwards. Coming back to the previous example, if the professor had the drinks «*Lemonade, Tea, Beer, Lemonade*», the most probable state (weather) sequence could be decoded as «*Cloudy, Rainy, Cloudy, Cloudy*». Hidden Markov Models will not be used in the scope of this thesis, but the presented algorithm is of major importance to decode the sequential output of neural networks as well.

The following section introduces the elementary building blocks of deep neural networks (DNN), provides insights into parameter optimization and explains the concept of alignment-free sequence understanding with deep architectures.

2.2 Deep Learning

2.2.1 Introduction

Deep learning (DL) is a sub-discipline of ML which focuses on the application of artificial neural networks (ANN). Due to many baseline-defining results achieved with DL models, they have become the primary choice throughout many fields of ML. Every component of an ANN relies on the same building block, the perceptron. An example of a perceptron, commonly also referred to as a neuron, is shown in Figure 2.8. The first version of this computational model had already been introduced in 1958 by Frank Rosenblatt [Roj96]. The main motivation of neurons used in modern neural networks is the combination of a linear and a nonlinear function. The

Figure 2.8: The base component of any deep architecture, the perceptron (also referred to as neuron), combines a linearity and a nonlinearity. By increasing the number of neurons, both in width and depth, deep models are expected to be able to approximate any function in the high-dimensional space.

linearity combines all inputs to a given neuron to a single value. In this step, every input value x_n is multiplied with its respective weight w_n , which is a learnable parameter. It is also common to add one last *auxiliary* input $x_{n+1} := 1$, which is then multiplied with the bias weight w_{n+1} . This resembles the offset from the origin if all inputs were equal to zero. The output of the linear combination is then plugged into a non-linear activation function. Such a neuron would then be able to model a linear classifier. Through concatenation of many different layers of these neurons, the Universal Approximation Theorem (UAT) implies that the entire network would be able to approximate any non-linear decision function [Alpa 19].

Although the first versions of an artificial neuron had been presented in the late 1950s, it took several more decades for the idea to show its full strengths. The original perceptron proposed by Rosenblatt would be unusable in a modern supervised learning setup. Unlike the neuron shown in Figure 2.8, it featured a step activation function. The derivative of that function is always equal to 0, hence it is unusable for gradient descent learning schemes. Another, rather practical hindrance, were the availability of parallel computing power and the lacking amount of training data. As the UAT implies, an ANN would only thrive if it was sufficiently large in size to be able to approximate a certain decision function. However, ANNs quickly comprise a large amount of trainable parameters if one concatenated several layers.

The last, and likely most important problem, was that researchers did not yet understand how to estimate an appropriate set of parameters for a neural architecture to solve a particular task. In 1974, Werbos was the first to mention the possibility of using the back-propagation algorithm to train deep networks. It took another 12 years until it was first used to successfully optimize the parameters of an ANN by Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams [Rume 86] in 1986.

2.2.2 The Backpropagation Algorithm

A major problem of gradient descent optimization methods for deep networks was that the error could only be computed at the output layer as the difference between the predicted and the expected output. At every hidden layer inside the network, such reference is unavailable. The idea of the back-propagation algorithm is, as the

name already implies, to propagate an error from the output layer through all hidden layers of the ANN, depending on how each neuron contributed to that error. Let

$$net_j = \sum_i o_i w_{ij} \quad (2.16)$$

denote the linear combination of model inputs (or outputs from a previous layer) o_i and weights w_{ij} to node j of the next layer. Let the non-linear function be the *sigmoid* activation:

$$o_j = \varphi(net_j) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-net_j}} \quad (2.17)$$

The output of this activation function ranges in the interval $[0, 1]$. If node j is an output node, we could determine the error E of the network output as the deviation between predicted o and true values y of all output nodes using the *mean squared error* (MSE) loss function L :

$$E = L(y, o) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j (y_j - o_j)^2 \quad (2.18)$$

In the above error formulation, y_j represents the expected output of node j . To optimize the parameters of the neural network, we want to find weight updates Δw . As the primary goal is to minimize the error E , the gradient w.r.t. each w can be formulated as

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ij}} \quad (2.19)$$

This term can be decomposed using the chain rule twice to get the full formulation

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} \frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{ij}} \quad (2.20)$$

Accordingly, after computing all required derivatives, the weight update can be expressed as

$$\Delta w_{ij} = o_i \cdot (o_j - y_j) \cdot o_j \cdot (1 - o_j) \quad (2.21)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} = o_j - y_j \quad (2.22)$$

$$\frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} = o_j \cdot (1 - o_j) \quad (2.23)$$

$$\frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{ij}} = o_i \quad (2.24)$$

$$(2.25)$$

As mentioned before, this update rule only applies if the error can be directly computed. At some hidden layer inside the neural network, the above formulation does not work, because the error cannot be computed in the same way. If i is a hidden

neuron which feeds information to all neurons $j \in J$ of the next layer, then the error at i can be computed as the neuron's contribution to the backpropagated errors δ_j of all neurons of the next layer:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} = \left(\sum_j w_{ij} \cdot \delta_j \right) \frac{\partial o_j}{\partial net_j} \quad (2.26)$$

This backpropagated error requires an initialization, which is precisely what happens at the networks output layer. Consequently, the backpropagated error can be written for both cases as

$$\delta_j = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_j} \frac{\partial \varphi(net_j)}{\partial net_j} & \text{if } j \text{ is output neuron} \\ \left(\sum_k w_{jk} \cdot \delta_k \right) \frac{\partial \varphi(net_j)}{\partial net_j} & \text{if } j \text{ is inner neuron} \end{cases} \quad (2.27)$$

With this recursive definition of the backpropagated error, we can write the gradient with respect to a particular weight w_{ij} as

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ij}} = o_i \delta_j \quad (2.28)$$

Lastly, the weight update Δw_{ij} can be determined by multiplying 2.28 with -1 , because we want to walk in the opposite direction to descent on the error hyperplane. In most cases, the raw gradient steps would be too large, it is therefore common to also apply a multiplicative learning rate η :

$$\Delta w_{ij} = -\eta o_i \delta_j \quad (2.29)$$

Independent of an individual neuron's position in the entire network, the weight update Δw always depends on the derivative of the activation function $\varphi(net)$. As it is multiplied with the rest of δ , if the derivative equals 0, the weight update will be 0 as well. Certain activation functions, for example the step-function, are therefore unusable for gradient descent learning schemes.

Another important phenomenon in deep layered networks when applying gradient descent optimization is the so-called *vanishing gradients* problem. Usually, the value of the derivative of $\varphi(net)$ lies in the interval $[0, 1]$. When the error is backpropagated through the entire network, it is repeatedly multiplied with this derivative in each layer. This causes the partial error at a certain node to shrink to very small values with increasing depth of the neural network. This in turn leads to very small weight updates, which could likely prevent the model from learning effectively. An effective countermeasure to deal with this problem is the implementation of skip-connections. A skip-connection is a shortcut for a hidden vector \mathbf{x} , which serves as the input to some network layer(s) $f(\mathbf{x})$. While being passed to f , it also bypasses these layers. After the computation of $f(\mathbf{x})$, the result is interpreted as a residual which is added to \mathbf{x} such that

$$\mathbf{x}_j = f(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{x}_i \quad (2.30)$$

The intuition behind the residual connection formulation in 2.30 is that any alteration of \mathbf{x} can also be expressed as the original \mathbf{x} plus some residual $f(\mathbf{x})$. During

Figure 2.9: The Sigmoid Linear Unit as an example of a non-monotonous activation function. In the plot, the two arrows represent the local gradient descent update steps if the neuron’s output was too small. Note that the output value y is equal for both arrows, and still they result in two entirely different update steps.

backpropagation, the error can pass through the skip connection without being mitigated, hence a neural network which makes use of skip connections is less likely to produce vanishing gradients.

If the gradient can shrink to very small numbers during backpropagation, the opposite behavior is also possible, because there exists no natural upper bound. This is the case of *exploding gradients*, where numbers grow so large that they usually result in a numerical overflow. Exploding gradients can be caused by high learning rates, but also by loss terms which are likely to yield large values in the beginning of the training procedure.

2.2.3 Activation Functions

As described earlier, the UAT states that by combining layers of linear combinations and non-linear activation functions, a neural network is, in theory, able to approximate any non-linear function. Whilst the linear combination does not leave much room for manipulation, the non-linear activation function can be chosen freely, if at least certain conditions are met. Two conditions had already been derived in the section on Backpropagation: Activation functions $\varphi(x)$ must *a)* have a derivative which is non-zero in at least parts of x , and *b)* should have a derivative in the range $[0, 1]$. Another very helpful, but not necessary property is monotonicity. If the activation function is not monotonous, this could induce chaos during weight updates. Figure 2.9 shows the Sigmoid Linear Unit (SiLU) [Elfw 18] activation function. The two red dot markers on the function (origin of the arrows) represent two different values of x which yield the same output $\varphi(x)$. Let us assume that, with respect to some loss function, the optimal output of the neuron would be 2 for a given observation. In that case, at the location of the left arrow, we would have to update our weights such that the next output would be larger. This however leads in the wrong direction (to the left). Values are increasing as we traverse further to the left, but they are limited at $y = 0$. Hence it is impossible at this location, for the desired output of

Figure 2.10: Common activation functions utilized in neural architectures. In the top, Sigmoid and Tanh functions are examples of continuous activations. In the bottom row, ReLU and Leaky ReLU are piecewise linear activations.

$y = 2$, to find the correct update step through gradient descent. Surprisingly, these activation functions had been successfully applied in numerous neural network architectures anyway [Li 20b, Rama 17, Merc 20, Hend 16]. It was not yet possible to fully explain why non-monotonicity could be helpful, but studies have shown that pre-activations (the result *net* from the linearity) strongly concentrated in the region where the sign of the gradient changes [Rama 17], indicating a high importance of the non-monotonic area.

With the introduced hard and soft requirements for suitable activation functions, it is now possible to outline some of the most frequently used non-linearities. Figure 2.10 illustrates four frequently used activations which can be found in many different models. One of the first activation functions which had been used in DL was the Sigmoid activation, also referred to as the logistic function. Its output is bounded in $[0, 1]$, and the maximum gradient equals 0.25 at the intersection with the y-axis. Whilst this function fulfills many requirements of a *good* nonlinearity, it comes with several weaknesses. First, the maximum gradient is rather small, and across the function, it decreases even further, which greatly increases the likeliness of vanishing gradients during backpropagation. In the same context, after a closer look at 2.29, we notice that the output of a node is a factor of the overall weight update. With the output of the Sigmoid bounded between $[0, 1]$, vanishing gradients become even more likely in the negative range of the function.

The Sigmoid is commonly not used as a standalone activation function for an entire neural network anymore, due to the presented drawbacks. However, the output bounds render it particularly useful for two scenarios. The first is the case of multi-class, multi-output scenarios, where a model is capable to predict various different classes, independent of each other. Another frequent use-case, which had slightly lost attention in the past years due to the decline of recurrent neural networks, is the application of Sigmoid activations for gating. The principle of gating is straightforward: Suppose there is a state vector \mathbf{s} that should be maintained by some instance. If the instance wanted to remove information from the state vector, this could be achieved

by zeroing out the respective information. A so-called forget-gate in recurrent networks is then realized as

$$\mathbf{s} = \text{sigmoid}(\widehat{\mathbf{s}} \cdot \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{s} \quad (2.31)$$

$\widehat{\mathbf{s}} \cdot \mathbf{x}$ denotes the concatenation of the state vector \mathbf{s} and the input vector \mathbf{x} . This is transformed back to the dimension of the original state vector through a linear projection with \mathbf{W} , and adding a bias term \mathbf{b} . The output of the resulting Sigmoid activation is a value between 0 and 1, which equals the amount of information that should be preserved from the original \mathbf{s} by multiplication. Such a forget gate is common in many implementations of recurrent cells, like the long short-term memory [Hoch97] or gated recurrent unit [Cho14]. In the case of gated activations, the idea is to produce a residual output, and have a second linear projection, the gate, which controls which parts of the suggested output should truly be emitted. This is commonly used in the *add gates* of recurrent cells, but also in other architectures like Wavenet [Oord16].

Gated activations lead straight to the second non-linear function shown in Figure 2.10, the hyperbolic tangent (Tanh). On the first glance, Tanh and Sigmoid look very similar. In fact, Tanh preserves all advantages of the Sigmoid activation function. At the same time, its output is bounded between $[-1, 1]$, making it less susceptible to the problem of vanishing gradients. It is also worth mentioning that the maximum gradient, found in the origin, is equal to 1. This is four times the maximum gradient of the Sigmoid activation, which clearly improves the effectiveness of error backpropagation. In the previously introduced case of gated activations, the idea is that two linear layers operate in parallel, and the outputs of each layer are passed through either a Sigmoid or a Tanh activation. The result is then multiplied to create the gate. The Sigmoid in this case adjusts the amount of information which passes, and the Tanh affects the amount and direction, positive or negative. In theory, one could argue that the Tanh layer alone should be capable to adjust both magnitude and direction of the output. In practice, however, it turned out that splitting this operation into two independent branches allowed neural networks to perform better, likely because the two separated tasks were easier to solve than the combination of both.

The rectified linear unit (ReLU) is an example of an activation function which, if we recall the principle of the UAT of combining linear and nonlinear functions, appears to be counterintuitive on the first glance, because it is a piecewise linear activation. For all input values $x \leq 0$, the output of the ReLU is 0. For all other x , the output equals the input. Consequently, the gradient for positive input values is always 1. This helps prevent vanishing gradients, but note that ReLU outputs have no upper bound. Therefore it is possible to run into exploding gradients if other hyperparameters, such as the learning rate, were chosen poorly. If exploding gradients had been ruled out, ReLU are usually the preferred choice over Sigmoid and Tanh, because of their (on average) slightly better results. Nevertheless, it is important to understand a tricky drawback of the normal ReLU activation, called the dying ReLU problem. If, for any reason, the pre-activation of a neuron always becomes negative, for example due to some unfortunate prior weight update, then the associated weights cannot receive any further updates, because the derivative of the activation equals 0 and thus negates any adjustments.

To overcome the problem of dying ReLU neurons, the last activation function from Figure 2.10, the Leaky ReLU, was designed. For all positive x , it is identical to the standard version of the function. In the negative area though, instead of outputting 0 everywhere, the activation now uses a very small gradient a . The function can then be defined as

$$\text{LeakyReLU}(x) = \begin{cases} a \cdot x & \text{if } x \leq 0 \\ x & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2.32)$$

A common value for the gradient a is 0.01. The behavior of the activation function is therefore very similar to that of the original ReLU, without the drawback of dying neurons. For a clear visualization, the gradient of the Leaky ReLU in Figure 2.10 was set to $a := 0.2$.

Another important property of activation functions which had not been discussed yet is whether its output is zero-centered or not. The output of an activation is called zero-centered if the mean output of a set of input values which follow a standard normal distribution is 0. From the aforementioned activations, only the hyperbolic tangent is a zero-centered activation function. To understand why zero-centered outputs are desirable, we have to take a few steps back. If we look at the activation functions again, and recall that neural networks often learn through backpropagation, then we want the outputs of our activation function to be distributed closely around 0, simply because the gradient is relatively high there, and the functions often have their largest expressiveness in this region. Expressiveness is simply a term which describes how different the output values for two similar inputs are, and it is directly linked to the gradient. According to the definition of a zero-centered activation function, if this property is violated, for example in the case of ReLU, then the outputs of layer i are not zero-centered anymore. This could cause problems for layer j , which could experience a drift away from the most expressive region of the ReLU. Without the implementation of effective countermeasures, the linear projection between layers i and j needs to learn to remove the drift. Whilst this is possible, in practice it turns out to slow down training significantly, because the drift adds up layer for layer. An effective strategy to mitigate any drift are normalization layers.

To round up the subsection on activation functions, we need to have a look at one of the most important activations for classification models, the Softmax activation. Its sole purpose is to scale the n outputs of a layer, generally the last layer of a classification model, to match a probability density [Good 16]. In other words, if every output node of the neural network represents a particular class, then the Softmax activation yields the posterior probability $P(y|x)$ for class y given observation x . The Softmax activation is defined as

$$\text{Softmax}(z)_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_j e^{z_j}} \quad (2.33)$$

However, the main motivation behind using a Softmax activation after the last layer of a classification network is not to determine actual probability scores. To find out which class the model predicted, a simple argmax would be faster, but this operation is not differentiable. The Softmax activation on the other hand provides class probabilities and, at the same time, it is a differentiable operation which seamlessly integrates into the backpropagation framework.

Figure 2.11: Visualization of batch and layer normalization strategy in deep neural networks and their respective field of view over which the normalization is applied. Axes represent batch (B), channel (C) and time (T) domain.

2.2.4 Normalization Layers

As explained in the section on activation functions, the statistics of a neuron’s input values contribute significantly to the expressiveness of its output. As an example, let us consider a set of $N := 100000$ input values, which follow a standard normal distribution with 0 mean and 1 standard deviation. After passing this set through a Sigmoid activation three times, a simulation yields a new mean of 0.65 and a standard deviation of 0.01. In a traditional neural network, it would be up to the weights and biases to shift the data back towards a centered mean and a more expressive standard deviation.

To enforce each layer inside a neural network to produce expressive output and not suffer from any shift inside the hidden representations passing through the model, different normalization techniques had been developed. They all share the common idea of re-centering and re-scaling the data distribution, but they normalize over different dimensions of the tensor passed through the model. Before looking at any particular normalization technique, let us define a tensor $\mathbf{H}(B, T, C)$ which comprises the dimensions of batch-size B , time T and channel C . The first technique which had been successfully employed to train deep models faster and with increased performance was batch normalization [Ioff15]. To understand the concept behind the approach, we first need to introduce the concept of batches. Coming back to the example tensor \mathbf{H} , one could argue that for a single audio signal, dimensions for time and channels should suffice. In DL however, it is common practice to show the model not only a single input (audio, image, text or others), but various inputs at the same time. This *stack* of inputs is called a batch, and the exact number of samples in one batch is described by the batch-size. The motivation is that by computing the error over an entire batch of samples, e.g. 32 inputs, the impact of outliers or label errors (mistakes in the ground truth annotation) is diminished. Training on a larger batch size can also help prevent overfitting, because the model cannot learn the characteristics of a single sample by heart. The number of possible combinations of samples in a batch, given a sufficiently large dataset, is huge.

During batch normalization, the content of tensor \mathbf{H} is normalized per channel, over all time steps and all samples in the batch, back to 0 mean and 1 standard deviation. The normalized dimension is also illustrated in Figure 2.11. It can be formulated as

$$\hat{x}_k = \frac{x_k - E[x_k]}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[x_k] + \epsilon}} \cdot \gamma_k + \beta_k \quad (2.34)$$

In the above equation, $E[x_k]$ and $\text{Var}[x_k]$ represent the mean and variance over all x of channel k , respectively. The ϵ added to the variance ensures numerical stability, and γ_k and β_k are learnable parameters. They enable the network to choose the optimal scaling and shift for each channel during normalization. As stated in the original paper, “*by setting $\gamma_k = \sqrt{\text{Var}[x_k]}$ and $\beta_k = E[x_k]$, we could recover the original activations, if that were the optimal thing to do*” [Ioff 15]. If tensor \mathbf{H} is normalized over the time and batch dimensions, then the scaling and shift applied to a particular sample depends on the other samples in the batch. This is fine during training, but during inference, one expects the model to behave deterministically. Therefore, batch normalization stores running statistics of all $E[x]$ and $\text{Var}[x]$ during training, which are then applied in inference mode, without computing new statistics per batch.

Another common technique is the so-called layer normalization, which is also illustrated in Figure 2.11. Unlike the previous method, the contents of \mathbf{H} are now normalized over each individual batch [Ba 16]. The formulation is identical to that in 2.34, all that changes are the considered dimensions. Because one sample is not influenced by other samples anymore when the normalization is applied, layer norm does not estimate population statistics during training which can later be applied during inference mode. Instead, the execution is the same in both cases.

For one particular DL model, it is common to choose either batch norm or layer norm, exclusively. Some argue that the former is the primary choice for image processing tasks, and the latter excels in the domain of natural language processing (NLP), but it is tough to back up these intuitions with well-grounded sources which address the topic. Another popular question of debate is the position of normalization layers within a neural network. In this work, the application of said layers was motivated as a solution to prevent the inputs to an activation function to shift away from the most expressive region of the nonlinearity. Consequently, it should be applied between the linear and nonlinear function. This was the case in the original paper [Ioff 15], but has changed ever since. There exists no consensus about whether the normalization should be applied before or after the activation function, and frequently, the difference between the two approaches with respect to the observed results are marginal. If we look at the example presented in the introduction of normalization layers, where the standard deviation would decrease from 1.0 all the way to 0.01, then this reduced spread of information could also be recovered by applying the normalization after the Sigmoid function.

2.2.5 Convolutional Layers

In Figure 2.8, we have seen the standard example of a linear layer, which projects n inputs to m outputs by applying a $n \times m$ weight matrix plus a m -dimensional bias. Such a linear projection is helpful for sets of independent features, but it is unable

Figure 2.12: Illustration of 1-D and 2-D convolutional layers, which are able to model temporal or spatial relationships between data points.

to properly represent spatial or temporal relationships. In a standard feed-forward architecture, any internal hidden representation could be formulated in terms of a batch dimension B and a channel (or feature) dimension C . In the case of sequential data, we can add a time dimension to this representation, as in the example for the normalization layers, and the resulting tensor would be again $\mathbf{H}(B, T, C)$. Note that neighboring samples along the batch and channel dimension are likely uncorrelated, but along the time dimension, there should be some sort of relationship between adjacent samples. Ideally, some building block in a deep model is able to pick up this relationship and learn patterns along the time dimension. One popular architecture choice for such a case is the 1-dimensional convolution layer. Any model (or part of it) which mainly relies on such building blocks is called a convolutional neural network (CNN).

Figure 2.12 illustrates a 1-D convolution, which moves over a signal in time-domain and repeatedly convolves the input window with a kernel of learned weights. The size of the convolution kernel can be chosen freely, but there are a few things to consider. Most importantly, it is helpful to incorporate prior knowledge about the signal of interest which the model should analyze. An appropriate kernel size for a 1-D convolution can only be estimated if factors such as the sampling frequency of the input signal and the frequency range of interest of the particular problem (where patterns are assumed) are taken into account. Furthermore, the kernel size contributes multiplicatively to the number of parameters of the resulting convolution layer. Instead of choosing one very long convolution window, it usually makes sense to stack multiple convolution layers on top of each other to increase the resulting receptive field. An example of such an increased field of view is shown in Figure 2.13. Notice that the 1-D convolution of the second layer applies a dilated kernel. In that case, the distance between neighboring kernel elements is greater than 1. By shifting a convolution kernel over an input signal, a model is able to learn kernel configurations which can extract meaningful features. Convolutional layers are also used frequently to downsample a signal. In the case of speech processing for example, let us consider a model which receives as input a raw waveform. This waveform was sampled at a frequency of 16 kHz, and the goal of the model is to predict the particular speech sounds produced in that audio sample. Let us further assume that we had already

Figure 2.13: A stack of two 1-D convolution layers. Both layers use a kernel size of 3. The first convolution applies a dilation of 1, whilst the dilation of the second convolution equals 3. The resulting receptive field covers 9 subsequent samples from the input signal.

chosen an appropriate field of view for a stack of several convolution layers, which covers a total of 400 samples. This equals 25 ms, which is quite a popular window size for ASR. If we shifted this window with a step size of 1, then our model would produce 16.000 predictions per second. This is far more than what one could expect with respect to the number of different speech sounds spoken within one second. Furthermore, it is computationally very expensive, particularly in that part of the model which analyzes temporal context. Hence, it is common practice to shift the entire receptive field not only by a single sample, but by some step size which was common in traditional approaches as well. In the case of speech processing, a popular choice for the step length would be 10 ms. The resulting model would produce 100 outputs per second, which is still larger than the number of speech sounds that could be expected, but the model should maintain a reasonable temporal resolution, while also reducing computational complexity.

Convolution layers are powerful feature extraction tools, and the process of sliding a kernel over an input signal can easily be parallelized. However, they also introduce certain disadvantages. One of the most important is the limited visible context. As we have seen in Figure 2.13, the receptive field of a convolutional architecture is defined during model creation, and at each time step, the model can only see information which lies within that receptive field. Any temporal or spatial pattern which exceeds this field of view cannot be recognized by such model. Therefore, it is common practice to use convolution layers solely for the purpose of feature extraction, and afterwards use another technique to model long-range dependencies.

In the context of 1-D convolutions, it is also worth mentioning a sub-type of kernel configuration which plays a major role for real-time signal processing. If we consider the receptive field from Figure 2.13 once more, we can see that the field spans over past (left), present (center) and future (right) time steps, relative to the centered time step which spans the field of view. For any type of real-time application, such configuration is not feasible, because future information is not available. It is possible to collect the required future information before feeding an input to the model, but this in turn results in a delayed prediction, which could be infeasible for many real-time scenarios. Consequently, there is a trade-off between the size of a bi-directional

receptive field (seeing both past and future context) and the responsiveness of the system due to the delay. A time-critical application, for example an electrical power-grid protection unit, cannot await a long buffer of several hundred milliseconds of future context to improve recognition results, because within such a long delay, a dangerous event such as a short-circuit could already cause severe damage.

Convolutional layers can quickly grow in size, not with respect to their field of view, but rather the number of learnable parameters. The most influential parameters are input and output channels, as well as the kernel size. In the case of a standard configuration, the number of parameters can be formulated as

$$N = \textit{kernel size} \cdot \textit{in channels} \cdot \textit{out channels} + \textit{out channels} \quad (2.35)$$

In Equation 2.35, the kernel size denotes the total number of elements in a kernel. If the kernel spans over multiple dimensions, the total kernel size equals the product of the kernel sizes along each dimension. Note that also the number of input and output channels contribute to the total number of parameters. This creates an important constraint on the size of a receptive field. In theory, the idea is to encode as much descriptive information about the receptive field as possible along the channel dimension. Consequently, with a growing size of the receptive field, one also requires an increasing number of channels to be able to store the information. If its size is too large, it requires too many channels, and this in turn causes the deep model to employ too many parameters, which could either prevent an efficient learning progress, or, even more likely, lead to overfitting problems. As the *kernel size* parameter represents the total number of elements in the convolution kernel, it grows quickly if it spans over multiple dimensions. For example, a 2-D quadratic convolution window with a size of 3 comprises 9 kernel elements. A notable technique to mitigate this problem is the application of separated kernels, also known as kernel factorization. Any $K = m \times n$ convolution kernel is called separable if it can be decomposed into two kernels such that $K = (m \times 1) \times (1 \times n)$ [Schu 90]. This approach was used extensively throughout the second version of the *Inception* model [Szeg 16] to reduce the computational cost and parameter complexity of 3×3 and 5×5 filter kernels.

2.2.6 Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) were extremely popular to model temporal context. In recent years, they were mostly replaced by attention-based approaches (see Section 2.2.7), but throughout this thesis, there will be many references to architectures which make use of recurrence. The core idea of any recurrent layer is to merge past (or future) and present information inside of a single time step, produce an output with temporal awareness, and yield a new vector which summarizes the current temporal context. This vector is frequently called state vector, and it is passed from one recurrent cell to the next, over the time dimension.

The idea of recurrent units inside of a neural network existed since the introduction

of the backpropagation algorithm in 1986 [Rume 86]. A quite popular realization of such building block was Elman's cell [Yang 20]. It can be decomposed into

$$c_t = W_r r_{t-1} + W_x x_t + b_r \quad (2.36)$$

$$r_t = \varphi(c_t) \quad (2.37)$$

$$y_t = W_y r_t + b_y \quad (2.38)$$

In the above equations, c_t represents the internal cell state as a summation of the recurrent (past) information $W_r r_{t-1}$ and the current input $W_x x_t$, both multiplied with their respective learnable weight matrices, plus some bias term b_r . As for other perceptron-based approaches, c_t is then passed through an activation function $\varphi(c_t)$. The result also represents the new recurrent output of Elman's cell at time t , which is consecutively the input at $t + 1$. The cell's non-recurrent output at t is given as y_t . The above formulation already provides a fully functional realization of a recurrent cell, but it comes at an important cost, which rendered the cell unusable for many tasks. In the subsection on backpropagation (2.2.2), we already learned how the parameters of a model could be updated such that the produced error would be reduced. The approach can also be used along the temporal dimension in the form of backpropagation through time (BPTT) [Werb 88]. Given the partial error δ at a certain time step, one can use the same approach as for simple feed-forward networks to determine the contribution of r_{t-1} and x_t to the local error at t . With this information, it is possible to pass error information along the time domain, allowing the trained network to learn temporal patterns which are of importance for a given task. However, the application of BPTT introduces an important restriction, which prevented Elman's cell from being successful on many sequence understanding tasks. Remember that we discussed the problem of vanishing or exploding gradients if a network would comprise too many layers. The repeated gradient computations would gradually lower the partial errors, leading to insignificant weight updates in very deep architectures. The same problem applies on the time dimension of an RNN. In every time step, the partial error has to pass a new layer. If the lag between the occurrence and the origin of an error is too large, then it cannot be learned efficiently anymore. In other words, if a pattern in the input signal contributes to a manifestation in the predicted sequence with a long temporal delay, then this is impossible for Elman's cell to interpret.

In 1997, the problem of vanishing gradients over time was successfully solved with the introduction of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cells [Hoch 97]. Figure 2.14a illustrates an LSTM cell which receives an input feature vector x_t , and additionally a hidden state and a cell state. The hidden state h_{t-1} represents the last output emitted by the LSTM cell at the previous time step. Note that h_{t-1} and x_t are concatenated, hence the cell can be considered a first-order autoregressive model. An LSTM cell comprises four linear projections to realize three important *gates*. A gate, in the context of a recurrent cell, is any sub-unit which performs a linear projection on some input and then uses the output to modify (or, in other words, to gate) the maintained state vector. In the LSTM cell, all linear projections receive the same input, which is the concatenation of local information and past output vector. The first gate inside the LSTM is the forget gate. It is used to remove information from the incoming cell state c_{t-1} . After the linear projection, the result is passed through

(a) Long short-term memory

(b) Gated recurrent unit

Figure 2.14: Two noteworthy architectures of recurrent cells inside a neural network. White boxes depict linear projections and their respective non-linear activation (σ denotes the Sigmoid). Red elements denote mathematical operations which involve no learnable parameters. The LSTM shown in (a) comprises four linear projections to maintain a hidden state \mathbf{h} and a cell state \mathbf{c} . The GRU shown in (b) could be considered an advanced version of the LSTM cell. It only requires three linear projections and solely maintains a hidden state h . The separate cell state could be omitted here.

a sigmoid activation function. The resulting output, which ranges from $[0, 1]$, is then multiplied with the cell state, such that information is either kept or removed. The next two linear projections form the input gate of the cell. One projection passes through a Sigmoid, the other through a \tanh activation. The results are multiplied with each other, which produces a *gated activation*. The new cell state c_t is then created by adding the state c_{t-1} coming from the forget gate and the result from the input gate. Lastly, the LSTM also controls the parts of information which should be outputted at the current time step. This is done by the output gate, which is designed in the same way as the forget gate. The result from the Sigmoid activation is multiplied with the cell state c_t , which had to pass through a \tanh activation beforehand. The result serves as the local output and the hidden state for the next cell h_t .

The gated recurrent unit (GRU) [Cho 14] which is shown in Figure 2.14b was strongly influenced by the general concept of the LSTM, with the goal to alleviate some of the weaknesses it held. Compared to the LSTM, a GRU maintains a hidden state which also serves as cell state. This reduces the overhead of information which has to be passed between individual time steps. Furthermore, note that the new cell requires only three linear projections. The underlying gating logic is a bit more complex though, due to the more sophisticated circuiting of information. The name (and purpose) of the individual gates is also not clearly defined, and many of the commonly used terminologies are not entirely accurate. The first linear projection in a GRU receives the input x_t and the hidden state h_{t-1} and applies a Sigmoid activation. This is very similar to the forget gate in an LSTM, but here, this step is not required to modify the hidden state which is passed on to the next time step, but rather alter a copy of this vector, which will then be used in the update gate. Hence, the first gate could be called the selection gate. The second linear projection receives the same

inputs as the first, and also uses a Sigmoid activation. This is the weighing gate. Its output is multiplied with the result from the update gate to control which updates should be applied to the hidden state vector, and at the same time, the inverse $1 - \sigma$ is used to control the information preserved in the original hidden state vector. The last linear projection forms the update gate, and it receives as input the local information x_t as well as the hidden state which passed the selection gate, hence only contains information which was considered *relevant* for the current time step. Like in the LSTM, the update gate is activated with a hyperbolic tangent function, and then gated with the result from the weighing gate. The resulting modification of h_{t-1} and the update vector are then added to receive the new h_t , which serves as the output of the current time step as well as the temporal context for the next unit, which makes the GRU, like the LSTM, a first-order autoregressive building block.

The key for the success of the LSTM and GRU cells lies in their logic for maintaining a state vector which summarizes past context. A closer look on the circuiting logic depicted in Figure 2.14 reveals that the cell state c_{t-1} (LSTM) or hidden state h_{t-1} (GRU) never pass through any linear projection or other operation which employs learnable parameters. Like in the case of residual connections introduced earlier, partial errors are able to freely pass through the unit along the time dimension, without the issue of vanishing gradients. In theory, this enables both recurrent cells to learn temporal context of infinite length. In practice, however, this turned out not be the case, most likely because with an increasing amount of time steps, more and more partial errors will contribute and the influence of long-term dependencies will be mitigated again.

Another really important property of any recurrent cell is their directed flow of information. A cell receives input from previous time steps, but usually does not know anything about the future. The same holds if the direction of operation is inverted, and the cell receives inputs from the future, going all the way into the past. This unidirectional context is a disadvantage compared to, for example, convolutional layers with a reasonably large receptive field. A common strategy to overcome this drawback is to apply two recurrent layers in parallel, with one going from past to future, and the other from future to past context, and afterwards fusing the results per time step by concatenation. Such setup is called a bidirectional recurrent layer. It is however only possible if the entire sequence is available, which renders this method unusable for real-time applications.

Using recurrent building blocks, like RNN cells, inside of a neural network often slows down the entire execution due to the time dependencies. Modern deep models benefit heavily from hardware designed for parallel operations, like graphics processing units (GPUs), which are able to perform thousands of simple arithmetic operations within one clock cycle, at the cost of a slightly reduced clock frequency. With the introduction of data dependencies (to execute the cell at time t , the execution of $t - 1$ has to be finished) along the time domain, this parallelization is lost in the recurrent layer, causing longer execution times.

Recurrent cells learn a general concept of temporal dependencies in the underlying data. They can therefore be applied to sequences which are longer than any of the training samples. In image processing, most models expect the image to be of a certain size, and if this requirement is not met, the input image is first resized to fit

the desired shape. In sequence analysis, the recurrent cell learns appropriate weights, and is then simply concatenated for every new time step. This idea of using the same recurrent cell over and over again is crucial to understand why RNNs are still used in environments with low computational resources. In a very simple setup, with no preceding layers, and only one linear classification layer after the RNN, the cell itself is able to maintain a state vector which provides a sufficient temporal context. Consequently, to operate in real-time on new samples which come in at a certain frequency, it is not necessary to create a buffer of past context. Every new sample can simply be fed into the cell, and all that is to be stored between individual calls is the state vector(s). This can be a significant advantage over other architectures, like convolutions, if the model is to be deployed on low-resource hardware, which often lacks parallel computing power and memory to store long buffers.

2.2.7 Neural Attention Mechanism

CNNs and RNNs were both designed to interpret spatial or temporal relationships in input signals. The former are known to have a limited available context, whilst the latter, in theory, could resemble infinitely long contexts, which is not possible in practice though. Furthermore, both building blocks lack *selectivity*, which is the ability to focus on relevant information only. In a set of observations, one can define the subset of *relevant* information only with respect to some reference that the information is relevant for. The algorithm would then try to focus its attention on this subset to produce better results.

Such an approach was first introduced by Bahdanau et al. in 2014 [Bahd15]. This first version of a neural attention mechanism, also known as additive attention due to the fact that queries and keys are concatenated, enabled an RNN at a certain time step to focus on surrounding time steps of interest. In this context, a query is a reference tensor, and the keys are candidate tensors which the query is compared to. The approach was first used in the context of machine translation to tackle the problem of altered word orders between different languages.

The first version of the attention algorithm was quite successful, but also used a lot of resources. This is why Luong et al. introduced their improved multiplicative attention algorithm [Luon15], which relies on a dot-product between queries and keys to interpret the similarity (and correspondences) geometrically. The logic behind multiplicative attention is illustrated in Figure 2.15. A query vector is compared to a set of key vectors by computing the respective dot-products. Afterwards, a Softmax activation is applied over all results, transforming them into a probability density. This density defines how much each key vector contributes to the final context vector. This is simply computed as the weighed sum of all keys. In modern approaches, the most widely used formulation of the attention algorithm is given as

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right) \cdot \mathbf{V} \quad (2.39)$$

In Equation 2.39, \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{V} represent the query, key and value tensors, respectively. The attention is computed as the dot-product of query-key combinations, and the resulting probability distribution is applied to the values. Keys and values

Figure 2.15: Schematic of the dot-product attention. First, the dot-product between the query and all key vectors is computed. A probability density is then derived through a Softmax activation, which indicates how much each key contributes to the final context vector, which is then the weighed sum of all keys.

may be the same, but in some cases, it is desirable to compute low-dimensional key representations of the original values to efficiently compute the attention, and then use the weights on the raw values instead. Another important special case is that of queries and keys being the same (and potentially even the values). This is called self-attention, hence each query attends to itself and its own environment. The dot-product result in Equation 2.39 is scaled by $\sqrt{d_k}$. As discussed earlier already, the emitted output from any layer ideally follows a normal distribution. If \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{K} are normally distributed, then their dot-product has a mean of 0, but a variance equal to d_k , which is the dimensionality of \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{K} . By scaling the dot-product with a factor of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ (division by the standard deviation), the resulting variance is brought back to 1.

Whilst the attention algorithm solves the problems of CNNs (limited field of view) and RNNs (vanishing gradients over time), it introduces new challenges. Let us consider a standard audio waveform of 20s duration, which contains a speech signal to be recognized. A standard approach would be to compute relevant features over a short time-window, which is then shifted over the signal to yield a sequence of feature vectors. With a self-attention mechanism, a frame at time t could be put into context with all neighboring frames that encode very similar information, simply because they belong to the same speech sound which spanned over multiple frames. However, the standard attention mechanism would also cause the system to attend to feature vectors of that same speech sound 15s later, only because it occurred a second time. In its original form, there is no limitation of potential context. Such restriction could be introduced by using an attention buffer, which would limit the attention to some window around the original query. However, this requires some sort of prior knowledge to choose an appropriate window size, and within the chosen attention window, there is still no information about the relative position of feature vectors. Another, much

Figure 2.16: Exemplary sinusoidal encoding for 64-dimensional (depth) feature vectors spanning over the first 200 time steps. Positional encodings and feature vectors are summed to enrich each vector of the feature sequence with information about its absolute position.

more popular approach is the combination of attention mechanisms and positional encodings. Given a pair of query and key vectors which are very similar and would consequently result in the model to strongly attend to this key, this attention should be large if the two vectors have a close spatial or temporal (or other) relationship. If they are further away from each other in the input signal, the attention should be lower. One of the first positional encoding techniques utilized in combination with attention mechanisms was a sinusoidal positional encoding [Vasw 17].

$$\begin{aligned} PE(pos, 2i) &= \sin\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right) \\ PE(pos, 2i + 1) &= \cos\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.40)$$

It is defined as in Equation 2.40 and produces encoding vectors of the same dimension as the queries and keys, hence the encodings can simply be added. Figure 2.16 illustrates the positional encoding vectors for a model depth of 64 over the first 200 time steps. Usage of a sinusoidal encoding was motivated by its ability to encode information about absolute positions instead of relative ones, which is important for tasks where the position of each word plays a critical role, like in machine translation or generative modelling.

Another approach to encode temporal or spatial relationships is that of positional convolutions. Unlike the predefined sinusoidal encodings, the parameters of said convolutions can be learned by the model during training. A positional convolution operates just like any other convolutional layer, but its hyperparameters were designed specifically for the task of encoding positional information. This includes, but is not limited to a large kernel size as well as a grouping of kernels per channels, effectively reducing the required number of trainable parameters. The result of the convolution is added on top of the input signal, forming a residual connection. The advantage of positional convolutions is their ability to learn a task-specific attention window (within their respective field-of-view). On the other hand, they are computationally more expensive than their sinusoidal counterparts.

In many modern model architectures, attention mechanisms are not built in as a

Figure 2.17: Encoder (left) and decoder (right) block of the Transformer module. The three input arrows of the multi-head attention blocks represent values, keys and queries in that exact order. Consequently, the first multi-head attention block of the encoder and decoder perform self-attention, whilst the second attention module of the decoder uses queries from the decoder to attend to keys from the encoder.

single, stand-alone module, but rather as part of a larger building block, the *Transformer* [Vasw17]. Figure 2.17 depicts the encoder and decoder parts of the entire Transformer architecture. In the discipline of sequence understanding, this is commonly a series of feature vectors collected over time. A positional embedding is applied, and the resulting vectors serve as input for a multi-head attention block. In the case of multi-head attention, multiple attention layers are applied in parallel, where each of them learns their own set of parameters. Notice that the input feature vectors serve as values, keys and queries at the same time, resulting in a self-attention layout. The attention result is then added to the original feature vectors, forming a residual connection, followed by a layer normalization. The second step of the encoder applies a residual linear projection and another layer normalization. The schematic in Figure 2.17 shows the connection between the encoder and decoder block, but in most architectures, it is much more common to use a series of several encoder and decoder blocks.

The input to the decoder is the sequence of embeddings from previously emitted symbols. In the case of natural language processing (NLP) for example, this would be the sequence of words that had already been predicted by the model in previous steps. Consequently, the decoder of a Transformer module operates in an autoregressive fashion. The first steps of the decoder are identical to that of the encoder, applying a positional encoding and residual self-attention. In the second step, the decoder applies yet another multi-head attention layer, but this time, it uses the output of the

encoder for the keys and values, and the intermediate decoder result are queries. The motivation for this setup originated from the core idea of the attention mechanism: The queries are used as a reference signal for which the algorithm tries to identify correspondences in the candidate keys. In the case of the Transformer, the decoder interprets the previously emitted tokens, for example words, and estimates the most probable next token. The attention mechanism then searches for matching query-key pairs in the encoded feature vectors. The encoder-decoder attention block is once again applying a residual connection, such that the feature vectors of the decoder are added to the attention result (the weighted sum of values) from the encoder block. The last step of the decoder is identical to that of the encoder again, applying a residual linear projection and layer norm. The final Transformer output can then be projected down to the number of classes, such as words in a dictionary, followed by a Softmax layer to create a probability distribution.

In the original paper [Vasw17], the Transformer was used for Machine Translation. The Transformer was found to be extremely capable of processing sequential data, making it one of the most important neural building blocks of this time. Particularly the encoder module has been used in many state-of-the-art sequence analysis models [Dev19, Baev20, Hsu21] to perform temporal contextualization, and the idea was adopted to the domain of image classification as well [Parm18, Doso20, Cari20].

2.2.8 Alignment-free Sequence Understanding

As discussed before, it is crucial for many applications to have some ground-truth annotation. In recent years, unsupervised learning schemes have massively increased in popularity because they enable researchers to pre-train large models without introducing a bias towards a specific task. The fact that no ground-truth annotation is required during pre-training significantly increases the amount of eligible datasets, because one only requires the data itself, without any annotation. These models can then be optimized for any particular problem, and the pre-trained initialization often helps to produce better results, particularly if the problem-specific dataset is much smaller than that utilized during pre-training. This secondary step of optimizing a model towards a distinct task is commonly referred to as *fine-tuning*.

In the domain of sequence analysis problems, ground-truth information could be classified into three major categories:

- Sequence-level: For each sequence of arbitrary duration T , there exist one or more descriptors which characterize the entire sequence (e.g. the gender of a speaker)
- Token-level: There exist multiple tokens (e.g. words or phonemes) in the sequence. Their order is known, but their respective position in the sequence remains unknown
- Frame-level: Information about the precise start and end times of each token in the sequence is available. At every time step $t \in T$, we know about the present token.

With increasing temporal resolution of ground-truth information, the annotation becomes much more expensive, both w.r.t. required annotation time and expertise to

correctly produce the annotation. Consequently, for larger datasets, it is less likely to have frame-level annotation available.

Most neural networks which process time-series information would interpret a sample as a sequence of frames for which the model can compute feature vectors. In a second step, the temporal contextualization, neighborhood relationships among feature vectors are evaluated to make better frame-level predictions. At the end of it all, the network is expected to emit the most probable class $c \in C$ for each frame. This is where things can become complicated if frame-level annotation is unavailable. One solution could be the usage of RNN-Transducer models (RNN-T) [Grav 12]. They operate in an auto-regressive fashion (like the decoder of the Transformer block) and predict the next symbol based on the encoded sequence and the previously emitted symbols. Whilst transducer models do not require alignment information, they are also able to learn a token-level language model. The predictor network which outputs the next symbol can learn transition probabilities and frequent token-patterns during training. This can be an advantage if the data used for inference is very similar to the training data. If this is not the case, the learned language model might introduce knowledge which is not representative for the given dataset. This would be the case if we trained a phone recognizer with healthy speech signals from large ASR datasets, but would then use this recognizer to analyze speech exercises from different pathologies, which have very different phone transition characteristics.

Another approach to train a sequential model without alignment information is the idea of *Connectionist Temporal Classification* (CTC) [Grav 06]. Instead of having to distribute a probability mass of 1.0 over C classes at every frame t , the algorithm introduces a blank token, which is very similar to a rejection class. If inside a single frame most of the probability mass was assigned to the blank token, then the model decided that there was no new information in that frame. The term *new information* implies that there was already some sort of baseline information available. In the case of sequence understanding, this baseline is simply the last predicted token. Given some signal X which could be decomposed into frames $f_0, f_1 \dots f_{t-1}, f_t$, CTC decodes the output token sequence from start to finish by following a simple set of rules:

1. If the current frame decodes to the blank token, add no information to the output sequence and proceed to the next frame
2. If the current frame decodes to a non-blank token, append this token to the output sequence if the last decoded token was any other token (including blank)
3. If the current frame decodes to a non-blank token, do not append this token if the last decoded token was that same token

With this set of rules for the decoding process, it is important to understand that for a given decoded token sequence S , there exist many unique frame sequences F . Figure 2.18 shows different framewise output sequences together with their respective decoding results. Both the first and second sequence decode to the same correct output *hello*, whereas the last two sequences produced an invalid decoding result. In a naive decoding scheme, every frame could be assigned the token with the local maximum posterior probability. However, the resulting sequence may not be the most probable token sequence. We can formulate the log-probability of any token

	Frame-wise output	Decoded sequence									
1.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>h</td><td>h</td><td>e</td><td>␣</td><td>␣</td><td>l</td><td>␣</td><td>l</td><td>o</td> </tr> </table>	h	h	e	␣	␣	l	␣	l	o	hello
h	h	e	␣	␣	l	␣	l	o			
2.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>␣</td><td>h</td><td>e</td><td>l</td><td>␣</td><td>l</td><td>o</td><td>␣</td><td>␣</td> </tr> </table> <p style="text-align: center;">Valid predictions</p>	␣	h	e	l	␣	l	o	␣	␣	hello
␣	h	e	l	␣	l	o	␣	␣			
3.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>h</td><td>e</td><td>e</td><td>l</td><td>l</td><td>␣</td><td>o</td><td>o</td><td>␣</td> </tr> </table>	h	e	e	l	l	␣	o	o	␣	helo
h	e	e	l	l	␣	o	o	␣			
4.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>h</td><td>e</td><td>l</td><td>␣</td><td>l</td><td>␣</td><td>o</td><td>␣</td><td>o</td> </tr> </table> <p style="text-align: center;">Invalid predictions</p>	h	e	l	␣	l	␣	o	␣	o	helloo
h	e	l	␣	l	␣	o	␣	o			

Figure 2.18: Decoding examples of frame-wise outputs which should decode to the true sequence *hello* following the CTC decoding rules. The blank token is denoted as ␣ .

sequence S as the sum of the log-probabilities of all frame-sequences Y which decode to that token sequence, where a single path $y \in Y$ can be defined as

$$p(y|X) = \prod_{t=0}^T p(y_t|X) \quad (2.41)$$

If we consider all paths Y which decode to the same token sequence S , then the probability of that token sequence can be written as

$$p(S|X) = \sum_{y \in Y} \prod_{t=0}^T p(y_t|X) \quad (2.42)$$

As we perform gradient-descent optimization for neural networks, instead of maximizing the conditional probability $p(S|X)$, we can instead minimize its negative log-likelihood

$$\sum_{y \in Y} -\log p(y|X) \quad (2.43)$$

At any time step $t \in T$, it is then possible to simply compute the derivative of $p(S|X)$ w.r.t. the model parameters and perform back-propagation.

One of the most critical assumption of CTC is that of conditional independence. The algorithm assumes that in an output sequence of N tokens, the emission probability of the token s_n is independent of the previously emitted token s_{n-1} . In many cases, this simplification does not resemble the true nature of the problem at hand. In speech, for example, certain combinations of phonemes are much more likely than others, and knowing about the previously emitted symbol could have a major impact on the likelihood of the next one. However, whilst the CTC algorithm assumes conditional independence, the underlying model, for example a phoneme recognizer, is still very much able (and likely) to learn that certain state (phone) transitions are more common than others. It should also be noted that information about conditional dependencies can still be recovered during inference by adding a language

model (or any other valid statistical state transition model) in the decoding scheme. In fact, this is a very common approach for any model that was trained with CTC, but throughout this thesis, all presented models and inference results were computed without applying a language model. That is because it would not make sense to estimate a language model over a large amount of healthy speech, which would then be unrepresentative for many of the pathological speech samples, for example because they represent speech exercises which did not follow a common language structure. The first two sections on traditional and deep machine learning introduced the theoretical foundation in terms of computer science. The analysis of pathological speech signals also requires a profound understanding of human speech production. The following section on phonetics introduces a categorization of human speech sounds, describes the key principles of speech production and explains the usage of phonetic symbols in mono- and multi-lingual scenarios.

2.3 An Introduction to Phonetics

Linguistics encompasses the study of all aspects of human language. Within this broad framework, phonetics describes the set of sounds used in human speech [Roac 01]. Research focuses on the production, transmission and perception of these sounds, and frequently overlaps with other disciplines like phoniatrics, acoustics, psychoacoustics or audiology for example. The explanations provided throughout this section were based on standard phonetics literature from John Laver (*Principles of phonetics* [Lave 94]), Lawrence Shriberg (*Four new speech and prosody-voice measures for genetics research and other studies in developmental phonological disorders* [Shri 93]), Peter Ladefoged and Keith Johnson (*A course in phonetics* [Lade 14]) as well as the handbook from the International Phonetic Association [Asso 99].

A quick web-search would explain that phonetics could be divided into three categories, namely articulatory, acoustic and auditory studies, and that they cover the production, transmission and perception of human speech, respectively. In his work *Principles of phonetics*, Laver interprets phonetics against the broad background of a semiotic framework. As “the general theory of signs”, semiotics had already been described by Stoic philosophers [Lave 94]. In the context of phonetics, information is encoded by a speaker in the form of a continuous acoustic signal (the sign) which can be perceived by another individual, the listener. The message transported through the sign is consequently not limited to the spoken text. Cutler emphasized the importance of prosody, stating that it can be viewed as “the sauce of the sentence – it adds to, enhances or subtly changes the flavour of the original” [Cutl 80].

Think of the very simple sentence “I’ve got no beer.”, uttered in three different scenarios: (1) After following an interesting conversation, you look down to your glass, just to realize it was empty. (2) After a dinner at home, you notify your friends that no more of the cold beverage was left. (3) The waiter in the pub forgot your beer order for the third time and just asked the round if everything was alright. The very same utterance, three completely different messages. In the first scenario, the intended recipient of the message is the sender himself. It’s the expressed surprise about the empty glass that, as an important piece of prosodic information, let’s the other people know that this statement does not require any reaction. In the second

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Figure 2.19: Places of articulation inside the vocal tract: (1) Labial (2) Dental (3) Alveolar (4) Post-alveolar (5) Palatal (6) Velar (7) Uvular (8) Glottal.

case, the plain message is simple, and the recipients are obvious as well. It is prosody that flavors the utterance with disappointment, leaving no need for a further verbal excuse, because it already became quite clear that the host is deeply sorry for the inconvenience. Moving on to the last example, a harsh intonation at an increased volume clearly reminds the waiter of your order. It further transmits your feeling about the entire situation, something in between anger and frustration. And the waiter is not the only receiver of the message. Intended or not, the customers on the next table will likely also hear your complaint due to the increased volume.

Coming back to the semiotic framework, phonetics describe the symbols one can use to create a new sign. In the case of speech, the sign is any utterance. The symbol sequence conveys the message, but the entire information transmitted through the sign is not limited to the sole meaning of the symbol sequence. Volume, intonation, speech rate, pitch – only a few examples of factors that shape the resulting signal. In phonetics, speech can be described as a sequence of phones (the symbols). A phone is defined as a unique sound that can be used to produce speech, and it is usually considered to be the smallest building block of any spoken language. The concept of phones allows to segment a speech signal into the sequence of produced sounds. Phones are independent of language, meaning that they solely describe the sound itself, and changing a phone within a word may not alter the meaning of that word in a particular language. For example, the character <t> in the English word *water* could be produced as the alveolar stop [t] or the glottal stop [ʔ], considering British English pronunciation. In the former, the stream of air is blocked by pressing the tongue against the alveolar ridge, in the latter, the stream is inhibited by closure of the glottis. The different places of articulation are illustrated in Figure 2.19. Al-

	Plosive	Nasal	Trill	Fricative	Approximant
Bilabial	p b	m		β	w
Labio-dental		ɱ		f v	
Dental				θ ð	
Alveolar	t d	n		s z	l
Post-alveolar			r	ʃ ʒ	
Palatal		ɲ		ç ʝ	ʝ ɥ ʎ
Velar	k g	ŋ		x ɣ	
Uvular			ʀ		
Glottal	ʔ			h	

Table 2.1: Summary of all phonetic IPA symbols used throughout the corpus. Not included in the table but part of the annotation are a symbol for silence as well as 26 elongated variants of presented phones.

though [t] and [ʔ] are two different phones, they are both valid productions of the British English phoneme /t/. Hence, the concept of phonemes is strictly language-specific. In the given example, two different phones ([t] and [ʔ]) could be used to express the same phoneme (/t/), without changing the meaning of the word. In this case, the two phones are referred to as allophones of the respective phoneme. On the other side, if one phoneme was replaced with another within the framework of one language, this could alter the meaning of the produced word. For the previous example, after exchanging the stop phoneme /t/ with the nasal /m/, the produced word changed from <water> to <warmer> for British English pronunciation.

Throughout this work, any phonetic notation follows the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) [Asso 99]. It was designed as an instrument to transcribe the sounds of all languages of the world. A key paradigm of the IPA is the distinction between vowels and consonants. Vowels are characterized by an unobstructed stream of air passing through the vocal tract. On the other hand, the production of consonants involves a constriction of the air-stream somewhere inside the vocal tract.

All phonetic symbols representing consonants which had been used in the scope of this thesis are listed in Table 2.1. Each row reflects a distinct place of articulation. Figure 2.19 shows that the different places of articulation can be found anywhere from the glottis upwards, with a majority of them located inside the oral cavity. In some cases, the place of articulation already gives a good impression of the involved articulators. For example, the lower lips and upper front teeth are used to produce the labio-dental fricative [f]. Articulation inside the oral cavity (from the lips all the way back to the uvula) is mostly realized as an interplay of the static place of articulation and the dynamic tongue muscle, which allows to precisely impede the airflow, a skill that requires good fine-motor control. In a study conducted on the speech acquisition characteristics of speech-delayed children [Shri 93], Shriberg grouped English consonants into early-8, middle-8 and late-8 clusters, depending on how long it would take the children to master their articulation. The group of early-8 consonants

([m], [b], [j], [n], [w], [d], [p] and [h]) required only little to no tongue control. This could be an indicator that precise articulation involving the tongue is more difficult, but it is also possible that the acquisition of these consonants is easier because most of their articulation happens at the visible end of the vocal tract. This allows an infant to see the required articulation, making it easier for them to reproduce them. Each column of Table 2.1 represents a manner of articulation [Asso 99]. Manner of articulation describes several different articulatory properties, for example the stricture of the vocal tract (degree of narrowness) or the position of the velum, which influences the degree of nasality. Consonants with similar manners of articulation are commonly grouped into the categories given in the table columns. Plosives, also referred to as stops, require full constriction of the vocal tract, thus the airflow is completely inhibited for a short period of time [Hard 12]. As soon as the constriction is released, a sudden burst of air is created. Note that in Table 2.1, in every cell where plosives are given in pairs, the left represents the unvoiced and the right the voiced variant.

The next group of consonants are nasals, which also require a constriction of the vocal tract, but allow air to stream through the nasal cavity instead. Although the airflow through the mouth is inhibited, the actual articulation of different nasal sounds happens there. For the alveolar nasal [n], the oral constriction is realized by pressing the tip or blade of the tongue against the alveolar ridge, for the bilabial [m], the tongue is lowered and the stream of air is blocked through the closed lips.

Trill consonants require a tight constriction at the respective place of articulation. The stream of air can pass through this narrow space and causes the tissue to vibrate, leading to the distinct trill sound. The oscillation frequency of the involved articulators lies in the range of 20-35 Hz [McGo 92, Reca 91]. This is even lower than the pitch frequency of the vocal folds, ranging from 40 Hz for a creaky voice up to a 1.000 Hz for children [Hard 12].

The majority of consonants considered throughout this work belong to the group of fricatives. The articulation of a fricative requires a tight constriction somewhere in the vocal tract. Unlike for trills, where the constriction causes the surrounding tissue to oscillate, the air is compressed to a turbulent stream. This ejected stream, also called a jet, produces the characteristic fricative sound [Hard 12]. Several cells in the fricative column of Table 2.1 contain pairs which, as for the plosives, show the unvoiced (left) and voiced (right) variants of fricatives that share the same place of articulation.

The last group of consonants are approximants. They are characterized by a wider constriction than any other consonant group. The resulting airstream is not turbulent anymore, as the stricture is not fully developed, but only approximated, therefore the name. The symbols [l] and [ʎ] could also be allotted to a separate group of lateral approximants. During their production, the center of the vocal tract is blocked at the place of articulation [Lade 14], and the air passes through the left and right openings. All consonants share the property that the airstream is constricted, partially or completely, somewhere inside the vocal tract. If no constriction is present that would result in a turbulent air flow, and the vocal cords are in vibration, the produced sound is called vowel. The different vowels considered throughout this work are summarized in Figure 2.20. The visualization is based on the vowel diagram provided in

Figure 2.20: Vowel trapezoid according to the International Phonetic Alphabet. Tongue elevation is reflected on the vertical axis, tongue position on the horizontal axis. Shaded vowels indicate rounded variants. F1 and F2 represent the frequency increase of the first and second formant, respectively, depending on the tongue configuration.

[Inte 20]. On the horizontal axis of the trapezoid, the position of the highest point of the tongue is illustrated. For different vowels, the tongue may be moved more to the front, center, or back of the vocal tract. As the position plays an important role, so does the elevation of the tongue, which is represented on the vertical axis. The more the tongue is elevated, the narrower becomes the vocal tract.

The vowel chart provides a fundamental impression on how the tongue is used to articulate different vowels by shaping the resonating cavity inside the vocal tract [Asso 99]. Lastly, entries in the chart have a light or dark shading. This represents the shape of the lips, which could be unrounded (light) or rounded (dark). It is common to include all this information when addressing a particular speech sound in phonetics. For example, the phone [i] is then referred to as the close front unrounded vowel. The arrangement of vowels in the shape of a trapezoid (which is, for some languages, sometimes simplified to a triangle) reflects not only morphological, but acoustic properties of the presented vowels as well. The vertical and horizontal axis represent the first and second Formant frequencies of every depicted vowel, respectively [Kent 18, Hill 01]. A formant describes the concentration of energy around a certain frequency which manifests as a peak in the spectral density. The first two formant frequencies (F1 and F2) are characteristic for a particular vowel. In the presented trapezoid, F1 increases as the elevation of the tongue is lowered. For the horizontal axis, the more the tongue is brought to the front, the higher is the observed frequency of F2. The difference of F2 values between [u] and [i] is much larger than that between [a] and [ɑ], hence the trapezoid shape.

By definition, no vowel could be found to lie outside of the area of the IPA vowel

chart. This is because the position of the four corner-vowels is not supposed to represent their actual articulation (which can easily vary among different languages). Instead, they much more resemble the extreme variants of tongue configuration. For example, the open front unrounded vowel [a] in the IPA chart actually shows the articulation with the tongue brought as far to the front as possible, while at the same time applying no elevation at all. In this sense, it is simply considered impossible to articulate any vowel outside of the presented area.

Because the IPA vowel diagram is meant to reflect articulation properties much more than acoustic properties, no formant frequency scales are shown in the chart. As mentioned previously, the actual production of vowels can vary between languages, and there are plenty of other influencing factors that have to be considered. One of them is the context of a vowel. Nöth showed that in the F1-F2-trapezoid, the area spanned by isolated vowels is much greater than that of vowels from continuous speech, which all converge towards the center of the diagram [Nöth 91]. Context can also be established by the phonetic neighborhood, i. e., the preceding and succeeding phone. Lastly, let context be the superseding information about the emotional state of a speaker, which could directly impact formant frequencies [Goud 09, Kim 15].

The presented phone inventory was further expanded by including information about length, nasalization and palatalization. Whenever a length mark [ː] was appended to a phone, it indicated that an elongated version of that phone had been observed. For vowels, the concept of elongation is quite intuitive, but a length mark could also occur in conjunction with a consonant. The lengthening of a consonant is called gemination. Geminations are very common in Italian phonology [Di B 21], in the word *fatto* (English: *fact*) for example, the [t] is elongated by lengthening the duration of the closure before the actual burst. Sometimes (in 10% – 12% of cases [Di B 21]), a second burst can be observed. The nasalization of certain vowels is frequently used in French phonology. It is indicated by a [̃] on top of the vowel. The airstream is directed through the nasal cavity by lowering the velum [Hard 12]. Lastly, palatalization is commonly found in Russian speech, and it is not to be mistaken with regular palatal consonants. Instead, consonants that have different places and manners of articulation are produced with the tongue raised towards the hard palate. This is indicated by a superscript [ʲ].

The introduced phonetic concepts should help to interpret, and ultimately, understand how a particular pathology manifests in the speech signal of affected patients. Given the set of phones that were found to be strongly affected by a certain condition, it would be possible to derive the impact on individual articulators. It could also be possible to directly link the observed patterns to a loss of muscle tension, instability of phonation, or a constriction of the vocal tract for example. Such knowledge is of particular interest in the scope of neurological diseases, as their influence on speech can vary significantly among patients, both in the way the impairment affects the individual as well as to what extent it actually decreases intelligibility. Understanding which speech sounds are affected by a pathology can greatly improve the quality of monitoring solutions as well. Instead of analyzing an entire speech signal, it is possible to focus on relevant groups of phones.

Before diving into the analysis of pathological speech signals, the subsequent chapter summarizes some of the key milestones during the development of reference models

for healthy speech production which ultimately led to this thesis. It also provides many insights into the recognizer architecture utilized throughout this work, how it was optimized, what data was used for training, and how well it performs for healthy speakers.

Chapter 3

Multilingual Phone Recognition

3.1 A Brief Model History

The phone recognition model utilized for all of the presented experiments is only the most recent variant out of a series of architectures that had been developed over the course of the last five years working on this thesis. The following overview of the different recognizers should provide an intuition of how acoustic modelling for phone(eme) recognition has evolved over time. This evolution could be seen in terms of model size, but other factors played a major role as well, for example the *curse of dimensionality*. In simple words, the curse of dimensionality describes how an increasing number of features can have various negative impacts on a machine learning model [Bish 06]. Ideally, features are independent from each other, and by definition, they serve as meaningful descriptors of an arbitrary input signal. From this point of view, the idea of having a large number of independent and descriptive features might appear useful. In practice, the more features are available, the more data is required to train an ML algorithm without experiencing overfitting. Furthermore, the number of trainable parameters of an ML model often increases along with an increasing amount of input features. Not only does this impact the computational load, but it once again increases the required amount of training data. Larger feature vectors can provide more detailed information about the underlying signal, but a meaningful exploration of a higher-dimensional space also demands for much more data. As the number of features increases linearly, the required amount of training samples usually grows in quadratic fashion [Bish 06]. This relationship played a major role during the development of each of the models presented throughout this section.

The very first attempts of reliable acoustic modelling were made using a stack of two bidirectional RNNs. The input was a sequence of feature vectors which contained 16 Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs), which describe the mel-compressed power spectrum of a short-term Fourier Transform (STFT), as well as their first- and second-order derivatives. For decades, MFCCs have served as a good choice of features for speech applications. Consequently, the neural network did not have to learn any low-level feature extraction from an input signal, but instead focused primarily on the task of sequence understanding. The model had been optimized on recognizing 35 different German phonemes, using a dataset of speech recordings from several hundred German teenage speakers [Stef05]. This recognizer comprised a little over

900 000 trainable parameters. The highest performance that this architecture was able to achieve was 0.59 unweighted average recall (UAR). The recall score describes a classifier's ability to detect a certain class $c \in C$, given that c is the correct class of a particular sample. An *unweighted* average is obtained by computing the mean over the recall scores of all classes, independent of their respective representation, such that seldom and frequent classes are reflected equally in the final result. Whilst the UAR of the model was not too good, the major problem which would hinder it from being able to produce decent recognition results for pathological speech was the fact that the training data was composed of recordings from German teens. While there would be certain pathologies where a classifier estimated from teenage speech came in handy (such as cleft lip and palate), it would remain unrepresentative for any other medical condition that predominantly affected adults.

Neural networks are quite strong at learning features themselves. These learned features might not have good generalization, in other words, if the model saw new data with slightly different properties, the features might already be unusable, but under somewhat controlled conditions, they could easily outperform their handcrafted counterparts. In this context, it is important to keep in mind that in a direct comparison of learned and handcrafted features, the latter are often more powerful if they are complex for the neural network to approximate, so it is impossible to rule out any feature set in advance. Furthermore, as discussed earlier, the curse of dimensionality implies that for every new feature that a model should learn by itself, much more data is required as well. A new variant of the phoneme recognition model used mel-spectrograms as its input signal. A spectrogram simply describes the energy distribution among different frequency bands within a short time window of an audio signal. It is then filtered with a mel-filterbank, which resembles the human perception of speech: A high resolution for lower frequencies, and a coarse resolution at higher frequencies. In comparison to the very first model, the set of features was increased by omitting the last step of the MFCC pipeline, the computation of the discrete cosine transform. A first variant of this approach was successfully applied in a contribution for predicting Spanish phonological posteriors [Vasq 19a]. The mel-spectrogram processed by the phoneme recognition model had a total of 256 frequency bands, and the number of output phonemes was reduced slightly to 31. The MFCCs and their functionals used in the original model had already incorporated information about the short-term temporal context of a particular frame with respect to its direct neighborhood. Whilst there is some overlap between frames of the mel-spectrogram (which had a window size of 25 ms at a step size of 10 ms), there was no further information available. To improve the local amount of temporal context, the spectrogram was fed through a sophisticated series of convolutional layers. They were largely inspired by the Inception architecture [Szeg 17], which employed many important design principles of convolutional neural networks, such as separable convolution kernels, residual connections and the application of different kernel sizes in parallel. Initially, the spectrogram was fed through a CNN stem, a plain series of convolutions which would significantly reduce the number of frequency bands and encode that information along the channel dimension. This intermediate result was then processed by a series of inception blocks. The residual blocks would leave the dimensions of an input unchanged, and were mainly used for feature extraction, while the second

version would compress the extracted information by gradually reducing the spectrogram's size (along the frequency axis) and further encoding the information in the channels. The subsequent long-term temporal analysis was once again performed by a stack of bidirectional RNNs. The introduction of convolutional layers increased the required amount of parameters to around 2.6 million. A new dataset was used for model optimization, called Verbmobil [Wahl13]. It comprised around 29 hours of recorded dialogue speech of almost 600 speakers. The final recognizer achieved a phoneme error rate (PER) of 17.9%. For reference, the first model which operated on MFCCs yielded a PER of around 30%. Note that this is not to be mistaken with the inverse of the UAR, which evaluated the correct prediction of every single frame. Due to imperfect alignments of the phonetic ground truth annotation, even if the predicted phoneme sequence was correct, there could still be framewise prediction errors. The new convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN) architecture was significantly more powerful compared to its predecessor, and it was possible to perform phonetic segmentation and feature extraction for a secondary German datasets to detect the presence of a surgical mask in front of a speaker's mouth [Klum 20]. To further improve the ability of the entire model to generalize and produce robust recognition results for previously unseen data, the restriction to one single language was removed. In addition to the German Verbmobil data, speech recordings from US English (TIMIT corpus [Garo 93]) and Mexican Spanish (DiMEX corpus [Pine 04]) were incorporated in the training routine. For the first time, it was not possible anymore to rely on language-dependent phonemes. Instead, the recognizer was trained with a set of 35 different phone unions (each could represent multiple underlying IPA phones) which acoustically described the three languages. Whilst the input frequency resolution of the model was lowered from 256 to 128 mel-frequency bands to reduce overfitting, the newly added languages and different acoustic conditions between the three corpora demanded an overall larger model. The core design of the CRNN remained the same, but the internal channel configurations and number of residual layers was increased, resulting in a recognizer which employed roughly 6.6 million trainable parameters. This architecture had been trained in framewise fashion once again, and resulted in a PER of 18.7%. Notice that this was slightly higher than the PER of the previous recognizer which had only been optimized for German phonemes. This was, at least partially, a result of the varying frame-level phonetic annotations of the different corpora. One might expect a higher PER because instead of one, the model now had to understand three different languages. However, to evaluate how well the architecture could be optimized without alignment information, the framewise training strategy was replaced with CTC (see Section 2.2.8) for the first time. It was not only possible to omit the requirement of having precise phonetic alignment information at training time, which allowed the incorporation of many other potential datasets which featured only phonetic transcription without alignment. The resulting model, which was slightly adapted and now comprised 7.2% million parameters, also improved w.r.t. phone error rate (PER will now always reflect phone instead of phoneme error rates) by two percentage points to 16.6%. This multi-lingual, alignment-free phone recognizer could be used for an in-depth analysis of Parkinson's disease [Klum 22b] and Covid-19 [Klum 21] speech samples. Every iteration of the phone(eme) recognition model so far has gradually increased

w.r.t. the amount of required trainable parameters. And while the first phoneme recognition model used handcrafted features (MFCCs), the more recent variants had access to a larger feature space, the mel-spectrograms, which they could explore during training. The last variants leading to this thesis were no exception to the trend of growing neural networks. However, before one could scale up the model once again, it would be crucial to have the required amount of training data available. A core motivation of this work was to make sure that the presented methods and results could be transferred over from one dataset to another, no matter whether the recordings were made with high-quality microphones in a clean acoustic environment, or just at an individual's home, using a cheap built-in microphone of any smartphone or tablet computer. If the model is expected to work robustly under all these circumstances, it has to be able to explore as many acoustic environments, hardware and speakers as possible during training. Large corpora did exist for such a task, a major one being *Mozilla's Common Voice* project [Ardi 19], but they would not provide a phonetic transcription of their speech samples, and more importantly, the dataset structure was heavily biased most of the times. As any user could voluntarily contribute to the project, the corpora of different languages were predominantly comprised of young male speakers. With the composition of *Common Phone* [Klum 22a], a refined version of the original English, French, German, Italian, Russian and Spanish Common Voice datasets, the balance of speakers was improved w.r.t. gender and age, and the included audio files were enriched with phonetic alignment information which had been generated automatically. The new corpus comprised around 116 hours of speech recorded from more than 11 000 contributors across all six languages. The phonetic inventory was increased significantly compared to the previous studies, using 101 unique symbols from the IPA. Given that the contributors could record their speech donation with their own devices in any acoustic environment, the new variability of signals was unmatched by the previous corpora which had all been recorded with good-quality microphones in clean acoustic environments. Consequently, it was possible to utilize a much larger model for phone recognition, based on the Wav2Vec 2.0 [Baev 20] base architecture. Instead of relying on slow RNNs with a sequential flow of information, the new model used a stack of 12 encoder blocks of the Transformer module. It was also an end-to-end architecture, meaning that the input was simply the raw waveform. The model itself would learn to perform frequency analysis with multiple 1-dimensional convolution layers. The key strength of Wav2Vec however was its unsupervised pre-training. The phone recognition model trained with Common Phone was not randomly initialized, but rather fine-tuned from a checkpoint that had already been warmed up with 960 hours of the English Librispeech corpus [Pana 15]. The unsupervised pre-training strategy will be outlined in more detail in the following section, but it was designed in a way that the resulting model checkpoint was not biased towards any particular task. After fine-tuning the Wav2Vec model, which now comprised 95 million parameters, it achieved a PER of 18.1 % on the Common Phone test set. On the first glance, this result is lower than that of the previous models, but keep in mind that the underlying difficulty increased significantly, being able to predict 101 different phones from six languages in noisy speech signals.

3.2 The Common Phone Corpus

As outlined in the history of models which led to this thesis, one major step of improving model performance on unseen data was the creation of a sophisticated corpus for robust phone recognition. The result was the Common Phone (CP) dataset, which had been created as a refined version of the *Common Voice* [Ardi 19] (CV) corpus. Only the most important facts about CP should be summarized here, further information can be found in the respective publication [Klum 22a]. Some of the core improvements over CV are:

- Fully gender-balanced
- Improved age-balance
- Reliable speaker distribution into training, development and test sets
- Machine-generated phone-level alignment
- No language is overrepresented
- Standard wave files included

The dataset is composed of 85.8 hrs of training, 15.2 hrs of development and 15.5 hrs of test audio. Whilst this might not sound like a lot of data, it was demonstrated that for fine-tuning a model that had been pre-trained on large amounts of speech already, a very small amount of training samples can be sufficient [Baev 20].

3.3 Multilingual Phone Recognition

With the introduction of Common Phone and the resulting Wav2Vec based model that had been fine-tuned with the corpus, a robust recognition of IPA phones, even under noisy conditions, was suddenly possible. Furthermore, it was possible to show that intermediate activation vectors from the neural network encoded all kinds of information [Diec 22]. This had already been discovered earlier [Klum 20, Klum 21, Klum 22b], and the behavior fully translated to the attention-based architectures. Could the model become any better from here? There was, indeed, one single number which led to the conclusion that there was one more model iteration left to be investigated. The PER of 15.6% on the English test split of Common Phone was the second-best result obtained across all six languages. It was noticeably better compared to the average performance, only being surpassed by Spanish, which is known to have a more simple phonetic structure combined with the smallest phonetic inventory out of all six languages. The explanation for the strong performance on English speech samples was very simple: The base model had been pre-trained on almost a thousand hours of English speech. This of course happened in an unsupervised fashion, but it might still introduce an acoustic bias towards the phonetic structure of English in the first place. A straightforward solution would be to pre-train the model on Common Phone rather than Librispeech. That poses a problem, because in the

Figure 3.1: Pre-training strategy of Wav2Vec 2.0. The CNN creates frame-wise feature vectors, which are then passed to a quantization module. The raw CNN features are also forwarded to the Transformer, leaving several time steps masked out. The Transformer has to identify the corresponding quantized representation of the masked time step out of a set of several other distractors.

average academic environment, the required resources for the unsupervised learning scheme of Wav2Vec are not available. As a reference, according to the Wav2Vec 2.0 paper [Baev 20], pre-training of the base model took 1.6 days using 64 high-end GPUs in parallel. The option of pre-training the model on Common Phone could quickly be ruled out, but fortunately, a variant of the large Wav2Vec model was released which had been pre-trained with speech data from 53 different languages, including many samples from Common Voice as well. The resulting model is more commonly known as Wav2Vec XLSR (cross-lingual speech representations).

As it plays such an important role in all Wav2Vec models, let us briefly outline the underlying concept of unsupervised pre-training. As the attribute *unsupervised* already suggests, there is no ground truth information used during this first optimization stage. The model itself can be broken down into two core parts, the convolutional feature extraction, which operates directly on the input signal, and the stack of transformer encoder blocks, which perform temporal contextualization. During pre-training, the feature vectors from the CNN blocks are passed into a quantization module. Quantization is achieved by concatenating quantized entries from several codebooks. The selection of discrete codebook entries is not a differentiable operation by itself. As a workaround, the quantization module applies a Gumbel softmax [Jang 16]. The Gumbel softmax function is an extension of the regular softmax, adding a temperature parameter τ . For smaller values of τ , the resulting distribution is pushed towards a one-hot vector. With increasing τ , the distribution becomes more and more uniform. In the forward pass of the quantization module, it is possible to use the hard categorical decision, whilst during the backward pass, the flow of gradients is preserved by using the Gumbel softmax distribution with values of τ which

Language	Base	XLSR
English	15.6	11.0
French	18.4	9.9
German	19.4	9.8
Italian	17.4	9.1
Spanish	15.0	6.6
Russian	21.4	8.8
Average	18.1	9.2

Table 3.1: Phone error rates of the Wav2Vec Base and XLSR models on the Common Phone test set.

decrease over time.

Several output time steps of the CNN are now erased by replacing them with a masking token. Figure 3.1 illustrates the following procedure. The raw and masked CNN outputs are fed into the Transformer, which has to solve the task of predicting the correct quantized representation q_t at masked time step t , out of a set of q_t and several distractors, which are simply quantized representations from other masked time steps of the same utterance. This identification of correct quantized representations is promoted by a contrastive loss \mathcal{L}_c , which applies a cosine similarity between context representations emitted by the Transformer and the different quantized vectors and then minimizes the negative log-likelihood of the correct quantized representation. At the same time, to prevent the codebook from collapsing into a single output entry, a codebook diversity loss term \mathcal{L}_d enforces equal utilization of all codebook entries. The pre-training loss can then be formulated in terms of the contrastive loss and the codebook diversity loss

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_c + \alpha\mathcal{L}_d \quad (3.1)$$

where α is an adjustable hyper-parameter. Simply speaking, during pre-training, the Transformer solves the task of identifying masked quantized information from an input waveform by utilizing information about the respective surrounding frames which had been assembled by the feature extraction layers. Having an already pre-trained model which is at the same time not biased towards any task such as phone recognition or full-fledged ASR allows for much shorter and less resource-demanding fine-tuning afterwards. It also lowers the amount of required labelled data drastically, considering that the original Wav2Vec 2.0 models were successfully fine-tuned only on 10 minutes of labelled audio [Baev 20]. In contrast to the relatively small amount of speech data required for fine-tuning stands the portion utilized for pre-training. The large Wav2Vec XLSR model had been pre-trained with an astonishing 56 000 hours (≈ 6.4 years) of multilingual audio.

For the fine-tuning step, all that is left to do is to add a final linear layer to project the Transformer output down to the desired number of classes. In the case of our IPA phone recognizer trained with Common Phone and CTC loss, this output space comprised 101 phones plus a blank token. The initial feature extraction CNN had a receptive field of 400 audio samples, which equaled to 25 ms for a 16 kHz signal. One 512-dimensional feature vector was emitted roughly every 20 ms. A subsequent

Figure 3.2: Asymmetric relationship between the waveform and phone sequence. The CNN block of the phone recognition model processed an input waveform as a series of equidistant chunks. The introduced temporal segmentation was preserved by the Transformer. The following Viterbi decoding introduced an asymmetry in terms of sequence length.

convolution with a kernel size of 128 served as a relative positional embedding. The following Transformer module was a stack of 24 encoder layers, which had an input dimension of 1024, a feed-forward dimension of 4096 and 16 attention heads. This final XLSR architecture comprised a total of 315 million trainable parameters and achieved a PER of 9.2% on the test set of Common Phone. PER results per language have also been listed in Table 3.1 for the Base and XLSR models.

There exists an asymmetric relationship between the number of features in the input sequence (e.g. raw audio samples or CNN feature vectors) and number of phones in the emission sequence. The latter is influenced by factors such as speech rate or the relative amount of silence in an audio signal. Figure 3.2 illustrates how a speech waveform is processed by the neural network: The CNN block was shifted over the signal in equal strides, gathering information about each frame within its respective field-of-view. Temporal context was then introduced by the Transformer block, using neural attention mechanisms. Notice that the Transformer would yield a new encoded vector for each vector of the CNN sequence. While the operations on the left side of Figure 3.2 followed an equidistant sampling scheme, asymmetry was introduced through the Viterbi decoding on the right side of the diagram. As explained earlier, not every frame contained a new phone symbol. Hence, to observe only the sequence of uttered phones, it was necessary to perform a decoding. While the introduced asymmetry resulted in a reduction of temporal information – the precise start and end time of an emitted phone were unknown – the point in time when the model was confident that a new phone was uttered by a speaker still corresponded to one of the frames sampled by the CNN. Consequently, it was possible to collect the respective CNN and Transformer feature vectors along with each decoded phone. Efficient decoding of the model’s sequential output to the underlying phone sequence was always

performed using Viterbi decoding. Following this strategy, corresponding CNN and Transformer feature vectors were extracted always at the point in time where a new phone was emitted. One important property of models optimized with CTC is that they tend to assign most of the probability mass to the blank token. If one would determine the predicted class at every frame of an arbitrary sequential input, the frames decoding to the blank index would almost certainly be overrepresented. The reason lies in the nature of the CTC loss, which promotes decoding the correct sequence of symbols, while not emitting any additional tokens (invalid insertions). Thus, the model tends to output a particular symbol once, and then fall back on the blank token, acting somewhat like a state machine. If we assume that the difference between the emission time of a particular symbol S and its time of occurrence in the signal was more or less stable, or, in other words, symbol S would constantly be emitted with some fixed delay Δt (possibly smaller than 0) compared to the reference signal, then the model would yield a somewhat stable snapshot of feature vectors. Given some stop phone for example, feature vectors from different realizations would still cover a similar view on the stop, for example with some delay δt to the closure-burst transition. This may not always be guaranteed of course and could also be influenced by the phonetic neighborhood, but it still solves certain problems of the framewise approach, such as always having more feature vectors for longer phones like vowels. The Wav2Vec XLSR model was fine-tuned with Common Phone using Adam optimizer [King 14]. The initial learning rate (LR) was set to $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$, would linearly increase to $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ over the first 10 warm-up epochs, and then remain constant for another 30 epochs. For the remaining 25 epochs, the LR decayed exponentially by factor 0.96. A complete model card with details about the architecture and information about how to reproduce the training is provided in Appendix A.1.1. Furthermore, the source code of the multilingual phone recognizer was published through a *Github* repository¹. This greatly simplifies the process of instantiating the model, downloading its parameters from Huggingface², feeding audio and ultimately decoding a sequence of IPA phone symbols together with CNN and Transformer feature vectors. Both the source code as well as the weights of the neural network are distributed under a CC0 (Creative Commons Zero 1.0) license.

With the final XLSR Wav2Vec 2.0 model that had been fine-tuned on Common Phone, it was possible to analyze audio samples which had been recorded under controlled conditions, but also those which had been captured in a noisy environment and with cheaper hardware. This ability already played a crucial role in the following chapter on the analysis of speech from individuals who suffer from Parkinson’s Disease. Unlike in a previous work [Klum 22b], it was now possible to lift the restriction of only including recordings made inside some kind of soundproof booth. Even those audio samples collected at the homes of several patients were successfully included in the evaluation of the system.

¹https://github.com/PKlumpp/phd_model

²https://huggingface.co/pklumpp/Wav2Vec2_CommonPhone

Chapter 4

Parkinson's Disease

4.1 Introduction

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Figure 4.1: Visualization of the brain areas affected by Parkinson's Disease. The main region, the basal ganglia, is highlighted in light blue.

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is the second most frequent neurodegenerative disease worldwide. It affects approximately one out of a hundred people over the age of 60 in industrialized countries [Prin 14]. With an increasing prevalence in elderly people, PD is considered a slow progressing disease of the central nervous system that often begins years before it can be diagnosed for the first time [Kali 15b]. What makes the early identification of PD even more challenging is the absence of any diagnostic test (such as a blood test). Thus, it is important to periodically re-asses the developed symptoms to validate the PD diagnosis [Jank 08]. Up until today, “the gold standard for diagnosis of Parkinson's disease has been the presence of substantia nigra pars compacta degeneration and Lewy pathology at post-mortem pathological examination” [Kali 15b]. Neuronal inclusions, called Lewy bodies, are considered to be

the major diagnostic marker, as they can be found in surviving cells of the substantia nigra of PD patients [Gibb 88]. The pathological fingerprint of PD is a loss of dopaminergic cells in the basal ganglia, a region located in the center of the brain, as shown in Figure 4.1. Post-mortem analyses have revealed that by the time of death, PD patients have lost 50% to 70% of neurons of the substantia nigra, compared to healthy specimen [Davi 08]. This degeneration of neurons in relevant brain regions is

Figure 4.2: Axial perspective of the degeneration of substantia nigra in a PD patient, compared to a healthy reference.

further illustrated in Figure 4.2.

The loss of dopaminergic brain cells causes a shortage of the neurotransmitter dopamine. This deficit is the primary cause for motor symptoms developed throughout the different disease stages. However, the first possible PD-related non-motor symptoms can occur decades before the initial diagnosis [Kali 15b]. They range from constipation, REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD), excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS), hyposmia (decreased sense of smell) to depression [Kali 15b]. The UK Parkinson's Disease Society Brain Bank clinical diagnostic criteria divide the diagnosis of PD into three steps [Hugh 92]. The diagnosis of Parkinsonian syndrome (step 1) requires the presence of Bradykinesia (slowness of voluntary movements), plus at least one of the three symptoms: muscular rigidity, a 4-6 Hz rest tremor (the involuntary trembling movement of a limb, typically the hands, during rest) or a postural instability “which is not caused by any primary visual, vestibular, cerebellar, or proprioceptive dysfunction” [Kali 15b]. In step two, the PD diagnosis is to be confirmed by ruling out different other conditions which could have induced the symptoms identified in step 1. Such conditions include, but are not limited to head injuries, encephalitis, strictly unilateral features after three years or the presence of a cerebral tumor. As mentioned before, it is important to continuously monitor the disease and confirm the initial diagnosis. This is done in step 3, in which several properties such as the progressive character of the disorder, an excellent response to the treatment with levodopa or a clinical course of more than ten years support the PD diagnosis [Kali 15b].

Braak proposed a categorization of PD into six stages [Braa 03]. The major strength of this categorization is that it does not account for the developed symptoms, but rather for the pathological progression of PD, hence it already classifies different stages before the initial diagnosis [Hawk 10]. Another frequently used categorization of PD are the five stages proposed by Hoehn and Yahr [Goet 04]:

1. Unilateral motor symptoms
2. Bilateral motor symptoms without postural instability
3. Mild to moderate impairment of postural reflexes
4. Severe postural instability, cognitive decline
5. Confinement to wheelchair or bed

Whilst these categories allow medical experts to accurately evaluate the progression of PD with respect to its main motor symptoms, it lacks descriptiveness for other health problems which are influenced by the lack of motor abilities, but do not manifest in primary motor symptoms. One such example are swallowing problems (dysphagia), because the process of swallowing involves a complex interplay of muscles in the esophagus. Another set of symptoms involves the production of speech, which requires a large amount of fine-motor muscle control.

PD can affect an individual's speech production with respect to voice (harsh quality, reduced loudness, improper intonation), fluency (initiation difficulties, inappropriate pauses, repetition of syllables) and articulation (imprecise articulation) [Ho 98]. All of the presented problems do have their root cause in the decreasing fine-motor control of PD patients. A lack of precise control of the vocal folds hinders them from accurately utilizing their voice during phonation. A healthy speech rate requires not only fine motor skills, but these skills also need to be utilized over a certain amount of time (for example several seconds to utter an entire sentence) and demand rapid transitions between the involved articulators. Due to the decreased fine motor control, PD patients are more likely to insert pauses or syllable repetitions in their speech, e.g. due to a misarticulation or to regain muscle control. As introduced in the section on phonetics, the production of speech involves a variety of articulators. This demands a high level of motor precision (for example w.r.t. tongue control) and, for certain sounds, also a significant amount of muscle tension. A prominent example are unvoiced stop sounds ([p], [t] and [k]), for which it is crucial to inhibit the flow of air by forming a constriction somewhere along the vocal tract.

Due to the progressive nature of PD and the requirement for regular re-assessment of the developed symptoms, clinicians rely on various scales to measure and quantify the strength of symptoms. One of the most well-known systems to determine the degree of impairment is the **Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale** (MDS-UPDRS) [Park 03]. It is combined of four unique parts, which involve I. non-motor experiences of daily living, II. motor experiences of daily living, III. motor examination and IV. motor complications [Goet 08]. The key strength of the UPDRS is its ability to correctly reflect the overall degree of impairment experienced by an individual. However, only two of the entire 65 items of the MDS-UPDRS

explicitly focus on speech.

Another frequently used tool to classify speech impairments in PD is the Frenchay Dysarthria Assessment (FDA) [Ende 80]. It is predominantly concerned with an individual's abilities on the level of different articulators (e.g. tongue or lips), but also includes information about respiration or jaw movement. A modified variant of the FDA, the m-FDA scale, aims to evaluate the progression of dysarthria based on speech recordings [Vasq 18] instead of performing an examination at a clinic or therapy center. To facilitate an analysis based solely on speech recordings, some items were dropped from the original FDA protocol, for example a swallowing task.

Current therapy options for PD are primarily focused on alleviating its symptoms. The loss of dopaminergic cells in the substantia nigra cannot be stopped, thus PD is a progressive neurological disorder. The resulting shortage of the neurotransmitter dopamine, which plays a major role in both the inhibition and excitation of motor signals coming from the motor cortex [Obes 08], is considered to be responsible to most PD-related symptoms. However, the pathophysiological model of PD is still not fully understood, as it falls short to explain certain characteristics of the disease, such as the increased activity of the subthalamic nucleus [Scho 22]. The primary lack of dopamine can be treated with the administration of levodopa. Levodopa is a pre-stage of dopamine, which, unlike the neurotransmitter itself, is able to pass the blood-brain barrier [Abbo 10]. The treatment is effective at compensating for the dopamine deficiency and allows patients to maintain a much higher quality of life while the disease progresses. At some point, however, usually after many years of successful administration of levodopa, the drug response becomes "less reliable and the anti-Parkinsonian drugs induce potentially disabling dyskinesias" [Svei 16].

One last resort to alleviate PD symptoms in later stages of the condition is surgical treatment. The core idea is to implant electrodes into the subthalamic nuclei, which could then be used "to modulate or disrupt patterns of neural signaling within a targeted region"[Bena 03]. The so-called **Deep Brain Stimulation** (DBS) is known to have positive effects on certain motor symptoms, but is less likely to improve an individual's speech production [Bena 03]. A long-term study on the effects of DBS revealed that the intelligibility of speech from patients who had undergone surgery decreased at a higher rate compared to that of a non-operated control group [Limo 19]. Another major role in the treatment of PD symptoms plays speech therapy [Schu 00]. Speech is a human beings primary tool for communication, and an impaired speech often has severe consequences on an individual's abilities of social interaction. A positive impact could be observed on the levels of prosody and intelligibility for a group of patients that had received daily at-home speech therapy over the course of two to three weeks [Scot 83]. More importantly, these improvements could be maintained for up to three months. The **Lee Silverman Voice Treatment** (LSVT) aims to improve a patient's loudness during voicing within a therapy period of four weeks [Fox 06]. After the initial sessions with a speech therapist, the patient is required to perform daily at-home speech exercises to conserve the improvements [Sapi 11].

While speech therapy can have a positive impact on an individual's life, it often requires a high exercising frequency together with a speech therapist. Additionally, it is important that patients practise their abilities for themselves at home. The high demand for speech therapy, particularly against the background of an

aging society, causes a diminishing availability of professionals who can assist patients [Reut 16, Gilm 18]. If a patient requires five hours of speech therapy per week, and one hour is covered with the medical expert, then the patient has to make up for the missing four hours by exercising at home. This is quite a normal procedure, but it comes at the cost of not having any feedback about what the individual is practising. The lack of feedback is not ideal, but in the case of PD, the problems go further. Dopamine plays an important role in the brain's reward system [Aria 10]. The reward system is responsible for the initial motivation to make an effort for a particular reward. In the case of PD, the effort is the speech exercise, whereas the reward is an improved intelligibility, resulting in more satisfying social interactions. Recent studies have shown that the lack of dopamine reduced the willingness of patients to exert effort for reward [Chon 15]. It was also shown that the treatment with levodopa significantly improved willingness, but it would still remain lower compared to that of a healthy control cohort. Consequently, the absence of feedback in self-supervised exercise sessions is only one challenge. Keeping PD patients motivated to continuously practise their articulatory abilities to maintain a better quality of life, despite the fact that the disease is still progressing further, is even more difficult.

The rise of digital therapy applications which provide detailed explanation of speech exercises, guide the patient through their respective at-home therapy plan, document therapy frequency and remind individuals of their daily practise sessions has introduced new opportunities to close the existing gap between expert-supervised and self-supervised therapy. Ideally, such an application should also be able to provide constructive feedback. A patient should be rewarded when they performed well, did many exercises or even if they completed an entire exercise session and the system detected that they *had a bad day*, simply to compliment them for their efforts. At the same time, it should also provide precise feedback for each item of an exercise. In the case of PD, there are different categories to provide feedback on. If the patient was doing a *sustained vowel* exercise, their task is to produce one particular vowel over an extended period of time, usually several seconds. This task focuses on an individual's voicing capabilities, as well as on loudness. The application could provide a real-time response about the produced volume, and inform the patient when their voice deviates from the target sound. Another popular speech exercise for PD are so-called diadochokinesis (DDK) tasks, which usually involve the rapid repetition of consonant-vowel clusters, like [pa], [ta] and [ka]. In this scenario, the focus shifts from voicing and loudness to precise articulation. Notice that if the three presented clusters are combined, the exercise is more challenging because the articulation travels from the very front (lips) over the alveolar area behind the teeth all the way back to the velum. For each target stop [p], [t] and [k], the therapy application should be able to provide feedback about how reliably the patient was able to produce the stop sound. One last popular exercise requires the patients to read a sentence or a longer text. In this case, it is possible to evaluate intelligibility on a broader scope, but it is also interesting to investigate how well individuals are able to maintain a certain loudness over an extended period of speaking.

In modern standards, an application is not limited to only providing therapy feedback though. By collecting speech data on a regular basis and performing a variety of analyses, it is possible to put a single daily result into much more context. Was

it just this one bad day, or is the patient's performance declining significantly over a certain amount of time? How big is the difference between the On (under the influence of medication) and Off (diminished medication influence) states? All this information could be helpful to better understand and monitor the effectiveness of a patient's therapy protocol, and, if required, schedule an appointment with their medical advisor as soon as a decline was identified.

4.2 Literature Review

The following section will outline the current state-of-the-art of the automated analysis of PD speech. It will cover different sub-topics, like the classification of PD versus healthy controls, the monitoring of speech-related symptoms as well as the generation of feedback during daily exercise sessions. For each of the presented works, this thesis will summarize the core idea and utilized architectures, the reported results and, in the context of this contribution, interpret how well the proposed systems could generalize for unseen data. All presented works focused predominantly on the analysis of speech.

All of the studies listed in Table 4.1 incorporated the PC-GITA corpus in their experiments. PC-GITA [Oroz 14] comprises speech recordings from Colombian Spanish speakers, 50 of them diagnosed with PD, another 50 age- and gender-matched healthy control speakers. It is one of the most well-recognized corpora for the analysis of pathological speech signals in the domain of PD and encompasses various signals, from dedicated speech exercises (sustained vowels, DDK), read sentences and longer texts, to free monologues. Additionally, there exists a subset of speakers who had been recorded over multiple sessions, either at their homes (over the course of several months) or in the recording institution (longitudinal protocol over the course of years). All recordings from the institution are of decent audio quality, captured in a (portable) sound-proof booth.

The first listed study from Amato et al. used prosodic as well as spectral speech features, plus MFCCs, as inputs for a k-nearest neighbors classifier. They employ a 10-fold cross-validation strategy for feature selection and experiment with early- and late-fusion approaches, ultimately reporting an average accuracy of 94.3% on randomly selected test splits of the corpus. Whilst such a high success rate looks impressive on the first glance, they also reported results on a secondary, not openly accessible PD dataset which is made up of Spanish speakers recorded in good acoustic conditions as well. The accuracy dropped sharply to 61%, which is only slightly above chance-level in case of a binary classification problem. Nevertheless, it was for this secondary result why the study was deemed worthy to be mentioned in the table. The authors highlighted a very important problem, which is the lack of generalization of many scientific ML contributions. In most ML disciplines, there exist a few standard datasets that can be used to compute metrics which then allow a direct comparison to other studies reporting results on the same problem. Whilst this is good practise from a scientific standpoint, the degree of generalization strongly depends on how representative the dataset in question really is. In the case of PD, despite having the same native language and acoustic conditions with very little noise, the results estimated over the PC-GITA corpus could not be transferred to the second dataset.

Title	Authors (year)	Task	Model	Features	Results
An algorithm for Parkinson’s disease speech classification based on isolated words analysis [Amat 21]	F. Amato et al. (2021)	CLF	kNN	prosodic spectral MFCCs	Accuracy (%) PC-GITA: 94.3 other: 61.0
Supervised speech representation learning for Parkinson’s disease classification [Janb 21]	P. Janbakhshi et al. (2021)	CLF	MLP	mel-spec auto-encoder	Accuracy (%) PC-GITA: 75.4
The detection of Parkinson’s disease from speech using voice source information [Nare 21]	N. P. Narendra et al. (2021)	CLF	end2end MLP	glottal flow signal	Accuracy (%) PC-GITA: 68.6
Convolutional neural networks and a transfer learning strategy to classify Parkinson’s disease from speech in three different languages [Vasq 19b]	J. C. Vásquez-Correa et al. (2019)	CLF	pre-trained MLP	mel-spec	Accuracy (%) PC-GITA: 72.0 German: 77.3 Czech: 72.6
Unobtrusive monitoring of speech impairments of Parkinson’s disease patients through mobile devices [Aria 18a]	T. Arias-Vergara et al. (2018)	CAT	MLP	mel-spec	Accuracy (%) PC-GITA: 58.0
Speaker models for monitoring Parkinson’s disease progression considering different communication channels and acoustic conditions [Aria 18b]	T. Arias-Vergara et al. (2018)	REG	GMM-UBM i-vectors	phonation prosodic articulation	longitudinal PC-GITA correlation m-FDA: 0.77
Evaluation of the Neurological State of People with Parkinson’s Disease Using i-Vectors [Garc 17]	N. García et al. (2017)	REG	i-vectors	phonation articulation	PC-GITA correlation m-FDA: 0.72
Towards an automatic evaluation of the dysarthria level of patients with Parkinson’s disease [Vasq 18]	J. C. Vásquez-Correa et al. (2018)	REG	SVR i-vectors	phonation articulation prosody	PC-GITA corr. m-FDA SVR: 0.58 i-vectors: 0.69
Parkinson’s condition estimation using speech acoustic and inversely mapped articulatory data [Hahm 15]	S. Hahm et al. (2015)	REG	MLP	MFCCs acoustic-to-articulatory inverse mapping	PC-GITA correlation UPDRS: 0.49

Table 4.1: A list of notable contributions in the domains of PD classification (CLF), categorical (CAT) severity analysis and severity score prediction (REG). Utilized models varied between k-nearest neighbors (kNN) classifier, multi-layer-perceptron (MLP), Gaussian Mixture Model Universal Background Model (GMM-UBM) and support-vector regression (SVR). All reported correlation values according to Spearman.

The three other studies from Table 4.1 which perform a classification between healthy and PD subjects all employed some sort of multi-layer perceptron (MLP). Janbakhshiel et al. trained an auto-encoder (AE) using mel-spectrogram input signals. The AE was trained partially in a supervised fashion by learning a speaker identification task from the bottleneck features. An adversarial strategy was then used during optimization to force the bottleneck features to encode as little speaker information as possible. Afterwards, the PD classifier trained on these bottleneck features achieved an accuracy of 75.4%. Narendra et al. implemented an end-to-end (end2end) approach. Strictly speaking, this is not entirely an end2end solution, because instead of operating on the raw waveform, they use the extracted glottal flow excitation signal as input. However, this approach seems reasonable as it covers the vocal folds' vibration signal, which is well-known to be affected by PD [Litt 08, Aroc 17]. The resulting model achieved an accuracy of 68.6%. Vásquez-Correa et al. presented another MLP which operated on mel-spectrograms, but besides PC-GITA, they utilized two other datasets from German and Czech PD patients. They successfully improved the accuracy of models for one particular language by using one of the other two languages for pre-training. This way, they were able to obtain an accuracy of 72.0% on PC-GITA, 77.3% on the German and 72.6% on the Czech data, respectively. The fact that speech samples from a foreign language helped the MLP to estimate better decision rules during fine-tuning strongly implies that it is possible to derive a general, language- and dataset-independent signal-level understanding of PD.

Classifying a disease like PD only from speech is, at best, an optimistic effort. The reason is that the degree of speech impairment developed during PD can vary a lot among individuals, and clinicians mostly base their decision on motor symptoms, like postural instability, freezing of gait and resting tremor. However, the studies on PD classification provide important insights into how the speech of PD deviates from a healthy cohort. This understanding is key to propose valid systems to track the progression of PD and estimate how severely an individual is affected.

One such approach was made by Arias-Vergara et al. in a study where the degree of impairment had to be classified into three different categories *mild*, *moderate* and *severe*. They proposed the usage of an MLP trained on mel-spectrograms. This technique had already been discussed previously in two studies that performed PD classification. The three-class categorization achieved an accuracy of 58.0%, with the model being biased towards the mild and severe cases. In this context, it is worth mentioning that the ground-truth categorization had been derived only from the single MDS-UPDRS-III speech score. Knowing that the UPDRS insufficiently describes an individual's abilities w.r.t. articulation, phonation and prosody, chances of label noise are also quite high.

The remaining works from Table 4.1 all conducted regression experiments to project the degree of speech impairment on a continuous scale. In a second contribution from Arias-Vergara et al., they used Gaussian Mixture Model Universal Background Models (GMM-UBM) and i-vectors, two methods originally developed for the task of speaker identification, to model the progression of PD for individual patients. They did this by estimating UBMs to which it was possible to compute the distance for a particular patient at a given point in time. The deviations from said UBM for one speaker over several recording sessions should model the progression of the disease.

The approach was particularly successful in the case of the longitudinal data, reaching a Spearman correlation of 0.77 with the m-FDA score, most likely because the time in between sessions was larger, thus the observed differences would be more pronounced. In another work by García et al., i-vectors were used to estimate the degree of speech impairment of patients at a single point in time. Here, instead of modelling changes in individual speakers, it was important to compare the abilities of one speaker to that of the others. Their system was based on phonation and articulation features and achieved a correlation of 0.72. I-vectors were also used in another study [Vasq 18] from Vaásquez-Correa et al., which yielded a correlation of 0.69. Additionally, they conducted experiments using a support vector regression (SVR) model. However, this performed significantly weaker compared to the i-vectors, resulting in a correlation of 0.58. All these findings strongly supported the assumption that models commonly used for speaker identification or verification were able to model other characteristics, such as the degree of speech impairment, as well. The last work from Table 4.1 from Hahm et al. used an MLP in combination with articulatory features which had been estimated by performing an inverse mapping. The interesting part of this contribution is that they correlated their predicted PD progression scores not with the m-FDA labels, which exclusively resembled speech, but with the UPDRS. As discussed before, the UPDRS mostly covers the motor abilities of individuals. Accordingly, the observed correlation of 0.49 is clearly lower than the correlations reported with the m-FDA score. This proved once more that there is no strong link between general motor impairment and the expressed speech deficits of individual patients.

Whilst all the introduced studies performed experiments on one of the most well-recognized PD corpora, their overall ability to provide models with high generalization is quite small. One major reason is that the works relied on leave-one-speaker-out (LOSO) or N-fold CV strategies. This is perfectly fine to report valid results, but one should keep in mind that while the speakers are different between training and test, the acoustic conditions, recording hardware, exercise protocol and other factors are not. If one of these key parameters changed, would the system still be able to work properly? In almost every case, the likely answer is *No*. The behavior of most ML models for new, previously unseen input data which suddenly lies outside of the distribution of the training data, is simply undefined. Particularly in the case of parameter-intensive MLPs, it is impossible to guess the outcome. The first work from Amato clearly showed how difficult it is to achieve good generalization from a small amount of training data, even when using an approach like kNN, which is known to be very cheap w.r.t. the required parameters.

4.3 The PC-GITA Dataset

As mentioned in the previous section already, PC-GITA [Oroz 14] is one of the most well-recognized speech corpora for research in the domain of PD. Within the scope of this thesis, the extended version of the corpus will be used, which comprises 86 healthy control (HC) speakers as well as 106 PD patients. In a previous study [Klum 22b], the number of speakers was reduced to 48 HC and 58 PD, omitting those who had either not been recorded inside a (portable) sound-proof booth or who were missing annotation w.r.t. m-FDA. All experiments conducted throughout this work were

Figure 4.3: Distribution of age and total m-FDA scores for the cohorts of healthy speakers and Parkinson's patients. Numbers are shown for all subjects where the respective annotation was available.

aimed to be transferable to any other relevant dataset, even if it had been recorded under noisy conditions, hence recordings from PD participants were only excluded if the respective m-FDA annotation was not available. Consequently, a total number of 86 HC and 58 PD patients could be considered. Notice that it was possible to include recordings from multiple sessions for the PD patients, not only those recorded under clean acoustic conditions.

The m-FDA score, which had already been introduced briefly during the literature review, is a composition of multiple sub-scores which describe unique properties of an individual's speech production. M-FDA always encodes an increased degree of impairment with a larger score. Evaluated categories (and score range) are lips (0–8), palate (0–8), larynx (0–12), breathing (0–8), intelligibility (0–4), monotonicity (0–4) and tongue (0–8). This results in a total score range from 0 (healthy) to 52 (maximally impaired). Every PD participant of the study had their speech samples evaluated w.r.t. m-FDA by three expert speech therapists. Afterwards, the final score was determined as the median of the three annotations.

Both the PD (female: 27, male: 31) as well as the HC (female: 43, male: 43) cohort were quite balanced in terms of gender. The age distribution of healthy and diseased speakers is shown in Figure 4.3a. They share almost the same mean and standard age deviation. For 10 PD and 4 HC contributors, the age was unknown. Furthermore, the second Figure 4.3b illustrates the relative frequency of m-FDA scores in individuals. For both plots, the underlying distribution was also estimated via a Gaussian mixture density, using one component in the case of age distribution, and two components for the distribution of m-FDA scores. The usage of two components was motivated differently for each group: In the case of healthy speakers, it was expected to see many scores close to 0, but some speakers might suffer from other speech problems, hence they should be reflected in a secondary component. For the PD group, there are likely clusters of less affected and more severely affected individuals. One could argue that it might be possible to add even more components for this group, but using two instances as for the healthy reference make a direct comparison much easier. Notice that the speech experts did not only provide labels for PD contributors, but also for

many of the healthy reference samples. This is incredibly helpful as it can be seen from the histogram. While most HC subjects had a very low m-FDA score, which was to be expected, there were several outliers that were evaluated to express a higher degree of speech impairment compared to some of the PD patients. Such knowledge can be crucial for the later understanding and interpretation of findings. At the same time, this histogram suggests that, given only a speech signal, it should be rather difficult to produce an algorithm which is able to perfectly classify PD and, at the same time, remains robust enough to be transferable to any new dataset. The higher the recall of PD cases (sensitivity) of a particular model is, the more likely it is to falsely classify healthy individuals as PD patients as well.

Another set of exercise recordings was collected from seven patients, three female and four male, at their homes using headsets. Over the course of four sessions (days) at intervals between one and two months, each patient was recorded four times during one day, in the morning, noon, early and late afternoon. All of the recordings had been annotated w.r.t. m-FDA, which allows researchers to investigate the disease progression over the course of months, as well as to understand the effect of medication On and Off states and related articulatory abilities.

The core set of PC-GITA comprised four major exercise categories. The first was made up of several DDK tasks, such as the rapid repetition of the word *pa-ta-ka*. The exercise requires strong articulatory precision over a certain amount of time. Each of the three stops [p], [t] and [k] requires a good amount of muscle tension to realize the closure and build up air pressure for the following burst, as task that is particularly difficult for individuals suffering from PD. The second block of exercises required participants to read different sentences. As the inventory of sentences was the same for all subjects, it was possible to directly compare the results of different groups of contributors to understand how their articulation might change. As an extension to this task, the third exercise had individuals read an entire short text. The duration of continuous speech production was longer than in the previous task, which would require greater efforts to maintain a certain level of speech quality over the full exercise duration. Such an exercise is perfectly suited to analyze the volume of speakers over time, but it could also offer interesting insights on the phonetic level. Lastly, all contributors were asked to speak a monologue at their own, describing their every-day routine. Monologues could vary in length, the duration usually ranged between 30s up to 3m. The major advantage of the monologue is that instead of reading a predefined text, subjects could freely choose their words, adjust their speech rate and make pauses. The ability to analyze free speech signals is a key requirement for any unobtrusive monitoring solution, for example using mobile applications as in [Klum 17].

All signals were recorded at 44.1 kHz sampling frequency, using a depth of 16 bits in single-channel configuration. For all performed experiments, the audio data had been resampled to 16 kHz sampling rate, matching the expected sampling frequency of the phone recognition model.

4.4 Experiments

4.4.1 Phonetic Footprints

The motivation of phonetic footprints is to provide a concise summary of an individual's phonetic inventory, estimated over a sufficient amount of time, usually several minutes of free speech. Significantly less time is required if the audio recording was captured following a dedicated exercise protocol, because recordings from different individuals from the same protocol can easily be compared with each other.

The phonetic footprint of any individual describes the prior probability of a particular phone s of a closed set of possible phone symbols S , such that $1 = \sum_{s \in S} P(s)$ forms a probability density. Depending on the data the phonetic footprint had been estimated over, it may not reflect the individual's general inventory, but rather the utilized inventory of the particular task. Phonetic footprints are influenced by the underlying phonetic inventory of the speaker's native language. On the one hand, there is a direct influence of the native inventory which is determined during the process of first speech acquisition. The unvoiced and voiced dental fricatives $[\theta]$ and $[\ð]$ for example are not part of the German phonetic inventory. If a large number of native German speakers were asked to say a sentence which contained both symbols, the expected probability of both phones to be produced is almost certainly lower than that of native English speakers. A second way how the native language might interfere with phonetic footprints is by means of allophones. Allophones had been briefly mentioned in the introduction to phonetics, and they refer to valid pronunciation alternatives within the framework of a particular language. In Spanish phonology, for example, there is no phonemic difference between $[d]$ and $[\ð]$. This might influence the results obtained for a particular exercise. Let the task be the rapid repetition of the consonant-vowel cluster *da*, native Spanish speakers might not produce the phone $[d]$, because they consider $[\ð]$ as a valid alternative.

The phonetic inventory of languages does not only manifest in terms of individual phones, but also in the higher-order categories. Let us consider the phonetic footprints averaged over all contributors of the Common Phone test set as shown in Figure 4.4. Instead of estimating a probability density function (PDF) over all 101 phones in the recognizer's inventory, the symbols were grouped into nine different phonetic categories. This illustration serves as the perfect example to highlight how phonetic footprints help reveal phonetic characteristics of certain speaker groups, for example that of a particular language, but also of cohorts of healthy and diseased subjects. The first and likely most obvious special case out of the six languages is French, being the only one incorporating any nasalized vowels in its phonetic profile. While this may not come as a surprise, there are other patterns that one might not have expected. Spanish has just about as many voiceless plosives as all other languages, but the amount of voiced plosives is considerably smaller. A likely explanation are the non-plosive allophones of Spanish voiced plosives, such as $[\ð]$ for $[d]$ as mentioned earlier. Another example of a clear deviation from all other languages is the relative frequency of non-lateral approximants in German. The language's only non-lateral approximant is $[j]$, but that was rather infrequent. Notice that this is likely not a recognition error, as the ratio of approximants is clearly higher in all other languages. With all the patterns that could be identified from such a simple footprint, it also

Figure 4.4: Exemplary phonetic footprints of the six different languages of Common Phone. The composition of individual categories has a major influence on the observable results.

hides a lot of information from the reader. Let us take a closer look at the profiles of English and Russian. Whilst there are minor differences, compared to the other footprints, the two look very similar. Does this mean that English and Russian sound very similar? Not at all! The illustration is simply hiding important information. As discussed in the section on phonetics, a single phone describes a number of different properties. If the diagrams from Figure 4.4 were to encode all those properties, they would have to visualize every single phone. Consequently, to group certain phones together by various shared properties, other properties have to be omitted. If the chart included a differentiation between regular and palatalized fricatives and plosives, the charts of English and Russian would look entirely different. Palatalization is a type of secondary articulation which results in distinctive phonemes (like /p/ and /p^j/) in Russian. It is therefore important to select categories carefully in accordance to the patterns one would like to observe.

In the case of pathological speech, it can be helpful to modify the original definition of phonetic footprints slightly. In general, it might suffice to estimate the prior probability of a symbol s as its relative frequency of occurrence. This works particularly well if the model assigned a vast majority of probability mass to that symbol at the time of emission. In other words, the recognizer emitted symbol s with high confidence. In the case of pathological speech, these confidences are not always as high, which will also be shown in one of the following experiments. The degree of uncertainty increases along with a decreasing intelligibility, which should also be reflected in the

Figure 4.5: Phonetic footprints for syllable *pa* of HC as well as several PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA lips score. The first phone is the target consonant, followed by its confusions. Then comes the target vowel, again followed by its confusions, concluding with the occurrence of silence. For this as well as all following illustrations, the cohorts with higher scores do not include the speakers which had already been assigned to a cohort with lower score (A speaker with an m-FDA lips score of 2 appears exclusively in the least affected PD group).

phonetic footprints. Consequently, instead of computing the relative frequency of occurrence

$$footprint(s|x) = \frac{N_s}{N} \quad (4.1)$$

given some signal x , one should take into account the posterior probability of the emitted symbol, such that

$$footprint(s|x) = \frac{\sum_{n \in N} p_n(s|x)}{N} \quad (4.2)$$

As a result, the recognition of symbol s at index n with high confidence $p_n(s|x) = 0.99$ will have a stronger contribution to the footprint of s than a recognition with confidence $p_n(s|x) = 0.5$.

Given some simple speech task, it is possible to determine footprints on symbol-level, instead of using any kind of categorization as it was done for the six languages from Common Phone. In the first presented DDK exercise, participants were asked to repeat the syllable *pa* multiple times in quick succession. The respective phonetic footprint is shown in Figure 4.5. Whenever patients had been grouped into several clusters of different m-FDA score ranges, the boundaries were chosen in a way that they yielded the most uniform distribution of samples possible (no group over- or underrepresented). Error margins represent the standard deviation of the respective bar. To keep visualizations clean, footprints were only plotted for those IPA phone symbols that yielded at least 1% posterior probability for any of the clusters. The most obvious difference between the phonetic footprints from the different speaker clusters is their respective probability of successfully producing the plosive [p]. Given

Figure 4.6: Phonetic footprints for syllable *ta* of HC as well as several PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA tongue score.

that each utterance usually started and ended with a silent segment denoted as (...), the probability of [p] and [a] should be close to 50 % in the case of flawless pronunciation. The group of healthy participants came closest to this ideal, with a very low number of other recognized symbols. In combination with the relatively small standard deviations for [p] and [a], this shows that their cluster was able to successfully complete the task almost all the time. Furthermore, it supports the assumption that the new phone recognition model is robust enough to not only analyze high-quality recordings, but also include the other data collected in the scope of PC-GITA. A closer look on the results of the different PD clusters immediately reveals a drastic decline of successful articulation of [p]. More importantly, the decline becomes more apparent with increasing impairment of the lips according to the m-FDA score. The probability of vowel [a] also experienced a decline, but it was less pronounced than that of the [p]. While it is well-known that the voicing accuracy of vowels decreases as PD progresses, the speaker groups had been assembled w.r.t. the lips impairment, which is likely not the optimal criterion. It is also possible that the overall reduction of the phonetic footprint of [a] is not as pronounced as that of [p]. Interestingly, the patients with an increased lips score did not only produce more voiced plosive counterparts [b], but also a noticeable amount of [t]. This could be the result of recognition uncertainty due to an imprecise articulation.

The articulation of syllable *pa* involves the front-most articulators. For the next exercise, the articulation travels further back, repeatedly producing the syllable *ta*. This time, the main articulator is the tongue. Accordingly, the phonetic footprints shown in Figure 4.6 had been clustered by the m-FDA tongue score. While the overall pattern of a declining footprint of vowel [a] with increasing m-FDA score remained the same as in the previous experiment, the overall posterior probabilities of [a] are slightly lower. A similar, but much more pronounced pattern could be seen for the unvoiced stop [t]. While the overall trend remained the same as that observed for the [p] in syllable *pa*, the absolute posterior probability of articulating a [t] was lower for all but the most impaired group, with the HC only achieving 30 %. In this con-

Figure 4.7: Phonetic footprints for syllable *ka* of HC as well as several PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA larynx score.

text, notice that the model detected far more realizations of the voiced alternative [d] compared to [b] in the previous exercise. This was observed for all clusters, also the HC group. Only the increasing frequency of [d] for the group of patients with highest m-FDA tongue score could be attributed to the increasing severity of PD, causing them to be less successful of building up the required muscle tension for the closure between tongue and alveolar ridge. Another notable observation which supports this assumption are the increasing probabilities of [s] and [ð], which have the same or very similar place of articulation as [t], but indicate a failure to also realize the correct manner of articulation, which would then result in a different phone.

For the last isolated syllable *ka*, the phonetic footprint is shown in Figure 4.7. Once again, the trends for the vowel [a] and the unvoiced stop [k] are very similar to the previous observations. This indicates that phonetic footprints are able to encode information about the speech production abilities on the level of individual articulators. As it was already observed for the syllable *pa*, some of the stop sounds were recognized as [t] instead of [k]. The simple and most likely reason here are misclassifications. Whilst the recognizer is quite powerful, it is by no means free of errors. Particularly the short stop sounds could easily be misrecognized between each other. For the most severely affected group of PD patients, the model identified a variety of other produced sounds, such as [r], [l], [ə], [s], [o] and [e]. Apparently, the pronunciation of PD patients became more and more volatile, resulting in a variety of new recognized phone symbols.

Looking at the results from all three presented exercises, it is clearly visible that the degree of impairment which had been annotated by a human speech expert strongly manifests in the phonetic footprint of different speaker groups. Furthermore, this did not only correspond to a general degree of speech impairment, but to the evaluation results of the involved articulators. Although the first three exercises focused predominantly on the articulatory capabilities of individuals, findings also revealed the increasing voicing difficulties of PD patients. Given that participants were always asked to produce the vowel [a], with increasing PD severity, the posterior probability

of the vowel decreased, and an increasing number of other recognized vowels could be observed. With respect to pronunciation alternatives for the required unvoiced stop, patients produced a variety of other phones, many of which shared the place of articulation with the target phone. This was another indicator of imprecise pronunciation. An important property of phonetic footprints is that they are strongly affected by the relative frequency of individual symbols. The observed strong differences between speaker groups in the presented speech exercises so far were also a result of many realizations of the particular phones. In free speech, where these phones have a significantly lower prior probability, the observed trends will almost certainly be the same, but they are going to be less pronounced, due to the smaller numbers.

For the syllables *pa* and *ta*, we could observe that PD patients tended to produce more voiced realizations of the unvoiced target stop, replacing the [p] with [b] and [t] with [d]. For the repetition of *ka*, this seemed not to be the case. In fact, it might be quite surprising that for none of the speaker groups, the average posterior probability reached at least 1%. A possible explanation for this observation can be found in the literature on American Spanish phonology. The phoneme /g/ is the plosive with the lowest prior probability in regular Spanish speech [Guir 90]. Furthermore, its unvoiced counterpart /k/ has a prior probability which is almost four times as high. The study also investigated relative phoneme frequency in the 27 most common Spanish syllables, and /g/ is not used among any of those [Guir 90]. This does not mean that patients did never produce the voiced phone [g], but it highlights a potential bias in the recognition results. The rapid repetition of syllable *ka* is not normal speech, which the model had been optimized on. For the recognizer, there is only one known pattern to exploit from those recordings: the syllable structure. If it had learned during optimization that the syllable *ga* is quite unlikely (poorly represented in the training data), this could result in a biased prediction result. Even if a participant had said *ga*, the model could map this to a syllable it had seen more often during training.

The isolated repetition of *pa*, *ta* and *ka* was already challenging for PD patients. The difficulty of the entire task could be increased further by requiring individuals to produce the syllable combination *pa-ta-ka* repeatedly, in which the place of articulation travels from the front to the back. In this case, it would be important to arrange the clusters of PD patients in terms of a score which is not bound to one particular articulator, like the tongue or lips. To satisfy this condition, for the next two experiments, the total m-FDA score was used to create uniformly distributed clusters. The phonetic footprint of *pa-ta-ka* is shown in Figure 4.8. During the first three exercises, there was always a clear declining trend for vowel [a] as the disease progressed. Suddenly, this trend is entirely gone. At the same time, the recognizer yielded far more productions of [o]. This result could not be attributed to the disease state by any means, because it was particularly profound in healthy reference speakers. To better understand the recognition results, it could be helpful to put the recognized [o] phones into more context. An analysis of the preceding consonant revealed a surprisingly one-sided result. Out of a total 1892 recognized [o], 1693 appeared right after the [p]. A very small number (32) was recognized after [t], and a slightly larger amount of 167 after [k]. Notice that a total of more than 98% of [o] phones were either recognized before or after the [p]. This is an important finding, not only be-

Figure 4.8: Phonetic footprints for syllable combination *pa-ta-ka* of HC as well as several PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their total m-FDA score. The plot shows all three target consonants first, because it is not always possible to exclusively attribute a consonant confusion to only one of the target consonants.

cause it reveals that the recognition results are not just random misclassifications. There seems to be a clear correspondence between the involvement of the lips during articulation of [p] and the opening of the mouth for the vowel [a]. More importantly, this appears to be particularly challenging during the travelling articulation exercise, as such a pattern was not observed for the isolated syllable *pa* before.

Looking at the footprints of [p], [t] and [k], the decline remained quite visible for both [t] and [k] throughout different speaker clusters. For the stop [t], the trend was found to be quite a lot weaker. An explanation for this can be found in the isolated syllable tasks: For both [p] in *pa* as well as [k] in *ka*, there was an increasing number of misclassifications of [t] for more severely affected patients. Consequently, whilst these patients may still have difficulties producing [t] correctly, as observed in the *ta* exercise, there might be misclassifications attributed to [t] at the same time, which lower the visibility of the overall trend.

The last phonetic footprint estimated over speech samples from a dedicated exercise visualized the phones utilized for the syllable combination *pe-ta-ka*. Notice that this is almost the same configuration as before, only the [a] from the syllable *pa* had been replaced with an [e]. For the evaluation of the findings presented so far, this is particularly interesting, as it replaced the [a] which had been frequently misclassified as [o] in the *pa-ta-ka* exercise before. The footprint is shown in Figure 4.9, where patients had been clustered according to the same logic as for the previous exercise. The trend of [p] and [k] remained almost unchanged. For [t], there appears to be a similar pattern of not showing much of a trend. It is to be noted here that with increasing m-FDA scores, a larger number of those recognized [t] were in the positions of [p] or [k], supporting the assumption that these are predominantly misclassifications instead of successful realizations of [t] in the correct place. Unlike for the previous *pa-ta-ka*, there appeared to be a slight decline of [a] again. More importantly, notice that almost all occurrences of [o] have vanished. As most of the [o] were previously

Figure 4.9: Phonetic footprints for syllable combination *pe-ta-ka* of HC as well as several PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their total m-FDA score.

recognized after [p], and this phone had now been replaced with [e], this appears to be a perfectly reasonable result. The [e] on the other hand was always recognized quite reliably for all speakers except for the group with the highest degree of impairment according to m-FDA. Lastly, let us take a look at the discovered pronunciation alternatives which yielded a posterior probability of 1% for at least one of the four groups. The bilabial fricative [β] corresponds to the [p], having exactly the same place of articulation. Given that [p] also showed the most profound decline for the severely affected patients, its bilabial fricative counterpart became increasingly visible. Another particularly interesting pattern is that of the second, even more likely pronunciation alternative recognized for [p], its palatalized variant [p^j]. As introduced earlier, the palatalized variants of phones appeared exclusively in Russian samples from the Common Phone corpus. Its recognition during the repetition of *pe-ta-ka* conveys multiple important messages at the same time. Firstly, during inference, the model is able to predict phones that were part of only one particular language during training, even if the speakers did not speak that language. In other words, the recognizer did not learn by heart that the palatalized variant of a phone could only occur in a Russian speech sample. This is a key strength of the model if it should be used for the phonetic analysis of pathological speech signal, and in this context, employ its entire phonetic inventory. Secondly, and this might be even more important for those readers that do not have a strong background in phonetics: Why did the model recognize the palatalized variant of [p] in the first place? In the footprint of *pa-ta-ka*, we could see how the presence of the stop [p] affected the following [a], which was frequently recognized as an [o]. Such an interaction of neighboring phones can be seen in the repetition of *pe-ta-ka* again. A quick look at the vowel chart in Figure 2.20 reveals that [a] is an open, whereas [e] is a close-mid vowel, which both share a front tongue position. Consequently, in the new exercise, the tongue has to travel a lot closer to the palate after the [p]. If the tongue is elevated too early, it results in a palatalization of the stop [p]. In normal speech, such a pattern would likely be unobservable, but in the closed environment of the dedicated speech exercise, and

Figure 4.10: Phonetic footprints for isolated sentences spoken by HC as well as two PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA intelligibility score.

under the condition that participants should produce the syllable combinations at a sufficient pace, these co-articulation artifacts could suddenly be revealed.

The remaining speech tasks did not require individuals to perform any kind of dedicated speech exercise. Instead, they were asked to read ten different isolated sentences or a longer coherent text, or describe their daily routine in a brief monologue. This time, phonetic footprints should be evaluated w.r.t. the general articulation capabilities of participants. Consequently, instead of clustering individuals by their m-FDA score associated to a particular articulator, they had been grouped according to their m-FDA intelligibility score. This time, PD patients were divided into two groups only. The primary reason for this decision was that the intelligibility score had a very small range between 0 (perfectly intelligible) and 4 (hardly intelligible). On the other hand, it was motivated by the smaller relative changes that were expected to appear in the footprints, simply because they were not estimated from dedicated speech exercises anymore. Phonetic footprints for the set of all sentences are visualized in Figure 4.10, this time using a clustering of relevant phonetic categories. In the following visualizations, each vowel realization is reflected in two categories. The first reflected the openness of the vowel (open / close), the second referred to the tongue position (front / back). Notice that for this plot, the standard deviations are expected to be quite a lot higher, simply because unique footprints were estimated over each of the ten sentences. Accordingly, the results may not vary too much between individuals of the same cluster, but rather between the different sentences. It immediately becomes clear that the strong differences observed during speech exercises are much harder to find in the footprints of regular sentences. However, there are still a few notable patterns which will become particularly interesting when compared to the other non-exercise tasks. For all vowel categories, except the open vowels, a slight declining trend could be observed. This is particularly important for the front vowels, because the absolute number of front vowel realizations increased from HC to mildly and again from mildly to severely affected patients. The footprints encode the number of realizations combined with the underlying prediction confidence.

Figure 4.11: Phonetic footprints for a longer text read by HC as well as two PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA intelligibility score.

Accordingly, the declining trend manifested despite an overall increasing number of front vowels. It was also possible to observe as slight decline in the group of plosive phones, but this observation turned out to be very patient-specific. When observed in the context of isolated sentences, plosives seemed not to reveal too much information about the disease state. One potential explanation could be the short nature of single sentences, which does not require an individual to pronounce a series of many plosives without catching a break, like it was the case in the speech exercises. A group that was clearly more affected were the fricative sounds. Among all consonants, they expressed the clearest decline from the group of HC to the poorly intelligible PD patients. Once again, this is a notable finding because the absolute number of fricatives, without incorporation of the associated confidence, was almost identical for all three groups. This indicates that the model became increasingly uncertain about the predicted phones of that category. A quick glance at Table 2.1 could also provide an explanation for this behavior: The inventory of fricatives of the Wav2Vec model is the largest of all consonants (and the table does not include co-articulations either), hence a slightly imprecise articulation could already cause the recognizer to have a hard time making a confident decision among the available alternatives. Lastly, the reducing trend in silent segments should be mentioned. Unlike for the speech exercises, the silent regions recognized at the beginning and end of most utterances were not considered for the phonetic footprints anymore. Accordingly, the silent segments which contributed appeared somewhere in the middle of the sentence. One could have the expectation that PD speakers would be more prone to insert pauses in the middle of a sentence, but the results contradicted this assumption.

One could argue that a single sentence is rather short, and the probability of pausing somewhere in between the sentence may not be increased for PD patients for that reason. This assumption is proven to be invalid by the results for the longer text-reading exercise shown in Figure 4.11. On a quick side-note, notice that the footprints had been estimated over the full text, and the only variability between results is introduced by different speakers again, unlike in the previous exercise of

Figure 4.12: Phonetic footprints for the monologue of HC as well as two PD groups, which were clustered with respect to their m-FDA intelligibility score.

isolated sentences. Because findings are quite stable for participants of a particular cluster, the standard deviations are now very small. Against the formulated assumption that the short nature of isolated sentences was the reason for a lower pause ratio of increasingly unintelligible speech samples, the trend manifested in the text reading exercise once again. While the footprints also account for prediction confidence, the raw number of pauses showed the same characteristic of fewer silent segments for PD patients. For no kind of read speech, the PD group showed any signs of increased pause ratio. Overall, the pause ratio clearly increased for all participants in the case of longer text reading, which seems reasonable as the readers had to insert breathing breaks more frequently during the extended exercise duration. Other findings from the isolated sentences were preserved as well, such as the reduced footprint of closed, front and back vowels. Simultaneously, the open vowels remained almost constant again. When looking at the raw occurrences of open and front vowels, both turned out to be produced more frequently with decreasing intelligibility rating. This observation puts even more importance on the decline of front vowels when the recognition confidences were incorporated like in the visualized footprints. Unlike in the previous exercise, there was once again a clear trend visible for plosive phones, which also showed the same pattern when ignoring the prediction confidence and only looking at raw numbers of occurrence. Other patterns, like the decrease in fricatives and approximants, remained visible as well.

In the last exercise, every contributor had to describe their every-day routine in a brief monologue. The results shown in Figure 4.12 revealed that during free speech, suddenly all vowel categories had been affected as the perceived intelligibility of an individual decreased. The same was the case for fricatives and approximants, an observation that was made during the different reading exercises as well. On the side of the plosives, only the poorly intelligible participants showed a decline. The footprints of the better intelligible PD patients and the HC subjects were almost identical. Throughout all exercises, it was possible to observe that for certain categories in which the more severely affected PD patients showed a clear trend of decline,

the best PD group achieved similar results compared to the healthy subjects. There are two important considerations to make when comparing these two groups. First, the mildly affected PD patients did, as their scores already implied, not show major signs of speech impairments. They were mostly intelligible speakers who expressed minor signs of deviations from perfect pronunciation. This leads straight to the second explanation, the cohort of healthy speakers. As it was already highlighted in Figure 4.3b, deviations from the ideal reference speech production were not only expressed by PD patients, but also by a number of healthy contributors. Accordingly, it should not be surprising that the HC group did not always separate clearly from mildly affected PD patients. At the same time, it was not an option to also cluster HC according to their m-FDA label, as the goal of the phonetic footprints was to demonstrate how the speech of PD at different stages would vary from speakers who did not suffer from PD. The last pattern which had not yet been addressed, but might be one of the most important findings after all exercise setups, is the increasing amount of silence (pause segments) of the strongly affected PD cohort. In all of the previous reading exercises, even in the case of reading a longer text, the opposite could be observed. However, when the contributors were asked to describe their every-day routine, this reading reference was suddenly gone. The task became much more challenging, because not only did the participants have to speak for an extended period of time, but they also had to think about what to say and how to structure their spoken language appropriately, leaving less time to focus entirely on pronunciation, rhythm, breathing and a stable volume. The PD patients who had already developed more severe speech problems inserted more pauses than the other speakers, a pattern that was only observable during the free-speech task.

The findings from the phonetic footprints suggest that patterns are likely not only observable w.r.t. the available phonetic inventory, but also in terms of general recognition confidence, as proposed in [Klum 22b]. The confidence had already been included in the computation of phonetic footprints, but the experiments so far, as much as they provided an insight into how PD affected phonetic properties, did not investigate the relationship between intelligibility and emitted recognition confidence of the model.

4.4.2 Confidence Analysis

The first evaluation of confidence scores was done by a simple correlation analysis. For the different speech tasks, Spearman’s correlation was estimated over the samples from all participants, using the total m-FDA score as reference. To make the results more interpretable, a few adjustments were required to make recordings comparable. For example, we only used the subset of 48 PD and 48 HC speakers which had been recorded inside a soundproof booth. Otherwise, there might be a systematic bias in prediction confidence due to differences in acoustic conditions between speakers recorded in the soundproof booth and those recorded with a headset. Furthermore, this reduction ensured that an m-FDA annotation was available for all HC speakers as well. This was important because for the correlation analysis, prediction confidences should be compared for all speakers, not only for those who suffered from PD. The correlation was determined between the scores and the mean prediction confi-

Task	All	Consonants	Vowels
DDK	-0.30	-0.31	-0.26
Sentences	-0.51	-0.48	-0.44
Read Text	-0.63	-0.60	-0.63
Monologue	-0.59	-0.62	-0.53

Table 4.2: Spearman’s correlations between total m-FDA scores and mean prediction confidence. Scores were determined w.r.t. all phones, all consonants and all vowels, respectively.

dence of all consonants, all vowels, or every phone of a particular utterance. The results are shown in Table 4.2. When compared to the correlations for the same task presented in [Klum22b], it turns out that the new results clearly showed a lower correlation with the total m-FDA scores. For comparison, the observed values from -0.30 (DDK) to -0.63 (read text) were lower compared to the ones presented in the previous study, -0.53 to -0.65 , respectively. The overall trend of increasing negative correlations (a higher m-FDA should result in a lower confidence) from DDK over sentences, read texts to monologues was not fully preserved either. Notice that the correlation observed with the dedicated speech exercise (DDK) was the lowest out of all. This may seem counterintuitive, because the exercise was designed to reveal articulatory weaknesses, but the explanation is straightforward: The utilized phone recognizer was optimized with many hours of continuous speech. During training, it had never seen a speech signal which only contained the rapid repetition of a single syllable. Accordingly, the prediction confidence was quite low in comparison to the other tasks, which can also be seen in the following analysis of confidence over time. With the new recognizer, the overall correlation between total m-FDA score and mean confidence values estimated over read texts was slightly stronger than that observed for the monologues when all phones were considered. Surprisingly, during the monologues, the confidence scores of consonants correlated much better with the annotated scores than those of the vowels. In general, the observed confidence scores were significantly higher than those from the old recognizer used in the previous study. The new model was built to operate a lot more robustly compared to the old recurrent one. It has seen many hours of noisy speech data and all kinds of recording conditions. It was also trained with far more individual speakers, making its overall predictions a lot more confident as it will be shown in several of the following experiments. Instead of just correlating the mean prediction confidences of individual samples with their m-FDA annotation, it is also possible to evaluate the recognition posteriors on a temporal level. This was not done in the previous study, but it might reveal insights into how the prediction confidence changes over time.

To do so, patients were grouped into three categories, once again by their total m-FDA annotation. All HC were considered as one group, in addition there were the cohorts of mildly ($m\text{-FDA} < 20$), moderately ($m\text{-FDA} < 35$) and severely ($m\text{-FDA} \geq 35$) affected PD patients. This made it possible to utilize the entire dataset again, including HC contributors without m-FDA annotation as well as PD patients who were recorded without a soundproof booth. Phone recognition confidences were grouped together with respect to the underlying index of occurrence of the corre-

Figure 4.13: Mean prediction confidence values over time estimated over both shorter exercise tasks for healthy speakers as well as three cohorts of PD patients. The x-axis represents the phone index.

sponding phone. The underlying motivation was to estimate the mean confidence of the first emitted phone, the second, the third, and so on, for the four different groups. Instead of using a real time axis, which would be heavily influenced by various speech rates, the raw positions of recognized phones were used. The resulting curves were smoothed using a simple moving average filter kernel with 5 elements for the short tasks (DDK, sentences), 11 for the read text and 21 for the monologue task. For the short tasks, the first $N = 5 \cdot x$ phones had been considered, in the case of longer read text and monologue tasks, the first $N = 25 \cdot x$, and choosing x such that at least 75% of speakers had still produced the phone at position N . The idea behind those intervals was to provide a rough estimate of how many phones should be considered for confidence analysis with samples from different speech exercises, without relying too much on specific properties of the PC-GITA corpus (e.g. 75% of speakers produced at least 113 phones in the read text task). Using a smoothed curve had several important advantages. Firstly, the predicted phone sequences are never perfectly aligned to each other. There could be insertions or deletions in the recognition result, but it is also possible that speakers inserted additional phones for example due to repetition of a word, misarticulation or other. Using wider kernel windows for longer speech recordings helped to account for systematic drifts which increased with time.

The result for both short tasks is depicted in Figure 4.13. A clear separation of the moderate and severe PD groups is apparent in both plots. At the same time, the curves of the mildly affected PD patients and the HC group overlap really well. Whilst this may sound contradicting at first, the explanation lies once again in the distribution of m-FDA scores within the healthy cohort (Figure 4.3b). Most of the speakers in that group have a very low total m-FDA score, but there are also a few outliers which even have m-FDA scores above 20, worse than any of the mildly affected PD patients.

For the DDK task in Figure 4.13a, all four curves showed a slight descending characteristic over time. This may be due to the increased likelihood of pronunciation errors the further an individual makes it into the exercise. The negative slope of a linear regression line fitted to each of the four curves is very similar for the HC and

Figure 4.14: Mean prediction confidence values over time estimated over both longer exercise tasks for healthy speakers as well as three cohorts of PD patients. The x-axis represents the phone index.

mildly affected (≈ -0.001), but it becomes steeper for the moderate (-0.0016) and severe (-0.0024) groups, indicating that they become less intelligible more quickly. Such a pattern could not be observed for the isolated sentences, but here, just like for the footprints already, the results tended to be rather noisy because of the very different structure of individual sentences. The overall outcome of the HC and mildly affected producing very similar results, and the moderate and severe group being slightly and more clearly worse, respectively, was preserved.

Many more insights provided the results from the longer speech tasks illustrated in Figure 4.14. The general pattern of the moderate and severe PD groups separating from the other two cohorts was mostly preserved. However, in the read text exercise shown in Figure 4.14a, the mild and moderate PD group both slightly outperformed the healthy speakers in the early part of the text. Roughly at the same point in time, or in this case, the same phone index, all groups suddenly expressed a clear decline from the initially high average confidences. This drop, however, was not equally strong for all groups. Somewhere around phone index 30, the mean confidence of the so far best group of mildly affected PD came down to that of the healthy speakers. The PD cohort with moderate impairment, which maintained an equal recognition confidence with the HC group until around phone index 20, suddenly developed a gap of approximately 4%, which would then persist until the end of the graph. The severely affected patients were never comparable to any of the other groups, but they also expressed an even more pronounced decline, and afterwards, continued to show decreasing confidence scores. This was also reflected in a regression line fitted to their curve, which showed a negative slope of -0.0007 . The slopes of the moderate (-0.0003) and mild (-0.0001) cohorts were more flat, with the one from the HC group being almost perfectly level. To understand what exactly had happened after the first approximately 30 phones, it is helpful to have a closer look at the read text exercise. Every participant had to read a short text which encompasses a dialogue between a patient and a doctor. Table 4.3 lists the different dialogue turns and also highlights the exact location where the recognition confidence suddenly started to drop for a various number of consecutive phones. It is exactly at this part of the dialogue where the patient salutes the doctor. Upon listening to many of the recorded

Speaker	Spanish	English
P	Ayer fui al médico.	Yesterday I went to the doctor.
D	<i>Qué le pasa?</i> Me preguntó.	<i>What happened to you?</i> He asked me.
P	Yo le dije: Ay doctor! <i>Donde pongo el dedo me duele.</i>	I told him: Ah doctor! <i>Where I put my finger it hurts me.</i>
D	<i>Tiene la uña rota?</i>	<i>Do you have a broken fingernail?</i>
P	<i>Sí.</i>	<i>Yes.</i>
D	<i>Pues ya sabemos qué es. Deje su cheque a la salida.</i>	<i>Then we now know what is happening. Leave your check at the exit.</i>

Table 4.3: Transcript of the dialog between doctor (D) and patient (P) which had to be read by every participant for the read text exercise. Marked in bold are the words for which the phone recognition model produced a clear drop in recognition confidences.

audio samples, it became evident that almost all speakers clearly emphasized this part, as if they were replaying the act of saluting their dialogue partner. Among all PD groups, as well as for the healthy speakers, this pronounced emphasis caused the recognizer to become more uncertain w.r.t. the predicted phonetic symbols. This uncertainty was observed to be much stronger in the case of PD patients. For the HC, the drop between plateaus equaled to around 3%, for the mildly affected it was already at around 5%. The drops were found to be even larger for the moderately (7%) and severely (9%) impaired PD patients. The sudden increased emphasis made the section more difficult for the recognizer to correctly understand every phone, but this uncertainty appears to be much larger in speech samples from individuals suffering from PD. As it was already described in the introduction to PD, the condition causes speech difficulties such as an improper intonation and reduced loudness. Both intonation and loudness play a key role in emphasizing certain segments of an utterance, and if individuals had difficulties achieving proper emphasis, it could likely also influence their intelligibility at this particular point of their speech. An important thing that should not go unmentioned here is the exact position of the drop itself, which happened usually short before the 40th phone. The reason why the drop already became visible earlier was the previously mentioned moving average filter with a kernel size of 11 elements. This also means that the raw numbers of the drop were even more pronounced. By using the filter kernel, however, the general pattern was much easier to visualize.

Lastly, the monologues revealed another interesting pattern which separated the four groups. In the case of free, self-paced speech, all curves shown in Figure 4.14b showed almost no declining trend over time on a global scale. There were some drops in the average prediction confidences of every group, but their strength was very different, and, more importantly, they occurred at different points in time. If we consider the

group of healthy speakers first, their only noticeable drop happened shortly after the 200th phone. For the group of mildly affected PD patients, a similar reduction was observed after phone index 75, significantly earlier. PD patients with a moderate total m-FDA score were able to maintain a stable prediction confidence level until almost the 50th phone before starting to gradually decrease. In the case of the most severely affected patients, it took on average only 20 phones into the monologue until the mean prediction probability started to decrease. This is approximately 10 times quicker compared to the healthy speakers. It should be noted that all groups were able to return to (almost) their initial mean confidence level. Further analysis would be required, for example looking at the confidence scores and their correlation to speech rate, to better understand why all participants developed some form of confidence decrease, but would mostly return to a stable level after all. A possible explanation could be that they decreased their initial speech rate during the monologue, thus being more intelligible and making it easier to articulate correctly.

4.4.3 Vowel Analysis

Along with every predicted phone symbol, the model also emitted two types of feature vectors. The first came from the convolutional feature extraction part of the Wav2Vec architecture, the second was the output from the last Transformer block. It was shown in a previous study [Diec22] that both variants can encode rich, but very different types of information. Whilst the former conveys much more detail about particular structures in the observed signal (such as information about the underlying gender), the latter mostly encoded higher-level information including the phonetic environment, which would allow to cluster a particular vowel into different context languages for example.

Both types of feature vectors could transport information about the disease state of PD patients. As the condition progresses, individuals are known to develop a monotonous speech. Their voice also tends to sound breathy due to an increasing laryngeal tension [De S03]. These symptoms are not only audible, but they should be detectable with a sophisticated feature extractor. As explained in the section on phonetics earlier, vowels can be arranged in the so-called vowel-trapezoid (as illustrated earlier in Figure 2.20). Each vowel can be described in terms of its openness (free space between tongue and palate), as well as its position (tongue position from back to front). The elevation and position of the tongue directly influence the frequencies of the first and second formant, respectively. Consequently, if there is a frequency-relationship between the arrangement of vowels in the trapezoid, this information could help describe how the voicing of individuals might change during PD. Before any experiment can be conducted, the vowel trapezoid requires a minor simplification. As all contributors of the PC-GITA corpus are native Colombian Spanish speakers, the experiments will rely on the Spanish phonology that employs only five different vowels ([a], [e], [i], [o], [u]) which span a vowel pentagon. The three vowels [a], [i] and [u] of said pentagon are cardinal vowels, because they represent extreme positions in terms of openness and position of constriction in the vocal tract. For all vowel analysis experiments, only the feature vectors from the monologue task were

Figure 4.15: Visualization of the vowel space spanned up by healthy speakers as well as two cohorts of PD patients. The areas spanned by the enclosing polygons were given in the top left corner of the plots for the CNN and Transformer feature results.

considered. They would provide the most natural vowel production observable in the context of free speech production.

First, the feature vectors of all five Spanish vowels were collected for the group of healthy participants as well as two clusters of PD patients. The patients had once been grouped according to their total m-FDA score, which should provide a general intuition about the degree of speech impairment. Furthermore, they had been clustered w.r.t. their m-FDA monotonicity score. As the score ranged from 0 to 4, two groups of mildly (monotonicity < 3) and severely (monotonicity \geq 3) affected individuals were created (such that speakers would be distributed as evenly as possible). In the case of total m-FDA, the first cohort comprised those with a score below 25, all other patients were assigned to the second cohort. After collecting all feature vectors from the monologue recordings for the five vowels, the minimum number of vectors among cardinal vowels [a], [i] and [u] was determined for the HC. This was to ensure that in the next step, an equal number of features from each of the three cardinal vowels of the pentagon would be utilized. After randomly selecting the minimum number of samples for each cardinal vowel from the HC group, a principal component analysis (PCA) with two components was estimated from the CNN (512-dimensional) as well as the Transformer (1024-dimensional) features. Afterwards, all feature vectors were projected to the 2-dimensional space using the estimated decomposition. The mean vectors of all five vowels were visualized, along with the area spanned by the enclosing polygon.

The results for the total m-FDA score are shown in Figure 4.15. The difference between the three speaker groups became particularly visible when using the CNN feature vectors. The area spanned by the vowel polygon of the HC contributors measured 211.0 units (PCA decomposition is dimensionless). The mildly affected PD group only covered 79% of the healthy reference with 166.2 units. Even smaller was the area (126.0) of the PD patients with a total m-FDA score of at least 25, with only 60% remaining from the area of healthy speakers. A similar, but less pronounced

Figure 4.16: Visualization of the vowel space spanned up by healthy speakers as well as two cohorts of PD patients. The areas spanned by the enclosing polygons were given in the top left corner of the plots for the CNN and Transformer feature results.

trend could be observed for the feature vectors of the last Transformer layer. When looking at the individual vowels in the CNN plot, it could be observed that all mean vectors seemed to shift towards the center of the polygons. It is also worth mentioning that there was a clear pattern in how the three polygons spanned up. They all seemed to share a perfect base with the connection of the most back and front closed vowels [u] and [i], with the only difference being the length of that base itself. Given the properties of vowel articulation, the polygons indicate a decreasing degree of openness as PD progresses, as well as a tendency to a centralization of the tongue position. The closeness of a vowel appears to remain unaffected. Such trends are not visible in the PCA decomposition of Transformer features, but they likely encoded too much other linguistic information. The CNN features on the other hand, as it was expected already, seemed to convey plenty of signal-level information, for example about the first- and second-order formants.

The general degree of speech impairment described by the total m-FDA score was closely linked to the available vowel space of individuals who suffered from PD. Ideally, the same pattern should be observable when patients are grouped according to their m-FDA monotonicity score as well. However, keep in mind that the range of this score is very small, and only if the feature vectors encode sufficient amounts of information about an individual's vowel production, it might be possible to still see the patterns observed with the total score.

Figure 4.16 shows the decomposition results with speaker clusters arranged according to only their m-FDA monotonicity annotation. Once again, the CNN features provided a much better insight how the different cohorts had been affected w.r.t. their vowel articulation. This time, not all vowels expressed a clear tendency to shift towards the center with increasing PD severity. Both [u] as well as [o] transitioned to a more closed nature, while the other three showed a profound shift from front towards a more back tongue position. The reduction of the convex area compared to the HC group was slightly larger with the monotonicity score as reference. Keep in mind

that the values for the CNN and Transformer results of healthy speakers are identical for both scores, because their group was unaffected by the changed clustering of PD patients. The area of the mildly affected PD polygon equaled to 72% , that of the patients with high monotonicity scores reduced to only 55% of the original vowel space spanned by the healthy speakers.

Even with the m-FDA monotonicity scores, which categorized the impairment on a rather coarse scale of five values, the differences in vowel articulation became very visible in the CNN feature vectors. At the same time, there are some important limitations which must be considered when using them, for example to compute the area of a vowel polygon. By no means it is possible to just compute the areas of many patients, and afterwards correlate them with the m-FDA score (monotonicity). The result will look surprisingly bad, with a Spearman correlation of around 0.25. The CNN feature vectors, as discussed earlier, encode plenty of signal-level information. Accordingly, they also include much information about other factors, an important one in this context being the gender. It turns out that given a PCA estimated over all healthy female and male speakers, the correlations computed only with the transformed samples of either female or male PD patients are much better with values of 0.58 and 0.64, respectively. The cause for this observation is likely rooted in the different fundamental frequencies of female and male speakers. It also manifests in the CNN feature vectors, and will greatly influence a projection into the 2-dimensional space. In simple words, the lower-dimensional feature vectors will attribute a good amount of their descriptive power to difference in fundamental frequency instead of knowledge about the first and second formant. Removing such underlying distribution can help the resulting PCA to encode more information about the signal of interest.

4.4.4 At-home Analysis

A core contribution of this work is to promote the availability of pathological speech analysis by significantly increasing the robustness and generalization of the underlying models. To achieve this, none of the presented architectures was ever shown data from PD patients at training time. In the previous experiments, it could be shown that a phone recognition model that had only seen healthy speech during optimization was still able to convey plenty of information about how PD affected an individual's speech at different disease stages. At the same time, the progression of PD is very unique in every patient, and whilst some might develop speech problems very early, others may be able to maintain a high articulatory quality until later stages of the disease. Instead of directly comparing one patient with another, it might be much more interesting to compare the performance of a particular patient at different points in time. The at-home subset (AHS) of PC-GITA comprised samples from seven individuals who had been recorded in their homes. Correctly predicting the disease state is particularly challenging in the case of AHS for multiple reasons. First, the patients were recorded at different times of a day, sometimes right after medication intake, sometimes with several hours between medication intake and actual exercise. Consequently, the performance of an individual might vary significantly even within a single day. The second challenging factor were the various time intervals

between exercises. As already mentioned, patients had to perform the same exercise four times during one day. Between different days however, there was usually a time span of several weeks. This unequal temporal spacing could make the analysis even more challenging. Arias-Vergara et al. studied the application of speaker-adapted Gaussian Mixture Model Universal Background Models (GMM-UBM) to estimate the progression of PD-related speech symptoms in the AHS corpus [Aria18b]. The goal of this thesis is to build a similar estimator, once again using only HC speech as reference. Additionally, the estimator should predict an interpretable feature, and not only a plain score.

The first important task was to identify a suitable metric that could be worth to be compared to the annotated m-FDA score. Despite the fact that they showed a clear declining trend along with different stages of PD in previous experiments, confidence scores were quickly rejected. The major reason is that they tend to require a rather large sample size to be used for a single individual, simply because they strongly depend on the uttered phones and recording conditions. If there was suddenly some minor background noise, this would already cause the confidence to be reduced, even if the patient's performance remained unchanged. For the same two reasons, the phonetic footprints had been excluded as well. Under controlled conditions, they could provide decent insights, even on a per-patient basis. However, they once again relied on stable acoustic conditions if they were used in combination with the confidence score, as described in Equation 4.2. The alternative of using raw phone occurrences as in Equation 4.1 usually requires a larger sample size to be sufficiently representative.

The last remaining option was the area spanned by vowel realizations of individuals. On the one hand, the previous results implied that the CNN feature vectors were very potent of encoding formant-related information. Nevertheless, these results had been obtained for recordings that had been captured from inside a soundproof booth. If the PCA decomposition could successfully encode information about formant frequencies, the approach might be transferable to the AHS data. Furthermore, the PCA embeddings of a particular vowel can show clear variations between different speakers, but for the same speaker, the variability is rather small. This indicates that the required amount of audio to achieve stable results could be smaller compared to that of the phonetic footprints for example.

Besides choosing a metric of interest, it was important to identify a meaningful task that the metric could be computed over. The DDK exercises were immediately ruled out, simply because they did not make use of the full vowel inventory in the first place, making a reliable vowel area analysis impossible. The read sentence were not part of the AHS protocol. The read text was included in the protocol, but the recordings were much shorter compared to that from the monologue task, which was ultimately chosen for the at-home analysis. The previous experiments on vowel space were also conducted on recordings from monologues, which further supported the choice of task. Across all experiments, there was a single recording missing, precisely the second measurement of the first session of patient *017PD*. Accordingly, for this participant, there were 15 instead of 16 available measurements.

To compute any vowel areas, the first thing required was a meaningful PCA decomposition. With the requirement that none of the algorithms presented throughout

Patient	Spearman ρ	Pearson r
001PD	-0.45	-0.57
008PD	-0.30	-0.27
009PD	-0.15	-0.07
011PD	-0.61	-0.71
017PD	-0.72	-0.73
048PD	-0.73	-0.81
049PD	-0.62	-0.61

Table 4.4: Spearman and Pearson correlations between estimated vowel area and total m-FDA scores of patients from the at-home sessions.

this work should have ever seen PD samples, the PCA was estimated only over the recordings of HC, in the same way as it had been done in the previous experiment. This would already introduce certain limitations, because most HC speakers had been recorded inside a soundproof booth, which was not the case for the AHS sessions, but it remained to be the best available estimate of a decomposition to be used with the new data.

The phone recognition results and corresponding feature vectors had then been computed for the AHS data. Just like before, the feature vectors of a single monologue exercise were decomposed to the 2-dimensional space, then grouped by the respective vowels, and the vectors of all vowels were then averaged to compute the spanned area. It turned out that for the AHS recordings, the results were slightly more stable when using only the area computed from the vertices of the three corner vowels [a], [i] and [u], likely because they had also been used for PCA computation with the samples of the HC group. The vowel areas and the total m-FDA scores were collected for all exercise sessions, and then scaled via z-score normalization to resemble a standard normal distribution to make the following visualizations more interpretable. Spearman’s and Pearson’s correlations were computed between the computed vowel areas and annotated m-FDA scores for each of the seven contributors. To evaluate the statistical significance of the results, the null-hypothesis was considered to be rejected for p-values below 5%. The unweighted average correlation among all seven patients was -0.51 . A decrease in vowel area should reflect an increase in m-FDA score. For patients *009PD* and *008PD*, the correlations were found to be the weakest of all participants, with values of -0.15 and -0.3 , respectively. Upon further investigation, it turned out that those were the patients with the lowest standard deviation in their m-FDA monotonicity scores. This was an indicator that their voice did not show major changes over the course of the different sessions. Table 4.4 summarizes the correlations observed for each of the participants. Whilst the inverse relationship between vowel area and total m-FDA score was observable for all speakers, it manifested quite differently among the seven contributors. With p-values > 0.05 , the null-hypothesis could not be rejected for patients *009PD* and *008PD*. For all others, the results were found to be statistically significant.

On average, Pearson correlation was -0.54 . While Spearman’s correlation only reflects monotonic (rank) relationships between two variables, Pearson’s correlation considers their direct linear relationship and thus provides a better insight how

Figure 4.17: Predicted vowel area (inverted) and corresponding total m-FDA scores of the four patients with highest correlation results.

changes of different magnitude had been preserved across variables. The highest correlations were observed for *048PD*, with values of $\rho = -0.73$ and $r = -0.81$. Keep in mind that neither the phone recognizer nor the PCA decomposition had ever seen vowel articulations from PD patients during parameter estimation, and the presented findings could simply be derived from a sufficient baseline of healthy contributors.

The estimated vowel areas and corresponding total m-FDA values of the four speakers with highest correlation are shown in Figure 4.17. After z-score normalization, the vowel area values had been inverted for the sake of visualization to account for the inverse relationship between area and m-FDA score. Clearly the noisiest estimate out of all four presented examples was that of patient *049PD*. However, out of the fifteen transitions from one session to the following, the direction of change was misinterpreted only three times, from session 11 until 14. In two out of the three transitions, the score remained constant (from 11 to 12 and from 13 to 14), which is hard for a continuous variable like the vowel area to properly reflect. Sample *011PD* had an almost equal Spearman correlation compared to *049PD*, but the correlation after Pearson was clearly higher. This was reflected in multiple of the steep transitions shown in Figure 4.17a, like that from session 1 to 2 or from 8 to 9, which had been conserved really well in the vowel area. Even slightly higher correlations could be observed for *017PD*. The very profound decline of the patient's speech between session 4 and 5, which manifested in an absolute increase of the total m-FDA score by 6 units, was also well-preserved in the vowel area. It also recovered the drops

during sessions 9 and after session 11, but like the other results before, whenever the score remained more stable, that pattern could not always be found in the progression of the vowel area. Clearly the best result could be obtained for patient *048PD*. The curve of the estimated inverted vowel area seemed to follow the trend of the m-FDA score throughout the entire investigation. In rather flat areas, the score maintained a more stable level, whereas after session 11 (m-FDA: 30), when the score suddenly increased noticeably until session 14 (m-FDA: 38), the steep transition was fully reflected in the vowel area as well.

The vowel area did not yield very strong correlations with the total m-FDA scores of all of the seven participants of the at-home subset of PC-GITA. Whilst the inverse relationship between spanned vowel area and annotated score could successfully be observed for all speakers and despite the promising average correlation results, the scores of two patients could not be estimated reliably. As already mentioned earlier, these two patients showed the smallest standard deviation of their m-FDA monotonicity rating, which was an indicator that they did not exhibit any major changes w.r.t. their monotonicity. This, combined with the finding that the predicted vowel area produced noisy estimates in rather flat score regions, likely highlights a limitation of the approach. At the same time, for the other five participants, the vowel area corresponded well with the expert annotation, and the measure was able to decently reflect profound changes in m-FDA score.

4.5 Discussion

The first experiment on phonetic footprints made use of the sequences of predicted phone classes as well as their associated probabilities. Various pronunciation difficulties could be discovered as the neurodegenerative disease progressed, affecting the production of both vowels and plosives within the framework of dedicated speech exercises. The phonetic footprints were then extended to all other speech tasks, revealing that PD-related patterns were not limited to vowels and plosives, but also affected the recognition results of fricatives.

The analysis of emitted phone prediction confidences showed that the mean posterior probability of a sufficiently large sample size was inversely correlated to the progression of PD. This observation became particularly evident in the longer read text and monologue exercises. Results from those two tasks might show a better correlation for two reasons: On the one hand, a larger sample size in the form of more recognized phones from a longer speech sample could result in a much more stable mean value for each individual. Additionally, an effect of articulatory fatigue might be observable only after a certain amount of continuous speech. This assumption could be supported by the findings of the confidence analysis over time. During the dedicated speech exercises in which participants had to repeat several consonant-vowel combinations multiple times, it could be observed that the mean prediction confidence experienced a slight linear decrease for all groups right from the start. This was most likely the case due to the exercise design itself, which was aimed to be sufficiently challenging in terms of required articulatory precision. Consequently, the exercise was not only challenging for PD patients, but also the control speakers. The average values of prediction confidence were also clearly lower compared to all other exercises,

and this pattern was observed for all cohorts. Accordingly, the dedicated speech exercise clearly put the articulation skills of each individual to the test.

The confidence analysis of read text exercises revealed another very interesting pattern, which was, once again, not only observed for PD speakers, but also for those of the HC group. A clear change in intonation which was required to emphasize a particular passage of the given text would have a major impact on recognition confidences. Such a trend would be impossible to observe without applying the confidence analysis over time. Using the indices of emitted phones for the time axis yielded interpretable results. Accordingly, the index of a particular phone class spoken by a contributor did not vary by much among different samples. This should be expected for a read text exercise, but it requires a robust recognizer which produces very few insertions or deletions such that the final results remained comparable over time. Analysis of mean prediction confidences over time for the monologue task revealed that the duration for which individuals were able to maintain a stable confidence level reduced markedly as PD progressed. Whilst the healthy control speakers produced the first approximately 200 phones without much variation in terms of prediction probability, the time until the averaged curve showed a first clear drop became much shorter as the disease progressed.

The availability of descriptive feature vectors is a key requirement for a successful ML model. Feature vectors must encode as much information about a particular problem as possible. At the same time, they need to be robust and provide good generalization. A feature extraction can be considered robust if the presence of different types and amplitudes of destructive noise leave the resulting feature vector mostly unchanged. The feature extraction does have decent generalization if different types of distractive noise, such as the presence of multiple different PD datasets recorded in various environments from many more speakers with different native languages, have little effects on the resulting feature vectors. Both robustness and generalization affect the feature extraction, but also the decision making logic of any ML model. The two sets of feature vectors that were extracted with the Wav2Vec phone recognition model encoded information very differently. For the vowel analysis in the domain of PD, the CNN features which encode much more signal-level information turned out to yield better results compared to those from the Transformer blocks. Whilst the general trends remained visible, and the structure of cardinal vowels could be preserved, it became apparent that much of the signal information had been superimposed with other information about the phonetic neighborhood of a particular phone. This is expected, and in general should not be considered a *bad* behavior, but it is crucial to keep these insights in mind to properly select the right set of features for a particular task. Using the CNN features associated with individual phone recognition results, it was possible to compute a PCA to create an unsupervised dimensionality reduction down to the 2-dimensional space. The decomposition had been estimated only from recorded monologues of healthy contributors to ensure that no part of the system had ever seen PD. The spanned vowel polygons estimated over all PCA decomposition results from three different groups visualized how the available formant space reduced as the neurodegenerative disease progressed further. Despite the fact that the PCA had only been estimated over the three cardinal vowels [a], [i] and [u], the remaining two vowels of the Spanish inventory correctly arranged in the spanned pentagon, as

they were expected compared to reference textbook examples. Accordingly, the estimated PCA did not encode specific characteristics of the three covered vowels only. It showed that the directions of greatest variance, which the PCA estimates, encoded information that was generally valid for vowels, even if they had not been part of the data utilized for estimating the decomposition. This, in combination with the fact that [e] and [o] correctly arranged in the vowel pentagon, lead to the conclusion that the two major influencing factors encoded in the CNN feature vectors were closely related to tongue elevation and position, or first and second formant frequencies, respectively. With this information at hand, it was possible to further interpret the reduction of vowel area in PD patients. The vowel openness, which was encoded on the vertical axis, with the most open position in the bottom part of the visualizations (see Figure 4.15a for reference), showed that it became increasingly difficult for patients to fully open their vocal tract to produce vowel [a]. On the other side, if the tongue was fully elevated and in the close position, the vowel production was absolutely unaffected. This unilateral impairment was not found for the tongue position. Instead, the disease affected both the most front and back configurations. The effect was found to be more pronounced for the front vowels [i] and [e] compared to their back counterparts [u] and [o]. The results were found to be consistent even when using only the annotation for monotonicity, which did not have as much resolution as the total m-FDA score.

It is important to understand that the presented vowel diagram would reach a limitation as soon as the disease had progressed to a stage where a patient was unable to produce one of the presented vowels any more. The presented approach only considered realizations of the five vowels of Spanish phonology, but the recognition model does have a much larger vowel inventory. Consequently, it would be able to assign a *much closer than normal* realization of [a] to an alternative such as [æ] or [ɐ]. The vowel would then be ignored for the estimation of the vowel pentagon, even though it indicated a clear decline in an individual's vowel space. At the same time, such transitions could be better covered by phonetic footprints for example, which, if calibrated for the particular patient, could certainly highlight changes in the utilized vowel inventory over a longer time period.

With the AHS subset of PC-GITA, it was possible to analyze the progression of PD over such a time period. Due to the precise annotation of every contributed speech sample, one could not only understand changes which happened over the course of several weeks, but even those present within a single day. This was very insightful because among different medication states, the articulatory capabilities of an individual might show profound variations. Also, the presented method is quite straightforward and produces interpretable results which can easily be used by clinical experts. As discussed earlier, the manifestation of PD in a patient's speech signal is very unique, and it is impossible to characterize such patterns w.r.t. a global reference. Instead, it could be much more helpful to use a patient's performance at one time as a reference to analyze how the disease progressed until a new measurement was performed. Not only could such an approach result in more stable results for a particular patient. It would also be possible to account for unique strengths or weaknesses. If a patient used to smoke for their entire life, this has a significant impact on their voice quality, but these patterns are not related to the progression of PD. A comparison to other

subjects who suffer from PD but have never smoked would likely produce biased results, with little to no descriptive capability about the actual disease state. With the AHS dataset, it was possible to evaluate how well a recognizer would be able to track the development of speech symptoms over the course of numerous recording sessions. This analysis could be performed individually for every patient, without comparing to any reference speakers other than themselves. Using the vowel area as proposed in the preceding experiment for the evaluation of patients over time had several important advantages. Instead of computing any kind of pooled feature vector over an entire utterance, or manually choosing an analysis window, the recognizer itself, only by applying the logic for phone recognition, selected relevant segments, including an annotation (the respective phone class). All that was left to do was to extract the feature vectors associated with the relevant phones. Furthermore, as the feature vectors were predominantly influenced by the first and second formant, they might be able to robustly encode information about the available articulatory space even under varying and potentially challenging acoustic conditions, which the recognizer had experienced during training anyway. The most important advantage, however, could be the interpretability of the system. With an unweighted mean Spearman correlation of -0.51 , it was clearly possible to identify the inverse relationship between the total m-FDA score and the spanned vowel area. An even slightly higher mean Pearson correlation showed that the relationship was not only conveyed in a rank-conserving fashion. Several steep transitions of m-FDA scores had been resembled in an equally pronounced change in the spanned vowel area. It turned out that for those patients that showed only little variation in terms of monotonicity score, the system performed weaker. For other individuals, the method was able to clearly estimate the m-FDA score over the course of sixteen sessions. This was particularly impressive because every four recordings were captured within a single day, the next four recordings were captured all within a new day, with a few months in between. Despite this very volatile setup, the vowel area estimated for five out of the seven participants of the AHS subset provided a decent insight into their individual disease progression. An important factor that could also contribute to the weaker results for two of the PD patients might be a greater variability in recording conditions. This might have also had an effect on the final results. Just like in other formant tracking algorithms, it could potentially happen to recognize a harmonic of the a formant frequency, which could quickly offset the recognition results.

An important advantage of using the vowel area for tracking the disease progression is the straightforward interpretability of the utilized feature. Without any in-depth understanding of ML techniques of the phone recognition model itself, a speech therapist or medical expert would be able to understand the decision-making process of the entire system. Instead of just outputting a new disease score, the feature vectors are projected to the 2-dimensional space in which the vowel area can be easily computed. The changes in vowel area over time already provide a good insight to any treating physician, and it helps them to understand why the system assessed the patient as stable or increasingly impaired. For the individual themselves, the vowel area holds another crucial advantage, which is easily overlooked. The patients could be able to see how their voice changed over time. They might also be able to see how their vowel area increases after taking their medication. What better motiva-

tion could a PD patient experience other than seeing a large colorful pentagon which overlaps a slightly smaller pentagon that had been estimated two weeks before when they started exercising.

Throughout the analysis of PD speech signals, the proposed model had allowed us to compute phonetic footprints, perform feature extraction for vowel analysis, and even estimate the speech quality of a small group of patients who had been recorded at their homes over the course of several sessions. In the next chapter, the same phone recognition model was used on speech signals from subjects who did not suffer from a particular form of speech impairment. Instead, they had reported an infection with some form of disease that would affect the respiratory system. The main objective of the following chapter was to identify whether there exist clear patterns in the speech signals of Covid-19 patients, which are unique for said disease at the same time. Only if such patterns can be found, it could be possible to reliably classify Covid-19 among other respiratory diseases.

Chapter 5

Covid-19

5.1 Introduction

In late 2019, the first cases of a new respiratory disease were reported from the province of Hubei, China [Fauc20]. They were caused by the novel SARS-CoV-2 (*Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2* virus, which transmitted the Coronavirus Disease 2019, commonly known as Covid-19 [Gorb20]. Many studies [Ye20, Sali21, Haid20] supported a zoonotic origin of the disease, assuming an initial transmission from an infected bat over to a human being. As the virus name already implies, it was not the first outbreak. The first variant of the virus was discovered in 2003, which caused the *Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome* (SARS). Besides the two SARS variants, a third zoonotic coronavirus disease outbreak occurred in 2012: Dromedary camels were identified as the intermediate host of the *Middle East Respiratory Syndrome* (MERS), which was the most lethal of the three variants with a mortality rate of approximately 35% [Bada16]. Unlike for SARS and MERS, attempts to contain the spread of Covid-19 failed, and on 11 March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) characterized the outbreak as a pandemic.

As a respiratory disease, Covid-19 primarily affects the lungs and the respiratory tract, causing symptoms such as fever ($\approx 81\%$ of cases), cough ($\approx 59\%$ of cases) and fatigue ($\approx 39\%$ of cases) [Alim20]. Other recognized symptoms were headaches, dyspnea (shortness of breath), diarrhea, a sore throat or a smell dysfunction [Alim20, Moei20]. The combination of symptoms had many similarities with a regular cold or influenza. Therefore, it was important to recognize infected individuals as early as possible in order to isolate them from others to prevent further spreading. This was particularly important during the earlier stages of the pandemic, when vaccines were not yet available and the treatment was restricted to several anti-viral drugs [Stas20], besides other therapeutic options to mitigate the developed symptoms. Two major test types had been established to identify Covid-19 patients. The first was the reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) test [Liu21]. Viral ribonucleic acid (RNA) of a specimen from the upper respiratory tract is reverse-transcribed to deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and then amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) [Weis20]. Because RT-PCR tests are considered a gold standard for the diagnosis of Covid-19 [Liu21], samples are commonly taken by trained experts to mitigate the chance of inappropriate execution which could lead to wrong

Figure 5.1: Thin-layer (left) and high-resolution (right) CT imaging of Covid-19 patient with pneumonia. Red circles mark several (but not all) patchy infiltrations of both lungs.

results [Vand 21]. The full test cycle from specimen collection until the final result would take at least several hours [Weis 20]. The second test option are rapid antigen tests (RAT), which enabled individuals to perform the entire cycle at home, without requiring any laboratory equipment. An RAT kit contains everything required for the collection of a sample from the respiratory tract or nasal cavity, the test cassette itself, and also some type of bag for the safe disposal of all exposed utensils. Despite their significantly higher error rate compared to RT-PCR tests, they have several other advantages. Firstly, a result is available within minutes, and no experienced personnel is required [Weis 20]. Without the need for any laboratory analysis, the associated costs are also considerably lower [Vand 21]. For that reason, RATs were identified as a helpful tool to regularly test individuals, and in case of a positive outcome, validate the result by means of a PCR test [Liu 21].

The similarity of Covid-19 symptoms with those of other, less harmful diseases, was not the only reason for the desperate need for tools to accurately classify the disease. Another was the number of asymptomatic courses, in which patients developed no typical Covid-19 symptoms. The relative frequency of such asymptomatic cases varied significantly between studies, indicating that on average, almost one out of every four patients (24.2%) [Kron 20] would not develop symptoms. The true number of asymptomatic patients is very difficult to estimate, because individuals who do not suffer from any symptom are less likely to conduct a test. Another study which investigated the ratio of asymptomatic cases during the Covid-19 outbreak on the cruise ship *Diamond Princess* revealed that out of the 634 individuals who tested positive (PCR), 328 (51.7%) did not show typical symptoms [Gao 21]. Patients who did not develop any of the typical Covid-19 symptoms were still found to be capable to further transmit the disease [Yu 20], posing the risk of increasing the spread even further.

Whilst some individuals would not show any symptoms after having a confirmed in-

fection with SARS-CoV-2, others might develop severe health problems leading to hospitalization and often requiring respiratory support in the form of supplementary oxygen or extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) [Bert 22], an invasive technique to oxygenate and remove carbon dioxide from the blood of a patient outside of their body [Brod 11]. Low blood oxygen levels are caused by a viral pneumonia, an inflammatory infection of the lungs [Gere 13], induced by SARS-CoV-2. An X-ray or CT scan of the lungs reveals patchy light consolidations in areas affected by pneumonia, as shown in Figure 5.1. Presented CT imaging was acquired in another study [Jin 20] from an early-stage Covid-19 patient suffering from typical symptoms such as fever, dry cough and shortness of breath.

The primary way of transmission behind Covid-19 is through airborne viral particles [Sali 21, Lotf 20]. The typical cough symptom naturally increases the chance of airborne transmission, but due to an increased awareness of patients who developed symptoms and hence took behavioral countermeasures such as self-isolation, the overall rate of spreading the disease would not increase significantly for symptomatic individuals [Ferr 20]. The visibility of an infection itself played a major role in how contagious a patient would be: Studies showed that the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 would start days before the first symptoms, but did not increase after symptom onset, likely due to the previously mentioned behavioral reactions [Ferr 20, Tind 20]. The time window in which a patient could already spread the virus, without knowing that they were infectious, greatly contributed to the growing incidence of Covid-19 [Hind 20]. One way to prevent further transmission were social distancing strategies, such as maintaining a safe distance (for example 1.5 m) from others in public, or simply reducing the number of contacts one would meet at work or at home [Thun 20]. Another important tool were face masks, which would cover both mouth and nose to reduce the viral load which could be ejected into the air through breathing or coughing [Chua 20]. Several studies supported the effectiveness of face masks to contain the spread of SARS-CoV-2 [Howa 21, Chua 20, Catc 21]. At the same time, face masks could give individuals a false sense of security, resulting in less social distancing [Cart 20].

The most effective countermeasure to overcome the Covid-19 pandemic were vaccines. Multiple different vaccine types had been developed and studied in clinical trials [Le 20]. The most frequently administered variant are messenger-RNA (mRNA) vaccines. Small lipid structures, usually referred to as *vehicles*, are injected into muscle tissue [Anan 21]. The lipid vehicles are able to enter certain parts of human immune cells, where the mRNA is then transcribed. It encodes information about the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2, which the virus uses to attach to human cells for replication [Zhan 20]. The immune cells display the same spike protein on their surface after successful transcription of the mRNA. The human immune system recognizes the foreign protein structure and starts to develop anti-bodies which are effective against Covid-19 [Fang 22].

The deployed vaccines were successful at mitigating the spread of Covid-19, but due to the virus' high mutation rate, new strains emerged which had a higher chance of escaping the effects of vaccination [Vasi 21]. The quick and reliable detection of infected individuals and their isolation from the healthy public remained an important aspect to keep case numbers low. Ideally, a test for Covid-19 was not only accurate in its

recognition results, but it should also be cheap, fast, highly available in terms of supply, and not require the presence of medical experts. This demand fueled research in all kinds of disciplines to identify potential bio-markers relevant for Covid-19. In the domain of speech processing, numerous datasets were made available for researchers to develop algorithms capable of recognizing an infection with SARS-CoV-2 from speech, breathing or cough signals [Shar 20, Xia 21, Orla 21, Pizz 21, Tria 22]. Many ML models had been proposed which supposedly solved the task of classifying this new type of respiratory disease, and several notable mentions will be introduced in the following literature review. In most cases, however, strong classification metrics had to speak for themselves, without answering – let alone asking – important critical questions. Many symptoms, especially those which could be related to speech production, such as dry cough, a sore throat or shortness of breath, are characteristic, but not unique for Covid-19. How good is a Covid-19 classifier if it achieved a precision score of 90% (the relative amount of true positive samples out of all positive predictions)? If it had to classify between healthy and diseased patients, then what would happen if the classifier was shown a sample from a negative patient who suffered from a cold? There are many other medical conditions which have symptomatic commonalities with Covid-19, making it difficult even for medical experts to assess an individual’s condition correctly without relying on established diagnostic methods. Besides the two main chapters on neurological conditions which affect a patient’s speech (Parkinson’s disease) or language (aphasia), this smaller chapter was dedicated to investigate how Covid-19 could affect speech signals. Without attempting to classify the condition, the main goal was to highlight influences of a respiratory disease on the realization of individual phones. Furthermore, it aimed to clarify if any of such patterns was unique for Covid-19, or if similar manifestations could be observed for other conditions as well. Lastly, the presented experiments should further support the idea of modelling speech phonetically, without relying on task-specific data, by analyzing English audio samples of speakers with a different mother tongue which the presented phone recognition model had never seen during fine-tuning.

5.2 Literature Review

Table 5.1 summarizes scientific contributions which cover the topic of Covid-19 classification from acoustic signals. Two main types of recordings had been used extensively, either cough recordings, or regular speech. One thing that quickly becomes clear from the table is the very high variance in terms of reported classification results, ranging from accuracy values between 54.0% for speech, which is only slightly higher than chance level, up to 97.1%. This already indicated that researchers have not yet reached any consensus on whether Covid-19 can truly be classified from audio signals alone.

The first contribution worth mentioning from Schuller et al. introduced a small snapshot of the *Covid-19 Sounds* [Xia 21] dataset in the context of a challenge. The baseline approach defined in the paper used a linear SVM classifier in combination with multiple different sophisticated feature sets to achieve recall scores of 73.9% on cough signals and 72.1% on regular speech. The Covid-19 Sounds data was crowd-sourced through a smartphone application. The Coswara dataset [Shar 20] was used

Title	Authors (year)	Model	Features	Results
The INTERSPEECH 2021 Computational Paralinguistics Challenge: COVID-19 Cough, COVID-19 Speech, Escalation & Primates [Schu 21]	B. W. Schuller et al. (2021)	SVM	openSMILE ¹ openXBOW ¹ auDEEP ¹	Recall cough: 73.9 speech: 72.1
Pay attention to the speech: COVID-19 diagnosis using machine learning and crowdsourced respiratory and speech recordings [Aly 22]	M. Aly et al. (2022)	MLP	MFCCs spectral	Accuracy (%) cough: 75.0 speech: 54.0
A study of using cough sounds and deep neural networks for the early detection of Covid-19 [Isla 22]	R. Islam et al. (2022)	MLP	temporal spectral	Accuracy (%) cough: 93.8
Exploring the Use of Artificial Intelligence Techniques to Detect the Presence of Coronavirus Covid-19 Through Speech and Voice Analysis [Verd 21]	L. Verde et al. (2021)	SVM	MFCCs spectral	Accuracy (%) speech: 97.1 F1-score speech: 82.4
Detection of COVID-19 from speech signal using bio-inspired based cepstral features [Dash 21]	T. K. Dash et al. (2021)	SVM	optimized cepstral features	Accuracy (%) cough: 74.1 speech: 71.4
COVID-19 patient detection from telephone quality speech data [Ritw 20]	K. V. S. Ritwik et al. (2020)	SVM	super vectors ²	Accuracy (%) speech: 88.6 F1-score speech: 92.7
COVID-19 cough classification using machine learning and global smartphone recordings [Paha 21]	M. Pahar et al. (2021)	MLP (ResNet)	MFCCs	Accuracy (%) cough: 95.3
End-to-end convolutional neural network enables COVID-19 detection from breath and cough audio: a pilot study [Copp 21]	H. Coppock et al. (2021)	MLP (ResNet)	spectrogram	Recall cough: 77.0
Exploring Automatic Diagnosis of COVID-19 from Crowdsourced Respiratory Sound Data [Brow 20a]	C. Brown et al. (2020)	SVM	transfer-learning bottleneck	Cough Recall: 72.0 Precision: 80.0

¹ openSMILE [Eybe 10]; openXBOW [Schm 17] auDEEP [Frei 18]

² Super vectors for speaker recognition [Kinn 10]

Table 5.1: A list of contributions in the domain of Covid-19 classification. Presented studies either used SVM or any multi-layer-perceptron (MLP). Utilized input signals either contained coughs, speech, or both.

in the second study from Aly et al., which mostly contains breathing, cough and English speech recordings from native Hindi speakers. The authors used an MLP with MFCCs and spectral features to classify the disease state from cough and speech recordings. Whilst they claimed that their methods could achieve an AUC (area under the receiver-operator characteristic curve) of 96.4% given a fusion of all three Coswara signal types, the results reported for individual tasks were much lower. Using only cough recordings, they reported an accuracy of 75%, and for those containing regular speech, the MLP did not perform much better than a random decision (54.0%). It appears reasonable that a cough signal might contain helpful information about the disease state, but the study did not explain how a fusion of all signals could yield such large improvements over the stand-alone results.

Islam et al. also used an MLP in combination with temporal and spectral features. They reported an accuracy of 93.8% on cough recordings. Whilst this number may sound impressive at first, it must be taken cautiously. They trained and tested their MLP using the Virufy [Chau 20] dataset, which, in their utilized version, contained a total of sixteen individuals who each contributed a single audio recording, totalling only 121 cough events. Even if the entire methodology was correct, there remain significant doubts whether an MLP with more than 10 000 parameters (according to their reported network configuration) could learn any meaningful and robust Covid-19 patterns from this very small sample size. Nevertheless, the authors concluded that “*the proposed algorithm can have a possibility to differentiate pathological cough sounds into distinct pulmonary/respiratory diseases, including COVID-19, asthma, bronchiectasis, etc.*” [Isla 22]. However, it remained unclear how their system could possibly be able to realize such differentiation.

Just like Aly, Verde et al. used MFCCs and spectral features to classify the disease state based on speech samples from the Coswara dataset. However, they chose an SVM over the parameter-intensive MLP, achieving an accuracy of 97.1%. The reported F1-score of 82.4 indicated that the accuracy result was heavily biased by class imbalances. While their system was able to detect slightly over 93.3% of all Covid-19 samples, it also misclassified many healthy subjects as diseased, such that the precision would only reach 73.7%. Besides the SVM, they also reported results for a Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) classifier. SGD is an optimization method, and it remained unclear what type of classifier the study was referring to.

Dash et al. proposed a set of optimized cepstral features which were specifically designed for the task of Covid-19 classification. They solved this task by learning appropriate filter bank windows for cepstrum computation which would take into account the respective input signal properties. The reasoning was straightforward: The fixed filter banks used for regular ASR were designed for speech signals, and are likely less informative for cough signals. Once again, results were reported on the Coswara dataset. An SVM trained with their proposed cepstral features achieved accuracy values of 74.1% for cough and 71.4% for speech recordings.

The study of Ritwik et al. used super vectors, which had originally been designed for speaker recognition. They reported a high classification accuracy of 88.6% along with an even higher F1-score (92.7%). However, once again these strong numbers were reported on the basis of a very small sample size. The entire dataset comprised only 19 speakers, 7 of them were held out for evaluation. Besides the reported numbers,

a key strength of their contribution was the performed phonetic analysis. Instead of only solving a binary classification problem, they also analyzed which category of phonemes would convey helpful information about the disease state. They concluded that nasals, stops and mid vowels were most informative for Covid-19 identification. Pahar et al. proposed the usage of large convolutional MLP models such as ResNet-50 [He 16]. They reported an accuracy of 95.3 % on the cough samples of the Coswara dataset. Despite using a CNN architecture, they chose MFCCs as input for the model, which could be considered a questionable decision. Any kind of spectrogram representation would have likely been more appropriate for such a model. The high reported accuracy for an MLP with over 23 million parameters using only MFCC features was certainly a surprise, but it would drop significantly to 74.6 % when testing on a secondary dataset. A ResNet architecture was also used by Coppock et al., who used the more reasonable spectrogram input. Although the title of their work suggests that the presented model was an end-to-end solution, the described architecture never used a raw waveform input, hence there was no true end-to-end system available. The reported unweighted average recall of 77 % had been observed for a classification between Covid-19 positive individuals and healthy subjects. The recall decreased to 53.5 % when the system had to differentiate between Covid-19 positive patients and healthy subjects who had a cough. While this number was very close to chance level and indicated that the proposed model was likely unable to classify Covid-19 reliably in the presence of other, symptomatically similar conditions, it clearly shed light on how much more difficult the differentiation of different respiratory conditions could be, compared to the simple problem of healthy and diseased individuals.

The last work from Table 5.1 from Brown et al. utilized bottleneck features which had been acquired by means of transfer-learning using a convolutional architecture. They used the Covid-19 Sounds dataset and an SVM classifier. A recall of 72.0 % was reported for the classification between positive patients and negative individuals who were suffering from a cough. The precision of the same experiment was 80.0 %, which indicated that the system had learned meaningful decision rules. At the same time, the reported standard deviations were quite high, with values of 16.0 % and 23.0 % for recall and precision, respectively. Another interesting result was that for the classification between positive and completely healthy individuals. Given the decent performance on the previous task, one might expect the numbers to increase, as the problem was likely easier now. In fact, the exact opposite was the case: Both recall (72.0 % and precision (69.0 %) declined in the new setup.

All of the presented works had the goal to detect an infection with SARS-CoV-2 from recordings of coughs or fluent speech signals. Whilst some of the results seemed promising, indicating that their could be bio-markers which enabled for a differentiation between Covid-19 and other respiratory pathologies, other works appeared to report overly confident results. A review of several contributions investigating the reliability of RAT tests came to the result that on average, the recall of said tests was 68.4 %. While the specificity was quite high with 99.4 %, the tests frequently failed to detect the presence of an infection. Against these numbers, accuracy, recall or F1-scores beyond 90 % for Covid-19 classification from audio signals appear to be highly optimistic results, at best.

Field	Information
Covid status	Whether someone had tested positive, was healthy, had recovered from Covid-19 or was suffering from any other respiratory disease
Country	Home country of the donor
Symptoms	Information about cough, fever, sore throat, fatigue, loss of smell, diarrhoea, pneumonia, breathing difficulties, muscle pain
Smoker	Whether somebody was a smoker at the time of recording
Covid-19 test result	Either positive, negative, or no test taken
Covid-19 test type	RAT or PCR
Vaccination	Fully, partially or not vaccinated
Other medical conditions	Asthma, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, chronic lung disease, hypertension

Table 5.2: Available annotation for a contributor in the Coswara dataset.

5.3 The Coswara Dataset

In early 2020, shortly after the pandemic had started, researchers from the *Indian Institute of Science* created a website to collect audio recordings from volunteers online, with the goal to create a dataset comprising healthy speakers as well as individuals who reported a positive test result. Today, everyone can access their website¹, record their own breathing, cough and speech signals, and get a posterior probability that they are currently suffering from an infection with Covid-19.

The first release of the dataset was presented at *Interspeech 2020* [Shar 20], and Coswara has since grown to be one of the most important audio corpora in the domain of Covid-19 research. Whilst information about the recording procedure and technical details presented in the original article [Shar 20] remained valid, a more recent version of the dataset, which is maintained via *github*², was used throughout this work. More precisely, the dataset was accessed on 25 March, 2023, considering all contributions until 24 February, 2022, inclusively. Each data donor had provided nine recordings: Two breathing signals (shallow and deep), two cough signals (shallow and deep), two speech signals of counting from 1 to 20 in English, as well as three sustained vowels ([e], [i] and [u]). In their paper, they referred to other symbols, but these did not fully comply with the IPA. Unfortunately, they used inappropriate example words for the requested sounds. For example, they would ask a contributor to produce a sustained phonation of vowel “a” as in the English word “made” (referring to the first of the three mentioned vowels). Not only was this a diphthong, making the clear identification of the requested sound more challenging, but the pronunciation of said vowel could also vary between [e] and [ɛ]. This variability could sometimes be observed in the audio recordings from different speakers.

Along with their speech samples, every individual had also provided background in-

¹<https://coswara.iisc.ac.in/> (as of 30 March, 2023)

²<https://github.com/iiscleap/Coswara-Data> (as of 30 March, 2023)

Figure 5.2: Distribution of self-reported health status (left) and test results (right) in terms of age groups.

formation about their general health status. This information would be crucial to analyze the effects of various other disease, which would have similar symptoms as Covid-19, and understand if it was still possible to tell the numerous conditions apart. Table 5.2 summarizes the most important fields of the provided annotation. Besides general information about age, gender (both not listed in the table) and home country, individuals provided self-reported feedback about their respective symptoms in case they did not feel healthy, whether they were currently smoking, had taken a Covid-19 test, were vaccinated or suffered from any other medical conditions. The field about Covid-19 status encoded information about whether someone was entirely healthy, had tested positive and was experiencing mild or moderate symptoms, had an asymptomatic infection with Covid-19, was waiting for their test result, or suffered from any other respiratory condition.

Most of the contributors came from India (2515), the second most frequent nationality were the United States (87). Accordingly, the vast majority of participants were non-native English speakers. Of the entire 2746 speakers, 844 were female, 1900 identified as male, and the remaining 2 chose not to specify. Figure 5.2a illustrates the distribution of individuals who reported to be completely healthy and those who suffered either from Covid-19 or any other medical condition at the time of recording. It clearly shows that with increasing age, a larger relative amount of the population was not healthy anymore, which is to be expected. On the other side, the illustration in Figure 5.2b displayed only those individuals who had taken a test and could report themselves as either positive or negative. Whilst the first plot showed that many of the young individuals were completely healthy, the second visualization highlighted that this trend would not translate to Covid-19 test results. Instead, the observed distributions were flatter. Only in the age group between 18 and 22 years, the ratio of negative test results was quite high, but this could easily be statistical noise. Between the ages of 30 to 50, positive and negative test results kept the balance. Older contributors were more likely to report a positive test result. This apparent relationship between an individual’s age and their health status and test result introduced an clear limitation to any ML model estimated over the Coswara corpus. Researchers would have to make sure that their algorithms would not exploit age

characteristics to draw conclusions about a potential Covid-19 infection. After what can be seen from the Figures 5.2, a classification model could easily recognize the age of a speaker, and then learn the respective prior probability of an infection for that age group. Such bias was not only observable in terms of age. Out of the 1900 male contributors, 393 reported a positive test result. This equaled a ratio of 20.7%. For the female donors, 280 out of the 844 speakers tested positive, a ratio of 33.2%. The gender of a person does not increase or decrease the chance of infection with SARS-CoV-2, there simply exists no such medical evidence. And still, the relative frequency of positive test results in the Coswara dataset was 60% higher for female speakers. Just like for the age, a classifier could easily learn that positive test results are more common in female speakers. Hence, recognizing the fundamental frequency to estimate a speaker's gender could already provide helpful information, although this would not translate to any applicable knowledge about how Covid-19 manifested in the speech signal.

Audio files were recorded in WAVE format at 48 kHz, single-channel configuration and 16 bits per sample. Each audio was evaluated by a human listener in terms of audio quality, categorizing into clean, noisy and bad samples. Throughout this work, all recordings which had been annotated as bad quality were discarded from the experiments.

5.4 Experiments

Although the phone recognition model had never seen Hindi as a native language during pre-training or fine-tuning, it had seen many other languages, and thus should be sufficiently robust against non-native pronunciation. Furthermore, all speech tasks were conducted in English, which the model had seen extensively, including non-native speakers. The experiments were following two major objectives: Most importantly, the goal was to identify Covid-19 related patterns compared to healthy reference speech, and then evaluate if any such pattern would be unique for Covid-19, or could be found in patients who suffered from any other condition as well. Secondly, the dataset itself should be evaluated in terms of quality. This would not only refer to audio quality (which was annotated as well), but also the general structure of the dataset. For example: *Does the provided data align well with the description in the paper?* The experiments section will be divided into several sub-sections, all of which consider a different set of exercises.

5.4.1 Sustained Vowels

In this exercise, contributors had to perform a sustained vowel phonation of three different types according to the original paper [Shar 20]:

- /ey/ as in *made*
- /i/ as in *beet*
- /u:/ as in *cool*

Figure 5.3: Five most frequently produced vowels for each of the three sustained vowel tasks.

In a first analysis, to validate which phones had actually been produced by individuals, the raw occurrences of phones in the respective audio files were determined. Instead of just summing all phone productions from all audio files of a particular task, the sequence of recognized phones had to be trimmed. The first symbol was removed, as it was almost always the initial silence of the recording. Then the next three phones had been considered for the histograms. The remaining phones (if there were more) had to be omitted. The reason was that in many cases, even in files that had been annotated as being of good audio quality, a noise reduction started to eliminate most of the sustained vowel, because the ongoing monotonous sound had falsely been identified as background noise. The resulting filter effect would either mute the recording, or cause the audio to sound somewhat distorted. The three plots from Figure 5.3 illustrate the raw occurrences of phones for the three different exercises. For the first task, it could already be seen that some individuals did not only produce the vowel [e], but also [i] or its elongated variant. Sometimes, they also produced an [a] instead of [e], most likely due to the imprecise task definition (/ey/ as in *made*). A somewhat similar pattern could be observed for the second task. Most contributors were able to produce either the short [i] or the elongated [i:]. Notice that the vowels had always been sustained, but the recognizer had never seen vowel realizations which would last over the duration of seconds. Consequently, it was not sure if the observed pattern belonged to a long or short vowel, because it was much longer than both versions. Figure 5.3b also showed a profound number of [e] realizations. The likely explanation could be found on the recording website, where the instructions differed from the ones presented in the paper. Instead of asking for /i/ as in *beet* like in the publication, the website asked for /e/ as in *beet*³. Once again, the task definition was not perfectly clear and this resulted in multiple different vowels to be produced by the participants.

In the first two exercises, the majority of produced phones still reflected the (supposedly) desired target phone. In the last exercise, where contributors had been asked to produce /u:/ as in *cool*, neither [u] nor [u:] could be found among the five most frequent vowels. Instead, the distribution was surprisingly even between multiple other phones. A manual evaluation of audio files revealed that in many cases, users would produce an [o] or [a], like the phone recognition result implied. There were

³Retrieved on 31 March, 2023

Figure 5.4: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors for the most frequently produced vowel of each of the three sustained vowel tasks. Blue markers represent healthy speakers, red those who tested positive for Covid-19.

less samples available in which contributors had actually produced [u]. The investigation also showed that the phone recognizer sometimes recognized a different vowel, even if the participant had produced [u] successfully. In a subsequent evaluation of recognition results for vowel [u] in fluent speech, the recognizer had no problems to reliably detect said vowel. The measured recall of the class was on the same level as that of other vowels. However, within the framework of sustained phonation (which the model had never seen during training), it would sometimes miss a correctly sustained [u] in the Coswara dataset. This could be caused by an uncertainty of how to correctly process very long vowel productions, but might also be the result of some audio processing, such as the previously mentioned noise reduction. Particularly in the case of sustained [u] vowels, the signals were frequently dampened after one or two seconds of continuous phonation. Once more, the description of the task provided in the paper deviated from that given on the recording platform, which asked for /o/ (not [u:]) as in “cool”.

The estimation of produced phonetic units in the three vowel exercises was helpful to select appropriate phones for the subsequent analysis of feature vectors. Throughout all vowel experiments, two sets of feature vectors had been analyzed. The first comprised those from entirely healthy individuals, who did not suffer from Covid-19 or any other respiratory condition. The second set contained all those vectors from participants who had tested positive for an infection with SARS-CoV-2, and showed either mild or moderate symptoms, or were completely asymptomatic. For each of the three exercises, all feature vectors of one particular vowel had been collected. For the first task (/ey/), the phone was [e], for the second (/i/) it was [i], and for the last task (/u:/) it was [o]. Particularly for the last task, for which the distribution of produced vowels was quite uniform across the first symbols, it could be tempting to consider more than just one symbol for the analysis. However, to investigate the high-dimensional feature vectors, they had been transformed to a lower dimension by means of t-SNE. T-SNE aims to greatly reduce the dimensionality of data, while preserving as much of the neighborhood relationship between data points as possible. If one would consider the feature vectors from more than one phone, the final embedding would mostly encode information about the various phonetic classes, instead of anything else. Therefore, it was important to only consider a single symbol throughout the analysis.

Figure 5.5: T-SNE embeddings of CNN feature vectors of vowel [e] from the first sustained vowel task. Left: Colored in terms of disease state. Right: Colored in terms of gender.

Figure 5.4 shows the three resulting embeddings for feature vectors from the Transformer encoder. The small number of samples for vowel [o] resulted in a plot with considerably fewer samples compared to the other two tasks. None of the three visualizations showed any clear trend which would manifest in speakers who suffered from Covid-19. This would by no means rule out the presence of any such patterns, but they were not pronounced enough to cause a clear separation between healthy and infected speakers. Only for vowel [e], there was a subtle trend visible in the embeddings: The left side of the plot was predominantly filled with healthy speakers, whilst many of the Covid-19 positive samples could be found on the right side. The difference of 7.7 between the mean values of healthy and infected speakers in the first embedding dimension was the only significant (t -test: $p \ll 0.01$) manifestation of Covid-19 which could be identified in the sustained vowel tasks. To find out if this pattern was unique for an infection with SARS-CoV-2, the same feature vectors were also collected for speakers who reported that they were suffering from a cold and who also declared to have tested negative. While the sample size of that group was quite small with only 33 feature vectors (many more reported to have a cold, but only few tested negative), it was still possible to perform a t -test between the t -SNE results of this group and the ones who tested positive. Without visualizing the data once again (the additional 33 data points would not reveal much new information), the statistical test revealed that the mean values of the two cohorts were quite close together, with a difference in terms of the first embedding component of 0.3. The individuals who declared to suffer from a cold had moved into the direction of the speakers who tested positive, and the difference between the two cohorts was not found to be significant anymore.

In the chapter on PD, the feature vectors from the initial convolutional layers turned out to encode much more signal-related information compared to those from the Transformer encoder, which already contained a lot of temporal context information as well. For the analysis of sustained vowels, the encoder vectors were still found to be more helpful, mainly for two reasons: First, the vowel had been sustained over a

longer period of time, which could not be captured by a single CNN feature vector, which only had a receptive field of 25 ms [Baev 20]. Additionally, when using feature vectors which encoded a lot of signal-level information, said information would also greatly affect the t-SNE result. The effect was visualized in Figure 5.5, which shows the t-SNE embedding of CNN feature vectors for productions of phone [e] in the first sustained vowel task. Both illustrations 5.5a and 5.5b show the same embedding result, but the data points had been colored w.r.t. different properties. In the left plot, the blue markers refer to healthy participants, whereas the red markers represent those who tested positive for Covid-19. In the right plot, red and blue markers represented female and male speakers, respectively. It can clearly be seen that the t-SNE embedding preserved signal-related information, in this case the fundamental frequency, which is closely related to the gender of an individual. Again, this would not rule out that CNN feature vectors could potentially encode information related to an infection with Covid-19. However, it just showed that other information could have a much greater influence on the distribution of observations in the high-dimensional space.

5.4.2 Counting Task

The counting task was made up of two contributions per participant. In the first, they had to count at a normal pace, from *One* up to *Twenty*. In the second, they had to repeat the same exercise, but count fast. There was no further specification of what *fast* would mean, such that some participants would just count a bit faster compared to their normal reference, whilst others tried to count as fast as they could. For the following analyses, both tasks were considered together. Throughout all experiments, the utilized feature vectors were taken from the last Transformer encoder layer. That was because experiments had been performed on the level of individual phones, hence there should not be any secondary influencing factor like a speaker's gender (like in the example from Figure 5.5) which would heavily impact the t-SNE embedding results.

Three speaker cohorts had been considered for the phone-level analysis:

- Healthy speakers who had no medical condition whatsoever
- Covid-19 positive speakers, both symptomatic and asymptomatic
- Speakers who, at the time of recording, suffered from a cold **and** who tested negative for Covid-19

The first two groups are identical to those chosen for the sustained vowel experiments. The third was introduced to verify if any of the potential findings for Covid-19 would be exclusive for that condition, or if similar patterns could also be observed for other medical conditions with similar symptoms. The number of contributors for the last group was quite small with only 57 speakers, compared to the first (1202) and second (621) cohort. However, the described restrictions were necessary to get a decent reference of participants who developed similar symptoms, but were very likely not suffering from Covid-19. Keep in mind though that some of the individuals in said group had only taken an RAT test, which could also produce a false negative result.

The presented approach was the best possible solution to facilitate a non-healthy, non-Covid-19 reference. The number of 57 speakers of the last cohort is not to be mistaken with the reported number of 33 samples of sustained [e] vowels in the last section. The latter reflected the 33 collected feature vectors for said vowel from the total of 57 speakers in said group, hence the different numbers.

To make sure that the t-SNE embedding was not influenced by the significant imbalance of speakers per cohort, the smallest number of collected feature vectors per group was determined per phone. From the group with the smallest number of feature vectors, all observations were considered, and from the other two groups, at most two times the smallest number of observations, chosen by random sampling. Accordingly, if for some phone, there were 5000 vectors for the first, 2000 vectors for the second, and 500 vectors for the third cohort, the sampling strategy chose 1000, 1000 and 500 vectors from the first, second and third group, respectively. This also reduced the computational cost of estimating the t-SNE embedding.

The three resulting point clouds in the 2-dimensional space were once evaluated on a visual basis to identify potential cluster. Furthermore, the difference between the distributions of individual cohorts were evaluated in terms of significance. Many statistical tests which aim to model significance are based on 1-dimensional distributions. Putting it simple, given two distributions, any significance test estimates the probability that an observed difference between the two distributions occurred by chance. In order to deem an observed deviation *statistically significant*, its associated probability of occurring by chance has to be below a certain threshold. If this condition for statistical significance is met, the null hypothesis, which assumes that the difference had been introduced by noise or any other source of error, can be rejected [Moor 89]. The statistical test used throughout this section is a variant of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test [Mass 51]. While the original version of the test was 1-dimensional, Peacock proposed a 2-dimensional extension for multivariate distributions. Another major advantage of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is that it is distribution-free [Moor 89]: It does not make any assumption about the underlying distribution of samples (like assuming a normal distribution). This is crucial for some of the t-SNE results, which were not normally distributed as well. The proposed method was further extended to three dimensions, while also simplifying the required computational efforts, by Fasano and Franceschini [Fasa 87]. A *Python* implementation⁴ of this 2-dimensional test was used to analyse the observed distributions from the t-SNE embeddings. Differences were considered significant and the null hypothesis rejected if the estimated p -value was below 0.1 % ($p < 0.001$).

The first two notable phones which yielded clear differences between healthy and non-healthy speakers were [e] and [o]. Both had already been investigated in the scope of the sustained vowel task. While it was not possible to find any significant differences before, things changed in the case of continuous speech. This may sound surprising at first, but it is important to keep in mind that the recognizer had been optimized with large amounts of continuous speech during training. On the other hand, it had never seen any sustained vowel productions. Consequently, it only made sense that the extracted feature vectors for continuous speech were much more informative.

The t-SNE results for the two phones are shown in Figure 5.6. In the case of vowel [e],

⁴<https://github.com/syrte/ndtest> (as of 3 April, 2023)

Figure 5.6: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

the non-healthy groups formed a distinct cluster on the right side of the plot. Each data point corresponded to the transformed feature vector of a single realization of the respective phone. Accordingly, not all data points of infected speakers could be found in a single cluster. Sometimes, they also produced the phone in a way that sounded very much like a healthy speaker. The differences between healthy speakers compared to both Covid-19 positive as well as participants who suffered from a cold were found to be strongly significant, which, given the visualization in Figure 5.6a, should not come as a surprise. The much more important question was: Are the distributions of the two non-healthy cohorts significantly different? It turned out that using the 2-dimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the null hypothesis could clearly be rejected, indicating statistical significance. The difference in terms of mean values, as well as the estimated p -values, were summarized in Table 5.3 for all discussed phones at the end of this subsection.

Given the embedding for phone [e], one could be surprised to see that the differences between the distributions of red and lime-green markers were identified to be significant. After all, the two point clouds shared a major overlap. This is a perfect example to introduce the second important factor, the effect size. While the statistical test revealed if the difference between two distributions occurred by chance, it would not say anything about the actual difference itself. This being said, the deviation between the two distributions could be quite small. Given a sufficient number of samples for each distribution, the small difference could still be found to be statistically significant. This was exactly the case for phone [e]. The difference in terms of mean vectors between the two non-healthy cohorts was rather small, compared to that between the healthy and Covid-19 positive samples. At the same time, keep in mind that the difference w.r.t. the mean value itself may not be very informative either, because the underlying distributions were not Gaussian.

The visualization of vowel [e] in Figure 5.6a provided another meaningful insight (which could be observed for other phones in the following analysis as well). Notice that the feature vectors formed various distinct clusters, which seemed no to be related to the disease state. This pattern could be observed because the utilized

Figure 5.7: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

vectors came from the last Transformer layer, and thus contained contextual information. The observable clusters often represented frequent phone combinations. In the case of vowel [e], feature vectors from the combination [en] were observed to arrange in such a cluster for example. For the t-SNE embedding of feature vectors decoding to phone [o], the observed differences between non-healthy groups were once again found to be significant. Now, the mean vectors of Covid-19 positives and those who suffered from a common cold had a larger Euclidean distance between each other than those from the Covid-19 positives and the healthy reference. In fact, in the bottom right part of the plot, there was a quite dense cluster of [o] productions from SARS-CoV-2 infected participants which had almost no occurrences of speakers with a cold. The pattern could be reproduced constantly throughout various iterations, which further supported the statistical significance of the results. More importantly, there appeared to be a pattern related specifically to Covid-19 related symptoms: Because both symptomatic as well as asymptomatic diseased participants had been included in the Covid-19 group, one could argue that the observed difference between the Covid-19 positive individuals and those who suffered from a cold was introduced by those samples which had an asymptomatic course of disease. This would shift the entire distribution for Covid-19 slightly towards that of the healthy reference, causing it to be significantly different to the one observed for the common cold. Consequently, the described experiment had been executed once more for both phones [e] and [o], this time omitting the asymptomatic Covid-19 patients. The results remained unchanged and were still found to be statistically significant.

Another very interesting group of phones which had been strongly affected by the presence of a disease were nasals. Nasals are characterized by a complete closure of the oral cavity, such that the stream of air could only escape through the nose. The t-SNE results for [m] and [n] are shown in Figure 5.7. In both cases, the point clouds of diseased speakers formed distinct clusters with relatively few samples from healthy participants. While these differences compared to the healthy reference were always significant, and also had quite pronounced effects on the distribution of samples, the deviation between Covid-19 positives and those with only a common cold

Figure 5.8: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

were never significant. At the same time, as can be seen from Table 5.3 once again, the differences between these two groups were much smaller compared to those between Covid-19 patients and healthy controls. The strong overlap between the two diseased cohorts, combined with its profound manifestation in nasal phones, should be a strong indicator of similar otorhinolaryngological symptoms in both conditions. Surprisingly, reports about the prevalence of different Covid-19 symptoms would not support this, as they found no major impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the nasal cavity, be it in the form of sneezing or a congestion [Qiu 22, Gran 20, Elib 21, Cali 20]. Despite the fact that Covid-19 patients would not report any such symptoms, the fact that SARS-CoV-2 does indeed affect the nasal cavity in some way was supported by other symptoms, such as a decreased or completely lost sense of smell and/or taste [Qiu 22, Gran 20, Cali 20].

One last group of interesting phones to be presented in the scope of the counting analysis were the approximant [l] and trill [r]. The t-SNE results for the two phones can be found in Figure 5.8. For the post-alveolar [l], the feature vectors of healthy controls were arranged in a diagonal line, from the top left to the bottom right. This line was characterized by a gap in its center, where very relatively few samples could be found. Many of the realizations from diseased participants had shifted away from said diagonal, far more to the left side, where they formed a new cluster. Once again, these deviations were quite profound, but when it comes to differences between Covid-19 and a common cold, the results were not significant anymore. A similar observation could be made for the [r]. The presence of a disease which affected the respiratory tract had a marked impact on the observed feature vectors from the last Transformer layer. This relationship was so strong in the high-dimensional space that it appeared to be one of the dominating factors during the step of dimensionality reduction. The observed effects on both the vocal tract and the production of approximants were very similar between the two diseases. As noted in Table 5.3, the difference between the mean vectors of Covid-19 patients and healthy controls was quite high, whilst that between the former and those contributors who suffered from a common cold was very small.

The six phones which had been presented on the previous pages, as well as in Table 5.3, were not the only phonetic units which showed clear effects resulting from the two diseases. Several more illustrations can be found in Appendix A.2. They also include embedding results for some rather unexpected phones such as [p] and [b]. In this context, it was not the fact that one could observe differences between healthy and pathological speech that was deemed unexpected, but the presence of said phones in the first place. When counting from one up to twenty in English, none of the words contained any voiced or unvoiced bilabial stops. However, it was possible to find many such realizations, far more than what could be expected from accidental recognition errors. Upon further investigation of the corresponding audio files, it turned out that in most of the audio files in question, the speakers had counted in their native language (which contained the respective phones), and not in English. A brief analysis of the prevalence of Covid-19 and the common cold in the groups of English and non-English counting samples revealed that there was no difference between the two groups. This was important, because otherwise, the observed results could have been induced by the underlying language, and not by the diseases themselves.

For only two of the discussed phones, the differences between Covid-19 positive individuals and others who only suffered from a cold but had tested negative were found to be statistically significant. Given the available annotation, which comprised also other symptoms beyond the common cold, it could be interesting to also test if the differences between Covid-19 and other medical conditions would remain significant. Table 5.4 summarizes the results of a further statistical analysis between patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 and those who suffered from another medical condition. Once again, it was asserted that any contributor who had been considered for the non-Covid-19 cohort had provided a negative test result. For both phones [e] and [o], it was possible to identify other medical conditions which would result in a distribution of feature vectors in the t-SNE embedding which was not significantly different from that of the Covid-19 patients anymore. In the case of [e], these two conditions were either a cough or a sore throat. In the case of the former, the p -value had increased to around 0.4, indicating that any observed difference was likely the

Phone	$\Delta\mu$ Covid-19 / HC	$\Delta\mu$ Covid-19 / Cold	p -value
e	13.3	6.4	$p \ll 0.001$
o	7.9	9.3	$p \ll 0.001$
m	14.5	1.3	$p > 0.001$
n	9.2	3.0	$p > 0.001$
l	8.9	3.9	$p > 0.001$
r	25.7	0.6	$p > 0.001$

Table 5.3: For each phone of interest, the observed Euclidean distance ($\Delta\mu$) between the mean vectors of healthy and Covid-19 positive or Covid-19 positive and individuals with a cold are given. The p -values resulted from a test for statistical significance between the observations of Covid-19 positives and individuals with a cold.

Condition	Phone [e]		Phone [o]	
	$\Delta\mu$	p -value	$\Delta\mu$	p -value
Cough (N=59)	5.7	$p > 0.001$	10.4	$p \ll 0.001$
Hypertension (N=17)	17.9	$p \ll 0.001$	3.7	$p > 0.001$
Sore throat (N=26)	1.5	$p > 0.001$	6.3	$p \ll 0.001$
Asthma (N=22)	12.1	$p \ll 0.001$	5.0	$p \ll 0.001$

Table 5.4: For the phones [e] and [o], the observed Euclidean distance ($\Delta\mu$) between the mean vectors of Covid-19 positives and individuals with a certain medical condition is given. The p -values resulted from a test for statistical significance between the observations of Covid-19 positives and individuals with that condition. For each condition, the number of available subjects who also provided a negative test is given in brackets.

result of chance. At the same time, neither a cough nor a sore throat would result in the differences for phone [o] to become statistically insignificant. This was only the case when feature vectors of said phone were compared to participants suffering from hypertension. The difference between Covid-19 positives and those who suffered from an abnormally high blood pressure was suddenly not significant anymore. It must be noted, however, that the overall sample size was rather small for most of the conditions, and the observed results could potentially change if more observations were available.

5.5 Discussion

Undoubtedly, an infection with Covid-19 can have a marked influence on the speech signal of a patient. As a potentially severe medical condition of the respiratory system, it causes multiple different symptoms, such as a dry cough, a sore throat or a shortness of breath. These symptoms are well-known to not occur exclusively in patients who tested positive for an infection with SARS-CoV-2, but also in others who suffered from a common cold for example. Many studies claimed that the identification of Covid-19 from only a few audio samples of cough, breathing and speech signals was possible. Furthermore, it had been concluded that even the differentiation between different pathologies of the respiratory system would not pose a problem for the presented ML algorithms. While this work only focused on tasks which involved the production of actual speech sounds, and did not encompass any analysis of breathing or cough events, it was possible to outline how Covid-19 affected speech production on the level of individual phones.

In the sustained vowel task, it was not possible to identify any major differences between healthy speech and Covid-19. While there was an observable trend for phone [e], it would be too optimistic to draw any conclusions from this finding. The reason was not to be found in the dataset, but more in the utilized feature extractor: The phone recognition model was highly capable of processing speech signals even from non-native English speakers under noisy conditions. However, what the model had never seen during training were sustained vowel realizations. Consequently, it would

not be possible to fully understand how a collected feature vector would summarize the very long vowel production. After all, a model trained with CTC loss emits a new class every time that it was sufficiently confident that a new observation was made. When a participant sustained a vowel for a few seconds, the model would output this one particular phone, but only once, because the observation had never changed. Whilst this might be sufficient in the case of plain phone recognition, it could be more error-prone when one tries to extract feature vectors to characterize the emitted phone. The feature vectors certainly contain plenty of helpful information. This was shown in several other tasks, and was observable in the following counting analysis as well, but for this assumption to be valid, the input signal should comprise a phonetic structure which the recognizer had seen before. If this was not the case, like for the sustained vowels, the descriptive properties of feature vectors could easily suffer. Of course this limitation applied predominantly for the Transformer vectors, which contained information about the temporal context. The CNN features are less likely to be affected by such problems, but even they could encode imperfect information if the model did not choose an appropriate time step to emit the phone of the sustained vowel.

The difference in terms of quality of extracted feature vectors became visible in the analysis of the normal speech task, when participants had to count from 1 to 20. Suddenly, one could observe clear patterns between the vowels of healthy and infected individuals. Furthermore, a statistical test showed that there were significant differences between the distributions of Covid-19 positive speakers and those who suffered from a normal cold. For the vowel [e], the effect size – the actual difference between the two groups – was not large. Given that the symptoms of both conditions have some overlap, this only seemed reasonable. In the case of the second vowel [o], the differences between the two non-healthy cohorts were a little bit more pronounced. Consequently, it was much easier for the phone recognition model to extract expressive feature vectors from continuous speech, rather than from a sustained vowel task. The strong influence in nasal phones was also quite remarkable. Even more important was the fact that the two distributions of the diseased cohorts were never significantly different. Their respective mean values were also quite close together. This implied that both conditions affected the stream of air through the nasal cavity in a similar and characteristic way. For a common cold, this could easily be explained by a congestion of the nose. In the case of Covid-19, however, medical studies found out that neither sneezing nor a congestion of the nasal cavity would occur frequently in those patients. The exact reason why nasal sounds from Covid-19 and cold patients appeared to follow a very similar distribution could not be identified from the available data and information.

Several approximant phones also showed characteristic patterns which were characteristic for an infection of the respiratory tract, but would not allow for any clear differentiation between the underlying pathologies. Whilst it might be impossible to perfectly track down the root cause of how both conditions affected this phonetic group, the following assumption could explain the observed pattern: Approximants are consonants which combine properties from fricatives and vowels [Lade 14]. Like for other fricatives, the articulation of an approximant requires the creation of some kind of constriction in the vocal tract, usually with the tongue and some other ar-

ticulator. However, fricatives form a narrow constriction which results in a turbulent airflow. This is not the case in approximants, which instead require an unobstructed stream of air, including a vibration of the vocal folds [Lade 14]. As seen before, feature vectors from vowels were significantly influenced by both pathologies. It could be this voiced component of approximants which manifested strongly in the t-SNE embeddings of corresponding feature vectors.

Lastly, the analysis of different other medical conditions in comparison with Covid-19 revealed that none of the observed differences between Covid-19 and cold patients which turned out to be significant would remain significant when compared to other pathologies related to the respiratory system. Hence, even though it was possible to identify typical patterns for an infection with SARS-CoV-2 from feature vectors, it could not be ruled entirely that these patterns would also occur in other diseases. More importantly, keep in mind that statistically significant differences were found, but their effect size was often very small. A large overlap between the two pathologies was very common. Therefore, despite finding interesting patterns after performing dimensionality reduction, which proved once more that no pathological data would be needed for training a potent feature extractor, none of these patterns could serve as a basis to support any speech-based diagnosis of Covid-19.

If it was likely not possible to reasonably classify Covid-19, what does this imply for a dataset like Coswara? The efforts of the research group could certainly not be valued enough. Yes, the corpus allowed researchers to come up with all kinds of simple or sophisticated solutions to supposedly solve the problem of identifying an infection with SARS-CoV-2, solely from a few audio recordings. However, the brief study presented in the scope of this thesis revealed that the corpus holds much more information than just the outcome of a RAT or PCR test. Only with the detailed information about other infections, chronic diseases or present symptoms related to the respiratory tract it was possible to perform the presented experiments and understand that Covid-19 would indeed manifest in the speech of individuals, but this manifestation was anything else but unique. Some of the task instructions, for example those for the sustained vowel exercises, were found to be potentially confusing for contributors. However, such problems frequently arise during data acquisition, and changing instructions later on in the collection process could introduce even more problems.

The creation, maintenance and distribution of a reasonable speech dataset for Covid-19 which included as much meta information as the Coswara corpus must be considered a valuable scientific contribution. It is the responsibility of every speech researcher to not only produce strong results, for example in terms of classification metrics, but also to question those results and critically highlight limitations of a proposed method. Ultimately, let us revisit the number of samples for each of the three discussed classes: For the counting task, there were in total 1202 healthy speakers (who did not suffer from any medical condition at all), 621 Covid-19 positive samples, and 57 participants who suffered from a common cold and had tested negative for Covid-19. If we increased the last cohort to all individuals with a cold, their number would increase to 175. A Covid-19 classifier which had only learned the difference

between healthy and diseased subjects, but would not know anything specific about Covid-19, would yield an accuracy of

$$Accuracy = \frac{1202 + 621}{1202 + 621 + 175} \approx 0.912 \quad (5.1)$$

This toy example was based on the assumption that all healthy speakers were correctly identified as healthy, all Covid-19 speakers as such, and all 175 speakers who suffered from the cold were misclassified as Covid-19 positive. Not only did this example illustrate the weakness of the accuracy as a classification metric. It also showed that a poor representation of one class could quickly be exploited by an ML model. Parkinson's Disease and Covid-19 are medical conditions which can impact an individual's speech production. In the case of the former, the resulting dysarthria could impair the articulation and phonation and even render the speech unintelligible. In the case of the respiratory disease, the intelligibility is usually not affected heavily, but the speech signal still conveys information about the presence of an infection of the respiratory system. The next chapter analyzes speech recordings from patients who suffer from aphasia, a neurological condition which primarily impairs language understanding in a way that the affected individuals struggle to semantically link words with the respective object or meaning. Phonetic analysis strategies are very helpful to evaluate speech problems. At the same time, the presented case for aphasia therapy highlights how such recognizers could also be employed successfully in the scope of a language disorder.

Chapter 6

Aphasia

6.1 Introduction

The second neurological condition after PD which was covered in detail in the scope of this thesis is aphasia. In fact, being a neurological condition might easily be the sole common property among the two. Whilst PD is known to be a progressive disorder, which often starts many years prior to the time of first diagnosis, aphasia is usually caused by some sort of sudden and serious damage to the brain. In most cases, this damage was caused by a stroke that affected a relevant brain region [Plow12]. In some cases, a traumatic brain injury [Demi06] or even another progressive neurological disease could lead to aphasia if it inflicted damage to the brain area responsible for language understanding. Among these progressive disorders are Alzheimer’s disease [Mesu08] and amyotrophic lateral sklerosis (ALS) [Baum14]. Another rare form is the so-called primary progressive aphasia (PPA) [Mesu01], a form of frontotemporal dementia [Mars18].

As a language disorder, aphasia does not affect an individual’s speech on the level of articulation, voice or prosody. Instead, the higher-order language structure is impaired, rendering patients unable to semantically link words with particular objects. Clinicians categorize into two major types of aphasia, the *fluent* and *non-fluent* variant. The underlying problem of losing the semantic connection between words and objects is the same in both types. Due to some form of damage to the brain area responsible for language understanding, a patient loses the ability to associate the correct word for a particular object [Dama92]. This loss of semantic connection is bi-directional. A person that sees an apple and is unable to come up with the word *Apple* is also likely to not be able to imagine and then draw the object given the word *Apple* in the first place. This inability to find the right word is sometimes also referred to as the *tip-of-the-tongue* phenomenon [Good76].

Coming back to the two main types of aphasia, this thesis mainly covers the non-fluent variant. It is also known as Broca’s aphasia, named after the affected brain area [Cant01]. The region is highlighted in green in Figure 6.1. An important property which cannot be illustrated on a 2-dimensional image is the unilateral character of the disease. In almost all cases, the brain damage leading to aphasia lies on the left hemisphere [Frid18]. The degree of impairment strongly depends on the particular region which had been impacted, as well as its overall size. Mild and moderate

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Figure 6.1: Affected brain regions in Broca's non-fluent (green) and Wernicke's fluent (blue) aphasia. This schematic gives an intuition about the location of the involved brain regions. Precise areas cannot be determined because the primary causes (stroke, brain skull trauma) result in very individual locations for each patient.

variants have an impact on the patient's overall ability to communicate in a fluent manner, whereas those suffering from a severe form of aphasia might be entirely unable to speak. Broca's is also referred to as non-fluent aphasia because individuals are aware of the words which they struggle to remember or the objects they cannot name. This causes their language to sound less fluent because they need to take pauses to think about the correct words.

The fluent form, which was named after the second brain region which could be affected during aphasia, Wernicke's area, also causes a loss of semantic links between words and their respective meanings [Frid 18]. The affected brain area was highlighted in blue in Figure 6.1. Patients are not aware of the words which they cannot memorize. Their language appears fluent, but due to the described symptoms, they insert other words. These *other* words are also called paraphasias, and can be categorized into three types [Bira 05]. The semantic paraphasia involves the replacement of a real word with another, likely unrelated and semantically meaningless, but real alternative. In the case of the neologistic paraphasia, the inserted substitute is not a real word anymore, but it usually still resembles the syllable structure of the original language. The last variant is that of a phonemic paraphasia. At least half of the phonemes of the correct word were produced, but parts of the word had been replaced with other phonemes, transforming the real word to a non-existent alternative. These substitutions occur mostly fluently, and patients are still able to speak entire sentences without a pause. However, with increasing severity of Wernicke's aphasia, their language becomes even more difficult to understand.

Compared to major neurological conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, PD or ALS,

knowledge and awareness about aphasia in the general public remains low [Sher 11, Elma 00]. According to the *Aphasia Fact Sheet* of the United States' National Aphasia Association (NAA), about 750 000 people each year suffer a stroke in the USA. About one third of all patients develop some form of aphasia as a result of the inflicted brain damage. Compared to the 90 000 patients who are diagnosed with PD each year in the USA according to the US Parkinson's Foundation, the numbers for aphasia are significantly larger.

As aphasia is most frequently caused by either a stroke or some sort of traumatic brain injury, this leads to several important implications. The damage to the affected brain region does not have any progressive characteristic (PPA excluded). On the one hand, this means that the effect on an individual's language is immediate, and does not develop over time. This causes the initial symptoms to be rather severe, but in the case of a stroke, an effective therapy like thrombolysis (drug-induced dissolving of a stroke-inflicting blood clot) can help the impacted brain area to recover at least partially [Furl 18]. In comparison to PD, where the loss of dopaminergic brain cells is unstoppable and consequently, the condition worsens over time, the effects of a stroke are immediate but non-progressive, leaving much more space for constructive therapy to not only maintain, but improve an individual's language abilities. At the same time, the fact that most aphasia cases are caused by a stroke means that it is not uncommon for patients to suffer not only from aphasia, but from other speech-related difficulties as well. In a large study covering more than 88 000 stroke patients, of the about 36 000 individuals who developed an aphasia, almost 25 000 patients also suffered from dysarthria [Mitc 21]. The presence of multiple communication disorders, on the level of both speech and language, has an immense negative impact on a patient's ability of social interaction.

The reduction of a patient's available vocabulary and semantic understanding – some words may still be remembered but their meaning is lost – is not necessarily irreversible. At least parts of the language that had been lost can often be recovered. Right after the initial stroke treatment, any patient who developed symptoms of a speech or language disorder, or both, usually undergoes some type of speech therapy. The intensity and duration of such treatment can have a major impact on the final outcome. It could be shown that a dense therapy coverage of about 10 hours of speech therapy during the first 12 weeks repeatedly yielded better clinical outcomes compared to other protocols with a less intense coverage [Bhog 03]. A fairly popular exercising technique for aphasia patients is referred to as the *Copy and Recall Treatment* (CART) [Bees 02, Bees 06]. It follows a homework scheme, in which patients are given several pages of exercises. They are split into two categories, the *copy* and *recall* stage. On a *copy* page, the individual is shown the picture of an object, along with the correct word. The task is to copy the word at least 20 times per day by writing it in the provided blank spaces. During the following *recall* stage, the same object is depicted once again, but this time, the page only contains blank lines, without giving away the correct word. In a self-test scenario, the patients have to validate their own exercising progress. Another very popular exercising technique is very similar to one of the most popular evaluation protocols for aphasia, the *Philadelphia Naming Text* (PNT) [Roac 96]. The test requires patients to correctly name a set of 175 pictures which show a variety of high-, medium- and low-frequency nouns

with a length between one and four syllables. In the scope of therapy, patients can be asked to name pictures of objects to re-learn the semantic link. It was shown that such exercise would not only improve the word-finding abilities of individuals, but that these improvements might also translate over to the more challenging domain of spoken dialogue language [Conr 09].

The outcome of any language therapy can vary significantly among patients, as it strongly depends on the exact region of brain damage, as well as its extent. Furthermore, studies found that patients suffering from Broca's non-fluent aphasia usually achieve better recovery results compared to others experiencing Wernicke's fluent type [Bakh 07]. This is mostly explained by the fact that the latter group of patients lacks awareness of the particular words they are missing.

After suffering a stroke, chances are that a patient's brain was not only damaged in an area responsible for language understanding and semantic knowledge, but also in one which is relevant for planning motor actions. That is because the relevant brain regions are fairly close to each other, with some overlap. Neurological damage to the frontal or parietal lobe might interfere with Broca's and Wernicke's areas, respectively [Gros 08]. The motor impairment is referred to as apraxia of speech (AOS), and it often co-occurs with Broca's aphasia [Ogar 05]. AOS and aphasia are two different disorders, with the former affecting the speech production, and the latter impacting the higher-order language understanding. Nevertheless, misconceptions between AOS and fluent aphasia are not uncommon because they affect the spoken language of individuals in very similar ways. Affected individuals exhibit a variety of phonemic errors, which makes it more challenging for the clinical expert to precisely differentiate between the two disorders [Ogar 05]. At the same time, phonemic errors also occur in patients suffering from the non-fluent variant [Kuro 16].

As aphasia often co-occurs with other speech disorders, like dysarthria and apraxia, it can be challenging to always provide correct therapy feedback. Particularly the combination of aphasia and dysarthria makes the assessment more demanding, as it may be impossible to reliably identify the root cause of error for every exercise item that had been produced incorrectly. Figure 6.2 illustrates an exemplary exercise item which could be used in the scope of a picture-naming therapy session for a German native speaker. It is common for patients to practice words of their everyday vocabulary for which they have lost the semantic connection. In the example, the picture to be named shows a glass of beer. The corresponding German target word is *Bier*. Unfortunately, the patient did not respond correctly, and instead said something else that sounded much more like the German word *Vier*, the number *Four* in English. The speech therapist has to make a difficult decision now: Was this error caused by the individual's aphasia condition? In that case, they remembered parts of the word, but not all of it, and instead used a phonetically similar alternative, resulting in a phonemic paraphasia. It is also possible that the patient suffered from a moderate or severe dysarthria, which would render their speech less intelligible. The various ways dysarthria affects speech production, and how different articulators lose their full motor ability due to a decreased muscle tension, was described in detail in the chapter on Parkinson's disease. If the subject had correctly remembered the word *Bier*, but was unable to correctly articulate the plosive [b], then the air flow between the lips had not fully been prevented, and a fricative sound such as [f], [v], [β] or [ϕ]

Figure 6.2: Example of a picture naming exercise. The target word is the German word *Bier*. An incorrect realization, which includes a phonemic error in the beginning of the word, resulted in another German word. It remains unclear if the error was the result of an incomplete word recognition (paraphasic aphasia), speech production deficit (dysarthria) or motor planning dysfunction (apraxia).

could be the result. Lastly, if the motor control of the patient was fine, and they correctly remembered the word, their motor planning could have prevented them from correctly saying *Bier*. In this case of an apraxia, they might have said some other words before, for example that this is “*A full glass of beer*”, and when they came to the actual word, they mis-planned their motor action, and consequently used the incorrect phoneme. This decision-making process is difficult, and it requires years of experience and prior knowledge about a patient’s general capabilities on the levels of speech and language.

Whenever there is only one pathology present that affects either the production of speech or the understanding of language, the decision-making process to assess a patient’s current state and provide feedback is straightforward. As soon as both speech and language become affected, this evaluation becomes a lot more difficult apparently. Suppose that the decision-making entity is now no longer the clinical expert with years of experience, but any kind of algorithm capable of processing the patient’s speech signal. This may introduce new opportunities in terms of digital therapy, but

it also adds yet another uncertainty factor to the diagram in Figure 6.2. Besides the three pathological causes, which assume that the subject had not said *Bier*, but *Vier*, there arises a fourth factor, namely recognition errors. The state-of-the-art ASR systems of our time achieve word error rates (WER) of around 3% on signals from healthy speakers [Baev 20]. However, these numbers can be misleading, as they are commonly reported for read speech from healthy contributors. Furthermore, these architectures are computationally expensive, and it is not always feasible to deploy them for general purpose use-cases. The presence of background noise, a low-quality microphone, or reverberation artifacts, the number of factors which could lead to an increased WER and consequently to a misrecognition of a particular word are endless. No ASR algorithm is robust enough to always produce error-free recognition results. On the other side, therapists could also experience difficulties to fully understand every spoken word of a patient. If a subject suffered from some form of speech impairment which resulted in a decreased intelligibility, this could quickly lead to ambiguities in the uttered sentence. Additionally, a therapist is likely not able to maintain the same high level of attention over the course of several therapy sessions on the same day. In terms of fatigue, the algorithm clearly has an edge over the speech expert. On the other hand, a therapist's available context during the assessment of a patient is larger. For example, the expert might also rely on the visual signal, which allows them to incorporate information about lip movement, facial expression or gestures which could help understand what a patient is saying.

The many different forms of aphasia – categorization done by medical experts knows several more sub-types besides Broca's, Wernicke's and PPA – combined with the presence of other speech and language problems, makes it very difficult to provide automated feedback systems. Unlike for PD or Covid-19, automated diagnosis solutions in the domain of aphasia are almost non-existent, simply because there is very little need. As discussed earlier, the primary causes of the condition are stroke and brain injury, both of which traumatic events which require hospitalization and in-depth examination by neurologists, who are then responsible for the correct diagnosis.

At the same time, rehabilitative speech therapy should start as soon as possible after the infliction of neurological damage, at a high frequency exercising protocol [Bhog 03]. While this may be achievable during the initial, often referred to as *acute* stage of a stroke, during which an individual is still hospitalized, it becomes increasingly difficult as soon as the patient is able to return home. That is, unless they return to a special-care home with dedicated speech therapists. In any other case, they have to exercise for themselves, ideally multiple times a day, and visit a speech therapist at least once every week. This implies that the patient does have a sufficient amount of adequate exercise items, they had the opportunity to learn self-training strategies with a therapist before, and their degree of impairment still enables them to exercise on a regular basis.

Furthermore, self-supervised speech therapy can already be challenging for dysarthric individuals, because they have to focus on the correct articulation as well as their own supervision simultaneously. In the case of aphasia patients, this is even more difficult. Whilst a PD patient knows what a particular word should sound like, and they are very much aware of what problems they have during pronunciation and voic-

ing, aphasia patients do *not* necessarily know the word in advance. One might argue that such a scenario should be much simpler, because any time a patient did not manage to find the right word, a feedback system could simply display the correct answer. However, in aphasia it is not only about learning the word from its written form. The *neolexon* therapy application for example requires patients to improve their capabilities in terms of spoken language production, comprehension, reading and writing [Pfab 15]. It even includes visual stimuli by showing the mouth of a therapist as he or she speaks an exercise item. A successful aphasia therapy is not limited to showing a patient the correct word for an exercise image. Ideally, individuals are able to experience the word, both visually and auditory [Frid 12].

6.2 Literature Review

As mentioned in the introduction already, the awareness of aphasia in the general public is rather low compared to other neurological diseases, despite the high number of patients who suffer from aphasia after a stroke or brain injury. Unfortunately, a similar pattern is observable in the scientific domain. An online search on *Google Scholar*¹ for contributions dated publication year 2017 and later yielded 326 000 results for the term *Parkinson*, 543 000 for *stroke*, but only 39 100 for *aphasia*. Whilst these numbers may not accurately resemble the true amount of research (in terms of funding or number of active researchers for example), they still outline the general trend of a relatively low attention towards aphasia.

Table 6.1 summarizes notable contributions in various research disciplines related to aphasia. They range from simple disease classification, estimation of severity, exercise-related keyword spotting (KWS) to full-fledged ASR. The first work presented by Balagopalan used a transfer learning technique, optimal transport (OT), which aims to find a low-cost transfer function from a source to a target probability density function, where the cost is defined in terms of some arbitrary distance metric. They used various aphasia datasets from different languages, and tried to transport linguistic features from one language to another one, such that they might be helpful for aphasia classification on a global scale. Their system performed quite well on French transcripts, but notably weaker on that from the Mandarin dataset. This indicated that the linguistic features they had found via OT were not equally successful among all languages, but they still improved the accuracy for Mandarin compared to the baseline which did not use OT.

Another classification approach suggested by Fraser [Fras 14] used a variety of syntactic and semantic features collected from speech transcripts of healthy individuals, as well as patients who suffered from either progressive non-fluent aphasia (PNFA) or semantic dementia (SD). Their SVM-based system was well able to distinguish between samples from aphasia and healthy individuals. With an accuracy of 75 %, the classification between PNFA and SD was found to be much more challenging. The high rate of success for aphasia recognition could mostly be attributed to the quality of handcrafted features, which also required background knowledge about the

¹Search date: 24.02.2023

From <https://scholar.google.com/>

Title	Authors (year)	Task	Model	Features	Results
Cross-language aphasia detection using optimal transport domain adaptation [Bala 20]	A. Balagopalan et al. (2020)	CLF	SVM	OT of linguistic features	F1-score French: 87.2 Mandarin: 66.3
Automated classification of primary progressive aphasia subtypes from narrative speech transcripts [Fras 14]	K. C. Fraser et al. (2014)	CLF	SVM	syntactic & semantic features	Accuracy (%) Accuracy: 96.7
Automatic speech recognition in the diagnosis of primary progressive aphasia [Fras 13]	K. C. Fraser et al. (2013)	CLF	ASR	text & acoustic features	Accuracy (%) clean: 65.7 noisy: 70.7
Predicting severity in people with aphasia: A natural language processing and machine learning approach [Day 21]	M. Day et al. (2021)	CAT	RF	bag of words	Accuracy (%) 62.7
Automatic word naming recognition for treatment and assessment of aphasia [Abad 12]	A. Abad et al. (2012)	KWS	ASR & 1-gram acoustic KWS 103 words	spectral	Accuracy (%) 83.0
NUVA: a naming utterance verifier for aphasia treatment [Barb 21]	D. S. Barbera et al. (2021)	KWS	Phoneme RNN & DTW 220 words	MFCCs	F1-score English 89.5
Improving automatic recognition of aphasic speech with AphasiaBank [Le 16]	D. Le et al. (2016)	ASR	HMM-GMM & HMM-DNN	MFCCs	PER (%) UMAP: 39.7 Aphasia-Bank: 64.2
Automatic speech recognition for acoustical analysis and assessment of Cantonese pathological voice and speech [Lee 16]	T. Lee et al. (2016)	ASR	HMM-DNN	MFCCs	SER (%) Aphasia: 57.8 Healthy: 42.7
Improving aphasic speech recognition by using novel semi-supervised learning methods on AphasiaBank for English and Spanish [Torr 21]	I. G. Torre et al. (2021)	ASR	Wav2Vec XLSR	end-to-end	WER (%) English: 36.7 Spanish: 42.8

Table 6.1: A list of notable contributions in the domains of aphasia classification (CLF), categorical (CAT) severity analysis, keyword spotting (KWS) and speech recognition (ASR). Techniques ranged from SVM, RF, multi-layer-perceptron (MLP), dynamic time warping (DTW) and various HMM strategies. Different ASR quality measures had been reported besides accuracy, such as the error rate on the phoneme (PER), syllable (SER) and word (WER) levels.

vocabulary. Word frequency and familiarity were found amongst the most informative features to classify between healthy individuals, PNFA and SD patients.

In another work on classification of PNFA from Fraser [Fras13], they used an ASR system to generate transcripts of speech samples. These transcripts were combined with a set of acoustic features to improve overall results. The system achieved an accuracy of 70.7% using the ASR-generated transcripts. Upon further investigation, it turned out that the ASR achieved a WER of 67.7% on PNFA samples, but would not perform much better on the control speakers either (WER: 64.0%). This made it quite difficult to understand that the classifier performed systematically worse when the clean human transcripts were used instead of those coming from the noisy ASR, yielding an accuracy of only 65.7%. With (almost) error-free human transcripts, the classifier should always achieve the best result. If this is not the case, the entire methodology appears questionable.

Day et al. published one of only a few contributions which investigated the feasibility of categorical severity estimation for aphasic patients. They used three categories (mild, moderate and severe) and achieved an unweighted average accuracy of 62.7% (the paper reports a weighted average of 73.0%) using an RF classifier. Instead of handcrafted features, they relied on a bag-of-words representation of transcripts, which simply summarizes the frequency of occurrences of individual words in an utterance. As the system was trained on English samples performing a closed set of picture description tasks, the results might not be very strong, but could be expected to be rather stable within the given setup.

The first work on KWS from Table 6.1 by Abad used an ASR system to estimate the sequence of spoken phonemes, which was then combined with a 1-gram acoustic model of the keyword. The advantage of said 1-gram is that it could reflect pronunciation alternatives on the phoneme level. Their system encompassed a vocabulary of 103 unique Portuguese keywords which could be recognized with an accuracy of 83.0%. In their work, they refer to the keyword verification rate (KVR) rather than accuracy, which they defined “*as the number of coincidences between the manual and automatic result (true acceptances and true rejections) divided by the total number of exercises*”. From an acoustic perspective, the data was restricted to recordings collected with a headset microphone to maintain equally high signal quality.

The second contribution in the domain of KWS was presented by Barbera et al. Their system was composed of multiple sophisticated building-blocks. They used a phoneme recognizer based on bi-directional RNNs and trained on healthy speakers to compute phonetic posteriorgrams. The recognizer achieved a PER of 15.9%. The posteriorgrams were then combined with phonetic representations of keywords through a dynamic time-warping (DTW) strategy. The time-warping distance served as a measure if a particular keyword had been produced or not. Over a vocabulary of 220 words, the system achieved a mean accuracy of 89.5%. Whilst this performance can be considered to be quite strong, it comes at the cost of certain restrictions. First, the system required at least two productions of each word from healthy control speakers, which the DTW algorithm could use as reference. Consequently, the algorithm would test for similarity w.r.t. a very restricted set of realizations of the word. Furthermore, a small group of only eight patients was considered during the study, that had been recorded with decent quality headsets, and were instructed to only

produce the target word with no other surrounding words. In an everyday exercising scenario, these conditions are fairly unlikely.

The last three contributions from Table 6.1 all investigated the feasibility of ASR for aphasic speech. The first work from Le used MFCCs in combination with various HMM strategies, either based on Gaussian mixtures or deep neural networks (DNN). One key finding they reported was an increasing PER along with more severe stages of aphasia. On the AphasiaBank dataset, where individuals had been categorized into one of four severity levels, the PER for mildly affected was on average 49.0%, whilst that of the most severely affected group was 89.3%. This showed how big of an impact aphasia had on the intelligibility of individuals. It is important to notice that the reported metrics refer to the recognition of phonemes, not words. A decline of word recognition success would be expected for aphasia, because a standard language model would not apply anymore. However, with increasing severity, the condition also affects the speech of patients, making it harder to understand for both humans as well as automatic systems. The second, very similar contribution by Lee, addressed ASR for aphasic Cantonese speakers. They used another HMM-DNN system, but in comparison to the work from Le, their recognizer had been optimized with healthy speech only. Le et al. used pathological speech data to train their ASR. The final model for Cantonese achieved syllable error rates of 42.7% and 57.8% for healthy and aphasia speakers, respectively. This indicated once more that the speech from aphasia patients is significantly less intelligible.

The last study of the list from Torre used a state-of-the-art acoustic model, in fact the same which had already been used throughout this thesis. They fine-tuned the XLSR architecture using the English and Spanish subsets from AphasiaBank [MacW11], which they distributed into training, development and test splits. With the final model, they obtained WER values of 36.7% for English and 42.8% for Spanish test speakers. Given the size of the model of some 300 million parameters, these numbers are not too strong, and a likely explanation is the limited amount of available training data when using AphasiaBank in the first place. This highlights once more that, even with models that had been pre-trained on many thousands of hours of multilingual speech, such as Wav2Vec XLSR, the usage of pathological speech data for training any such models often does not yield optimal results. Just like Le, Torre et al. also reported results for the different severity levels for the English subset, and they perfectly match with the observation of the first study. The WER of mildly affected patients was 22.3%, that of the very severe group was 55.5%. Whilst their work was one of the most recent contributions to the domain of ASR for aphasia, and it utilized a very strong and well-known pre-trained model, some of the methodology remained unclear. The authors reported that they used *SpecAugment* [Park19], a popular technique for data augmentation in the spectral domain. The core idea is to mask out consecutive time frames or frequency bands of a spectrogram, following a predefined policy. The technique helps to improve robustness of ASR systems and greatly prevents overfitting. In the case of Torre et al., however, they never mention that they used an XLSR model which had been pre-trained with spectrograms. Instead, they describe an end-to-end model, for which the application of *SpecAugment* would be very difficult to realize.

6.3 The ASA-KI Corpus

Throughout the research project *Automatische Sprachbewertung bei Aphasie mithilfe Künstlicher Intelligenz (ASA-KI)*² (English title: *Automatic language assessment for aphasia by means of artificial intelligence*), it was possible to collect speech recordings from individuals who suffered from aphasia and used a digital at-home therapy solution to perform daily exercises. Subjects used the *neolexon* [Pfab 15] therapy application with a tablet computer, supported operating systems are both *Android* and *iOS*.

The application had been used by patients and speech therapists for years prior to the presented research project. In many cases, the feedback which was provided by the program required self-supervision. For example, if a patient had to name an object, the spoken utterance would be recorded and afterwards played back for the patient to listen and review their result. This may sound inappropriate at first, but it is important to keep in mind that not only the production, but also the perception of language is impaired in aphasic patients. Hence, the auditory feedback seems reasonable. At the same time, however, if the subject did not respond correctly, they are likely unable to identify their mistake by listening to their own incorrect speech sample. Accordingly, without proper feedback, much of the potential learning progress is lost. The importance of exercise feedback was also discussed w.r.t. a patient's motivation. An individual who can track improvements over time, for example in terms of correctly recognized keywords, will likely develop a greater motivation to continue working on his or her language abilities.

The goal of the ASA-KI project was to develop the simplest kind of feedback strategy, a keyword spotting system. It should be robust enough to deal with a large variety of audio signals as input. Together with the speech signal, the system would receive a keyword which had to be spotted. The most straightforward approach to create such recognizer would be the implementation of an entire ASR solution. Whilst other applications on the market had started using off-the-shelf ASR systems to process aphasic speech during the lifetime of the project, that approach is questionable from multiple points of view. First, sending any kind of patient data captured in the scope of a medical exercise application to a third-party web-service – one application used *Google's* speech-to-text (STT) API – even with an individual's consent, is a highly fairly dubious practice. Secondly, a quick glance back at Table 6.1 reveals that ASR for aphasia patients is extremely difficult. As explained earlier, many subjects suffer from a combination of speech and language impairments after experiencing a strong or traumatic brain injury. To make things even more difficult, in the scope of a speech exercise, individuals usually do not speak entire sentences, but perform picture naming tasks for example. An off-the-shelf ASR always expects some sort of language structure, which is usually not available. Consequently, the recognizer has to rely much more on the speech signal, which might be less intelligible due to a concomitant dysarthria.

Instead of employing a full-scale ASR, KWS solutions can actively look for the expected keyword. In the preceding literature review, two KWS solutions had been introduced. Both solved the problem by modelling a keyword acoustically in terms of

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Figure 6.3: Distribution of age and intelligibility annotation for aphasia patients. Intelligibility scores were not available for all speakers.

phonemes of the respective language. One system used 1-grams to describe the transition probabilities between subsequent phonemes in a particular keyword. The other used posteriorgrams estimated over reference speech samples from healthy speakers. Both approaches have in common that they rely on a closed vocabulary. In the case of 1-grams, the transition model needs to be estimated for each new keyword. When using reference posteriorgrams, one even requires real audio samples of every keyword. Despite the decent-looking results, this method is hardly feasible on a large scale.

The goal of ASA-KI was to implement a KWS method which is able to process the speech of individuals who suffered severe neurological damage. Furthermore, the system had to be able to spot any arbitrary keyword, such that the vocabulary could be extended at any time. This would require the underlying models to be robust against imprecise articulation or non-optimal acoustic conditions. On top, the keyword recognizer must be able to learn the fundamental concept of KWS from read speech samples from healthy speakers, and then transfer that knowledge over to aphasic patients who instead performed speech exercises.

The ASA-KI dataset comprised 53 female and 90 male speakers. Their respective age distribution is shown in Figure 6.3a. The mean ages of female (59.8 years) and male (57.0 years) participants were quite similar, with the former having a greater standard deviation of 15.4 compared to 12.7. The assumed similarity of mean ages was confirmed through a Student's t-test, which confirmed the hypothesis that both means were not statistically different according to a p-value of 0.24. Besides information about gender and age, 78 individuals were also assessed in terms of intelligibility. A patient was assigned a percentage score ranging from 0% for completely unintelligible to 100% for perfectly intelligible in steps of 25%. The result is shown in Figure 6.3b. The presented intelligibility score is quite a lot different from the one introduced with the m-FDA assessment in the chapter on Parkinson's disease. The m-FDA intelligibility rating provided insight into the overall correctness of pronunciation of an individual. In the case of the ASA-KI dataset, intelligibility only reflected what amount of speech was intelligible over all, ignoring precise articulation. Consequently, a patient could have a slurred speech, but still be considered intelligible,

which would result in a score of 100%, despite the fact that their pronunciation was not entirely correct. Another important factor which had been annotated in the scope of intelligibility assessment was the overall quality of audio signals. This was important because patients were allowed to perform exercises and contribute speech samples from at home, without the supervision of a therapist. This could cause all kinds of unwanted artifacts. Out of the 78 assessed subjects, 29 provided speech recordings with low signal quality. Reasons for low signal quality were:

- Noisy audio quality
- Secondary speakers
- Audio signals cut off
- High amount of recordings without speech
- Influence of comorbidities
- Low volume

Noisy audio quality could be caused by background signals, poor recording hardware, a reverberated signal or many other reasons. Numerous speakers provided samples which contained speech from secondary sources, such as other persons in the same room and television or radio transmissions. As patients were doing the exercises themselves, they had full control over the recording procedure. When they were shown an image, they clicked a button to start the audio recording, and once they had finished, they had to click the button again. Some subjects pressed the button either too late in the beginning, or too early at the end of the recording, cutting off parts of the keyword. Controlling the exercise flow manually also resulted in many empty recordings for certain individuals, because they started the recording multiple times for one image for example, or they simply did not know what to say or weren't aware that the recording was already in progress. As described before, comorbidities such as dysarthria have a major impact on an individual's speech, and patients who suffer from aphasia are very likely to experience other speech-related symptoms as well. Lastly, some patients were simply too far away from their recording device, or the microphone did not adjust the gain properly, which ultimately resulted in recordings with very low volume.

Despite the sometimes challenging signal conditions, the ASA-KI corpus holds several advantages. First and foremost, the non-optimal recordings perfectly reflect the real world. Elderly people are no experts when it comes to using a tablet computer and making sure that the microphone can pick up an unobstructed signal. They don't think about other persons in the room, the TV or radio or the open window. Why would a patient who suffered from aphasia ever think about the wall right next to their table which reflected acoustic waves and created a lot of reverberation. Putting it very simple, these are the audio signals one could expect when such an experiment was done without perfect lab conditions. Consequently, if it was possible to achieve decent results for the ASA-KI dataset, they are likely transferable to any other setup, as the current scenario is already quite demanding in terms of model robustness.

Not every signal which had been labeled as being of poor quality was the result of

non-optimal patient-device-interaction. A frequently occurring issue was that of a pronounced variation of signal amplitude. Built-in microphones of many tablet computers have to operate reliably in a variety of acoustic environments. Sometimes, the source speaker is very close to the device, in other circumstances, they are meters away, but the microphone still has to be capable of picking up the speech signal reliably. To achieve this, said microphones rely on an automatic gain control (AGC). AGC algorithms are part of the pre-processing pipeline of many microphones. They estimate the current volume level and adjust the gain, the sensitivity at which the microphone records the incoming audio signal, to maintain a certain amplitude. AGC works really well in most devices, and it is crucial to achieve decent volume levels when recording patients at home as well. However, AGC algorithms operate with a minor delay, that is because they have to record a small audio segment first to estimate the appropriate gain from it. When a patient clicks the button to start a new recording, and they immediately start to speak, their initial volume might be very low, until the AGC adjusts the microphone accordingly. Right after the adjustment, there is a pronounced increase in the signal's amplitude. If this artifact occurs within a keyword, it becomes very difficult to recognize the entire word.

Initially, patients were introduced to the therapy application and the research project by a speech therapist. If they agreed to donating speech samples (patients who did not want to contribute could use the app as well, without any restrictions), they were given an explanation of how the recording process works and which exercises would be recorded. Over the course of several months, the participants were then able to exercise at home and collect samples of said exercise sessions. Unlike the previously introduced datasets used in other studies, which utilized a very restricted keyword vocabulary, the final ASA-KI corpus contained exercise samples of 3009 unique German words. They reflected the day-to-day vocabulary of all 143 participants, and already provided a decent insight into how individualized an appropriate aphasia treatment can be. Each contribution had been annotated by a speech therapist, the respective fields are summarized in Table 6.2. Besides the standard information one would expect for any keyword recognition dataset, such as the keyword itself, a binary label whether it was produced and a link to the respective audio, the ASA-KI corpus annotation comprises much more detailed information. For example, it had been documented if there was noise in the audio, if an article was used together with the keyword, or whether the audio was empty because the patient did not say anything. Artifacts like a keyword which had been cut off had also been documented to make the selection of appropriate samples during the evaluation more straightforward. The annotation detail also reflected the difficulties which arise during the assessment of aphasic speech. There are phonetic as well as phonematic errors. In the case of the former, the patient attempted to produce the correct phoneme(s), but had difficulties doing so. For the phonematic errors, patients had used incorrect phonemes, not because they were unable to produce the correct ones, but rather because they did not know the correct pronunciation in the first place. Furthermore, there is the possibility that an individual used a different word that is either semantically similar to the keyword (*window* instead of *door*), a synonym (*story* instead of *tale*), or entirely unrelated. Sometimes, subjects also produced the incorrect word class.

To better understand the difficulty of the problem, the speech samples donated by

Field	Type	Information
Keyword	Text	The plain text keyword
Patient ID	Text	Anonymized identifier
SAMPA transcript	Text	Phonetic transcription of the word produced by the patient
Note	Text	Additional item-specific information
Item correct	0/1	Expected output of the recognizer
Article	0/1	Whether the keyword was produced together with the article
Article correct	0/1	If article was produced, was it correct?
Empty reaction	0/1	Recording contained no attempt to produce the keyword
Keyword cut off	0/1	Keyword was cut off
Keyword repetition	0/1	Keyword was produced more than once
Speech before	0/1	Speech before the keyword
Speech after	0/1	Speech after the keyword
Noise before	0/1	Noise before the keyword
Noise after	0/1	Noise after the keyword
Keyword cut off	0/1	Keyword was cut off
Wrong keyword	0/1	Less than 50% phonological overlap with target keyword
Disfigurement	0/1	Replacement of entire syllables
Phonetic error	0/1	Mispronounced phoneme(s)
Phonematic error	0/1	Incorrect phoneme(s)
Semantic error	0/1	Semantically similar alternative
Synonym	0/1	Using a valid synonym of the keyword
Word class change	0/1	The wrong word class was produced, for example a noun instead of a verb
Singular / plural	0/1	Incorrect singular / plural usage

Table 6.2: Available annotation categories for a single keyword item in the ASA-KI corpus. *0/1* indicates binary categories.

5 subjects had been annotated by two independent speech therapists. They were both familiar with the therapy and annotation protocols. The goal was to estimate the inter-rater agreement from this smaller subset of the data. *Cohen's* κ was used for the agreement analysis, which is defined as

$$\kappa = \frac{p_o - p_e}{1 - p_e} \quad (6.1)$$

where p_o is the observed ratio of agreement, and p_e is the expected agreement if both raters had annotated randomly. Consequently, p_e mitigates the ratio of agreement which could have been induced by chance.

For the annotation *Item correct*, the agreement was 0.82. This reflected the expected output of the final keyword recognition model, and already shows that even among therapy experts, it is not always clear what the ultimate verdict of the system should

look like. The disagreement was the result of different expectations from the keyword recognizer. The purpose of the *Item correct* annotation was not only to reflect the expected output in terms of correctness, but also in terms of what could be expected from the recognizer. If a keyword was correctly produced, but the patient's intelligibility was very low, or there was a lot of background noise, the expected output could still be labeled as *not produced*, simply because the therapists would not expect the system to be able to identify the keyword. However, this expectation was not always the same among therapists, and ultimately resulted in a lower inter-rater agreement for the item. For the phonetic (0.42) and phonematic (0.00), the agreement either dropped significantly or was completely gone. The main reason here is the difficulty to correctly identify said errors, and attributing them to the correct error class. In this context, the term *correct* by itself becomes very subjective and the definition varies between experts. Lower agreements were also observed for the annotated quality of audio samples. On average, the noisiness (anywhere in the audio) was labeled with an agreement of 0.58, the consensus about whether a keyword was cut off was also not high with 0.42.

Recordings had been collected via different platforms (Android and iOS). Instead of choosing a unified audio format which was supported throughout all devices, Android distributions stored audio data in the Advanced Audio Coding (AAC) format [Bran 99], whereas iOS clients used the standard wave (WAV) format. There were two major reasons for using one lossy (AAC) and one lossless (WAV) audio encoding. First, the entire recording pipeline of the existing app did not support a standardized audio format across all devices without further changes in the underlying application logic. Secondly, the final keyword recognizer was meant to be executed on a server. Consequently, it was important to evaluate the performance of the system on signals which had undergone a lossy audio compression to reduce network traffic and improve overall response times. The sampling rate of all signals was 44.1 kHz. The 143 patients contributed a total of 14 097 audio recordings which had been annotated by speech therapists. Before feeding the audio signals to the KWS systems, they were downsampled to 16 kHz, the expected sampling rate of the phoneme recognition modules. The number of audio samples which could be used in the final evaluation was 12 225, because the remaining 1872 files were empty or had the keyword cut off.

6.4 Open-vocabulary Keyword Spotting

When it comes to keyword spotting, one of the most popular sub-types is that of wake word detection. A wake word is a short phrase which triggers any further interaction between a human user and some sort of voice assistant. Using a wake word such as *Alexa!*, *Hey FaceBook!*, *Hey Google!*, or *Hey Siri!* has several advantages over regular KWS systems. First of all, large companies can collect many hours of speech samples, which all contain the wake word. Such an amount of training data is beyond the scale of any normal KWS solution, and it does not even take into account the large number of different speakers, environments and other factors such as the distance to the microphone array. The fact that large amounts of training data are available pairs up with the extremely limited vocabulary of wake word systems, which usually

only attend to a single phrase. This makes it possible to optimize an ML algorithm for that particular task, and makes the presence of a higher-order language model or a sophisticated acoustic model obsolete.

Traditional wake word systems are usually divided into two parts. The wake word recognizer is a lightweight model which runs on distributed hardware, for example a voice assistant. It performs all operations locally, and whenever it detects the wake word, the relevant audio is sent to a wake word verification model. This secondary model only verifies that the wake word was truly produced to minimize the false-alarm rate [Kuma20]. A recognition model that attended to *Alexa!* might trigger on the phrase *Alex!*, which could then be rejected by the verification model, which either runs locally or on a remote server. Unlike a wake word model, a KWS model has to be able to recognize more than one single keyword. In most applications, the amount of available training data is much smaller, but the number of keywords of interest is significantly higher. Combined with pathological speech, the problem becomes increasingly difficult.

To achieve open-vocabulary KWS, it was necessary to decouple the actual keyword from the entire architecture. A keyword should behave identical to any audio signal: It serves as an input to the model, but it may vary between requests. And just like the waveform, there may be new, previously unseen keywords, during inference. On a conceptual basis, it was necessary to move away from an actual (written) keyword, which would be a sequence of graphemes. Like in other studies, keywords were instead defined as a sequence of phonemes. This has the advantage that it is also possible to model pronunciation alternatives, for example the result of a local accent or unique, patient-specific articulation patterns.

Throughout this work, three KWS systems will be introduced. They were all designed to be capable of processing any arbitrary keyword, based on a waveform input as well as a keyword query. All three models will use a pre-trained phoneme recognition model to process the waveform input. The most important advantage of this approach was that the phoneme recognizer, being the most parameter-expensive component of the KWS architectures, could be frozen during training. Only a small portion of parameters of the entire model had to be optimized. This mitigated GPU memory problems, allowed the use of a much larger batch-size and ultimately prevented any overfitting issues during training. One of the three models was a convolutional RNN (CRNN), which did not employ any Transformer layers or other types of traditional neural attention mechanisms in the keyword recognizer. The second model used a Transformer-based encoder-decoder logic to process the sequence of recognized phonemes as well as the keyword query. Lastly, the decoder-only model's design was inspired by the most recent advances in the domain of NLP. It's general structure and flow of information is very similar to that of the latest large language models (LLM), such as GPT-3 [Brow20b].

Experiments had been performed with the base and large version of the presented phone recognizer, but instead of using the multilingual variant, the model had been optimized towards German phonemes. Because ASA-KI is a German dataset, it only seemed reasonable to optimize towards this particular language, given that the underlying task is very language-specific in the first place. Consequently, throughout this chapter, the term phoneme will be preferred over the term phone, because the

recognizer now models German phonemes. This restriction to only a single language also had an impact on the available training data. Whilst Common Phone comprises almost 86 hours of multilingual training data, the German subset alone only has 13.6 hours. This small amount is still enough to train the base Wav2Vec 2.0 model without experiencing early overfitting issues, but it falls short for the XLSR variant. It would have been possible to try and mitigate the overfitting – Wav2Vec models already employ a dropout of 10% in their Transformer layers for example – but this would almost certainly not result in the best-performing model. As it was shown in the original study on Wav2Vec 2.0 [Baev 20], very small amounts of training data already sufficed for optimization, but the results would always improve if more data was available. Accordingly, it was necessary to enrich the amount of training data before optimizing any German phoneme recognizer.

6.4.1 German Training Data

The German subset of Common Phone did not hold the required amount of training samples to optimize the large 315 million parameters XLSR model without running into overfitting issues. However, Common Phone itself applied a very useful logic to create a diverse dataset. If this logic was applied only on German data, it should be possible to generate a larger distribution. Common Phone based its data on version 7.0 of the Common Voice corpus, which had been released in July 2021. It comprised 966 hours of validated German speech donations. The most recent version, Common Voice 12.0, holds 1205 hours, and the number of unique speakers was also increased by around 12%. Accordingly, the new corpus should be based on the most recent release to get as many different speakers and hours of recorded speech as possible.

Once again, all contributions who lacked information about the speaker’s age and gender had been omitted. This was not only done to maintain the best possible equilibrium in terms of gender and age, but also because the speech samples of all those speakers who had provided said annotation could accurately be attributed to that speaker. Common Voice allows anonymous speech donations, which introduces a challenge upon creation of speaker-separated training, development and test splits. The problem was further addressed in the paper on Common Phone and will not be discussed in-depth here.

After collecting all relevant speakers, they were once again organized in a two-dimensional table in which each cell held all contributors of a particular gender and age group. For each cell, a pair of one female and one male speaker was then drawn as long as there were sufficient speakers. 12.5% of all pairs were assigned to the test, 12.5% to the development, and the remaining 75.0% to the training set. In Common Phone, the maximum number of samples from one speaker depended on the underlying language. That was done because for certain languages, there were far more speakers available than for others. To end up with an unbiased dataset in terms of language, the more speakers a language had, the less samples had been drawn from each speaker for the final corpus. In case of German, the number of maximum samples was 13. For the new German-only corpus, it was not necessary to maintain any inter-language equilibrium. However, it was important not to blindly

accept all samples from one particular speaker, as discussed in the original article already, because a few outliers donated more than 10 000 utterance, which would once again induce a massive bias. A maximum number of 100 samples per speaker was chosen for the new German corpus, which would yield a sufficiently large amount of training data, but at the same time prevent any unwanted speaker-bias.

If a speaker had been chosen for the corpus, and had donated 100 audio samples, that would not yet mean that all of their samples would ultimately be part of the final dataset. That was because every spoken sentence – Common Voice is read speech – must only occur once in the final dataset. Consequently, if a subject had donated speech samples with transcripts that had already been acquired through other speakers, these samples were omitted. This resulted in some speakers from the development and test sets not having any samples with unseen transcripts, and they did not make it to the final dataset. However, having only unique transcripts seemed more important than keeping a few more speakers in the end, who then had spoken tests that were already seen during training.

The new dataset comprised 952 speakers in the training, 128 in the development, and 131 in the test split. Compared to the 13.6 hours of the original German Common Phone training split, the new assortment provided 71.1 hours for training. This was much closer to the total amount of training audio in Common Phone (85.8 hours) and greatly helped to prevent overfitting. After speaker and sample selection, every audio file was annotated using the same web-service and identical parameters as for Common Phone. This way, it was possible to produce an automatic annotation on the phonetic level, including time-alignment.

From the original 101 phone symbols of the multilingual recognizer, the new German corpus conserved 44 phonemes. The number slightly deviated from the German inventory reported in the Common Phone paper (48 symbols), which had been estimated over all symbols that were seen among German samples. It included four phones which are not part of the native German inventory, and were instead introduced by loan words from other languages, such as /ð/ and /θ/ from English. Because they were found to be irrelevant for training a German KWS model, they had been removed from the inventory. In fact, there is a very small chance that an exercise item contains an English word, and the respective sounds might be of interest again. However, for the KWS model to reliably process any such non-German phoneme, it would be necessary to see that phoneme during training with sufficient frequency. Due to the very small number of occurrences of the four omitted phones, this requirement would already be violated. Accordingly, it was the best option to remove them from the known set of German phonemes.

6.4.2 CRNN Model

The general structure of the entire CRNN is outlined in Figure 6.4. It receives a query keyword as well as a sequence of phoneme probability densities as input. The raw phoneme densities were first passed through a masking module to reduce the overall computational workload of the following building blocks.

Phoneme recognition models were optimized w.r.t. CTC loss. This requires an additional label, the blank token. Models which have successfully been trained with CTC

Figure 6.4: Design of the CRNN architecture. Blank token predictions are masked from the phoneme densities. Channel-wise matrix product between the keyword queries and phoneme densities yields C similarity maps of shape keyword length $S \times$ phoneme length T . The maps are processed by a stack of convolutional layers, and the result is passed through an unidirectional LSTM. The last hidden state of the LSTM serves as input for a binary classification layer.

tend to assign most of their output probability mass to said blank token. That is because it serves as a state-maintaining instance. If the model emits a blank token, that means as much as “*there is no new symbol to be predicted*”. Consequently, if 20 successive frames all span over the same class, the class is usually emitted only once, and in the remaining time frames, the model emits the blank token.

For phoneme-based KWS, this property of CTC can be exploited. Frames which have a high probability for the blank token can be masked from the sequence, such that only those frames remain which encode to actual phonemes. This results in an average reduction of sequence length of 75%. It is crucial to apply an appropriate masking logic to avoid removing too many frames from the signal, ultimately erasing important information. All of the presented models performed worse when the logic would mask every frame in which the blank token was the one with the highest probability (equivalent to an *argmax*). That was because it is possible that the blank token had, for example, a probability of 45%, whereas another phoneme had 40%. The remaining 15% probability mass was distributed among the remaining classes. In the described frame, the blank token had the highest probability, but the model expressed quite a lot of uncertainty. Given that the final KWS system should be able to process pathological speech, such uncertainties are only likely to occur even more frequently. Another variant which had been evaluated was a threshold-based masking logic. This solution was clearly more powerful, as it was now possible to only remove those frames which had been attributed to the blank token at a high probability. A static threshold turned out to be less reliable compared to a dynamic one, because for some noisy audio files, it could happen that many blank frames would be missed

during masking if the threshold had been set too high. A dynamic threshold could be realized by simply computing the mean value of the blank token’s posterior probability over time per audio sample.

At the start of the training, all parameters of the KWS model were initialized randomly. As a result, it might be more challenging for the architectures to identify corresponding symbols between the phoneme and keyword sequences. In other words, the models had to learn for each keyword phoneme symbol the corresponding index in the densities which came from the phoneme recognizer. Using a simple embedding layer for the symbols in the keyword which learns a projection of symbol indices into a high-dimensional space was possible, but could result in very long training times. Further investigation also revealed that said embedding would not learn any acoustic or articulatory similarities. Ideally, the model should be able to learn typical confusions on the phonetic level. In the chapter on PD, it could be shown that it was difficult for the phone recognizer to perfectly differentiate between the three stop sounds [p], [t] and [k]. Understanding these properties is important for the KWS to be more tolerant for common recognition errors of the phoneme model. Instead of using a standard embedding, each symbol in the keyword query was one-hot encoded. The encoding space was symmetric to that of the phoneme densities, such that the phoneme at index i was the same in the density as well as in the keyword. To allow the model to seamlessly learn phonetic similarities, both the densities as well as the one-hot encoded keyword sequence were projected to an internal dimension (dim_{Model}) through a shared linear layer before feeding them to the subsequent building blocks of each architecture.

To encode similarities between the symbols in the keyword query and the phoneme densities, the CRNN first computed the matrix product of the two sequences. Conventional neural attention mechanisms rely on the dot-product to estimate how similar a pair of query and key are. The matrix product fulfilled the exact same task. Given a keyword query Q of size $S \times C$ and a phoneme sequence V of size $T \times C$, where $C = dim_{Model}$, the resulting matrix product $Q \times V^T$ would be of shape $S \times T$. The performance of the model was greatly improved by replacing the standard matrix multiplication with a channel-wise operation. The result would be one similarity map for every channel C .

Not considering the batch dimension, the input tensor of the following stack of convolutional layers was of shape (S, T, C). For the convolutional layers, the CRNN model used a highly sophisticated arrangement of convolutions which had originally been implemented in the domain of image processing. A common problem of convolutional layers is that they quickly accumulate a massive number of parameters as the number of channels in the input signal increases. This does not only result in very large models which consume plenty of memory, but could also harm the performance if the over-parameterized model started to overfit on the training data. ResNeXt blocks aim to mitigate this problem by applying expensive convolution kernels only on inputs with very few channels [Xie 17]. As the name already gives away, the overall design is based on that of the ResNet architecture [He 16]. The major contribution of ResNet was the introduction of residual connections, which had already been explained in the section about Backpropagation. ResNeXt blocks also rely on a residual connection, but the structure of the employed convolutions is different. Let $C = 256$, a first

convolution projects the 256-dimensional input-signal to a much lower dimension of $C = 8$, using a kernel size of 1. This was done k times in parallel, where k is denoted as the cardinality of the ResNeXt block. For each of the k feature maps, the model then learned a unique convolution layer, this time with a kernel size of 3 along the keyword time dimension S and 5 along the phoneme densities time dimension T . Lastly, each of the k feature maps was projected back to the original channel configuration C with another convolution of kernel size 1. The k results were then merged additively. The outputs of each convolution operation were scaled through batch normalization, followed by a Gaussian Error Linear Unit (GELU) activation function [Hend16]. The CNN stack comprised a total of 8 subsequent ResNeXt blocks. The third and sixth of them were special versions, because they halved the time dimension S of the keyword, while leaving the amount of channels constant. This operation helped reduce the input size to the following recurrent layer.

The unidirectional RNN used an LSTM cell to process the incoming sequence. Notice that so far, the data is not 1-dimensional yet. The objective of the RNN was to iterate over an arbitrarily long sequence of detected phonemes and predict whether the keyword query was found. Accordingly, the time dimension T of the phoneme densities had to be preserved. It was required to remove the time axis S of the keyword query and concatenate the information of all time steps along the channel dimension. To do this, it was necessary to have a keyword query length which was always constant. This could be achieved by defining a maximum keyword length of 16 phoneme symbols. This number was large enough to cover most German words, and in case the keyword sequence was shorter, the query was padded with zeros. The introduction of this constraint was also very helpful for the CNN stack, which reduced the number of time steps along the keyword axis. With a fixed input length of $S = 16$, the output was also fixed at $S = 4$. Accordingly, after collapsing S into C , the number of input channels for the RNN was $4 \times 256 = 1024$. The LSTM used a 256-dimensional cell-state and operated in a sequence-to-one fashion, such that only the last emitted hidden state of the recurrent layer was passed to the final linear layer which performed binary classification.

Compared to the following Transformer architectures, the CRNN was the model with the lowest amount of parameters and required floating-point operations. However, this did not mean that it was the fastest model in terms of execution time. In fact, quite the opposite was the case. Despite the larger size and computational effort of the Transformer-based models, they would run faster almost every time. The explanation for this behavior could be found in the data dependency introduced in the RNN. The individual time steps cannot be executed in parallel, because at time step $t \in T$, where T once again represents the length of the masked phoneme densities, the result of step $t - 1$ needs to be available. Consequently, the runtime of the CRNN increased along with the number of phonemes recognized in an audio sample.

6.4.3 Encoder-Decoder Model

The encoder-decoder model was the first of the two Transformer-based models which had been implemented to solve the task of open-vocabulary KWS. As the name already suggests, it was composed of an encoder and a decoder component, which both

Figure 6.5: Encoder-Decoder model architecture for the KWS system. Raw phoneme densities are masked, then processed by the Encoder. The Decoder receives the concatenation of a classification (CLS) token and the keyword query. It then uses the keyword symbols as queries to attend to the encoded sequence of phoneme densities. The classification token is extracted from the output sequence and serves as the input to a linear binary classification layer.

handle unique tasks. In traditional NLP, the encoder is usually responsible to process some input sequence x such that it can be interpreted by the following decoder. In the case of the Transformer architecture, this was achieved with self-attention layers. The raw input x had to be superimposed with positional information, usually in additive fashion, before feeding it to the encoder.

The decoder on the other hand would see a sequence y of previously emitted outputs, up to the current time step. After performing a self-attention on that sequence as well, it uses its internal result as queries to attend to the keys and values composed of the last encoder layer's output. The entire Transformer model would then operate in an auto-regressive fashion, predicting a new output symbol y in each inference step. It made any convolutional or recurrent layers obsolete, but the auto-regressive execution would result in a rather slow inference speed.

For the encoder-decoder keyword recognition model, the entire architecture is outlined in Figure 6.5. The encoder block processed the predicted sequence of phoneme densities. Again, this sequence was masked to reduce the computational overhead and allow the model to focus on relevant parts of the sequence more effectively. Keep in mind that the Wav2Vec-based phoneme models also used the Transformer's encoder block to process the waveform and perform temporal contextualization. Accordingly,

it might seem like a valid approach to omit the encoder from the model design in Figure 6.5 and instead use the encoder outputs straight from Wav2Vec, before they had been projected to the phoneme densities. This does work in theory, but their dimensionality is quite high with 768 units for the Base and 1024 units for the XLSR model, resulting in a much more parameter-expensive KWS model. Furthermore, the results (one model had in fact been tested in this way) fell short of the presented architecture. The most likely explanation is that the additional encoder for KWS explicitly learned how to map certain prediction patterns to combinations of query phonemes if there existed no straight 1-to-1 mapping.

Whilst the encoder never saw the actual keyword, it was the responsibility of the decoder to process the given query sequence of phonemes. And because the final task was a binary classification problem, the sequence of target phonemes was prepended with a classification token. The idea of the classification token is to serve as an auxiliary time step, in which the Transformer model can store information that is relevant for the final classification task. After the final decoder layer, the token was extracted from the output sequence to serve as input to a linear projection with binary output. An alternative approach would be the aggregation of all outputs over time, commonly achieved by average- or max-pooling.

One more important aspect of the model was the usage of positional embeddings. As the attention layers of the Transformer are, by themselves, position-invariant, an additive sinusoidal positional encoding was applied to the masked phoneme densities. The query keyword sequence was also enriched with positional information, however, experiments showed that this was not always necessary to spot a particular keyword. Without the addition of positional information to the keyword query, the model would perform only slightly worse. The recall of keywords would remain almost unchanged, but the rate of false positive classifications had increased. Further manual analysis of incorrect examples revealed that the model had a tendency to falsely trigger on words with very similar phonetic configuration, in which the order was changed. For example, the recognizer detected the German keyword *Nebel* (English: fog) if the utterance contained the word *Leben* (English: life) in a manual experiment, because both contained the phonemes /l/, /e:/, /b/ and /n/. Only the order had been changed, but information about the arrangement of phonemes in the query keyword was never preserved through positional information.

The encoder-decoder variant held several advantages over the plain CRNN model. First of all, both the phoneme sequence as well as the keyword sequence can be of arbitrary length. In the CRNN setup, the arbitrarily long phoneme sequence could be processed, but the keyword query had to be transformed to some constant shape which would then be processable by the CNN and subsequent RNN layers. It should be mentioned that it is possible to use an arbitrary keyword length and interpolate the 2-dimensional feature map to some predefined size, because the operation of interpolation is differentiable and integrates into the backpropagation cycle. However, the interpolation would completely distort the keyword time axis, making it very difficult for the KWS model to reliably interpret keyword queries of arbitrary length. Another important benefit compared to the non-Transformer architecture was the clean structure of the model itself. The encoder would only process the phoneme densities, whereas the decoder would use the keyword query to attend to the encoded

Figure 6.6: Decoder-only model architecture for the KWS system. Raw phoneme densities are masked, then prepended by the keyword query as well as a classification (CLS) token, with separates the two sequence. The entire sequence is processed by the Transformer decoder. The classification token is extracted from the output sequence and serves as the input to a linear binary classification layer.

phoneme sequence and store relevant information in the classification token. Lastly, despite using a full Transformer architecture, the overall amount of parameters was still a lot smaller compared to the phoneme recognition model.

6.4.4 Decoder-only Model

The second model based on the Transformer architecture incorporated several key improvements which had been contributed to the original model design [Vasw17]. Figure 6.6 reveals that compared to the encoder-decoder model, one major building block had been removed. This design had been introduced to allow the decoder to attend to much longer sequences compared to the reference architecture [Liu18]. It had since been adopted by many successful state-of-the-art NLP models, such as GPT-3 [Brow20b] or PaLM [Chow22]. Besides their strong performance, the model design had some very important advantages over the previous encoder-decoder logic. The new setup could be executed faster, because the data dependency between the encoder and decoder – the latter had to await the result of the former – was removed. Additionally, without the need for an encoder, the parameters of said component could be saved. In fact, most models would not save the parameters, but rather spend them on a more powerful decoder though. One important aspect of the new decoder-only design is the setup of the decoder itself. Unfortunately, many articles

refer to the decoder as “*the decoder from the Transformer*”. Whilst this is truly a decoder from a conceptual perspective, it is often not identical to the Transformer’s decoder block (see Figure 2.17). In most cases, the decoder in a decoder-only model is identical or very similar to the encoder of the Transformer architecture. That is because the decoder would perform a self-attention step, as well as a second attention step to attend to the encoded sequence. This second step is obsolete, thus the decoder-only model uses the encoder block of the Transformer.

To feed the keyword as well as the sequence of masked phoneme densities to the decoder at the same time, it was necessary to separate the two inputs. This could be achieved by the CLS token, which had already been used in the encoder-decoder architecture. Now, it served the purpose to store classification-specific information and to separate the keyword query from the phoneme sequence at the same time. This design is not entirely new, it is frequently used in conversational LLMs to separate human input from machine-generated responses. Before inserting the CLS token, the keyword and phoneme sequence were concatenated and then superimposed with the same positional encoding used for the encoder-decoder variant. The CLS token was included in the sequence afterwards. This ensured that the token itself would not be modified in any way, making it easy to identify for the decoder.

The shared projection of one-hot encoded keyword queries and phoneme densities was adopted from the encoder-decoder architecture, as well as the final linear projection for binary classification.

6.4.5 Model Training

All proposed models had been trained with a learning rate schedule similar to that of the phoneme recognition model. Throughout the first 10 epochs, the initial learning rate of 1×10^{-5} was increased by factor 10. It then remained constant for the next 40 epochs. After epoch 50, it would decay exponentially by 0.96. The batch size of 24 samples was kept constant across all three variants. The overall GPU memory requirements were considerably lower for the KWS models, because the majority of parameters which came from the phoneme recognizer had been frozen and did not receive any further updates.

Instead of optimizing each of the three models once with the small and once with the large phoneme recognizer, training was only done with the small German Wav2Vec 2.0 instance. This would speed up the process and also yield less perfect predictions which the keyword models then had to process. If the models generalized well, it should be straightforward to remove the phoneme recognizer from a fully trained model and replace it with another version optimized on the same data.

Because all models throughout this work should exclusively be trained with samples from healthy individuals, it was necessary to create an artificial KWS task. Instead of choosing an additional German dataset for KWS, which would ultimately result in a restricted vocabulary again, the models were optimized with the same German training dataset which had been assembled for the German phoneme recognizers. For each utterance, the generated annotation files provided not only the most probably sequence of phonemes produced by the speaker, but also the gold-standard phonetic transcription of every word which came from a grapheme-to-phoneme (G2P) model.

Figure 6.7: Example probability density after applying a regular Softmax function (left) and after applying Gumbel Softmax (right) with temperature $\tau = 1.5$.

Together with the time-alignment of word occurrences in the utterance, it was possible to choose one of the words spoken in a slice of audio as the desired keyword which the model was supposed to spot. To simulate a keyword which had not been produced, a random word from another training sample was chosen as the query which did not occur in the training audio sequence. The ratio of samples in which the audio sample truly contained the keyword query was set to 0.67, leaving one third of all samples with only non-keyword speech. It was not possible to model this prior to reflect the probability of a successful keyword production of aphasia patients more accurately, because said probability strongly varied among patients.

Using the same training data for the KWS models as for the phoneme recognizer introduced an important problem during optimization. As described earlier, all models relied on the sequence of phoneme probability densities. Because the phoneme recognizers had already been optimized for the training audio samples, their emitted densities were very likely to represent an overly confident prediction. To mitigate this influence and simulate audio samples which had been more challenging for the phoneme recognition model to process, densities were estimated by means of a Gumbel softmax function [Jang 16]. It had been introduced earlier in section 3.3 where it was used during pre-training of Wav2Vec 2.0 models to perform differentiable codebook quantization. The Gumbel softmax function scales raw logits by some temperature parameter τ before applying the actual softmax function to scale the input to a probability density function. For quantization, small positive values of τ close to 0 are used to push the distribution towards a one-hot encoded vector. This property can be used in the opposite direction as well. By choosing values for τ which are greater than 1, the overall distribution becomes more and more uniform. An example is shown in Figure 6.7. The regular softmax function yielded a very confident prediction with most of the probability mass being assigned to class 3. By applying Gumbel softmax with temperature $\tau = 1.5$, this confidence could be scaled down to resemble a slightly more uniform distribution, without changing the predicted class itself. During training of KWS models, the emitted logits from the phoneme recognition models were scaled by a temperature $1 \leq \tau \leq 2$. The temperature was chosen randomly, but remained constant for one audio sample, modelling the same degree of confidence over the entire utterance. This step helped mitigate overfitting, because

phoneme densities of the same file varied between iterations, and it notably increased performance on validation and test data throughout all experiments.

Another important factor during model training was the duration of audio samples. Whilst the length of an input waveform had been sliced to 2 seconds during optimization of the phoneme recognition models, this length could be increased for the KWS models, due to the lower GPU memory constraints. As much as a training sequence of 2 seconds appeared reasonable for acoustic modelling, it seemed to be too small for KWS. Eventually, the final architectures were expected to correctly identify a keyword out of a potentially long sequence of distractor words. For that reason, a sequence length of 5 seconds had been chosen for all KWS models initially.

Unfortunately, it turned out that none of the models was able to converge. Training and development loss values would remain stable over the course of 30 epochs, and would eventually start to decrease very slowly. No architecture seemed to ever learn meaningful parameters for KWS. The challenging problem was the very small window of correspondence between the query keyword and the phoneme densities. If the phoneme recognizer detected some 25 phonemes (which is a rather small guess, given an audio length of 5 seconds), and the keyword comprised 4 phonemes, the model had to learn which phonemes the query belonged to. Whilst the direct comparison of two sequences of equal length would be straightforward, the task of localization is not. It turned out that, without understanding the plain task of recognizing a query keyword in the first place, it was almost impossible for the models to solve this problem from longer sequences.

Instead of using a static audio sample duration throughout the entire training procedure, the duration would grow over time, such that the models could learn from very short examples in the beginning, and then transfer that knowledge over to long sequences. In the first epoch, every architecture was shown only 0.5 seconds of audio. Because it was not always possible to find a word in such a small segment, the ratio of non-keyword examples, which should be 0.33, was larger in the beginning of the training, with values around 80%. The audio sample duration would then increase linearly with every new epoch, such that it would come to a peak training sequence length of 12 seconds after 60 epochs. After about 10 epochs, the non-keyword ratio had returned to the expected value of 33%, with an audio sample duration of 2.45 seconds.

The approach of steadily increasing durations of training samples completely solved the problem of very slow or non-existent model convergence. Furthermore, the architectures were able to quickly scale the logic learned over short duration training segments to the up to 12 seconds long samples from the development set, which were never shortened during training. An example of this learning progress is illustrated in Figure 6.8. The training loss decreased quite quickly in the beginning, and then started to increase again once the training sequences had reached a duration of around 2 seconds (around epoch 8). This increase continued until almost epoch 30, where training samples already surpassed 6 seconds. From this point on, the model fully translated the keyword recognition logic to longer sequences. After a full training run, all models had reliably learned to identify arbitrarily long keyword queries from audio recordings which could contain more than 100 uttered phonemes.

Several key properties of the three KWS model designs are summarized in Table 6.3.

Figure 6.8: Exemplary training progress of the encoder-decoder architecture when using linearly increasing audio sample durations. The model quickly learned the task of KWS for a given query sequence within a short audio segment. From epoch 8 onward (2s audio samples), the training loss increased again, as the model had to transfer the logic over to longer sequences. *LR* denotes the learning rate.

	CRNN	Encoder-Decoder	Decoder-Only
Base Params		94 406 317	
XLSR Params		315 484 845	
KWS Module Params	2 117 634	8 976 898	6 342 658
Computational Load	100 %	47.8 %	34.3 %

Table 6.3: Key properties of the three different architectures. Base and XLSR Params refer to the number of non-trainable parameters introduced from the underlying phoneme recognizer. Computational load was given in percent, describing the relative amount compared to the model with highest load (CRNN).

All architectures shared the same Base or XLSR phoneme recognizers. In terms of newly introduced trainable parameters, the encoder-decoder variant was the largest model. Compared to this, the decoder-only model was almost 30 % smaller. By far the fewest trainable parameters were introduced by the CRNN, with approximately 24 % of that of the encoder-decoder. Given the very different designs of all three architectures, a larger number of parameters would not necessarily result in a more computationally expensive model. To estimate the computational load during inference, each of the three models was provided with 5 seconds of audio input, plus an 8-phonemes long keyword query. This execution was repeated 100 times on a mobile CPU (*Intel Core i7-9750H*), and the phoneme model was bypassed to determine only the computation time of the KWS modules. Running the experiment 100 times yielded very consistent results across different cycles, with maximum absolute deviations from the average runtime of less than 4 %. Despite the relatively small number

Keyword length	Positive	Negative	Keyword Prior
2-4	201	101	0.67
5-7	1016	506	0.67
8-10	1851	826	0.69
11-13	1424	680	0.68
14-16	605	283	0.68
17+	341	174	0.66
Total	5438	2570	0.68

Table 6.4: Number of positive and negative test samples, clustered in terms of the number of phonetic symbols in the keyword query.

of parameters, the CRNN had the longest runtime. The primary cause here was certainly the recurrent layer, which introduced a sequential operation that would ultimately slow down the execution. Particularly for long audio sequences, the RNN would have a clear negative impact on the observed runtime. The encoder-decoder variant was more than twice as fast as the non-Transformer design, despite having more than four times as many parameters. The most efficient model in terms of computational load was the decoder-only version, which reduced the runtime to almost one third of that of the CRNN. A fast execution speed would play a major role during deployment, as quicker response times could improve the overall user experience. A more detailed description of each KWS model including layer configurations and internal dimensions is provided in the model cards in Appendix A.1.

6.5 Experiments

6.5.1 German Test Data

The two newly trained phoneme recognizers were tested in the same way as their multilingual counterpart before. The Base Wave2Vec 2.0 model achieved a PER of 11.5%, whereas the larger XLSR variant reached 7.8%. In comparison to the multilingual phone recognizers, the performance in terms of PER was observed to be better, which was expected as the problem had been simplified to only a single language. The goal of this simplification was to yield optimal KWS performance for German pathological speech, and the improvements w.r.t. PER clearly supported this decision.

Before running experiments on the pathological data, the trained KWS models were evaluated on the test portion of the newly created German data. During training, random keywords were chosen, with a prior for the correct production of a query keyword of approximately 67%. That is because for testing, it was important to maintain equal conditions between all models. Consequently, for each of the 8008 test audio files, a predefined keyword query was created, so that every test run would query the same keyword for the same file. The underlying prior of correct keyword production was left unchanged. Furthermore, test queries had been chosen in a way such that the prior was roughly the same among various keyword lengths. The

Model	Keyword length					
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+
Base CRNN	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00
Base Decoder-Only	0.98	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.99
XLSR CRNN	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.99
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.98	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99

Table 6.5: Precision scores obtained on the German test data. The XLSR variants share the same KWS model parameters with their Base counterparts, only the phoneme recognizer was replaced. Results are given w.r.t. different keyword query lengths.

resulting test distribution is shown in Table 6.4.

All three models were evaluated in terms of precision and recall of the keyword class. The *Encyclopedia of Machine Learning* [Samm 11] defined precision as

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (6.2)$$

and recall as

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6.3)$$

where TP denote the true positive, FP and FN the false positive and false negative examples, respectively. The precision score provides insight about the rate of success if a particular class was predicted. The recall on the other hand reflects the ratio of samples that belong to a particular class which were successfully identified as said class. In the context of speech exercises for aphasia patients, a low precision would cause many falsely recognized keywords, which had not been produced by the patient. A low recall could be even more frustrating to deal with, as it would indicate many correct keyword productions which had not been recognized as such by the underlying system.

The precision results are shown in Table 6.5. All of the proposed architectures could predict the presence of a keyword highly reliable. The number of false positive outputs was very low. Every model produced the weakest precision for the shortest keyword query lengths. This seems reasonable, because the shorter the query sequence was, the more likely were the KWS models to confuse an unrelated phoneme sequence in the audio with the target query. Despite being the smallest model, the CRNN architecture produced the best results across all experiments. Lastly, it was also possible to simply replace the phoneme recognizer with a more powerful variant which the KWS model had not used during training. The observed improvements, however, were negligible, mostly because the experimental results in combination with the Base phoneme model already left very little room for improvement. The results in terms of recall score are given in Table 6.6. Once again, the performance of all models was very strong. Despite the already high precision values, which indicated that almost every predicted keyword was correct, the number of keywords which were missed by

the model was very low. Once again, shorter keywords were slightly more prone to yield errors. The reason was likely the same as for the precision score, shorter keyword queries were much harder to accurately differentiate from the entire sequence. Because both precision as well as recall scores were so high, there appears to be no reason to prefer the larger XLSR model over the smaller variant for healthy speech. A core building block of all three architectures was the initial projection of phoneme densities and one-hot encoded phonetic query symbols to a shared dimension. Both the densities as well as the queries were passed through the same linear transformation which was learned during training of the KWS models. The goal was to allow the model to learn similarities between different German phonemes, such that it would be much more tolerant of phoneme recognition errors. To evaluate the quality of the learned projection, a single one-hot vector per phoneme class was passed through it to evaluate the excitation signal for each symbol. The projection layer of the CRNN model was used throughout the following experiments, but similar results were obtained across all three architectures. The projected vectors could be further evaluated by means of dimensionality reduction. Because the number of samples was identical to the number of different phoneme symbols (44) and hence quite small, a t-SNE embedding was chosen over the PCA decomposition. In the chapter on PD, it was of particular interest to find out if the largest variance within a point cloud encoded phonetically relevant insights (such as information related to the first and second formant). Now, it was mostly important to preserve stochastic relationships between data points in the high-dimensional space. Accordingly, a t-SNE embedding was much better suited for the task.

A perplexity of 5 was chosen for the embeddings of all projections of one-hot encoded vowels or consonants. Vowels and consonants were projected separately to reduce the number of symbols in one visualization and see correspondences more clearly. Figure 6.9 shows the resulting t-SNE embeddings for the various vowel phonemes. Realization were colored according to their respective tongue position required to produce the underlying phoneme. The illustration shows many meaningful correspondences between the individual symbols. Although the KWS models only had access to probability densities of predicted phonemes, that information was sufficient to learn dependencies between unique classes. Information was not only preserved in terms of tongue position, but also w.r.t. other properties such as the openness, with

Model	Keyword length					
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+
Base CRNN	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00
Base Decoder-Only	0.98	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.99
XLSR CRNN	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 6.6: Recall scores obtained on the German test data. Results are given w.r.t. different keyword query lengths.

Figure 6.9: T-SNE embedding of German vowel symbols. Vowels were colored according to their underlying tongue position: front (blue), near-front (violet), central (red), near-back (olive) and back (green)

vowels of the same tongue elevation frequently being close to each other. At the same time, the plot did not fully resemble a vowel triangle. This seemed reasonable, as no information about the underlying signal was available to the projection. Numerous clusters of phonemes could be observed which all share similar phonetic properties, but there were also a few exceptions. A decent example were the near-close near-front unrounded vowel /ɪ/ and its rounded counterpart /y/. They share the exact same tongue configuration, but according to the projection results, they were very unlikely to be mistaken with one another.

The t-SNE embedding of all consonant phonemes is depicted in Figure 6.10. This time, the individual symbols were colored in terms of the underlying manner of articulation. Just as for the vowels, there were many symbols which could easily be mistaken with one another. Notable examples were the two nasals /m/ and /n/, the bilabial voiced and unvoiced plosives /b/ and /p/, the alveolar voiced and unvoiced plosives /d/ and /t/ or the labio-dental fricatives /v/ (voiced) and /f/ (unvoiced). Some other patterns were not as clear, for example that of the last plosive category, the velar variants. However, the two symbols found between /g/ and /k/ were /ç/ and /x/, palatal and velar fricatives, respectively, which share an equal or very similar place of articulation.

If a KWS model was able to understand many common confusion patterns of the phoneme recognizer, it could process the emitted sequence of phoneme densities much more effectively. Let the keyword query be the German word *Spielfeld* (English: *playing field*) with the phonetic transcription /ʃpi:lfe:lt/. There exist a variety of potential pitfalls for the phoneme recognizer. Under somewhat noisy conditions or imprecise articulation, the /p/ might be mistaken with a /b/, the /t/ with a /d/, or the fricative /f/ could be misrecognized as /v/. Because the one-hot encoded query symbols

Figure 6.10: T-SNE embedding of German consonant symbols. Consonants were colored according to their underlying manner of articulation: fricatives (blue), plosives (violet), approximants (red), trills (olive) and nasals (green)

would encode to very similar vectors in the learned projection, the KWS model could still be able to successfully identify the keyword, even if multiple of the presented confusions were present at the same time. On average, the Base phoneme recognizer produced an error in one out of every nine phonemes. Nevertheless, the precision and recall results indicated that particularly for longer query sequences, the model had no problems to identify keywords reliably, while maintaining a very low rate of false positives at the same time. This was only possible because the model could learn how realizations of a keyword could deviate from a given query during training, and this information was, at least partially, encoded in the initial shared linear projection.

6.5.2 ASA-KI Data

After all three KWS models showed a very strong performance on the test data from healthy German speakers, they were used to evaluate picture-naming speech exercises from the ASA-KI corpus. In the first experiment, the *Item correct* (see Table 6.2) annotation was used as the ground truth label. This label held one major advantage for the initial evaluation: It had been designed to encode the expected output of the recognizer, and thus marked those keyword productions which could be very difficult for the recognizer to understand (due to noise, poor pronunciation or other artifacts) as *not produced*.

Table 6.7 summarizes the results in terms of precision score, following the same arrangement by length of the keyword query as used for the German test data before. As expected, the numbers were not as high anymore as it was observed with the healthy German speakers. Throughout all architectures, it was possible to observe that the precision for longer keywords started to decline. This was exactly the op-

Model	Keyword length						
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	All
Base CRNN	0.88	0.85	0.85	0.76	0.75	0.73	0.85
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.88	0.81	0.79	0.72	0.70	0.64	0.81
Base Decoder-Only	0.86	0.80	0.78	0.74	0.74	0.70	0.81
XLSR CRNN	0.89	0.85	0.84	0.75	0.71	0.73	0.85
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.87	0.81	0.78	0.70	0.68	0.72	0.81
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.86	0.81	0.77	0.72	0.71	0.69	0.80

Table 6.7: Precision scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. In this and all following tables, the best results for the Base and XLSR variants are highlighted in bold for particular keyword lengths and once for the combined score (All).

positive behavior as compared to the healthy reference. Naturally, the probability of a false positive prediction is expected to be larger for short keyword queries, because other parts of the phoneme sequence might be mistaken as the keyword. For long sequences, such mechanism would be far more unlikely. Nevertheless, some of the architectures reached precision values below 70 % for long (14 and more symbols in the query) keywords. Overall, the CRNN models achieved the best precision with 85 % of all keyword predictions to be correct. The precision values of the Transformer architectures were lower, but still at least 80 %. The decoder-only model yielded a very interesting result in terms of precision values between the models using the Base and XLSR phoneme recognizer, respectively. When the more accurate XLSR model was used for the German keyword test data, none of the models performed worse. However, the opposite was the case for the decoder-only model on the ASA-KI data. Apparently, despite having a more accurate phoneme recognizer, the architecture detected even more keywords which had been labeled as *not produced*.

Whilst the precision results were still found to be rather similar across all presented models, the recall scores looked more different. As summarized in Table 6.8, the best performing models were the Base and XLSR variant of the decoder-only variant. Both systems were able to correctly identify 94 % of all keyword productions as correctly

Model	Keyword length						
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	All
Base CRNN	0.80	0.76	0.83	0.93	0.98	1.00	0.80
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.88	0.88	0.91	0.94	0.97	0.95	0.89
Base Decoder-Only	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.95	0.97	1.00	0.94
XLSR CRNN	0.89	0.86	0.90	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.88
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.89	0.90	0.93	0.97	1.00	0.95	0.91
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.98	1.00	0.95	0.94

Table 6.8: Recall scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation.

Model	Keyword length						All
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	
Base CRNN	0.91	0.88	0.86	0.78	0.80	0.72	0.87
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.90	0.84	0.79	0.72	0.73	0.67	0.83
Base Decoder-Only	0.88	0.82	0.79	0.76	0.79	0.68	0.83
XLSR CRNN	0.90	0.87	0.85	0.77	0.76	0.73	0.87
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.89	0.84	0.80	0.73	0.75	0.70	0.83
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.88	0.83	0.78	0.73	0.75	0.70	0.82

Table 6.9: Precision scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. Keywords with positive *Phonetic error* label were always considered as produced as well.

produced. More importantly, this level of correctness was preserved throughout almost all keyword query lengths, reaching the lowest result of 92% for keywords of 2-4 phonemes with the XLSR model. The second Transformer-based architecture, the encoder-decoder, also reached strong recall values of 89% with the Base and 91% with the XLSR phoneme recognizer. The most notable difference between the two underlying phoneme models was observed for the CRNN version, which only managed to recognize 80% of all produced keywords with the Base model. A marked improvement to 88% could be observed after replacing the Base variant with its XLSR counterpart. Across all architectures, more keywords had been missed if the underlying query length was between 2 and 7 phonemes. However, the decoder-only architecture still managed to recover most correct productions in that category.

The high amount of false positive predictions could come as a surprise – the speech of aphasia patients should be more difficult to understand according to the findings from the literature review – but the detailed annotation allows for further investigations to understand the recognizers’ behavior. As mentioned before, the *Item correct* label also encoded information about whether the recognizer might not be able to identify a keyword. One reason for a therapist to deem a keyword production unlikely to be recognizable for the KWS model were phonetic errors, which were also annotated separately according to Table 6.2. Phonetic errors arose from poor intelligibility. The individual wanted to say the correct phonemes, but mispronounced one or more of them. Such mispronunciations might be still tolerable for the KWS models, because they learned common confusion patterns during training as could be shown with the healthy German test data. Consequently, in a second evaluation run, all samples which had a negative *Item correct* and a positive *Phonetic error* annotation were ultimately treated as correct productions again. From this point on, whenever certain error types (such as a phonetic or phonematic error) had been treated as correct keyword productions, they were only treated as correct if at least 50% phonological overlap with the target keyword had been observed (as annotated with item *Wrong keyword*).

The precision results of the new experiment are summarized in Table 6.9. Every model’s precision had suddenly improved by 2 percentage points. At the same time, the general trend of lower precision values for longer keyword queries remained un-

changed. The recall scores on the other side, presented in Table 6.10, decreased by 1 percentage point for the Base decoder-only model as well as for the XLSR variants of the other two architectures. The remaining models achieved the same results as before. The slight improvements in terms of precision which had been observed for every model were a clear indicator that some of the words which were previously recognized as correctly produced were indeed realized by the individuals, but with some phonetic errors, such that the therapists expected them not to be recognized by the KWS models. Apparently, all architectures were able to recognize a keyword even if it had not been produced perfectly accurate.

The phonetic errors helped to explain some of the positively recognized keyword queries which had not been annotated as correctly produced in the *Item correct* field. However, according to the numbers, phonetic errors were not the only kind of pronunciation deficit. In a last global experiment, the phonematic errors were also considered as positive keyword productions. Whilst a speech therapist might still be able to differentiate between a mispronounced phoneme (phonetic error) and the intentional use of an incorrect phoneme (phonematic error), this might be very difficult for the KWS systems.

The new precision and recall results were summarized in Tables 6.11 and 6.12, respectively. After slightly modifying the logic of which keywords were considered as produced and which were not another time, the precision scores of all architectures experienced a major improvement of at least 8 percentage points. The predictions of produced keywords were now correct in at least 92 % of all positive predictions, with the non-Transformer architecture achieving the best results, no matter which phoneme recognizer had been used. Very long keywords still tended to be more challenging for all models, but particularly those queries with lengths between 11 and 16 phoneme symbols experienced a large improvement. The overall very profound increase in precision performance indicated that throughout the previous experiments, many keywords with phonematic errors had been recognized by the system, but were not considered produced according to the logic, which ultimately lead to many false positive results.

As the precision values increased markedly, the recall showed a slight decline. This reduction in the ratio of recognized keywords out of the ground truth of all keywords

Model	Keyword length						
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	All
Base CRNN	0.80	0.76	0.83	0.91	0.96	0.95	0.80
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.89	0.88	0.90	0.92	0.98	0.95	0.89
Base Decoder-Only	0.93	0.92	0.94	0.94	0.96	1.00	0.93
XLSR CRNN	0.88	0.85	0.90	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.87
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.88	0.90	0.92	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.90
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.99	1.00	0.94

Table 6.10: Recall scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. Keywords with positive *Phonetic error* label were always considered as produced as well.

which had been considered as produced in this run could be expected, because said ground truth had been increased by all realizations which had been produced with phonematic errors. The models were still able to discover the produced keywords in many of the samples, but due to the phonematic error, this was not always possible. The CRNN variants, which achieved the strongest results in terms of precision, had suffered the sharpest drop in their recall scores, such that with the Base phoneme recognizer, only 75 % of all positive (keyword produced according to logic) samples were detected. The version which used the more powerful XLSR phoneme model still recovered 83 % of all produced keywords, but it had also experienced a clear drop by 4 percentage points. Clearly the strongest model design in this last evaluation was the decoder-only architecture. It achieved the same results w.r.t. precision as its encoder-decoder counterpart, but produced clearly better recall values of 91 % with both phoneme recognizers. Nevertheless, even the two Transformer-based versions were not able to identify all keywords which had been produced with a phonematic error.

In an additional experiment, the effect of decreased intelligibility on the KWS models' performance was evaluated with the respective subset of 78 individuals. Because the previous experiments had already outlined the results in terms of precision and recall scores extensively, the F-score as the combination of both was used for the new evaluation. The same logic as for the last experiment was used, such that keyword productions including phonetic or phonematic errors were still considered correct. F-scores were computed for each speaker, and afterwards accumulated for different intelligibility levels to estimate the mean and standard deviation. This ensured that speakers with a large number of contributed samples would not be overrepresented in the final result. F-scores are summarized in Table 6.13. Notice that there was only a single speaker available with a 0 % intelligibility annotation, so the standard deviation was always 0.00. Overall, the comparison of different models did not yield many new findings, the decoder-only variant was once again the strongest of the three architectures. The much more interesting result turned out to be the decline of F-scores as the intelligibility decreased. As mentioned in the corpus description, the intelligibility in the case of the ASA-KI corpus described the relative amount of speech which was considered to be understandable for a human listener. Unlike for PD, it did not

Model	Keyword length						All
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	
Base CRNN	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.92	0.84	0.95
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.94	0.92	0.90	0.88	0.90	0.77	0.92
Base Decoder-Only	0.94	0.92	0.91	0.93	0.93	0.79	0.92
XLSR CRNN	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.94	0.92	0.85	0.95
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.94	0.92	0.91	0.89	0.89	0.84	0.92
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.93	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.92	0.78	0.92

Table 6.11: Precision scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. Keywords with positive *Phonetic error* or *Phonematic error* label were always considered as produced as well.

Model	Keyword length						All
	2-4	5-7	8-10	11-13	14-16	17+	
Base CRNN	0.79	0.71	0.76	0.85	0.91	0.95	0.75
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.88	0.93	0.91	0.86
Base Decoder-Only	0.92	0.91	0.90	0.88	0.90	1.00	0.91
XLSR CRNN	0.87	0.80	0.83	0.88	0.93	1.00	0.83
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.90	0.98	0.95	0.87
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.90	0.92	0.91	0.92	0.96	0.95	0.91

Table 6.12: Recall scores obtained on the ASA-KI data. Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. Keywords with positive *Phonetic error* or *Phonematic error* label were always considered as produced as well.

Model	Intelligibility in %				
	0	25	50	75	100
Base CRNN	0.74	0.60	0.61	0.73	0.86
	0.00	0.25	0.27	0.15	0.13
Base Encoder-Decoder	0.79	0.74	0.71	0.82	0.90
	0.00	0.17	0.22	0.07	0.08
Base Decoder-Only	0.88	0.78	0.72	0.87	0.91
	0.00	0.18	0.18	0.09	0.08
XLSR CRNN	0.79	0.74	0.68	0.74	0.91
	0.00	0.14	0.27	0.14	0.08
XLSR Encoder-Decoder	0.79	0.72	0.70	0.80	0.90
	0.00	0.20	0.25	0.08	0.10
XLSR Decoder-Only	0.87	0.78	0.75	0.88	0.92
	0.00	0.12	0.22	0.07	0.08

Table 6.13: Mean F1-scores obtained on the ASA-KI data for different intelligibility levels (Standard deviations below respective mean). Ground truth label was the *Item correct* annotation. Keywords with positive *Phonetic error* or *Phonematic error* label were always considered as produced as well.

reflect articulatory precision. As expected, all models performed best with the large cohort of patients which were considered fully intelligible. The standard deviation for this category was also rather small and only increased beyond 0.1 for the Base CRNN variant. At 75% intelligibility, when some parts of the speech became difficult to understand for a human listener, most models also showed a clear drop in terms of their F-score. The only architecture that decreased by as little as 0.04 in F-score were the Base and XLSR versions of the decoder-only design. The F-scores for speakers with intelligibility ratings of 50% or 25% had larger standard deviations, indicating that the performance between different speakers showed profound variations. One major reason here might be the respective cause of the decreased intelligibility. Whilst some speakers really suffered from a very poor pronunciation, the speech samples from others had a lot of background noise or reverberations for example. Whilst this was found to be challenging for a human listener, the phoneme recognition models

turned out to still be robust enough to emit probability densities with sufficient information for the KWS modules to detect keywords reliably for some patients. The sample size for the two intelligibility categories 50 % and 25 % was also very small with 5 speakers in each set. For the sole speaker which had been annotated with 0 % intelligibility, the result w.r.t. F-score was still very high, given that according to the annotation, none of the samples was understandable for a human listener. Once again, the reason was not a very poor articulation, in which case it would most likely be impossible for any of the models to produce such a strong result. Instead, there were multiple factors which ultimately convinced the speech therapist to annotate the speaker with the lowest intelligibility rating. In many recordings, there were multiple background speakers, frequent signal peaks due to extensive finger tapping on the recording device and the individual spoke very slowly. Apparently, the intelligibility of a speaker could have an impact on the performance of KWS models, but many artifacts like background noise, an overall decreased signal quality, for example due to poor recording hardware, or secondary speakers would not necessarily lead to weaker results.

6.6 Discussion

Open-vocabulary keyword recognition was implemented in three different architectures. They relied on the outputs of a German phoneme recognizer to detect an arbitrary query phoneme sequence in an audio file. With a sophisticated training strategy, it was possible to learn the task of KWS from the context of very short audio segments, and then translate this logic to longer sequences. Test results on the German healthy dataset indicated a very strong performance of all three model variants, both in terms of precision and recall. The most difficulties were observed for very short keyword queries of lengths between 2 and 4 phoneme symbols across all models. This observation could be expected, because such short queries could easily lead to false-positive results by detecting a similar but unrelated phoneme sequence in the audio. The strong results observed with the healthy data were backed up by an analysis of the learned phonetic hyperspace, which was used by each of the models to project one-hot encoded query symbols as well as densities from the phoneme model to a common, high-dimensional space. Even though the KWS models never had access to the actual audio signal, but only to phoneme probability densities, they were able to resemble meaningful correspondences between various consonants and vowels. The ability to project similar phonemes to similar regions in the hyperspace enabled KWS models to be much more robust against noisy phoneme recognition results.

The proposed method requires either a phonetic dictionary of target words, or some form of grapheme-to-phoneme translation module. While this could be considered a minor disadvantage in terms of general accessibility, the method would allow therapists and other speech and language experts to easily account for pronunciation alternatives, for example due to a regional accent, by simply adding an according phoneme representation. If the models had been optimized to recognize query sequences of characters instead, it would be much more difficult to *transcribe* an alternative pronunciation.

It also appeared to be helpful to train KWS models only with the Base phoneme re-

cognizer. This had several advantages. The computational load of the Base model, as well as its required GPU memory, were smaller compared to that of the large XLSR recognizer. Additionally, the Base model had a higher PER, which would result in a less accurate prediction of phoneme densities. This was not a problem, but rather an advantage for training KWS models, as it required them to operate more robustly and learn which recognition errors could be tolerated and which should result in a rejection of the query. It could then be shown that for inference, the Base recognizer could simply be replaced with the XLSR version, which would slightly improve the results, without having to run extensive training procedures for the XLSR configurations.

The first experiment with the speech samples from aphasia patients revealed a clear decline in terms of precision for the prediction of correctly produced keywords. At the same time, the recall of all produced keywords was still very high, with values of up to 94% with the decoder-only model. Consequently, the models were still very much able to recognize keywords, but contrary to the healthy data, they detected many more keywords compared to what had been annotated as correctly produced by the human experts. The reason for this behavior was the fact that in the first experiment, only those items were considered as produced which did not include any kind of phonetic or phonematic error. During training, the KWS model had learned to identify a keyword query from a sequence of phoneme densities. The chance of an accidental overlap between the query and some part of the density sequence was higher for short keyword queries, thus the models learned to operate more cautiously in such a case. For long queries, however, the chance of an accidental overlap was much smaller during training. In the case of pathological speech, the probability of observing a deviation from the target keyword was much larger. On the one hand, this was the result of imprecise articulation or challenging acoustic conditions. On the other, patients sometimes only remembered parts of a keyword, or unknowingly replaced certain phonemes or syllables. As a result, the audio sample could contain a word that would not match the query sequence entirely, but still have a relatively high degree of similarity with it. This in turn would result in the KWS model to recognize the keyword as produced, simply because it had not seen incorrect productions with a high degree of similarity during training. Such behavior also explained why the precision even decreased along with an increasing number of phonemes in the keyword query. The longer the target word, the more likely it was that one or more phonemes had been modified.

The precision scores of all architectures improved slightly after all keyword productions which included phonetic errors were also considered as correctly produced. But, just like before, none of the models achieved a precision above 0.9. Interestingly, throughout the first two experiments, the CRNN model was always the one with the highest precision. However, these numbers must be looked at in more context. While having the lowest relative amount of false-positive predictions, both the Base and XLSR CRNN models had also produced the highest ratio of false-negative errors. Accordingly, their performance compared to the Transformer-based architectures was not better, they only employed a slightly shifted decision boundary.

The last experiment, during which also those productions with phonematic errors were considered as correctly produced, resulted in the precision scores to improve

even further. This clearly showed that the KWS models recognized many keyword productions as correct which had been altered on the phonetic level. This disagreement between the expected and produced phoneme sequence had to be reasonably small – the models were still able to reliably reject keyword productions with less than 50 % of phonetic overlap with the ground truth – but it enabled the system to recognize keyword productions even from those patients who suffered from a dysarthria or other type of speech impairment which would reduce their intelligibility. In this last experiment, the decoder-only architecture was the only variant which achieved precision and recall scores above 0.9. Its precision score was slightly lower compared to that of the CRNN, but the latter missed 25 % and 17 % of all produced keywords with the Base and XLSR phoneme recognizer, respectively.

The robustness against poor intelligibility was further supported by the findings from the last experiment. Once again, the Transformer-based architectures yielded stronger results, this time in terms of F1-score. The decoder-only model, despite having fewer trainable parameters, outperformed its encoder-decoder counterpart in every intelligibility category. Results showed high F1-scores with low standard deviations for intelligibility levels of 75 % and above. For lower ratings, the scores showed a greater amount of variation, because the models performed decent for some, but poor for other patients. In the presented annotation, intelligibility referred to the relative amount of speech from an individual that was considered to be recognizable for a human listener. Consequently, a low score might not exclusively refer to poor pronunciation, but could also be caused by inappropriate recording conditions, a lot of background noise or other artifacts. This also explained the high degree of variability observed in the F-measures of lower intelligibility categories. Some artifacts which reduced the perceived audio quality were easier to mitigate for the phoneme recognition models than others. The Base and XLSR variants had seen plenty of noisy audio recordings during training, hence they did not struggle to provide reliable recognition results for audio samples with poor acoustic conditions. On the other hand, if there was a secondary speaker in the background, and the phoneme sequence of the patient was superimposed by a secondary sequence from another speaker which had also been recognized, this would greatly influence the KWS performance, because the models had never seen such patterns during optimization.

Besides the recognition of a particular keyword within an audio file, it could be very helpful to reliably identify problematic patterns, such as the phonetic and phonematic errors. Some patients showed a tendency to remember parts of the target word, but not all of it. This resulted in alterations of phonemes or syllables, which would then manifest as a phonematic error. Others just had difficulties pronouncing certain phonemes, so they produced an imprecise articulation. An optimal KWS system might be able to provide feedback about such patterns. Instead of a binary (keyword produced / not produced) output, the system could provide feedback about the incorrect phonemes, or, in a more simple solution, accept the keyword as correct but indicate that the production was not optimal. One way to estimate the *goodness* of the keyword production could be the evaluation of the observed posterior probability. Ideally, it should be lower if the overlap between the query and spoken phoneme sequence reduced. However, this approach had several limitations. First of all, one of the key strengths of all presented KWS models was their ability to robustly handle

highly variable acoustic conditions, cheap recording hardware and various speaker traits. Even if the predicted phoneme densities were not perfect, for example due to background noise or other artifacts unrelated to correct pronunciation, the models were still able to reliably process the sample. However, this also would result in a decreased posterior. Another, potentially even more important consideration, should be that of the two error types. The phonetic errors were introduced due to poor articulation. The phonematic errors resulted from an incorrect production of a keyword because the patient did not remember the correct phoneme sequence. Even for experienced speech therapists, this differentiation can be difficult (as was shown earlier with the inter-rater agreement of the respective annotations). For an automated system, which also had to factor in the recognition errors coming from the phoneme model, this decision would be even more difficult. If a patient had to say the German word *Traum* (/traʊm/, English: *dream*), but the phoneme recognizer assigned most of the probability mass of the first phoneme to /d/ instead of /t/, was this the result of poor pronunciation? Did the patient not remember the correct phoneme and intentionally produced a /d/? Was the pronunciation entirely correct and the phoneme recognizer yielded a faulty prediction? According to Figure 6.10, a confusion between /t/ and /d/ was not uncommon. This differentiation is very difficult for any KWS system. Ultimately, the patient could have spoken with a regional accent. Should this pronunciation be considered incorrect then? The major problem which arose in the presented scenario is the mixture of speech and language error patterns. The assessment of an isolated speech disorder is possible if there was a sufficient margin for error coming from the phoneme model. An isolated language disorder on the other side might also be more straightforward to evaluate: If one could assume that patients had a highly accurate pronunciation, then it might be possible to attribute profound alterations in the phoneme sequence to phonematic errors more reliably. In the case of aphasia, however, many patients suffer from both a speech and language disorder. This makes the categorization of observed deviations from the target phoneme sequence extremely challenging. Given the low inter-rater agreement for phonetic ($\kappa = 0.42$) and phonematic ($\kappa = 0.00$), it would already be challenging to derive a reliable ground-truth reference in the first place.

The chapter on the analysis of word-naming exercises from aphasia patients showed how phonetic recognizers trained from healthy references could not only be used for the evaluation of speech quality. As a language disorder, aphasia primarily affected the patients' ability to correctly recall the semantic link between words and their respective meaning. By robustly modelling a German phoneme inventory, various keyword recognition models could be implemented. They did not only yield strong results in terms of precision and recall, but most importantly were able to handle any arbitrary keyword after it had been translated to a phoneme sequence, even if said keyword had never been observed before. The presented methods as well as the reported results for the three medical conditions PD, Covid-19 and aphasia will be discussed jointly in the following chapter.

Chapter 7

Discussion

In each of the three main chapters, the results had already been discussed in an isolated fashion, limiting the scope to the particular disease. This chapter should provide a global discussion of all results. The key objective is to outline strengths and weaknesses of the presented methods from each chapter. Furthermore, the global discussion focuses a lot more on the core idea of this thesis, to exclude pathological speech data from the model optimization process, and only learn from healthy reference speech.

In many recent ASR research contributions, a clear trend towards end-to-end models could be observed [Synn, Li 20a, Higu 20, Li 21, Prab 23]. These architectures are quite powerful, because they are able to learn hierarchical relationships between speech units like phonemes, syllables or words, without relying on decoupled modules, such as an acoustic model in combination with a subsequent language model. Additionally, they provide very limited access to intermediate information. Given some input signal, a highly robust end-to-end ASR model could reliably output the uttered word sequence. At the same time, despite having a powerful model, it would be impossible to extract the sequence of phonemes without any further efforts. Unsupervised optimization strategies such as the contrastive learning from quantized speech representations used for pre-training Wav2Vec 2.0 [Baev 20] enable models to interpret a signal in terms of similarly structured information units mapped to a code book. All these are mostly strategies to leverage unsupervised learning capabilities in the first place. The estimated quantized units are later dropped during fine-tuning to achieve optimal results.

Because end-to-end ASR models solve the problems of feature extraction and temporal contextualization at the same time, they could be considered black-box solutions. If we take another look at the history of monolingual phoneme- and multilingual phone-recognition models presented in 3.1 which had been implemented and trained throughout the years of groundwork for this thesis, this development towards end-to-end solutions becomes even more evident. Whilst the very first model still relied on established hand-crafted MFCC features as input, and would thus not have to learn any feature extraction itself, every new iteration of the recognizer gradually shifted towards the audio signal, using mel-spectrograms, normal spectrograms, and ultimately the raw samples. In the last case, models had to learn how to extract frequency-domain information from a time-domain signal.

The estimated vowel space of PD patients and healthy speakers, which was highly dependent on the produced formant frequencies, strongly supported the claim that end-to-end models learned frequency-domain information. A vowel triangle could be identified in a two-dimensional space acquired from a linear dimensionality reduction by PCA. The projection of other vowels, which had not been used to estimate the PCA, showed that these phones would perfectly arrange in their expected locations within the vowel trapezoid. Not only did this observation prove that there was frequency information in the intermediate feature vectors of an end-to-end model. More importantly, it turned out to be a dominating factor in the high-dimensional space. As the objective of PCA is to preserve as much variance as possible during dimensionality reduction, the strongest variance for vowels was apparently closely linked to the first and second formant frequencies.

The utilized phone recognition model had never been optimized for formant tracking. It was never given any formant or frequency information during training or inference either. And yet it encoded plenty of information related to formant frequencies in its hidden output from the convolutional feature extraction layers. This was not only a perfectly sensible observation – after all, in phonetics, different vowels are characterized by their underlying formants – supporting the idea of supervised representation learning, but it also showed that even an end-to-end model may not necessarily be a black-box. The section on PD vowel analysis did not only encompass experiments with feature vectors from the CNN layers, but also those coming from the Transformer encoder. Whilst these vectors still encoded frequency information, they had already narrowed down the influence of the first and second formant on the entire vector. Unlike the CNN features, which only encoded properties of the observed signal, the Transformer features had undergone numerous layers of temporal contextualization. As pointed out earlier, the goal of the model was not formant tracking, but phone recognition. And many of the phones in the recognizer’s inventory were consonants. Accordingly, the extracted information from the CNN layers had been processed in a way that it would converge towards a cluster in the high-dimensional space which was characteristic for said phone. However, in this high-dimensional space, formant frequencies were not a dominating factor anymore, because they would hold no meaningful information for fricatives, for example. That being said, if the model had only been trained on vowels, it would be much more likely to preserve formant information until the final linear projection for classification. Whilst clear deviations between healthy and diseased vowel realizations had been observed from the feature vectors of the CNN, these deviations seemed to have vanished in the final Transformer output. A more accurate interpretation would be that the deviations introduced by varying formant frequencies were not a dominating factor in the high-dimensional space after temporal contextualization anymore.

During the analysis of Covid-19 speech samples, the feature vectors from the Transformer turned out to be much more helpful. It could also be shown that the respiratory condition would not have a major impact on the CNN features, which were still heavily influenced by other information, such as gender. This would not mean that Covid-19 had no effect on the speech signals. However, the effects were not as pronounced as other sources of variability in the feature space. In the beginning of this thesis, the concepts of destructive and distractive noise had been explained. Both

the speaker’s gender as well as the disease state introduced some form of distractive noise, but the amount of noise originating from different genders was much stronger than that from the disease. The observable differences between healthy speakers and those suffering from a respiratory condition would likely vanish as well if any of the utilized t-SNE embeddings had been estimated with feature vectors from different phones at once. In such a case, the differences between individual phone classes themselves would have a profound impact on the embedding results, and the disease state would play an inferior role.

Two sets of feature vectors proved informative for experiments in the domains of PD and Covid-19. Let us consider the utilized phone recognition model once again as a function $f(x) = g(h(x))$ as proposed in the initial problem formulation of this thesis, where $h(x)$ represented the hidden network activation after some internal layer, and $g(h(x))$ represented the subsequent layers which complete $f(x)$. Equation 1.5 decomposed the output of $h(x)$ into a signal and a noise component. Given an estimate of an arbitrary noise profile in the form of a Gaussian mixture (Equation 1.6), this noise component effectively causes a perturbation of the clean $h(x_{signal})$ in the high-dimensional space. In most cases, noise is an undesirable byproduct of signal acquisition (or any other step within a common signal processing pipeline). However, keep in mind that the presence of a neurological or respiratory disease also introduced noise. It were the perturbations resulting from PD and Covid-19 in the high-dimensional feature space of the CNN and Transformer outputs that had been visualized by means of dimensionality reduction techniques. Furthermore, it were these perturbations which had a dominant impact on the distribution of data points. If the disease state was once again considered to be a form of distractive noise, then the impact of this distractive component was apparently strong enough to not vanish behind the many sources of destructive noise. This is an important observation, particularly in the case of Covid-19, where patients could record themselves with their own devices, similar to the data collection procedure behind Common Phone. As expected, the phone recognition model had learned during optimization how to mitigate the effect of different types of noise, which inherently occur in an acquired signal. One such type could be the microphone used for recording for example. Different microphones result in different noise patterns, but a robust approximation of $f(x)$ sufficiently mitigated the influence of the recording hardware on the final result. If $f(x)$ was decomposed into g and h , then this mitigation, which could effectively be considered a noise reduction, would take place throughout the entire forward pass. Consequently, one must expect a stronger influence of noise characteristics which are inherent to the signal in earlier layers of the entire model. In other words, if $h(x)$ resembled only the convolutional feature extraction layers of the model, the expected impact of signal-inherent noise – any noise which must necessarily be present in some form, like the microphone or a speaker’s age or gender – should be larger. This assumption aligns perfectly with the observations made for the vowel triangle in the case of PD and the t-SNE embeddings of CNN feature vectors of a single phone class in the case of Covid-19. In the former, the inherent variability of formant frequencies had been mitigated to achieve a successful classification, in the latter, the underlying gender still had a profound impact on the embedding results.

The phone recognition model’s ability to reliably process noisy audio data and ex-

tract meaningful feature vectors together with every emitted phonetic symbol made it possible to analyze large amounts of speech data on the phone-level, without having to perform any kind of manual segmentation of the sequential input signal. This was a major advantage in the case the input truly contained speech. In any other case, however, this could also be considered a disadvantage. In the case of Covid-19, for example, one might also be interested to analyze breathing and cough signals if the scope of research was not restricted to approaches on the phonetic level. In this case, the proposed model would not emit any meaningful phone symbols, simply because there were no phones in the audio file. The CTC blank token, which also serves as a rejection class, would consume almost all of the probability mass in the output layer, resulting in an empty prediction sequence. This by itself is not an undesired behavior, but it must be taken into account when using a strong feature extractor optimized on speech for signals which do not contain speech anymore. With an empty output sequence for breathing or cough signals, there are also no feature vectors available. As a workaround, one could utilize the CNN layers of the recognizer for feature extraction, but this would come with several limitations. As mentioned before, the early feature extraction layers did remove some portion of inherent signal noise, but even more of the noise was mitigated in the subsequent Transformer layers. Furthermore, the segmentation provided by the phone recognizer would also not be available. Accordingly, the acquired sequence of feature vectors would have to be partitioned into meaningful segments, for example those which contained breathing and others which contained the burst of a single cough event.

Whilst the CNN block could freely be used for feature extraction with the discussed limitations, things might look different for the Transformer layers. They had been optimized to perform a temporal contextualization suitable for the task of phone recognition. In this scope, they had certainly learned meaningful field-of-views for certain phonetic classes which the model would rely on during inference. This assumption was supported by the experiments on sustained vowel productions in Covid-19, where the model's behavior seemed to become less predictable. Despite the fact that individuals produced prolonged vowels, these events were barely recognized as elongated variants of the particular vowel class. The most likely reason was that the duration of the sustained vowel was much longer than anything the model had seen during training, hence it would not recognize the elongated vowel, but instead predict the more frequent (in terms of overall prior probability) short variant. Furthermore, the feature vectors associated with the recognized vowels held very limited information about the disease state. A subsequent analysis of the same vowels in the context of actual speech revealed that suddenly, the respiratory condition had a significant impact on the feature vectors. This was a good example which demonstrated that Transformer features should be used cautiously when the underlying signal significantly deviates from what a model has seen during training.

In the chapter about PD, it was shown that even the straightforward end-to-end output, namely the phone symbol plus its associated posterior probability, could provide meaningful insights into an individual's phonetic inventory as well as their overall intelligibility. The phonetic footprints helped to understand which categories of speech sounds were most affected by the neurological condition. Particularly in the case of dedicated speech exercises, the manifestation of PD in the phonetic footprints of

patients became clearly evident. The observed patterns would also translate over to read and spontaneous speech, where they would be less pronounced due to the lower relative frequency of the difficult speech sounds. An important observation was made in terms of how phonetic footprints should be defined. An earlier study which first introduced the idea of phonetic footprints [Klum 22b] only considered the relative frequency of occurrence. However, with the most recent iteration of the phone recognizer, the model had become so powerful that even an imprecisely articulated instance of [p], [t] or [k] could still be successfully classified as that phone. In this thesis, phonetic footprints accounted for the associated posterior probability of each phone, because a less accurate articulation of a speech sound would result in a decreased posterior probability.

Phonetic footprints were not only helpful to identify differences between healthy and pathological speech. It could also be shown that by tracking down the observed deviations to individual parts of the vocal tract, for example in terms of the place or manner of articulation, it was possible to accurately attribute an impairment to a particular morphological structure. This could prove vital to understand how a disease like PD progressed in an individual patient, and how the effect of medication would alleviate the developed symptoms. Phonetic footprints could also help to bridge the gap between digital therapy and monitoring solutions and expert speech therapists. Instead of providing a straight estimate of the disease state, phonetic footprints provide a much better insight into a patient’s phonetic inventory, while leaving any decision-making process in the hands of the speech expert.

An important advantage of the proposed phone recognizer was its high number of phonetic symbols. During optimization, this allowed the model on the one hand to make use of a larger inventory during inference, but it also meant that it had to learn much more details about speech sounds to correctly resemble their subtle differences, for example in terms of duration or nasalization of a vowel. A question which cannot fully be answered is to what extent the recognizer would make use of this inventory. For example, elongated variants of stop phones were only found in the Italian portion of the training data. If an individual from Colombia was speaking Spanish, and they were producing elongated stops, for example due to an increased effort to build up the required muscle tension, then these phones are not part of the regular phonetic inventory of Spanish. It cannot fully be answered if the model would still be able to recognize the elongated stops, or if it would reject the hypothesis of an elongated variant because it had learned that such pattern only existed in Italian. One could argue that in the case of the dedicated PD speech exercise repeating the syllable combination *pe-ta-ka*, the recognizer was able to recognize a trend towards a palatalization of the stop phone [p], which had likely been caused by the following vowel [e]. Strictly speaking, if the model had learned that certain phones only occur in certain languages, the palatalized variant of [p] should only be found in Russian. However, the contributors of the PC-GITA corpus were all native Colombian Spanish speakers. At the same time, the syllable combination *pe-ta-ka*, if spoken like [p^jetaka], would resemble valid Russian words, translating to “*no matter what*” in English. In this context, it is important to understand that while no language model had been used during the CTC decoding procedure, the model itself had learned an acoustic language model, intrinsically resembling the transition probabilities between

different phones. Given the training data, this estimate certainly reflected a multilingual instance of a language model, which would greatly reduce the encountered bias for certain language-dependant patterns such as frequent syllables. Nevertheless, it is still possible that the model would deem particular phones more likely if it had observed certain other phones in the direct neighborhood. The recognized palatalization of [p] in the speech exercise *pe-ta-ka* was not only the result of a biased prior probability, as the co-articulation could be validated acoustically in several audio recordings (e.g. *032EHC_S1_DDK3.wav*). Nonetheless, it could not entirely be ruled out that some bias introduced by the training data had also contributed to this observation. One could also argue that it had enabled the recognizer to detect this subtle change in the first place.

Whilst the large phonetic inventory turned out to be advantageous for modeling speech signals directly, it was less helpful in the scope of a language disorder like aphasia. Early experiments with the proposed KWS models revealed that the multilingual inventory contained many symbols which were irrelevant for a German-only keyword recognizer. After a reduction to the set of German phonemes, the performance of all models as well as their required training time had improved noticeably. The improvements in terms of performance (namely the F1-score of models) could be observed for two major reasons. First, the reduced set of only German phonemes made the task more simple for the model, compared to the multilingual setup. Accordingly, the PER of the base and large German models were lower than those of the corresponding multilingual versions. As the KWS models relied on an accurate phoneme recognition result, they would be able to perform better if the underlying phoneme recognizer yielded more reliable outputs. Another reason was the reduction of utilized phonetic symbols to create keyword queries. Whilst it would be possible to only utilize the set of relevant German phones (assuming the multilingual case) in the first place, one would still have to allocate indices in the one-hot encoded phonetic symbol vectors for all other non-German phones, because the densities from the recognizer and the one-hot encoded embeddings both served as input for the same linear projection layer, which expected a feature space of constant dimension.

The idea of this initial shared projection was to enable KWS models to learn similarities between different phonemes, such that the models would be able to account for any frequent confusion patterns of the underlying phoneme recognizer. A visualization of the projections of vowel and consonant one-hot encodings revealed that the individual symbols arranged meaningfully to each other. Phonemes which sounded similar, or only differed in terms of length in case of vowels, showed a close neighborhood relationship in the high-dimensional space. In combination with a sophisticated optimization strategy, this enabled all three models to achieve very strong results in terms of both precision and recall for the healthy German test data.

The experiments with the ASA-KI dataset revealed how difficult the analysis of speech signals from aphasia patients could be. In the case of healthy speakers, the presence of a keyword had to be modelled artificially: To simulate the case that a particular keyword had not been produced, the query simply contained another valid word from the training dataset, which did not occur in the audio sample. In terms of pronunciation and phonetic correctness, errors were limited mostly to imprecise recognition results which were successfully modeled by the systems, or simply noisy

acoustic conditions. Hence, during training, none of the models had seen samples in which a participant had mixed up the order of phonemes, omitted or inserted a syllable, or made any other mistake which would be common in a language disorder. Consequently, it would not be a surprise if models were either not able to detect the altered keyword productions, or would detect far more keywords as valid realizations, which were actually only close approximations of the target word. Findings revealed that the latter was the case: Whilst the recall scores had decreased compared to the results on healthy data, the decline in precision was much more pronounced in all proposed architectures. The KWS models frequently considered keyword productions which were not entirely correct as valid if they sounded sufficiently similar to the target query. In this context, it was impossible for the models to interpret what the deviation from the query had resulted from. Was it solely an imprecise pronunciation due to an articulatory deficit? In this case, the keyword should be accepted, as the system should be capable to tolerate speech deficits which are frequent in patients who suffered a stroke or other type of brain injury. Or did the patient not remember the correct word, and had only produced some phonetically similar instance? This would be a clear aphasia-induced language deficit, and the item should be rejected. The very low inter-rater agreement observed in the manual annotations from two speech therapists already indicated that this decision was incredibly difficult, even for the human experts. In addition to that, the KWS models only had access to the results from two phoneme recognizers, which, at best, had an error rate of 7.8%. This was already a strong PER result, but it still meant that on average, one in every thirteen phonemes was wrong, apart from the fact that these numbers were computed for healthy speakers.

When certain types of minor keyword production errors were considered as valid realizations, the precision scores of all models improved, because many of the false positive predictions were the result of close approximations of the exercise item. This further confirmed the difficulties of correctly differentiating between error patterns resulting from speech and language deficits. At the same time, it could be shown that the Transformer-based models were much more capable of dealing with altered keyword realizations, detecting many more of those items which were produced with a phonetic or phonematic error. The CRNN model improved markedly in terms of recall score (see Table 6.12) when the more potent XLSR phoneme recognizer was used. While this by itself was good, it also showed that the architecture was much more dependent on accurate phoneme recognition results. In general, results revealed that it was clearly possible to reliably detect keywords even in pathological speech, but the presence of both a speech and language impairment would greatly influence those results. Furthermore, a clear limitation of all proposed systems was their inability to provide feedback in terms of pronunciation correctness. Given a minor deviation between the target keyword and the respective realization from the patient, it was not possible to identify whether said error was caused by a speech or language problem, or simply by an incorrect phoneme recognition.

On the subset of patients who had been annotated in terms of intelligibility, the Transformer-based models outperformed the CRNN. It could be shown that even for patients who were difficult to understand, the models were still able to produce meaningful results on average. The rate of success also depended on the root cause of

why the intelligibility had declined. Once again, in the case of aphasia, the annotated score did not indicate the quality of pronunciation, but the overall amount of speech that was understandable in the first place. Consequently, even if patients had some difficulties to speak, they might still be assessed with a 100 % intelligibility rating. If said rating had decreased, this could be for various reasons. For some speakers, there was a large amount of background noise, for example coming from a TV or another person in the same room. This was very difficult for all KWS models, because the phoneme recognizer would emit many more symbols which were not produced by the patient, but by another instance.

Looking at all experiments together, the decoder-only model had yielded the strongest results of all architectures. Additionally, it was the model with the lowest computational load. All three implementations showed that they were capable of an open-vocabulary keyword recognition. Furthermore, the phonetic approach held several advantages, such that the systems were able to learn which phonemes were similar to each other and thus more likely to be confused. It was also possible to train all models only with the lightweight version of the phoneme recognizer, and then adopt the much larger model during inference, without requiring any further adjustments. Lastly, decoupling the phoneme recognizer from the KWS logic resulted in much smaller models for the latter component. The KWS modules comprised between 2 to 9 million parameters, approximately, making them significantly smaller compared to the utilized phoneme recognizers.

The following chapter will summarize the key findings of this work once again to outline how the presented methods could help improve the quality of care in the context of speech and language therapy. Furthermore, it draws a conclusion about how phonetic information was used successfully to gain a better understanding of pathological speech and language with ML models that had been trained only with healthy reference data, while also highlighting potential future research directions which could be grounded on the results of this work.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Outlook

Regardless of the domain, whenever modern deep learning architectures are utilized to solve a particular ML problem, they introduce a tremendous amount of parameters which need to be optimized. At the same time, the larger the underlying model, the more data is required to successfully estimate a valid, well-generalizing decision function. Unsupervised pre-training strategies have further leveraged the capabilities of complex models [Erha 10, Caro 19, Schn 19, Jian 20, Hsu 21]. On the one hand, they enable systems to explore the structure of data in an unbiased fashion. In speech processing, for example, during unsupervised pre-training, a model could learn representations of different parts of a waveform, while at the same time performing contextualization of said representations to draw conclusions about temporal relationships. All this is possible without learning any downstream task, such as phoneme recognition or full-fledged ASR, which would naturally introduce a bias towards that domain. Another reason why unsupervised pre-training methods became so popular is that they lifted an important restriction of supervised methods: The availability of annotated data. In most cases, the amount of data that had been annotated for a particular task is much smaller than the amount of data that was generally available. By lifting this restriction, it is possible to incorporate many more samples, for example audio recordings or images, during the initial training stage.

While the ability to robustly train larger models with decent generalization has led to many new state-of-the-art results in terms of various, task-specific metrics, these new architectures often lacked interpretability. Deep learning models were never known to provide explainable solutions in the first place, but the trend towards large-scale end-to-end systems greatly reduced access to the different stages of a traditional ML pipeline [Maie 19]. In many disciplines, for example in the medical domain, the explainability of a result is at least as important as the bare result itself. Whenever the associated cost of an incorrect decision of an ML model is high, explainable systems enable engineers to identify potential edge-cases and general limitations. In that sense, ML models could be considered airplanes. In case of an accident, investigators need to identify the chain of events that had led to the event. If they successfully identified the root cause, the issue, whatever it might be, could be addressed to prevent further accidents in the future. If the search for said cause was unsuccessful, however, the entire fleet could be grounded until the problem had been identified and resolved. What applies in aviation also applies in the discipline of ML to a certain

extent. While the domain still lacks powerful regulations which had been in place for decades (like in aviation), new solutions often compete with traditional, well-established methods. If an ML model operated in an unreliable or incomprehensible way, its users could quickly revert back to a traditional approach.

One important goal of this thesis was to analyze pathological speech signals in an interpretable way, while still making use of the most recent advances in ML. As mentioned earlier, modern methods require a vast amount of training data, which was not available for any of the discussed diseases. Instead of adjusting the optimization schemes to prevent overfitting, generating large amounts of synthetic data or trying to merge many different datasets for one particular medical condition to ultimately be able to train a state-of-the-art architecture with pathological speech data, this study proposed to do the exact opposite: Training all models exclusively with speech samples from healthy speakers, while entirely leaving out any pathological signals during optimization. To facilitate such an approach, the model would have to learn a more general task which was unrelated to any kind of disease in the first place. In this study, the proposed high-level problem was the recognition of phones, units of distinct sounds used to produce human speech. Training a model on such high-level task held the advantage that the general availability of data would not be a problem. Accordingly, it was possible to show the system several thousand different speakers during fine-tuning, let alone the even greater number of speakers it had already explored during the (multilingual) pre-training stage.

As the phone recognition model had also been exposed to countless combinations of recording hardware, acoustic environments, languages and sentences, it had developed a high degree of robustness. This was incredibly important, as it would enable the system to process not only those audio files collected in a clean recording setup, but also other samples which, for example, were recorded by the patients themselves, in their home environment using their own devices. Many algorithms which had been designed to process pathological speech were optimized with in-domain data. Consequently, they almost always lack the ability to transfer their knowledge over to unseen datasets of the same medical condition. This problem was also observed in studies which had been discussed in the literature reviews of PD ([Amat 21]) and aphasia ([Le 16]). Ironically, the reason for this problem lies in one of their key strengths of neural networks: Deep architectures are very potent in utilizing any information helpful to minimize the prediction error during training, however, this powerful behavior quickly backfires in the presence of even the slightest systematic differences between healthy and diseased speakers in a pathological speech dataset. These differences would also be learned and exploited by a model in order to reduce the classification error.

In this context, let us also revisit the definition of destructive and distractive noise from chapter 2: “*On the one hand, there is destructive noise, which occurs randomly and could be the result of any process which is independent of the original signal. Additionally, there is distractive noise, which is a by-product of the undistorted signal*”. If an ML model had been successfully optimized with a small dataset of pathological speech to classify a particular medical condition, what could be said about the respective noise types? In terms of destructive noise, all recordings within the said corpus were likely captured with the same microphone, maybe even in the same acoustic

environment. This helps to mitigate the influence of said noise type on the obtained experiment results. On the side of distractive noise, the pathological speech dataset did (almost certainly) not include several thousand unique speakers. As a result of the little amount of perturbation introduced by destructive and distractive noise, a good amount of variance in the feature space could be attributed to the signal of interest (in our example case, this is the pathology). This is desired for experiments under laboratory conditions, but whenever the ML model would process a new sample from an unseen dataset which suddenly lies outside of this small hyperspace spanned by the low variance, it enters an unseen part of the feature space. The behavior of our ML model in this unexplored region is unpredictable. The high degree of robustness of the proposed phone recognizer could only be achieved by allowing the system to explore a large amount of the potential feature space, which had strongly been influenced by both destructive and distractive noise. For example, if the model was shown a new speaker, it had likely seen other speakers already which had a very similar pitch, speech rate or recorded audio with the same background environment such as traffic noise or singing birds. None of this would be new for the model, hence it could reliably produce recognition results.

In the proposed setup, all that had ever been used during parameter optimization was data from healthy individuals. This begged the question: How could it be possible to analyze pathological speech with a model that had never learned anything about pathologies in the first place? This was the point where phonetics came into play. The outputs of the phone recognition model could be considered as plain class indices, but in fact, they held much more information. Every recognized phone could be interpreted in much more detail: If it was a vowel, it encoded rich information about the tongue configuration during production in terms of position and elevation. Furthermore, the vowel could be nasalized, rounded, or elongated. If the phone was a fricative, it could be characterized by its unique place and manner of articulation. Additional properties such as the presence of voicing or some form of co-articulation further describe the observed speech sound. The phone recognition model with its 100 unique symbols (excluding silence) provided rich insights into a particular speech signal on a phonetic level. The different classes which could be predicted by the recognizer were not just independent categories. Instead, they could be categorized in various ways to further structure the extracted information. For example, [d] is a plosive, whereas [n] is a nasal, but both are voiced and share the same place of articulation (alveolar).

For the analysis of PD, phonetic insights greatly helped to understand how the neurological disorder affected the speech of patients. In the scope of this thesis, the primary goal was not to identify any new, previously unreported effects of a disease, but to show that known influences could be observed without ever using pathological speech data during model training. The manifestation of PD in the phonetic footprints, mean recognition confidences and the estimated vowel space was expected, but all these observations could be made without touching any PD data. On the one hand, this approach simplified the training process, because it was not necessary to worry about any data shortage. More importantly, the observed results are very likely to be transferable to other datasets as well. That is because the utilized system had never learned anything from the PD corpus and was only used for inference. One

more important advantage of the phone recognition model and the derived analysis methods for PD was that they would yield highly explainable results for the medical expert. As discussed before, black-box solutions, which output a posterior probability for a given disease, or predict an estimate of how a medical condition had progressed, greatly lack the ability to explain the observed results, or even provide any sort of justification for the particular decision that had been made. If a model, instead of solving the decision-making process itself, yielded descriptive outputs such as phonetic footprints or visualizations of the vowel space, any speech therapist could make much more use of the information. Furthermore, it would be possible to summarize the observations collected over the course of several days or weeks in just a few tables, which provided helpful insights for the medical expert about the phonation and articulation of a PD patient.

Information about therapy success is relevant to the treating physician, but it can also play an important role in keeping patients motivated to continuously work on their speech or language disorder. With the current advances in generative language models, it could be possible to briefly summarize the therapy progress in a few sentences. Such a message could be formulated in a way that it is much easier for a patient to understand, leaving out high-level medical terminology and instead relying on a simple, straightforward wording. The interaction with such a generative agent could even go beyond the scope of providing information to the patient's therapy progress. Engaging in conversations can help individuals to exercise on both their speech and language production and understanding. And at the same time, the speech signal from any spoken dialogue, even if it was conducted outside of a dedicated therapy session, could be evaluated with tools presented throughout this work, like phonetic footprints or an analysis of the available vowel space. The scenarios in which a patient has to produce free speech are the ones which matter the most to them, because they enable individuals to participate in social interactions much more effectively.

The main motivation for the brief chapter about Covid-19 was to analyze whether the respiratory condition would leave a distinct pattern in the speech of infected individuals. According to many other studies, it was possible not only to identify Covid-19 positive speakers, but also to clearly separate them from several other respiratory conditions. The presented results indicated profound effects of the respiratory condition on many phones, but at the same time, it was never possible to clearly separate between Covid-19 and other conditions, such as a sore throat or a common cold. While minor deviations were observed, some of which even found to be significant, the effect sizes in the two-dimensional embedding space were very small. Consequently, because t-SNE embeddings aim to preserve as many of the stochastic neighborhood relationships as possible from the original feature space, a clear separation of feature vectors from a sore throat and an infection with SARS-CoV-2 should not be expected.

With the findings from this thesis, the presence of distinct Covid-19 patterns cannot be ruled out. At the same time, the results illustrated very clearly how it may still be possible to report promising results for the task of Covid-19 classification. Given the distribution of healthy speakers and the different respiratory conditions in the Coswara dataset, all that would be required was a binary classifier which only indicated the presence of any disease. To produce more meaningful results, it might be necessary to restructure the relevant datasets entirely: The healthy reference group

should only be used in the comparison with fully asymptomatic Covid-19 patients, which did not develop any symptoms. On the other hand, the classification of patients who tested positive for the condition should be evaluated against an equal representation of numerous other diseases which affect the respiratory system in various ways, such as the ones reflected in the Coswara corpus. Only if a model was able to identify Covid-19 successfully as in one of the presented setups, it could likely be considered helpful.

From a phonetic point of view, the analysis had shown that many voiced sounds were influenced by a respiratory disease. At the same time, another group strongly affected speech sounds were nasals. For a common cold, this seemed reasonable, but in the case of Covid-19, this was a surprising observation, mainly because medical studies had reported that nasal symptoms such as sneezing or a congestion were less common in the disease. The findings in this thesis suggest that there likely was some effect on phones which required an unrestricted air stream through the nasal cavity. The group of velar phones was poorly represented in English, with only the [k] occurring in sufficient frequency that an embedding could be estimated. Velar speech sounds had previously been identified to carry rich information about the presence of an infection in the respiratory tract [Klum 21], particularly the fricative [x]. This also implied that the detection of such medical conditions could closely be linked to the underlying language of a speech sample. The velum is located quite far in the back of the oral cavity (see Figure 2.19), hence it appeared reasonable that a respiratory condition could have a profound impact in this area. A language like German with more velar phones ([g], [k], [x], [ŋ]) in its inventory could potentially be analyzed more reliably compared to English, for example.

The Covid-19 experiments once more highlighted a key strength of the presented phonetic analysis approach: Without requiring manual investigation of hours of speech data, it was possible to quickly reveal undocumented patterns in the utilized dataset. At no time, participants were explicitly instructed to perform the counting exercise in English. Consequently, some users had counted in their native language, and not in English, like the majority. The frequent presence of phones which were not required for the English counting task had indicated that other languages were present as well. While the dataset provided annotation about a contributor's home country, it would not document the language in which they had performed the speech tasks. This could obviously become a problem whenever there was a systematic difference between the prevalence of Covid-19 in different languages, as it would allow a model to exploit language information to better classify the respiratory condition. In the presented experiments, however, this turned out not to be the case.

Lastly, the presented phone recognizer was used in the scope of a language rather than a speech disorder. For the application with German aphasia patients, it turned out to be helpful to reduce the phone recognition model to only the inventory of German phonemes, making the task of finding keywords more robust. At the same time, despite transitioning from purely speech- towards a more language-related problem, the core idea was to preserve the motivation of incorporating phonetic knowledge estimated over a large cohort of healthy speakers. Instead of learning a large inventory of potential keywords during training, the presented architectures applied an open-vocabulary approach. Target words were modeled as sequences of the underly-

ing German phonemes, which could then be retrieved by the KWS logic. Phonetic knowledge also played a major role in the model design of all proposed architectures. By using a shared projection layer for the phoneme probability densities as well as for the one-hot encoded symbols of the keyword query, all models were able to learn which sounds were phonetically similar. These similarities could be derived from uncertainties and confusions in the predicted phoneme sequences. Ultimately, the three architectures were able to be much more tolerant w.r.t. imprecise articulation or poor phoneme recognition results. This could be demonstrated with the healthy test data: Almost every keyword query was successfully recognized, while maintaining a very low false positive rate at the same time.

When the proposed models were fed with speech data from aphasia patients, it became very clear that the combination of a language disorder, a frequently co-occurring speech disorder and the omnipresent recognition uncertainties coming from the phoneme model posed a very difficult problem for any ML approach. Even before the first experiments, the inter-rater agreements of the ASA-KI dataset indicated that the clear distinction between speech- and language-related error patterns was extremely difficult. When only perfect realizations of keywords had been considered as correct productions, all proposed models were well able to detect the respective items in the audio samples. At the same time, however, they yielded many more false positive results. This was caused by many close-to-perfect productions, which had been recognized as valid keyword events. The difficulty, for ML models as well as for human speech experts, was to differentiate which of those errors were caused by an incorrect language understanding, and which were the result of poor pronunciation. In the case of the former, the production should be rejected, but otherwise, a decreased intelligibility should be tolerated. By extending the set of keywords which were considered as correctly produced by all those which included minor pronunciation or language errors, the results in terms of precision and recall became more balanced. It also turned out that the models which relied on Transformer modules were able to outperform the more traditional CRNN approach. From the current literature, no keyword recognition model for aphasic speech could be found which would yield precision and recall values above 90 %. More importantly, these results were obtained for smartphone recordings collected in the patient's home environment, without any controlled recording conditions. The fact that the systems were able to process any arbitrary keyword query, thus being able to also reliably recognize new keywords which had never been seen during training, greatly improved the accessibility of the method. In terms of explainability, the most important contribution was the clear separation between the phoneme recognition module and the KWS logic. After all, this enabled the expert to retrieve the predicted phoneme sequence, making it much more easy to understand why a false positive or false negative result was observed. For all three discussed pathologies, phonetic analysis methods turned out to produce meaningful and interpretable results. The reference models utilized throughout the experiments had never seen any relevant amounts of pathological speech data during training – of course it remains impossible to rule out the presence of any pathology in a crowd-sourced dataset like Common Phone – and yet were able to provide very good insights into how a disease would affect the human speech production. Deep neural networks could often be considered black box solutions, particularly in the

case of end-to-end architectures. This thesis has shown that it was possible to utilize even the intermediate results from such end-to-end model to gain valuable insights into a time-domain signal. Furthermore, the foundation on phonetics greatly helped to understand and interpret many of the observed results. The phonetic inventory and vowel space of PD patients, the effects of a respiratory condition, or the ability to recognize a particular word despite suffering from aphasia and maybe even a co-occurring speech deficit, all of this was possible using large, state-of-the-art deep models which had been optimized only with healthy speech. This was an important contribution not only in terms of circumventing the problem of data shortage and poor generalization in many pathology-related research questions, but it also showed that the proposed models provided much more information than just a plain phone sequence.

Building on the findings presented in this study, one could think of various follow-up research questions which should be addressed in future works. For example, it would be helpful to find out if the proposed system could also be applied successfully to speech signals of children. Compared to other age groups, children were poorly represented in the Common Phone corpus. Speech, as most other bio-signals as well, experiences various transformations during aging. The speech characteristics of children and adolescents can once again be considered as manifestations of distractive noise. Consequently, if an ML model had seen insufficient amounts of training examples to explore said distractive noise types, it would likely operate less robust for those speakers. At the same time, this thesis showed that recognizers optimized with Common Phone were well capable to process speech recordings from elderly speakers, and their age group also lacks a very strong representation in the healthy reference data. To evaluate the abilities of the proposed system on pathological childhood speech, it could be very interesting to transfer some of the analysis methods, for example phonetic footprints, over to the domain of articulatory deficits caused by cleft lip and palate.

In a broader context, a follow-up study could also address the question how native speakers of a particular language utilize a phones which are not part of their language's phonetic inventory. The recognizer proposed in this work was capable of detecting about a hundred different unique speech sounds. None of the six languages from the training corpus came close to utilizing the entire inventory. Consequently, it could be quite interesting to evaluate under which circumstances and to what extent speakers would make use of phones which do not belong to the native inventory of their language. Such an analysis should not be limited to the scope of pathological speech, because other factors, for example accented pronunciation from non-native speakers, could play an important role, too. Particularly in the case of free speech, a better understanding of the utilization of native and foreign phonetic inventories could provide further insights about how a pathology affected the speech production. One last potential research question which could be derived from this work might push the boundaries of the proposed learning scheme: To increase the amount of available training data, all parameters of models presented throughout this work had been optimized exclusively with healthy speech samples. Instead of learning any knowledge about speech pathologies, the recognizers had to predict the correct sequence of speech sounds in an audio file. Consequently, the training data had to feature

some sort of phonetic annotation. What if such annotation was only available for a portion of the training data? What if one wanted to include speech recordings from other languages, for which no phonetic annotation was available? Self-supervised optimization strategies were already used successfully to learn hidden representations of speech signals [Baev 20, Hsu 21, Lee 22] without requiring labelled data. Such self-supervised learning methods, in combination with clustering strategies, could also be used to enable future recognition models to infer phone classes at training time, even if the classes had never been annotated in the provided data. To preserve valuable phonetic information, a newly inferred class could be encoded in terms of various phonetic properties, which would later help to estimate the true underlying speech sound. In simple words, the model would be able to extend the known and annotated phone inventory with additional classes of speech sounds and provide a meaningful background context about each new class, such as its type (consonant or vowel), and type-related information, like the estimated place and manner of articulation for a consonant. A recognizer which would be able to dynamically extend its phonetic inventory could provide an even better resolution in terms of the many possible pronunciation details, and ultimately, these small details might play an important role in the analysis of pathological speech signals later on.

Given the rapid progress of current ML research, the models used throughout this thesis are likely going to be outdated in a few years. At the same time, the task of phoneme (or multilingual phone) recognition will remain relevant, and with new models at hand, it might be possible to gain even better insights into pathological speech. The large Wav2Vec 2.0 XLSR phone recognizer with its more than 300 million parameters was anything but a lightweight architecture. A potential next *big leap* in deep learning might not come in the form of yet another generation of even more powerful Transformers. Instead, any reduction in the number of required trainable parameters would hold many more advantages: Lower computational complexity and memory requirements, less overfitting and better generalization. In the future, it might further be possible to decouple logic from memory, such that an ML architecture only had to learn the former, and could dynamically adjust to the latter during runtime. After all, the process of speech acquisition does not require an infant to listen to many thousands of different speakers to develop a robust speech understanding. This problem of deriving general concepts from a closed set of observations has not been solved yet. The introductory chapter briefly introduced the example of a neural network capable of recognizing cars in photographic images. Most of these models would not be able to make sense of any simple hand-drawn images. In that regard, current ML algorithms are able to yield very strong results in their particular task, but at the cost of a very narrow understanding beyond their explored environment. Up to this point, it is the ability to define reasonable expectations for the unknown, unexplored and undiscovered, that subordinates the machine to the human being.

In the last chapter of the thesis follows a summary of the contents presented throughout this work. It will briefly go over the main motivation and problem formulation, and also outline the core topics from the theoretical background. The methods and results for each pathology will once again be described, following a roundup of the discussion and outlook. The chapter is not intended to be a plain recapitulation of each section, but should instead reflect the core messages and findings from this thesis

while encouraging the reader to dive deeper. In the last chapter of the thesis follows a summary of the contents presented throughout this work. It will briefly go over the main motivation and problem formulation, and also outline the core topics from the theoretical background. The methods and results for each pathology will once again be described, following a roundup of the discussion and outlook. The chapter is not intended to be a plain recapitulation of each section, but should instead reflect the core messages and findings from this thesis while encouraging the reader to dive deeper.

Chapter 9

Summary

For several years, people can use smart speech-recognition-based assistants on their smartphones or at home. Their robustness has increased markedly even under challenging acoustic conditions. And the release of *ChatGPT* in late 2022 marked an important milestone in the development of language models (LM). For the first time, the general public had access to a generative LM which featured an unmatched experience in terms of natural language understanding and production. Soon – this was resonating with fear and anticipation at the same time – artificial intelligence could take over many complex tasks and make human experts obsolete. While this assumption might be valid for some disciplines, we still have a long road ahead of ourselves in many others. Be it robust speech recognition or generative language modelling: The foundation for all major breakthroughs of the past couple years was the utilized training data. The state of the art method of choice for many machine learning (ML) problems are deep neural networks (DNN). The corresponding discipline of deep learning (DL) has defined new standards in terms of the required number of trainable model parameters and, consequently, the amount of training data. General purpose automatic speech recognition (ASR) or generative LMs require a tremendous quantity of samples to learn from: DL models have to explore vast amounts of the feature space during optimization to produce a robust result, simply because DNNs lack the ability to extrapolate knowledge into unexplored hyperspaces at inference time. Consequently, if the available amount of training data is small, it is impossible to rely on such same parameter-intensive architectures without experiencing overfitting problems, during which the model does not learn valid decision rules anymore, but instead memorizes specific patterns of individual training examples. A good example for a limited availability of data is pathological speech. Understandably, datasets collected from Parkinson’s (PD), stroke or cleft lip and palate patients are quite a lot smaller (several hours of recorded audio) compared to modern ASR datasets (many thousands of hours).

However, the shortage of data is only one out of several limitations. Suppose that we had access to a sufficiently large PD speech corpus to train a modern end-to-end architecture. The resulting model would consume the raw audio signal as a time series, and at the end output a posterior probability that the recorded person suffered from PD or not. Even if this recognizer operated highly accurate, it would always leave the medical experts wondering: *How did the model come to its conclusion?* Apart from

the raw performance of ML architectures, the explainability of their emitted results plays a major role in medical (and other critical) applications. If an at-home smart assistant recognized a spoken command incorrectly, the consequences are small. If a similar model wrongfully diagnosed a PD patient as healthy, the individual might not be given appropriate care. Therefore, black-box architectures are likely not the solution for critical tasks, such as the analysis of pathological speech and language. The goal of this thesis was to overcome the presented restrictions in terms of data availability and model explainability, while still relying on the most recent advances in ML research.

On the first glance, it might seem counterintuitive that the shortage of training data was solved by omitting even the little amount of recorded pathological speech that had been available for training. Instead, all parameters of the proposed models had been optimized exclusively with recordings from healthy speakers. After all, large amounts of data were available for this group, which would benefit the model in terms of robustness. In that context, this thesis introduced the concept of distractive and destructive noise. In general, every part of a signal which does not convey the encoded information can be considered noise. Distractive noise is that portion which is a natural by-product of the signal. In speech, this is for example a speaker's fundamental frequency, pronunciation patterns from a local accent, or any other property which could characterize the speaker. On the other hand, destructive noise is not an inherent part of the original signal, and it usually appears randomly, for example background noise or recording artifacts. By allowing the model to explore a vast variety of different speakers, acoustic conditions and recording setups, it is more likely to be able to process unseen manifestations of distractive noise (for example in the form of a certain speaker trait). At the same time, the presence of different types and amounts of destructive noise should not hinder the model from operating robustly. Because pathological data was excluded from training, it would not be possible to train any sort of binary (healthy vs. diseased) classification model. That is why an auxiliary objective was required for which the model could be optimized, one that could be learned from healthy speech signals and that could also be applied to pathological speech.

This is where phonetics came into play, the science of human speech sounds. It aims to interpret speech as a sequence of sounds, also referred to as phones, and describes these phones in terms of their acoustic or articulatory characteristics. For one particular language, one can define the inventory of speech sounds which occur in said language, as a closed set of phonemes. It is the set of speech entities which are used to differentiate between words within the framework of the particular language. Phonemes are defined per language because it is possible that more than one phone can be used to produce the same phoneme, and hence would not change the meaning of the spoken word. In British English for example, the phoneme /t/ in *button* could be pronounced either with an unvoiced alveolar stop [t] or with a glottal stop [ʔ]. Consequently, whenever one wants to describe the phonetic inventory of more than just a single language, the more distinct definition of phones should be applied. Optimizing an ML model for the task of recognizing the uttered series of phones in a speech signal had several advantages. The science of phonetics could help to draw many more conclusions about the observed speech signal based on the characteristics

of the spoken phones, because it does not only interpret them as independent classes, but further enriches each class with information, such as whether a sound is voiced, insights about the tongue configuration or the involvement of certain articulators. Furthermore, phones can be observed in any speech signal, even in the scope of dedicated speech exercises, which would not necessarily rely on the defined vocabulary of a language. Lastly, and this would be a major leap towards more explainable AI algorithms, any conclusion about the presence or progression of a disease drawn from insights gathered with a phone recognizer would enable medical experts to understand on what information a classifier based its decision.

The experiments presented throughout this thesis were based on important existing ML methods. Traditional algorithms such as support vector machines (SVM) for classification, principal component analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction or Viterbi’s algorithm for sequence decoding were explained. Additionally, because a better part of this work relied on DL, many core concepts for the implementation and optimization of neural networks were introduced. Among them were the back-propagation algorithm for model training based on the idea of gradient descent as well as different activation functions. A key foundation of DNNs that was also discussed in this context was the universal approximation theorem: Every neural network can be considered a sequence of simple linear functions, which would ultimately be able to approximate any non-linear decision function. And because such a function approximator can be exposed to various kinds of data, different types of input features favor different neural network designs. For example, neighboring pixels in an image form a spatial context together, which can be extracted with a convolution layer. And the changes between measurements at subsequent points of a time series can be evaluated with a recurrent neural network cell. Ultimately, a tool for both spatial and temporal contextualization is described: The Transformer architecture relies on a neural attention mechanism, which allows it to pay attention to specific parts of an input signal, depending on how relevant that part might be at the current position. Many state-of-the-art DL architectures make use of Transformers, and so did the phone recognizer which had been implemented in the scope of this work.

It is based on the Wav2Vec2 [Baev 20] architecture and was trained via an alignment-free optimization scheme. The model would output the recognized sequence of phone symbols from the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA), along with two kinds of feature vectors (FV) per detected phone. The first came from the very early convolutional layers and encoded rich information about the input signal. The second FV was collected after the Transformer layers, hence it contained much more higher-level information about the current phone as well as its phonetic neighborhood. Instead of optimizing a randomly initialized version, a warmed-up checkpoint of the model had been fine-tuned to recognize 101 unique IPA phones. The checkpoint was published by *Facebook AI*¹ and stored the parameters of the model after self-supervised pre-training with speech recordings from 53 languages. For fine-tuning, this study employed the *Common Phone* (CP) corpus, a refined variant of *Mozilla’s Common Voice* dataset. CP comprises six languages, is fully gender-balanced and features an automatically generated phonetic annotation. The resulting multilingual phone recognizer achieved a phone error rate (PER) of 9.2% on the test split of CP. The

¹Now *Meta AI*

corresponding source code as well as the model parameters were also made available online.

In the first experiment, the goal was to analyze speech recordings from patients suffering from Parkinson's Disease (PD). PD is a neurodegenerative disease which affects the basal ganglia in the human brain. Due to a lack of the neurotransmitter dopamine, patients gradually lose their motor abilities over the course of years. Because speech production requires a significant amount of fine-motor control, it is often affected as the severity of PD progresses, resulting in a slurred, imprecise articulation and a monotonous voice for example. The utilized PD dataset had been collected from Latin American Spanish speakers and contained PD patients as well as healthy controls (HC), who all contributed recordings of dedicated speech exercises, isolated sentences, a read text as well as a monologue. All speech samples had been annotated in terms of the modified Frenchay Dysarthria Assessment (mFDA), an evaluation of the quality of speech production in terms of the various involved articulators. To analyze how individuals utilized different categories of phones in certain tasks, this work proposed the application of phonetic footprints. Those footprints encode the average posterior probability of a particular phone (or category) observed within a speech recording. For the dedicated speech exercises, participants had to articulate different consonant-vowel clusters, hence it was possible to reduce the number of expected phones to a small set. Through phonetic footprints, it could be shown that as the speech deficits progressed, patients produced significantly less unvoiced stops, phones which require some degree of muscle tension, among all speech exercises. They also became less stable in producing the correct target vowel. This by itself was an important observation, but even more importantly, the results could be closely linked to the individual articulators which were involved in the production of the respective stops [p], [t] and [k]. This could enable medical experts to draw conclusions about the state of individual morphological structures in the vocal tract from phonetic footprints.

Because PD patients would gradually develop articulatory deficits as the condition progresses, those imprecisions in pronunciation should also be reflected in the recognition confidences of the proposed model. In fact, mean confidences correlated with the total mFDA scores by up to -0.63 (Spearman). A high confidence would correspond to a lower total mFDA score, because increasing mFDA indicated a stronger impairment, hence the correlation is expected to be negative. The prediction confidences can be noisy for many reasons, and the analysis of confidence scores over time revealed one scenario which would cause the model to suddenly emit phones with a lower posterior probability: During the text reading exercise, participants had to imitate a dialogue between a doctor and a patient. At one point, the dialogue demanded a change of intonation, which had a profound impact on the observed confidences which dropped markedly among all speakers, PD as well as HC.

Because PD affected not only the articulation, but also the voice of patients, this study proposed to estimate the vowel space of individual speakers through the collected feature vectors of certain phones. Vowels can be characterized by the openness of the vocal tract as well as the position (back to front) of the narrowest constriction formed with the tongue. And their production directly influences the resulting formants, accumulations of energy in certain frequency bands. If a vowel is produced

more openly, the first formant increases. The same holds for the second formant if the position of the vowel moves further to the front. Consequently, one can define the vowels of an individual language which are the most open/closed or front/back version, and any other vowel can be found somewhere in between. In case of the Spanish PD dataset, these vowels [i], [u] and [a] formed a triangle. By using the signal-level FVs from the recognizer, it was possible to estimate the space of said triangle for speaker groups, but also individual speakers. It was shown that the annotated monotonicity of PD patients resulted in a markedly reduced area spanned by the vowel triangle of said speakers. With the proposed estimate of the available vowel space, it was also possible to analyze patient recordings which had been collected over the course of sixteen sessions distributed over several days in their individual homes. The estimated vowel space correlated with the annotated total mFDA score over time by up to -0.81 (Pearson).

Against the background of the recent Covid-19 pandemic, this thesis also investigated how a respiratory disease affected the speech production of infected individuals. Several scientific contributions had already concluded that the accurate detection of an infection with SARS-CoV-2 was possible. Instead of building yet another Covid-19 classifier, the aim of this study was to gain a better understanding of how the disease affected individual speech sounds. Furthermore, the goal was to identify significant differences between healthy speakers and those suffering from Covid-19 to determine if these differences were unique in the pandemic disease. If this was the case, the differences should also be observable between Covid-19 patients and those who suffered from any other respiratory condition, such as the common cold, to allow for meaningful prediction results.

The analysis was based on t-SNE embeddings – a dimensionality reduction technique which aims to preserve the neighborhood relationships between samples in the high-dimensional space – using the convolutional and Transformer-based FVs from the phone recognizer. It quickly became apparent that any disease-related patterns in the convolutional FVs were superimposed by signal-level information about the fundamental frequency of speakers. Consequently, further experiments included only FVs from the last Transformer layer. It could be shown that numerous vowels (e.g. [e], [o]) and consonants (e.g. [m], [n], [r]) were affected by the presence of a respiratory disease. However, the observed differences between Covid-19 patients and healthy reference speakers were mostly larger than those between Covid-19 patients and others who only suffered from the common cold. Particularly for both nasal consonants [m] and [n], the likely explanation was straightforward: Both conditions could lead to a blocked nose, and the resulting effect on the speech production was identical.

Only for the two vowels [e] and [o], it was possible to find significant differences in the FVs between Covid-19 and the common cold. To deem these patterns Covid-19-specific, the observed differences must also be present if the infected speakers were compared to another reference. However, this was not the case: Patients who suffered from a sore throat exhibited almost identical patterns as the pandemic group for vowel [e]. The same could be observed for vowel [o] when comparing to speakers who reported a hypertension. Hence, it was never possible to identify any clear Covid-19 pattern in the analyzed speech signals which could not also be linked to any other

disease. From a phonetic point of view, the observed patterns could be explained by the particular symptoms of a respiratory condition, but no supporting evidence could be found that it would be possible to diagnose an infection with SARS-CoV-2 only from a speech signal.

The proposed phonetic reference models which had been trained exclusively with samples from healthy speakers were not limited to the analysis of speech disorders. Severe damage to the central nervous system, inflicted by a stroke or a traumatic brain injury for example, could cause patients to lose the ability to semantically link certain words to their respective meaning. This clinical condition is referred to as aphasia, a language disorder which usually manifests in either its fluent or non-fluent form. In the case of the former, an individual is not aware of the loss of language understanding and hence will produce fluent speech by replacing missing words with neologisms. Patients who instead suffer from non-fluent aphasia try to remember the missing words while speaking, resulting in an interrupted speech production due to the inserted pauses. Unlike PD, most forms of aphasia are not progressive, because neurological damage is inflicted immediately during a stroke or a severe accident. In the early weeks after such an event, it is often possible to regain at least parts of the lost vocabulary through intensive language therapy.

In a common exercise protocol, participants are shown pictures of actions or objects which they have to name. Traditionally, the trained vocabulary in the exercises is tailored to the specific needs of an individual. For a successful at-home therapy, it can be crucial to provide users with reliable feedback whether the spoken word was correct (matched the depicted target word) or not. This could be solved either by using off-the-shelf ASR or dedicated keyword (KW) recognition systems. A modern ASR is robust enough to operate under non-optimal acoustic conditions and features an extensive vocabulary, but on the other hand, speech recordings from a medical therapy session must not be sent to any third-party speech recognition interface. Furthermore, aphasia is often accompanied by a concomitant speech disorder, which likely leads to a significant performance reduction of a conventional ASR. There exist a few methods which implement a keyword recognition logic for aphasia patients, but they usually feature a very reduced inventory of a couple hundred words. Additionally, they introduce further constraints such as a massive reduction in terms of the utilized vocabulary, and the requirement of having at least a small number of example utterances which include each word from that inventory. The performance of these systems is not perfect, with a maximum F1-score of 0.895 reported for a small set of high-quality speech recordings [Barb 21].

After restricting the presented phone recognizer to the set of German phonemes, this work introduced three keyword spotting (KWS) architectures. One utilized a recurrent neural network (RNN), the other two were based on the neural attention mechanism. The core idea behind the implementation of all three models was to facilitate open-vocabulary KWS systems. They would receive an audio file, together with the target keyword – in the form of the expected phoneme sequence – and had to classify whether the provided keyword was produced in the speech recording. On the one hand, this should enable the models to learn common pronunciation alternatives (for example a replacement of /p/ with /b/ due to a local accent or an imprecise recognition result). On the other, the final systems should be able to recognize key-

words from an open vocabulary which they had never learned during optimization. The adapted German phoneme recognizer as well as all KWS models were once again trained only with speech recordings from healthy references. On the healthy test set, all systems achieved precision and recall scores of 0.98 or higher, despite the fact that these signals had been collected from individual contributors in absence of any controlled recording setup. It could also be shown that the learned embeddings of phoneme symbols encoded plenty of phonetic information, such that similar phonemes (in terms of various properties, e.g. the involved articulator or the openness of a vowel) are closer to each other in the high-dimensional embedding space. This knowledge could be used by the models to operate more robustly in the presence of varying pronunciations or inaccurate recognition results from the phoneme recognizer.

Using the recordings from naming exercises of German aphasia patients, it could be shown that all three models were able to correctly assess most of the samples in which the target word had been produced. At the same time, the precision scores were considerably lower, a trend that became particularly evident as the length of the target keyword increased. The reason was that only those keyword productions had been annotated as correct which were free of any pronunciation error. Consequently, if a patient mispronounced the word, for example due to a concomitant speech deficit, the mispronounced item would not be considered entirely correct. By subsequently adding other keyword productions to the category of correct realizations, for example the mentioned mispronunciations, the precision scores improved markedly, whilst the recall experienced a small reduction: The best model, a decoder-only architecture, yielded a very balanced result with a precision of 0.92 and a recall of 0.91. This was also the model which maintained the highest robustness among patients with a lower intelligibility rating in the annotation. Comparing to the state of the art, the proposed systems outperformed all methods presented in related works, featured an open keyword vocabulary and did not require any speech recordings from aphasia patients for training.

The experiments and results presented throughout this work clearly suggested that it was possible to analyze pathological speech signals without the need of having access to in-domain datasets to optimize large ML models. In fact, it was shown that the phone(me) recognizers which had been trained with large amounts of crowd-sourced healthy speech data were able to robustly process high-quality audio recordings from soundproof booths, but also noisy signals which had been captured by patients using mobile devices at their homes. During training, the recognizers were able to explore a vast amount of varying recording hardware and software, different acoustic environments, a large number of speakers with all kinds of unique traits – and in the presence of all these variables, they had to recognize the correct sequence of phone(me)s. Coming back to the concept of destructive and distractive noise introduced earlier in this work, the models had learned to mitigate the influence of the former, but would still encode plenty of information about the latter noise type. In other words, every actual production of a particular phone could be interpreted in terms of the deviation from the average production of that phone. This deviation could then be explained by the pronunciation characteristics of the individual who produced said phone, for example due to a different pitch, accent, or any other speaker trait. Because the recognizers

were able to explore many of these deviations, they were not only robust against distractive noise, but were also able to systematically encode related information in their internal state vectors.

This ability was key to use the architectures not only for the recognition of uttered speech sounds, but also for feature extraction. It could be demonstrated how FVs from different stages of a neural network encoded different kinds of information. The early hidden states from the convolutional layers encoded a lot of signal-level details, making them the ideal choice to estimate the available vowel space of PD patients. The FVs collected from the last Transformer layer held much more contextual information about the particular phone, summarizing insights from a wider temporal field of view. They were successfully used to analyze the speech of patients who suffered from some form of respiratory condition, because they turned out to be less influenced by signal-level characteristics such as a speaker's fundamental frequency. Just like it was observed for PD already, phonetic knowledge could be used to interpret the outputs of the phone recognizers to better understand how a particular disease affected a speech signal. Be it a lack of muscle tension which gradually caused PD patients to struggle articulating plosive phones, or a blocked nose in Covid-19 or cold patients which had a marked influence on nasal sounds: By combining the plain phone recognition results with a detailed understanding of the phonetic background knowledge for each speech sound, it was possible to provide much better explanations of how different clinical conditions could have a characteristic effect on various morphological parts of the vocal tract.

The proposed approach of training state of the art DNNs with healthy speech signals to later use them for the analysis of pathological speech could also be transferred to the domain of language disorders. Like in all preceding experiments, the foundation of the presented KWS methods was a robust phonetic recognizer. By means of a sophisticated training procedure as well as a model design that facilitated open-vocabulary keyword recognition, it was possible to implement feedback-algorithms which were on the one hand very precise, resulting in few false positive results. At the same time, the obtained results clearly showed that the systems were quite forgiving if the pronunciation of the target word was not perfect, a common pattern which could not only be caused by a concomitant speech deficit, but also by poor phoneme recognition results. Furthermore, it was possible to illustrate how the models had learned relationships between similar German phonemes. This was a key step to becoming robust to pronunciation changes, but would also provide insights into the various pronunciation alternatives which were more likely to be tolerated by the KWS systems.

With datasets from PD, Covid-19 and aphasia patients, this thesis showed how it was possible to rely entirely on healthy training data for general purpose ASR to analyze pathological speech signals. It solved the problem of having only very little pathological data available, but also proposed the incorporation of phonetic knowledge to bridge the gap between the healthy reference models and the pathological speech signals. After all, this approach would not only allow ML experts to implement potent architectures using state of the art methods (like the parameter-intensive Transformer). It also enables the medical expert to better understand the outputs of an ML model, give them access to key insights into a patients speech and language

production, and equip them with a powerful yet transparent tool for diagnosing or tracking the progression of a disease.

In future works, the proposed method could be applied to other diseases which affect speech or language production to overcome the shortage of training data and the limited understanding about an ML model's decision making. Given that the proposed phone recognizer featured a multilingual inventory of speech sounds, it could also be interesting to evaluate if patients of a particular disease were more likely to utilize phones outside of the phonetic inventory of their native language. Providing meaningful insights to the medical experts can be helpful in the clinical workflow, but recent advances in generative language modeling could also help to prepare the results in a much more simple and concise manner, for example as a brief summary about the therapy progress of an individual patient. This feedback can play a crucial role in keeping the users of digital speech and language therapy solutions motivated over an extended period of time. Ultimately, with tools such as a highly robust phone recognizer and the proposed phonetic footprints, it could even be possible to detect abrupt changes in the articulation patterns of a person, which could be an indicator for an acute stroke. Consequently, the presented algorithms and methods could be applied for early diagnosis as well as for therapy to support patients as well as medical experts.

Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Model Cards

A.1.1 Wav2Vec2 XLSR Phone Recognition Model

The phone recognition model was based on the Wav2Vec 2.0 architecture [Baev 20]. Its configuration is summarized in Table A.1. The model comprises a total of 315 543 270 trainable parameters. The entire architecture can be trained from scratch

	Property	Value
CNN	Layers	7
	Kernel-sizes	(10,3,3,3,3,2,2)
	Strides	(5,2,2,2,2,2,2)
	Field of view	400 samples (= 25 ms)
Transformer	Layers	24
	Model dimension	1024
	Inner dimension	4096
	Attention heads	16
Linear	Layers	1
	Output space	101 phones + blank token

Table A.1: Configuration of the XLSR phone recognition model used for the analysis of PD and Covid-19 speech, structured by layer types.

using the following recipe:

1. Instantiate a new instance of `Wav2Vec2Model` from a pre-trained checkpoint using the *Huggingface* Transformer environment¹. Use checkpoints
 - `facebook/wav2vec2-base-960h` for Base variant
 - `facebook/wav2vec2-large-xlsr-53` for XLSR variant
2. Add a final linear layer to map the 1024 output features (768 in case of Base model) to the 102-dimensional output space. The input for said layer is the `last_hidden_state` result from the `Wav2Vec2Model` forward pass.

¹<https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers> (as of 25 April, 2023)

3. Train the model using the hyperparameters summarized in Table A.2. Use the initial learning rate and scheduler configuration as described in section 3.3.
4. The trained model can be used for inference by applying any decoding strategy on the emitted sequential probability densities. An implementation of Viterbi decoding² was used throughout this thesis.

Property	Base	XLSR
Criterion	CTC loss	
Sample length	2 seconds	
Sample rate	16 kHz	
Signal scaling	$X_{scaled} = \frac{X-\mu}{\sigma}$	
Optimizer	Adam	
Batch size	24	16
Epochs	≈ 120	≈ 140

Table A.2: Training hyperparameters used during the optimization of the Base and Large phone recognizers.

All experiments for PD and Covid-19 were executed with the XLSR version of the recognizer. The Base configuration was also described in this context, because it was adopted for training the three German KWS models in the chapter on aphasia. To access the already-trained XLSR architecture, simply clone the model repository³ from *Github*. Afterwards, read the `example.py` script which outlines how to download the model weights from *Huggingface* and use the final instance for inference.

²<https://github.com/nanoporetech/fast-ctc-decode> (as of 25 April, 2023)

³https://github.com/PKlumpp/phd_model

A.1.2 KWS Models

CRNN

The CRNN was the only KWS model which did not employ any modern neural attention mechanism. Its configuration is described in Table A.3.

	Property	Value
Density Masking	Threshold	Adaptive (mean)
	Gumbel temperature	$1 \leq \tau \leq 2$
Shared Linear	Output dimension	256
	Activation	GELU [Hend 16]
	Norm	Layer Norm [Ba 16]
Similarity Maps	Output shape	KW symbols \times phones
	Output dimension	256
CNN	Layers	8
	CNN Block	ResNeXt [Xie 17]
	Reduction layers	3 rd and 6 th
	ResNeXt groups	16
	Kernel size	3×5
	Output shape	$4 \times L$
RNN	Cell	LSTM
	Direction	Forward
	Operation	Seq2One
	Input dimension	4×256 (concat)
	Output dimension	256
Linear	Layers	1
	Output space	2 (binary CLS)

Table A.3: Configuration of the CRNN KWS model used for aphasia, structured by layer types. Uncertainty simulation was part of the initial masking module applied to the phone probability densities coming from the phone recognizer. The CNN collapses the initial keyword query length two times from 16 down to 4. The channels of the remaining 4 entities were concatenated, resulting in the input dimension of the RNN.

Encoder-Decoder

The Encoder-Decoder architecture was based on the two respective building blocks from the original Transformer architecture. Its configuration is described in Table A.4.

	Property	Value
Density Masking	Threshold	Adaptive (mean)
	Gumbel temperature	$1 \leq \tau \leq 2$
Shared Linear	Output dimension	256
	Activation	GELU [Hend 16]
	Norm	Layer Norm [Ba 16]
Pos. Encoding	Style	Additive
	Type	Sinusoidal
Encoder	Layers	6
	Model dimension	256
	Feed-forward dim.	1024
	Attention heads	4
Decoder	Layers	4
	Model dimension	256
	Feed-forward dim.	1024
	Attention heads	4
	Operation	Seq2One
Linear	Layers	1
	Output space	2 (binary CLS)

Table A.4: Configuration of the Encoder-Decoder KWS model used for aphasia, structured by layer types. Uncertainty simulation was part of the initial masking module applied to the phone probability densities coming from the phone recognizer. The Encoder processed the densities, the Decoder processed the keyword query and attended the encoded sequence. The output of the Decoder was encoded in a CLS token, which was then passed to the linear classification layer.

Decoder-only

The Decoder-only architecture was based on the encoder building block from the original Transformer architecture, which served as a decoder in the proposed setup. The configuration is described in Table A.5.

	Property	Value
Density Masking	Threshold	Adaptive (mean)
	Gumbel temperature	$1 \leq \tau \leq 2$
Shared Linear	Output dimension	256
	Activation	GELU [Hend 16]
	Norm	Layer Norm [Ba 16]
Pos. Encoding	Style	Additive
	Type	Sinusoidal
Decoder	Layers	8
	Model dimension	256
	Feed-forward dim.	1024
	Attention heads	4
Linear	Layers	1
	Output space	2 (binary CLS)

Table A.5: Configuration of the Decoder-only KWS model used for aphasia, structured by layer types. Uncertainty simulation was part of the initial masking module applied to the phone probability densities coming from the phone recognizer. The Decoder processed the concatenated sequence of keyword query symbols, CLS token and phonetic densities. The output at the position of the CLS token was then passed to the linear classification layer.

Training

All models shared the same training hyperparameters listed in Table A.6. The strategy to linearly increase the duration of training samples over time was described in 6.4.5. All models shared the same optimization parameters. However, as outlined in the model description of the CRNN architecture, this was the only variant that expected a fixed keyword query length of 16 symbols. Zero-padding was applied for shorter queries. The number of required training epochs varied between the three architectures. All presented hyperparameters were used for optimization in combination with the Base German phoneme recognizer. It can be replaced with the XLSR recognizer during inference to further improve recognition performance.

Property	Value
Criterion	Cross Entropy
Initial sample length	0.5 s
Sample length increment	≈ 0.2 s per epoch
Sample rate	16 kHz
Signal scaling	$X_{scaled} = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma}$
Optimizer	Adam
Minimum KW length	2 phones
Augmented KW prior	$\approx 67\%$
Batch size	12
Epochs	75 – 100

Table A.6: Training hyperparameters used for training the three KWS architectures.

A.2 Covid-19 t-SNE embeddings

The following pages contain further t-SNE embedding results which showed significant deviations between healthy speakers and those suffering from either Covid-19 or a common cold. Figure A.1 shows embedding results for the voiced and unvoiced

Figure A.1: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

alveolar stops [d] and [t]. While the differences between healthy and diseased speakers were pronounced, no significant deviations between a cold and Covid-19 could be identified. Besides the alveolar plosives, other consonant phones with the same manner, but different place of articulation, were also affected by symptoms related to an infection of the respiratory tract. This is shown in Figure A.2. Both the bilabial [p] as

Figure A.2: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

well as the velar [k] produced clear sub-clusters which were predominantly composed of realizations from non-healthy individuals. In the case of the bilabial stop, even the differences between speakers with a common cold and others who suffered from

Covid-19 were significant. Just like in the experiments before, however, these significant deviations between the two distributions were entirely gone when the Covid-19 samples were compared to only speakers with a sore throat.

This pattern, which had been observed for the vowel [e] in the presented experiments already, also manifested for another vowel, the front open [a]. The embedding results

Figure A.3: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

shown in Figure A.3 yielded significant differences between the two disease groups once again, which were found to be insignificant if compared to those speakers suffering from a sore throat. In general, many vowels (like the presented [a], [e], [i], [o]) turned out to convey information about the disease state. The clear differentiation of the particular underlying disease was impossible at the same time.

Another category of phones which could be affected by respiratory conditions were fricatives. Figure A.4 illustrates the t-SNE results of phones [f] and [s]. Once again,

Figure A.4: T-SNE embeddings of Transformer feature vectors from healthy (blue), Covid-19 positive (red), and Covid-19 negative with a cold (lime).

there were distinct regions in which mostly diseased samples could be found. And like

for most other phones, it was not possible to find any significant differences between the two diseases themselves.

For the phones (such as [a], [f] and [s]), the embeddings yielded several distinct sub-clusters which were apparently unrelated to the disease state. These accumulations were induced by the presence of temporal information. The feature vectors from the Transformer had been enriched with insights into the neighboring context of a phonetic symbol. By manual investigation, some of the observed clusters could be attributed to specific trailing or preceding phones, or even the spoken language, because some of the samples were not given in English, as expected, but in another language.

A.3 Publications

The following publications, authored as well as co-authored, were derived from this thesis.

- **P. Klumpp**, P. Chitkara, L. Sarı, P. Serai, J. Wu, I.-E. Veliche, R. Huang, Q. He. *Synthetic cross-accent Data Augmentation for Automatic Speech Recognition*. Pre-print on arxiv.org, 2023.
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